

Generative AI in corporate communications: ethical challenges in Swiss German communication departments – Appendix documents

Marta Pellegrino

Appendix

Appendix A: [Participant Contact E-mail Example]

Sehr geehrte Damen und Herren

Ich bin Studentin an der ZHAW im Masterstudiengang «Strategic Communication Management» und in Rahmen meiner Masterarbeit untersuche ich den Einsatz von künstlicher Intelligenz im Kommunikationsabteilungen in der Schweiz.

Genau möchte ich herausfinden, welche ethische Herausforderungen am meisten vorkommen und wie Kommunikationsexperten damit umgehen. Um dieses Ziel zu erreichen, möchte ich qualitative Interviews mit Kommunikationsexperten aus verschiedenen Branchen durchführen.

Ich würde mich sehr freuen, wenn Sie oder jemand aus Ihrem Team Interesse an einer Teilnahme hätte.

Hier finden Sie einige wichtige Informationen:

1. **Datum und Zeit:** Die Interviews werden ab Februar möglich sein, vorzugsweise im März. Falls das nicht passt, bin ich flexibel und offen für alternative Terminvorschläge.
2. **Dauer und Modus:** Die Interviews werden voraussichtlich 30–45 Minuten dauern und über Microsoft Teams stattfinden.
3. **Anonymität:** Eine Vertraulichkeitserklärung wird von beiden Seiten unterzeichnet, um Anonymität zu garantieren. Sollten Sie bestimmte Informationen explizit machen wollen, können wir dies besprechen.
4. **Sprache:** Meine Masterarbeit wird auf Englisch verfasst, deshalb wären Interviews in Englischer Sprache ideal. Sollten Sie Deutsch bevorzugen, kann ich die Fragen entsprechend vorbereiten.

Weitere Informationen erhalten Sie bis Februar.

Vielen Dank im Voraus für Ihre Rückmeldung. Auf eine mögliche Zusammenarbeit freue ich mich sehr.

Freundliche Grüsse

Marta Pellegrino

English below

Dear [COMPANY'S NAME's] communication department,

I am a student in the master's program *Strategic Communication Management* at the ZHAW's University of Applied Sciences.

For my master's thesis, I am investigating the use of artificial intelligence in communication departments in Switzerland. Specifically, I aim to analyze the most common ethical challenges related to AI and the ways in which communication experts navigate them.

To do so, I will conduct qualitative interviews with communication experts from various industries. I would greatly appreciate it if you or someone from your team would be willing to participate in an interview.

Here is some key information:

1. **Date:** Interviews will be possible starting from February, with March being the preferred period. If this does not work for you, I will be happy to find an alternative time.
2. **Duration and Format:** Interviews will take approximately 30 to 45 minutes and will be conducted via Microsoft Teams.
3. **Anonymity:** A confidentiality agreement to ensure the anonymity of the data will be signed by both parties. If you would like to make certain information public, we can discuss this beforehand.
4. **Language:** As the master's thesis will be written in English, it would be ideal to already conduct the interviews in the same language. If preferred, I can prepare the questions and conduct the interview in German.

You will be provided with further information by February.

Thank you in advance for your time and consideration. I am looking forward to your answer.

Kind regards,

Marta Pellegrino

Appendix B: [Interview Guidelines]

Qualitative Interviews: Questions Guidebook

1. Introduction – 4-5 minutes

Explaining the master's project and the interview. Commenting and showing the informed consent form. Explaining details about anonymity and confidentiality. Creating a common ground regarding ethics definition:

“For the purpose of this interview, ethics is understood as an intersection of ethical AI, business ethics and ethics in corporate communication. In this context, ethics entails acting responsibly to balance innovation and societal impact, mitigate risks and promote fairness and respect towards social and human values”

Open questions to create a relaxed atmosphere:

- 1) How long have you been working in corporate communication?
- 2) In what does your job consist at the XY company?

2. AI's implementation – 6-10 minutes

- 1) How often do you or your colleagues use generative AI to complete communication tasks?
- 2) Which specific AI tools do you use (ChatGPT, Gemini...) and why did you choose them?
- 3) In which tasks are these tools implemented? (E.g.: correcting or improving texts, generating texts based on a prompt, generating images etc.)
- 4) How are these tools implemented when working on a task? (e.g. human in the loop process)
- 5) What advantages do you see when using generative AI tools in communication tasks?

3. Ethical challenges – 10-12 minutes

- 1) Where do you see the main ethical challenges regarding the general use of AI in the field of corporate communication and why?
- 2) Does your view differ from the one of your department? If yes, what could be the reason?
- 3) Which specific ethical concerns can you link to the specific way in which AI is implemented in your department?
- 4) Which of these ethical concerns discussed is the most relevant to your work and why?

4. Strategies implemented – 10-12 minutes

- 1) Can you describe how your department deals with these ethical concerns?
- 2) Is your approach mainly preventive (avoiding the issue beforehand) or reactive (finding a solution to the problem once it occurs). Could you provide an example?
- 3) Do you have guidelines or handbooks regarding the topic of AI and ethical challenges? How useful are they?
- 4) How would you evaluate your current strategy?
- 5) Are you satisfied with your current method, or do you think something else might be needed?

5. Further discussion possibilities – 3-6 minutes

- 1) Do you have a concrete example of ethical challenges you encountered and the way in which you dealt with them?
- 2) Do you want to share anything else that could be relevant to this interview?

6. Closing statements – 2-3 minutes

Thanking the interview partner. Explaining further steps (analyzing the answers and writing the thesis), asking if they would like to have a copy of the final work. Asking if there are any questions.

Appendix C: [Interview Transcript_E1]

1	Interview Transcript – E1:
2	March 5th, 2025, h.09.30, Interview on Microsoft Teams
3	PM: So now that the recording started, I will switch to English.
4	E1: Mm hmm mm.
5	PM: I will start by giving you a definition of how we understand ethics for the purpose of this interview. So, for this interview ethics is understood as an intersection of ethical AI, business ethics, and ethics in corporate communication. In this context, ethics entails acting responsibly to balance innovation and societal impact, mitigate risks and promote fairness and respect towards social and human values. Does this resonate with you? Does this work for you as well, or do you have anything to add to that?
6	E1: No, absolutely.
7	PM: Perfect. I will just start with a few more light questions. So how long have you been working in the field of corporate communication?
8	E1: It's coming up to five years, but I have started during my studies, so.
9	PM: OK.
10	E1: Just part time at the beginning.

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PM: Yes. And what does your job consist of in your company where you are currently working at?

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E1: Currently I do a lot of work in social media, so a lot of content creation, content strategy, analytics and all of these things. But then I also am part of the employer branding team, so we do a strategy for that and try to figure out how we can make everyone basically feel like [COMPANY NAME] is the place to work at. So, it's mostly those two fields at the moment, yeah.

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PM: OK, great. I will now go to the way in which you implement AI, and, in this case, my first question would be: How often do you or your colleagues use generative AI to complete communication tasks?

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E1: How often... very often I think, personally I think I use it every hour at least, like two or three times.

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PM: OK.OK.

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E1: I know that some of my older colleagues use it a little bit less, but just because they're not that used to it yet, but we did recently have a little course that we hosted in our team as well to get everyone on board and really like make them want to use it because I think it's life changing when it comes to work.

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PM: Do you use any specific tools?

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E1: Yes, I have a list.

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PM: Yeah, that's great.

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E1: So, we use OK, it starts with CopyAI, Synthesia.IO, then obviously Copilot, so Microsoft 365 Copilots, Copilot studio. AI attack which is Azure OpenAI basically.

InferenceCloud and [COMPANY'S NAME] GPT, and [COMPANY'S NAME] GPT is an internal tool we developed that combines-

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PM: OK.

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E1: - All the different... yeah, all the different models we kind of know, I think we also have like DeepSeek on there... ChatGPT and we basically get to use all the models as well, yeah.

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PM: There is a specific reason why you use this tool? So, you mentioned quite a lot. Maybe for some tasks some tools are better suited... how do you use them?

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E1: Yep. Yep, absolutely. So, I think the one I use the most is [COMPANY'S NAME] GPT. In this case, I mostly use ChatGPT 4.0 at the moment, and I think that's mostly for rewriting my emails. Writing copy for social media. Giving me ideas for slides and presentations. New ideas for or just like creative idea generation, which most of the time it's not that great at because it's not creative in a sense, but it will just give me a little bit of help if I have some kind of blockage in my brain. So, I think that's the one I used the most. Yeah.

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PM: So, you were telling me already a bit about the tasks. Are there generally speaking in your department tasks in which your tools are used more frequently? How do you mainly use AI?

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E1: Yes, I think mostly to write copy. So, if it's for a newsletter or for a booklet that we publish for our customers or copy for social media, I think we use it a lot, especially if we already have some type of idea on what we want to write. It's good at summarizing certain content and like, really, yeah, helping us there to combine everything, yeah.

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PM: That is mainly writing, summarizing, and maybe brainstorming. Yes, do you also use it to generate images or videos?

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E1: Yeah. Yeah, we don't at the moment, we have an internal policy that we don't, I think, and this maybe comes into like the ethical perspective of a lot because it is using pictures that are not our own. But we are working on a tool that will be doing it. So, we will be able to do image generation with [COMPANY'S NAME] internal pictures. So, it is in progress. We don't know when it's going to start, but we have seen some results, and it looks fantastic. So, if that's going to work soon, I'm very excited, yeah.

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PM: And when you implement these tools, how do you basically implement them? So, for example, do you have humans that are always in charge of controlling? There are certain tasks where maybe you just use the prompt, or I mean how is the process?

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E1: The process is that we do have a global generation AI team, so they are responsible for implementing new tools, staying in contact with the regions to figure out what we need and what our needs are and when they implement a tool is basically available to everyone and we stay up to date and then we can it's up to us to use it or not use it. So, it's pretty simple.

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PM: Do you have someone in charge to check the outputs or do you sometimes just leave them as they are without controlling?

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E1: We do have... well, this is up to every team, but we have the policy in our team that we look over it. We will never just use the copy that is generated. We will always like work through that and have our own opinion that still matters in that case, yeah.

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PM: Mm hmm. OK. Yes, perfect. Now that I've got an overview of how you use it, I will move to the ethical challenges. So where do you see the main ethical challenges regarding the general use of AI in the field of corporate communication? So generally speaking, and broadly speaking, where do you see possible ethical issues?

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E1: Mm hmm. I think one of the parts is that, well, it is taking information from somewhere. So, we do know that. And I think when it comes to copy, it's not necessarily the most disturbing part, but I think what I mentioned before with the image generation when you know that the image you now receive is part of many images, I think that's where... yeah, copywriting and copyrights. Copyright infringement, that type of thing is a huge problem and I think that's where ethical discussions have to go or already are happening.

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PM: It's mainly copywriting and the fact that you do not know where the information comes from. Basically, you do not have...if you think more specifically about the way in which it is used in your department or in your field, then do you have more concerns that might be more specific?

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E1: Not in our field just because we're very careful, I think as a company in general, we try to really figure out everything before we start with a new tool or a new-

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PM: Yeah.

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E1: -New way of working so not specifically to my work, no.

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PM: OK. So, is there something that you discuss quite often, maybe in your team or an ethical concern that you feel is mostly shared among the people you know, or you work with?

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E1: I think one thing that we discuss a lot is, well the output and the information that you sometimes receive is faulty. I think that it's very important to not trust the information and the output unless you already have put the input in, if that makes sense. There's a lot of mistakes that happen regarding facts and things like that, and I think that's the main part for us. To always fact-check.

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PM: Yeah, fact-checking. So, you mentioned you also had a course. Do you have anything basically going on that helps you deal with these ethical challenges that you may tell me about?

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E1: So, we have biweekly Gen AI calls that are led by the global team, so everyone's able to join them, ask questions, get the newest updates on what's happening at the moment within our company. So that's a helpful way and channel to figure things out. But yeah, I think that's mostly what's happening. And then every team kind of does their own thing. So, in our team we have updates as well that are led by the social media team.

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PM: OK.

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E1: We have to make sure you get the information to them as well, especially if they're not regularly working with AI.

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PM: Yeah. Yes. If you think about the approach you have to these ethical issues, would you describe it as being more preventative? So, trying to avoid the issue beforehand or more reactive, so trying to find a solution in case of something happens which does it fit most?

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E1: Absolutely. The first one, so preventative.

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PM: OK.

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E1: As I mentioned, we're very careful always trying to figure out every possible scenario first.

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PM: OK.

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E1: To not get into trouble later.

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PM: If we talk about every possible scenario, what are possible scenarios that you are thinking of?

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E1: So, one of the things is always “How? How well do we know at all?” I think that that’s more on the global perspective though, when they decide on what tools we’re able to use specifically. But I do know they always check. What’s happening with our data? What’s happening with our inputs? I think that’s a big, big part as well. And we’re also not able to use all the information and all the tools. I think that’s also very important. So, we have different classifications for different tools. So, I think when it comes to scenarios on what we want to work with and not want to work with it? First, yeah, what’s happening with our data. Second of all, is it useful for our use case? And how is the output? I think that’s the most important ones.

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PM: Yeah. Do you have a specific guideline, sort of if ever if ever something was going to happen, if a crisis may be related to the use of AI was going to come out. Do you know what to happen or would you kind of have to find a solution on the spot?

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E1: That’s again with the global team. So, we have our direct contact partners. So if anything should happen that is regarding AI, which has contact them. So that’s very helpful.

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PM: OK. Yeah. OK, perfect. So, you have a team in charge of that, yeah. And general guidelines such as maybe prewritten prompts that might be used... do you have something similar?

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E1: Absolutely. Yeah. So, we have a whole wiki online with different prompts and also different systems on how to work with.

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PM: Yeah.

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E1: The different models. Also, guidelines on again what data to enter. What type of persona the model would be in a sense, so it’s very, very helpful.

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PM: Mm hmm. Oh, it’s useful. Are you satisfied with this current method that we’re using, or do you feel like something more could be done or something different?

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E1: We had this conversation last week with one of the Gen AI teams and the two things we're missing is image generation and the other thing is presentations. So, slides generation. So, anything visual, I think a lot of also iconography is a big part, so anything visual I think we're still lacking models that we can use, but they are aware of that and are working on that. So, let's hope.

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PM: OK.

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E1: We get them soon.

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PM: Did it ever happen that something happened in your company where you said, "Well, AI might have been used more carefully?" Or, On the contrary, a great example of how AI was used where you thought, "Wow, that's the great implementation"?

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E1: Yeah, I think a mixture of both we had for Christmas globally, they did the first AI visual campaign with the visual image generator.

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PM: OK.

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E1: Though it was all about factories and the [COMPANY'S NAME] buildings and Santa Claus, and how we're helping Santa Claus going digital. It was very fun to see what is possible with image generation, but then we also noticed how much work it will be used afterwards. I don't know. You know about fingers [*in AI's image generation*] that don't align and things like that. So, it was a lot of Photoshop after the actual image generation. So yeah, that was one example, but the output was great. It was very creative in a sense, but also it didn't land that well with our audience. I think it was very-

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PM: OK.

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E1: -It didn't seem real, and I think right now you're still able to tell if an image is AI generated to a certain extent. I know there's like really good models that you wouldn't know, but yeah, it didn't land that well.

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PM: OK. Yeah. I think some in some cases might be a bit soon, maybe for the audience. But I think that the AI is going to improve drastically if we think about that. Is there any kind of risk or issue that you or your team might be able to foresee thinking in the next years for the next generations?

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E1: I don't think my team specifically. I think it's like all the discussions we have in general about ethical issues.

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PM: Yes.

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E1: And also, about different companies, I think which is watching very carefully on what's happening in the market as well. I know, like recently with the development of DeepSeek and what that means. Then again for the political environment, I think that is also something we have to watch. Yeah.

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PM: Yeah. May I ask you, when did you start developing all these AI solutions that you have? Because it seems that you are quite well prepared in your company. So, when did you start and how long did it take to create such a an organized environment?

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E1: Great question. I think that Gen AI team was established...was it a year ago? Let me just check that real quick because I do have the team slides on here. Yeah, it seems as though it was like 1 to 1 1/2 years ago. And then we slowly started implementing everything.

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PM: Is acceptance good in your department or are there people kind of resisting it?

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E1: I think communications is very open to new tools in general, so we were very open.

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PM: Yeah.

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E1: It's also extremely, extremely well perceived by anyone that works in analytics or things like that, where you have to process a lot of data. So yeah, but communications, I think overall they, they love new things, so.

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PM: So, we already went through all the questions that I prepared.

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E1: Fantastic.

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PM: That I'm thinking if there is something more that I can ask you to maybe deepen some aspects since I plan some minutes more. Otherwise, I will let you go early.

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E1: Mm hmm. Yep. Yeah, of course. Yeah, no worries.

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PM: So, you mentioned for example that you use prompts and about that do you have. For all the teams, or mainly for certain teams, how do you organize them?

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E1: I wouldn't know exactly how it is for other teams just because we're such a big company. I know that for our team, which is around 20 people in Switzerland, we have a global community which is thousands of people that do communications for [COMPANY'S NAME] and we have specific prompts that that's the only thing I know. And I know that the Generative AI team has a specific person that is responsible just for the communications departments.

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PM: OK.

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E1: And they will work things like that out with us in collaboration so.

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PM: Yeah.

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E1: I do think there's...

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PM: Yeah.

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E1: There must, there must be. Yeah. Because they're so well organized as well.

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PM: For which tasks are your prompt? So maybe social media or newsletters or like everything.

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E1: The prompts they give us... we have, well, we have prompts for everything. It's also with copy AI. We have pre-saved prompts that we can just use if we want to generate a newsletter or LinkedIn post. It's basically for every use case. They will already have thought of that, or they will implement it later on. So, we always are able to give feedback as well, which I think is very important to always stay in contact. With each other, but yeah, basically for every use case.

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PM: You feel that they are well done, or do you sometimes feel maybe they forget some aspects or that they limit your creativity or freedom?

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E1: Prompts are a lot of the time, very over engineered.

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PM: Mm hmm. Yep.

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E1: They're a bit complicated sometimes I just need quick info and I'm not going to use them. I actually don't think...I don't think I use them. That is great to say [*ironic*], "OK, I don't think I use them. I think I'll write my own"

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PM: OK. Mm hmm.

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E1: And I have more of a conversation with the bot in a sense. A lot of the time it can be helpful to just have an understanding on how the model works and to know what input it needs to generate output. But once you have that done, you don't really need prompts anymore, I'd say.

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PM: So they are not requirement, they are something you might use, but they're not the requirement, yeah.

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E1: Yeah. Yeah, exactly.

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PM: OK, so to wrap it up, I think that I got a nice understanding of how you use it. So you are basically... I'm revising my note as I speak to you, you use in your department AI quite often and you use quite a lot of systems at least them and have the recording the main tasks in which you use them are summarizing, copywriting and brainstorming. Am I missing something?

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E1: I think copywriting's the biggest one, yeah.

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PM: Yeah.

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E1: Summarizing, yeah, maybe. I mean, is that copywriting again, like creating speeches, like presentations like bullet points, I think that is another big thing.

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PM: Yeah, yeah. Yes, and the reason why I use AI is maybe because it is more fast or efficient. Like why would you? Why do you use AI so intensively?

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E1: I think it helps with brain blockages, especially features needed fast input to start working on something. I think it is very quick. I think it helps save massive

amounts of time. Especially if you have material and you just need the material in another format, it's fantastic. Yeah, I think saving time is the biggest one.

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PM: Yeah. And in your department, you have the rule basically, that you always have someone like going through the outputs and making sure that they are reliable, making sense, that they can be used. So, kind of things. Yeah. So, it's for its own, basically.

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E1: I think every person has to do that though, yeah. Yeah.

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PM: And then the main ethical issue for you would be that the information comes from we don't know where exactly so. And then of course, it has to do with copyrighting, because when you write something, it's kind of difficult. I mean, I am interpreting it as you do not. You cannot be sure about ownership. I'm not sure if you are on the same page as that. Yeah. And then you feel that in your company and in the field in general, you are very careful. So, you do not see specific issues that might arise other than the general ones.

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E1: Yeah.

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PM: And then we talked about your strategies that are also quite intensive. You have biweekly calls, regular updates, prompts, Wiki and guidelines. And also you have a specific team which is basically behind these whole AI things. OK, so I think I've summarized our discussion. I have already asked you for the example that you gave me with communication with the Christmas campaign. So, I think I have everything that I need for my interview, so if it is OK for you, I can let you go already.

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E1: Amazing. Yeah, of course. Are you happy with the output? Do you need anything else?

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PM: Yes. I was revising it because I was surprised by how fast we were today, but I think I could answer all my questions.

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E1: Yeah. Yeah.

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PM: So, I think I have everything. Thank you very much.

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E1: Oh, no worries. Thank you.

Appendix D: [Interview Transcript_E2]

1	Interview Transcript – E2:
2	<p>March 25th,2025 h.14.00, Interview on Microsoft Teams</p> <p>PM: OK, so the transcription started by me, so I would like to start with the actual interview and therefore I switch to English. Before starting, I would like to give you a sort of common understanding of what communication of what ethics is in this context. So, I have prepared a definition.</p>
3	<p>E2: Yes.</p>
4	<p>PM: This is: Ethics is understood as an intersection of ethical AI, business ethics and ethics in a corporate communication in this context ethics entails acting responsibly to balance innovation and societal impact, mitigate risks and promote fairness and respect towards social and human values. Does it work for you, or do you have anything else that you want to add? Or is it OK for you as well as a definition?</p>
5	<p>E2: I think it's a good, very good definition, very complex and therefore, yeah, I think a lot of aspects are already touched. Mm hmm.</p>
6	<p>PM: It works for you. Perfect. I would like to start with a couple of easy questions. The first one being how long have you been working in the field of corporate communication?</p>
7	<p>E2: It's two years and almost three months, so I'm kind of new in in the field, yes.</p>
8	<p>PM: Yeah. And how long have you been working at the company you are working at right now, also three years?</p>

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E2: It's also two years and three months, and before I was at intern in a different position. So, it's two and a half years in total.

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MP: Yeah. Yes. And what does your job mainly consist of right now? What are your tasks or responsibilities?

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E2: So, my job position is called "marketing and communication specialist", and I am working for two teams. One team is the internal communication which is a lot of creating content based on internal news-

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PM: Yes. Mm hmm.

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E2: -Creating pages for different business units. They want to have their information distributed on our Internet. For example, doing interviews internally. We have also an internal platform for social media. It's called Viva Engage. It's connected to Microsoft products. So, there I'm also helping people to publish and create content, then a second pillar I would say is all the event management support. We have a lot of online and mostly offline events like trade shows, customer events... we are planning now, for example, the opening of a new site in [COMPANY'S LOCATION]. Where we also create a big opening ceremony and customer event, and the third pillar is also digital marketing. There I am responsible as of this year for LinkedIn Strategies. Same, like organic posting but also ad campaigns and so I'm divided into the like the normal marketing communication team and also the digital marketing team.

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PM: Yes. It's quite a lot. I would say you cover quite a broader area.

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E2: It is. Yes.

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PM: So now that I understand more or less what you're doing, I would like to ask you more about AI. And my first question would be how often do you use it? Or do your colleagues and people in your team use AI?

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E2: I would say... I use it, for the moment, just for my LinkedIn content creation. For example, I have to create a post, and the business gives me input regarding a new product we are launching, and I get some bullet points or some information or a brochure and out of this I try to create appealing content post for LinkedIn or yeah and therefore I use LinkedIn [meaning: AI] as my counter partner, I insert all the information I have and wait for some inspiration. But I would say-

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PM: Mm hmm.

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E2: -Not a lot. Also, sometimes I still stick to creating my own texts because in... yeah, how can I say? In formulating all the things I would like ChatGPT to create, I am sometimes quicker in just writing it down myself.

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PM: Yes. Do you have other people working with you that use it to more often or less often? Or do you think it's balanced?

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E2: Yeah. Yeah, I think I am one of the of the people who are less using it for the moment. I see more and more people having ChatGPT open.

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PM: OK.

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E2: And I think also for all the slides and content creation. We do a lot of, I don't know, leaflets, brochures and before we were, we outsourced this completely with our agency. But now the more and more we have to cut costs. So, we are doing this internally.

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PM: Mm hmm. Yes.

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E2: So, the people from the business, actually the engineers, have to provide the content. So, they are using and working a lot with AI, yeah.

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PM: OK. Yes. Do you use any specific tools? So, you mentioned ChatGPT. Is it the main one, or are you also using other tools?

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E2: Yes, it's ChatGPT. And me personally not, but I learned that they're also using Perplexity.

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PM: OK. Yes, I've heard of it.

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E2: Do you know it?

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PM: Not personally, but I've heard it already, but I've never used it.

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E2: Yeah, I can also drop it into the chat, so you have the link, maybe it's helpful.

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PM: Thank you. Thank you very much. So, LinkedIn is...

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E2: You're welcome. There's another one. We are also using Copilot in Microsoft Edge.

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PM: Do you personally use all these others?

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E2: I'm just using ChatGPT for the moment I started using also...there is a possibility... we are using for example for images and video, stock images and stock videos. We're using Shutterstock and in Shutterstock there is the possibility-

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PM: Yes. Yes.

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E2: -I don't know to create your content with AI don't know how it's called, but yeah, it's kind of you describe what you need and then yeah, you have there a button AI generated content in Shutterstock.

38

PM: OK. Yes. OK, so the tasks in which you use these tools that you've mentioned are content creation. In your case on LinkedIn. And then you also have video and picture creation which have Shutterstock. Am I correct?

39

E2: Yeah. Yes, yes. Correct, because we-

40

PM: Or is there anything else you do?

41

E2: No. Yeah, because we have mostly... how can I say? For example, it's very handy for images in the future. I think we will more relate on AI because we always have the problem that we have highly confidential products or customer scenarios application, so.

42

PM: OK. Mm hmm.

43

E2: Therefore, it's very difficult sometimes to show the real product, because then somebody from our competitors could just steal them so-

44

PM: Yes.

45

E2: -I think in the future we will rely more there on the AI pictures and videos to kind of show what it is but hide at the same time the confidential parts.

46

PM: OK. Yes. So, you basically already gave me the reason why you use it, because I was going to ask you why you decided to use certain tools. So, this one is privacy and sort of hiding sensitive things... and anything else?

47

E2: Yeah. Yes. Correct, because [*COMPANY'S NAME*] or the division where I'm sitting is [*NAME OF THE COMPANY'S DIVISION*]. It's one of three divisions, and my division is mainly creating, producing applications and products for end-customers which then, for example, produce pharmaceutical products or they do plastic and so we provide them the machines. So, each you can imagine each customer has a different scenario. So, all the products we create are really, really-

48

PM: Yeah.

49

E2: -Specific for these customers, so they don't want to have competitors know what they are doing because of course they want to be competitive and that's why it's always an issue. I think it's the biggest challenge we are facing in marketing communication in this kind of area. You want to share, but you cannot share. So, we have a big success project and we want to share it with the world and show "look what we can do".

50

PM: Sure, I understand. Yes.

51

E2: But on the other hand, we have to hide it.

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PM: Yeah, sure.

53

E2: So, to find there somehow a way to publish something nice is difficult. So that's why in the future it will be, I think more and more-

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PM: Yes.

55

E2: - And a topic for AI to create content creation, yeah.

56

PM: And when it comes to text generation, do you see advantages in using AI? I mean you said to use it for text generation ...yeah.

57

E2: Yes, yeah. Yes, very much.

58

PM: OK.

59

E2: I think it's. It's so nice because in my opinion, it's kind of a counterpart, so instead of scheduling a meeting with a work colleague, you just go to ChatGPT, you insert your ideas and your thoughts, and you have an immediate reply. I think it's kind of replacing-

60

PM: OK. Yes.

61

E2: -Yeah, long meetings. And you, you have also for idea creation or like brainstorming. It's amazing or there are even people... they're recording with ChatGPT. I never did it, but it's possible. I heard they're recording a meeting and then they entered the prompt "Please, what are... What do you think are the points? Are there more pros or more cons?"

62

PM: Mm hmm.

63

E2: Or are people more into it or not based on the recording, so they kind of resume or yeah... Compile the OR do like meeting notes as well... yeah...

64

PM: Yes. Yes. Do you... oh, sorry. You can go on. Sorry.

65

E2: Or yeah sorry. Or out of this meeting, create some slides for example even.

66

PM: Yes, yes, it does a lot, yeah, my question was going to be do you also use it for like content that is going to be published outside? So maybe text for social media posting, yes.

67

E2: Yeah. Yes. Yep. Awesome.

68

PM: And yes, this also works effectively for you?

69

E2: I would say we always have to double check it, of course. So, in my case it's just the LinkedIn post, but I know that also it's used to create a draft for brochures, for example. But then we always make sure to double-check the content. Of course, we have a procedure of how our content gets approved internally and also externally. So that's a very strong process.

70

PM: Yes. You always have someone which is also checking the outputs of ChatGPT?

71

E2: Yes. Not overall, but in our like normal process, the content creation is going through many hands, so this is the same. It does not depend on if it's created by or with the help of ChatGPT or if it's created just writing like this, yeah.

72

PM: Mm hmm. OK. Yeah, yeah. You always have someone, yes, but it would have been... Do you do regardless of the use of AI or not?

73

E2: Yes, regardless. Yeah, because we have to make sure that all the technical information shown is something we can publish and is correct. So, there are always some people involved in double and triple checking.

74

PM: Yeah, sure. Now that I have this overview of your work, I would like to go specifically to the ethical challenges, and I would like to ask you: Where do you see the main ethical challenges regarding the use of AI in corporate communication? Of course, considering your experience, the fact that you're working in this field specifically, but yeah, the question is where do you see these ethical challenges?

75

E2: I think it's always a challenge to avoid misinformation, false information. To also, if we use ChatGPT or AI to really be aware that we...do not trust the source, so we have to double check and therefore, I think the use is still limited because

you still have to have some experts or professionals double checking the content and also fake news.

76

PM: Yes.

77

E2: The fake news is a big part, I would say and. Yeah, out of this... sometimes I see ethical challenges. It's not ethical, but also it's a challenge because the texts are very plain and always the same. So, I think from a language point of view-

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PM: Yes.

79

E2: The... all the texts you can see more and more in social media and also outside printed world that the language is sounding more and more the same. So, it gets like-

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PM: Yes.

81

E2: One big "einheitsbrei", I don't know how to say it in English.

82

PM: Yeah, but I understand what you mean here.

83

E2: Yes. So, I think the language is losing a little bit of its variety. And yeah, I think in the future everything we have to make sure that still we have some individual language parts-

84

PM: OK.

85

E2: -In content and so it does not sound all the same.

86

PM: Yes, yes.

87

E2: If I see for example, I am thrilled, or we are thrilled to announce I know already that's AI.

88

PM: And you know.

89

E2: And there are so many more words for this. So, in my point of view it's a little bit boring if you just rely on it, yeah.

90

PM: Yeah. Are you afraid that ChatGPT can create like general text for all kinds of context is going to take away something, not necessarily people or workforce, but taking away something from the field of communication?

91

E2: Yes, I think definitely it will be a threat, but we should see it as a chance.

92

PM: Yes.

93

E2: To work smarter and to also, we will still need a workforce, I think so, but the profile or the job profile will change, and I think now the challenge for us is to first understand what the new skills will be we need, what kind of job-

94

PM: Yes.

95

E2: -Or background or jobs will still be needed. And then try to push ourselves to do the jump and yeah and learn the new skills or get prepared for the new the new world kind of. Because I think that's definitely a threat. And people who are just saying, "Yeah, I don't care. It's nothing. Nothing is going to change. I don't want to change." There will be a problem in some years I think so.

96

PM: Yes. Yes. No, I understand, yes. Yeah. What you told me is something that old people in your department agree on. Or are there people who are more optimistic or even more pessimistic? What is the general feeling?

97

E2: In the company I'm working for now, I would say people are completely open, so it's an industry where we are. So, we'll we are so... it's constantly evolving. So, I would say most people have an open mindset regarding changes.

98

PM: Mm hmm.

99

E2: And I think it has also nothing to do with the age I see like, yeah, like all people very, very up to date technology wise.

100

PM: Yes.

101

E2: Yeah, I would say it's, it's an environment here where people are overall open to these changes. Yeah, I would say.

102

PM: There is something which is very specific to your field, so I've well you will be put in an area which is called industry engineering businesses because it is the broader area that you are working in. So, for my thesis you would be put under this category. If you think of this category, there is something specific which concerns the use of AI, something that makes you feel more nervous considering that you are in this field or are your worries like general?

103

E2: Yeah. Yeah. It's a good question. I would say they're more optimistic or I don't see that they're so scared or they see challenges. I think there may be more. It's difficult for me to answer. I can, yeah.

104

PM: Oh yeah, but I was. Yes, I was thinking maybe just for you or just for your communication job, but inside his engineering board, is there something which makes you more nervous?

105

E2: Yeah. Yeah. Mm hmm.

106

PM: I mean, it might be a possibility that using AI in a technical way or for technical topics makes you more nervous. As an example, it might be something else...

107

E2: Mm hmm. Yeah, yeah, I think it's. I think they're aware that they will use it more and more and then misuse the data protection. The topic like, yeah, "How we can avoid data getting stolen". That's a big point. I would say which, which is something they have to balance and to find a solution between. Yeah.

108

PM: Hmm. When it comes to finding a solution, it's good because I can switch to my next set of question, which is about the strategies. Do you have anything in place which helps you navigate these challenges when it comes specifically to AI? Sort what you said, finding a solution for something that might be a trigger.

109

E2: I mean, we have a page on our Internet regarding opportunities and limitations of generative AI.

110

PM: Mm hmm. Is it something that you can describe? Yeah.

111

E2: I'm just throwing it down. I will definitely ask my boss if I can share the info.

112

PM: Yeah, I mean, I don't need to, I don't need to read it in detail, but I was more curious to know if it is something that helps you to sort of navigate the limitations.

113

E2: Yeah. Yeah. I mean, there are some kind of recommendations. For example, the first step, be aware of its limitations there. Now they are talking more about ChatGPT.

114

PM: Mm hmm mm hmm. Yeah. Mm hmm.

115

E2: Then, ChatGPT maybe responds based on outdated or biased data. Number two, share the insights, share your ideas and insights about ChatGPT with your colleagues. And number three, be responsible, use ChatGPT to increase your productivity, but be mindful how you use AI generated content. Number four learn and experiment. Use ChatGPT as a tool for learning and experimentation. So, there are also some don'ts. AI can be wrong. Point 1. Point two. proper permission.

116

PM: OK.

117

E2: Do not use information provided by commercial purposes without proper permission. Point data classification applies. Don't insert any internal confidential or secret information into ChatGPT and point four data privacy don't share any personal information about yourself or others with ChatGPT.

118

PM: Yes.

119

E2: This kind of guidance... we have for the moment in my knowledge, I don't know if it's if there's something else out there, maybe in some teams internally they have.

120

PM: Yes.

121

E2: They have more restrictions, or ideas, but that's the one I could share.

122

PM: Is it specific for your team or is it for the whole company?

123

E2: For the whole company, that's also overall not just [COMPANY'S DIVISION], it's really sort of overall, yeah.

124

PM: And do you have specific guidelines or discussions for your communication team, like all regarding communication or is always more general?

125

E2: There's nothing special, specific. Yeah, for the moment.

126

PM: I have a question which is unrelated to that, but before I forget, since we are, I am going to provide a transcript in my thesis of our conversation without your name and without the name of your company. You've read me out loud. The content of the-

127

E2: Yeah. Yes.

128

PM: -The pages regard the limitation opportunities. Do you want me to eliminate this part, or do you want me to leave it? I can do both. It's just for your confidentiality.

129

E2: I would... as it's internal. You mean the opportunities and limitations. OK, I would.

130

PM: Yes, yes. Because you read number one, number two, number three, I can just blur it out so that no one can read it.

131

E2: I would have to ask my boss if she... because she knows.

132

PM: Yes.

133

E2: Yeah. For my understanding, it's nothing specific, it's general information, but let me ask her and I will, after the interview, send you an e-mail if you can use it or not.

134

PM: Yes. OK. Yeah. Yes, that's perfect. Yeah, that's perfect. I was just wondering. Thank you very much.

135

E2: Thanks.

136

PM: Yes, looking back at the AI, is it something that you regularly work with, the one you have doubts or is it something that you know is there, but it's not really a part of your work in the process. This sort of guideline?

137

E2: The guidelines.

138

PM: Yes.

139

E2: I kind of I don't look at them because I know them already. So, for me it's kind of... and also for my use, it's clear that first what I produce for LinkedIn is something external. So, I have to pay attention a lot and I get my approvals before I publish. So yeah, instantly I apply the guidelines and the rules regarding AI.

140

PM: Yes, OK.

141

E2: In my work.

142

PM: You also have discussions or meetings regarding that or just the guidelines?

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E2: For the moment, just the guidelines, yeah.

144

PM: Umm I have another question. So, you have some sort of guidelines explaining how to use it and kind of already know from your experience. Would you say that your approach regarding AI and communication is more preventive, so sort of avoiding an issue beforehand, or is sort of more reactive?. So, try to find a solution for an issue that has already occurred. Which is your strategy?

145

E2: I think it's preventive, yeah.

146

PM: Yes. And would you know what to do in case of a crisis? Of course, related to AI or an issue. Do you have something already prepared?

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E2: I don't think that we will have an issue because we are so strict.

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PM: Yes.

149

E2: In what we do before.

150

PM: Yeah, that you don't think anything is going to happen.

151

E2: If there is an issue, I would just report it to my boss and then it would go, but I have really no idea what an issue in this field and all the security data could be. That's not something we are dealing with. That's something in our IT department, yeah.

152

PM: Mm hmm. OK. Yeah. Yeah. Are you satisfied with the current use and strategy that you have with AI, or do you think that's something more would be needed to be more effective?

153

E2: For the moment, I'm happy. Yes. Maybe another topic would be the video creations. We have announced... ah, now that we are mentioning it. We have also on a regular basis some compliance-

154

PM: OK.

155

E2: Trainings kind of and there the last one in our last trainings, they mentioned the deep fakes to pay attention. So, it's not completely related to communication, but also it touches base. So, there is some, some, yeah there is more information on a regular basis I would say about AI, yeah.

156

PM: Yes. Mm hmm. Yes, it's still. Yeah.

157

E2: But yeah, I think for video creation we could use it more. Cause we do creation for LinkedIn for social media, also for our website, and it is quite intense, like in resources and money wise you have to invest a lot of time and maybe there we could use it more.

158

PM: Yes. Yes. Would it need more training using it for video creation? Or do you think it's still part of what you already have?

159

E2: Yes, for in my case, yeah, I would need more training, yeah.

160

PM: So, my questions have been answered. I had for a set of questions regarding yes, the implementation of AI ethical challenges and strategies.

161

E2: Very good.

162

PM: So, before I completely, we completely stopped the interview. I would like to give you the possibilities to tell me anything basically that you feel is relevant for today's interview, but we didn't touch upon during the meeting anecdote stories. I would like to give you to let you free, to do or to tell me anything that is nice and relevant to you.

163

E2: Yeah. I think it was very complete already the interview and I was surprised I could answer so many questions because really it's an it's a new, it's a new topic for us as well. And for me especially so I have no further questions, no further topics to mention, it's fine for me. Yes. And as I said I will, I will I will check if I can share with you just in a Word document.

164

PM: Yes. Yes, it was really helpful. Mm hmm. OK, it's fine for you, yes. Perfect. Yes, no worries.

165

E2: Yeah.

166

PM: The final I mean I will. I will have to give him the thesis in June. So until June, no one is going to see anything. So you basically have until June to reply. There's no stress in it.

167

E2: OK. OK. Perfect. OK. So you have some months still ahead?

168

PM: Yes, I have a couple of months until I can. Yeah. Finish. I would start now evaluating the interviews. This was the last one and collecting the data I had 10 Yes, yes, yes. I think it's sort of me the point.

169

E2: OK, OK. Yes, I did too many, many interviews. 10 not bad, huh? Very good. Yeah. Yes, yes. Are you full a full time student or part time full time?

170

PM: It's now I'm doing it full time. Yes, I'm. I'm happy to be almost done.

171

E2: Good. Very good. Yeah, otherwise. Yeah, I can imagine. Yeah. No. But you did very good, very good questions, interesting insights. And I think it was an interview where we start thinking about the topic and it's important. So thank you very much. Yeah.

172

PM: Thank you. Thank you to you as well. You had some great answers that you could cover all the aspects, so I was very happy with it as well. And yes, thank you very much.

173

E2: Thanks. Thanks a lot. Perfect. OK. I will get back to you via e-mail regarding this point.

174

PM: OK. Yes, yes. Thank you very much. Bye. Thank you very much. Bye bye.

175

E2: Thanks. Take care. Bye bye.

Appendix E: [Interview Transcript_FI1]

1

Interview Transcript – FI1:

2

March 3rd, 2025, h. 13.00, Interview on Microsoft Teams

3

PM: So, I've explained to you what I am going to do. We are talking about ethics in communication departments when it comes down to artificial intelligence. In order for us to have a shared understanding, I would like to start the interview with the definition of what is ethics for this specific purpose. So, for this interview, ethics is understood as an intersection of ethical AI, business ethics, and ethics in corporate communication. So, in this context, ethics entails acting responsibly to balance innovation and societal impact, mitigate risks and promote fairness and respect towards social and human values. Do you agree with this definition? Is there anything else you feel would be relevant for you to add, or does it work for you?

4

FI1: Mm hm. No. So yeah, it works for me.

5

PM: Perfect. So, I would just like to start with a couple of easy questions. I mean, I know you're not directly from the field of corporate communication, but you are an AI expert. So how long have you been working in this field? Yes, a bit about your story with this aspect of the field.

6

FI1: Well, sure, no problem. Principally, I'm head of innovation and since two years I'm responsible for scaling the whole generative AI approaches in our company and well, I have a strong relationship also with all the communication and ethics things, even though my history is mainly focused on, on the technical part, but if you scale it up, the ethical and governance discussions are absolutely relevant, and yeah, we did several things there.

7

PM: OK. So, are you basically kind of an expert in both fields, or could you define yourself this way?

8

F11: Yeah, I wouldn't say an absolute expert in communication, so I didn't study or something, but I'm aware of the questions you wanna pose.

9

PM: Yeah. Yes.

10

F11: We work intensely also with communications and marketing.

11

PM: Perfect. That's good. So now let's start with the actual questions related to AI's implementation. So, how often do your communication team in your company use generative AI to complete their tasks? So, in what frequency is AI applied?

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F11: Well, I would say today it's on a daily base, but we need to differ on... on one hand we have a really open tool, like we currently have Copilot. This is some kind of ChatGPT adoption which is secure, which is currently based on GPT 4.0 model, and is provided by Microsoft with all this data protection possibilities, which enables us to use more than just public data. And I'd say I know of my colleagues at the communication department, that they often use it as a hint giver or to start with something, or to challenge some texts. And so... therefore this approach... and we enable that also with an intense program at [COMPANY'S NAME] and, and I'd say, and I know from these colleagues, that they often use it.

13

PM: Right. So, you already mentioned Copilot. My second question would have been which tools do you use? Do you only use Copilot, or do you also integrate other tools and why?

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F11: We primarily for the flexible usage, we use Copilot. We know that some people use, on their private computers, they use other tools, but from the official side at our company it is Copilot, for the for the chat functionality versus an LLM feature. We certainly also have quite a journey behind us in identifying concrete use cases where you need a more strict implementation, and where you also use cloud

resources. We currently work primarily with Azure, and there we have an AI foundation developed which can be used to implement specific use cases. Or we work together with some partners that provide us with concrete implementations, for example, one use case in communication is to shorten a press text. Often you need to provide different newspapers with more shorter information than we edited, and therefore we have developed a hardened prompt setting, or agents, which really shorten the text but still keep the tone of voice of [COMPANY'S NAME] and the way we communicate the essential information we want to provide in this text and therefore we have developed like a more strict workflow in use cases like this.

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PM: When you say strict, what do you mean by that?

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F11: This means that that it is a controlled ad option. If you use Copilot, it depends on the prompt you use...you can use a prompt, shorten the text and he does it, but he does it in a manner which is not reliable. Maybe it might be good, and you can... I always say "In Copilot is like... it is absolutely important from the ethical side to have a human-

17

PM: Mm hmm. Yes.

18

F11: -Controlling everything", I mean, we must be aware at [COMPANY'S NAME] and we use all these Gen AI tools, primarily human based. This means it's always the human that controls and that deploys. So that is, we'd have no automated tasks in communication where we just for example say, "This is the text and send it directly to the newspaper". There are always men in the loop. A human, I mean, not just men.

19

PM: It's really nice, because you basically with one answer you already answered A couple of my questions.

20

F11: OK.

21

PM: Another one that I wanted to add is that you were saying you have use cases. So, for example, shortening texts. Are there any other activities in which AI is frequently implemented that you know of?

22

FI1: Yeah, there is. There's quite some, I mean, what we did, we did make an intense business analysis where we collected all the use cases, primarily focusing on generative AI adoption. At our company currently this is a catalogue of around 450 use cases which we know of, and some of them are worth to be implemented in the way that we say "Well this needs to be implemented", the more reliable approach. But those are most are mostly not in the communications environment because in communications, well, I'd say with copilot itself you have quite a good tool set to use. And sure, with this example of shortening text, this is a good sample which helps us to communicate. I mean, on the other hand we have we have like... but this is more on the pilot phase, things to edit or to-

23

PM: OK.

24

FI1: -To draft internal use for the Intranet, or maybe even for the Webpage, where we provide some tools and where we try to find out if this shortens the process to develop these kinds of text.

25

PM: You were talking about these 450 use cases that you have. Does this mean that you kind of have a set of regulations or prompt ideas for your employees that kind of already know what is possible for them to do? Or is something that you have noticed that people were doing?

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FI1: No, no, no, this is. This is primarily the business use cases where we could use Gen AI. What we also have is a prompt library.

27

PM: OK.

28

FI1: This is like a set of predeveloped prompts that we provide or that employees develop and share with us, and we share it with the whole company. So, where we say "Well, this is this is basically approved, it works this prompt", but this is more in

the usage and adoption of a tool like Copilot. For example, if someone has translation of text. We say, “Well, principally we have a standard approach where we currently are switching from a language model to element-based translation with a partner and still use the glossary feature”, for example. We also have a prompt but here using the glossary, which is in our case a set of...I mean we communicate in in three languages officially. And there we have a set of words or phrases that need to be translated in a proven manner and with open prompting. This is not so reliable, so therefore we have there translation tool which is being switched because we've seen that the quality with LLM based translation is better than with the historic approaches we used. But yeah-

29

PM: Do you have...I mean, I assumed these prompts are for every department in your company. Do you have any aspect or prompt from the prompt library that you mentioned, that are specifically relevant for the field of corporate communication, or that are designed specifically for them?

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FI1: We have several, yeah. And we might invite every, every department to share with us. I know they have some... I mean it always starts personal, then then you maybe share it in in your department... we're not aware of every prompt that is being shared, but what we just provide centrally is this library where we say “Well, share it with the whole company”. I mean in our company... it is good to know we are cooperative banks, so this means we have

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PM: Mm hmm.

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FI1: 19 legal entities, and all of them use... and all of them have some communication also, and we have corporate communication at [COMPANY'S NAME] in Switzerland, which is doing the official communication versus the market or the... yeah, the official publications but for example marketing, a lot of banks have their own marketing who do their own jobs and therefore yeah. It differs.

33

PM: Yes. I think I kind of got an overview of how you use AI, so I would like to switch to concrete ethical challenges. In that case, my first question would be, where do you personally see the main ethical challenges regarding the use of generative AI in the field of corporate communication?

34

F11: I think that there are some challenges that need to be addressed. If we look at the ethical challenges at first and that's how we mitigate principally all the ethical approaches is... we need to control by a human. I mean, depending on the models, models have biases. Because they're trained with historic data, so if historic data, for example, has issues with discrimination, I mean, this is nowadays lived otherwise than it used to be 1020 years ago, but the LLM has texts...historical texts. And we know that that it is the job of a statistical system, with these LLMs, even the new ones that, yeah...they try to mitigate some ethical challenges, but they can't do all of them because yeah, as I said it's statistics. So, if you say for example "Give me a text for [meaning: *about*] a person that is absolutely intelligent". It might be that there are only common examples of men, because historic data is full of these kinds of texts, and therefore you need to proofread what comes out and to check it on these kinds of elements.

35

PM: Is there a concern that you hear most about people coming from the communication department, maybe talking to you about a specific problem that they encounter, or do they have? Yes, anything that they are concerned about.

36

F11: Well, interestingly, I mean...we're used to... as long as, as you understand what you do. We don't hear a big issue with these elements, to be honest, I'm sure we're aware of that. That's why we do a lot of literacy, so that people understand what they can expect. But as long as it's not automated, there is no issue. We still have enough people that control these, these texts, and honestly in in business related communication, the discrimination part, for example, well, it's not so huge if we communicate, for example, our numbers.

I mean, these ethical questions we often hear about are really important if you maybe have some educational formats or whatever and that is often not the case in our in our situation.

37

PM: I think it's interesting what you're saying, that basically the problems that we encounter depend on what you communicate. Considering that you are from the financial field, let's say do you see a specific issue which is very relevant for your field and might not be as relevant for others?

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F11: No, no, I honestly, really, really don't.

39

PM: OK, that's fine.

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F11: There are issues but, but I think it's not ones that are more relevant because we are a financial institution and as I say it, it depends on the kind of text you do. I mean, what's the, what's the public and who is at adressant, and is there no biases in it, or...yeah, things like these questions need to be posed. I mean, there's just something, but it's just this is more... Well, it might be addressed in the ethical part. We say to our employees "If you don't redigate [meaning: *edit*] the text mostly, if you don't change a lot of things we expect you to put in a remark saying this has been created with the help of AI. This is this is mainly relevant in sense of using images, I mean this is not in the field of communication primarily, but yeah if we would use... but we don't... we for example clearly decided not to use AI generated pictures of humans because we we're a company saying we want to be close to the people. So, we want to show real people but we for example use AI to generate ideas-

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PM: Yes.

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F11: -On how we could make some kind of communication on the visual side.

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PM: Yes, I have this feeling that your company feels pretty safe when it comes to... I'm sorry, there's something going on outside. I don't know if you hear the noise, but I was saying, I feel that you are pretty confident in the way not only you, but the company... it sounds like you know what you're doing when it comes to AI. So, do you have any specific approaches or guidelines? So, for example, we talked about the prompt that you use, and that people can consult if they have any questions or a set of strategies. Anything concretes that helps you regulate how you use AI.

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F11: We do have for the usage of Copilot. I mean there, there we put on a small set of rules which we defined in a in a cross functional team. And this... is but his is mainly addressing things like data protection. It is things like what kind of information you can use. For example, we don't use any data of persons versus LLMs. We have some information that we say "Well, check on legitimacy and freeing text of discrimination. So, proof on that directly. Yeah, we have some kind of telling

them when to mark, if it's Gen AI generated content. Yes. So, these are some rules we define and which we also train the people.

45

PM: I would say that these are more sort of preventive rules that make sure that your employees do not do anything that might lead to problems. If anything happens and a problem or....so for example, an ethical problem occurs with the way someone uses AI. Do you also have strategies in that sense?

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F11: Yeah, it's a. It's a normal... well, we have, but they're not there because of AI.

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PM: In case of a crisis, or for crisis communication...

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F11: Because we say that the person publishes, the responsibility lies in human. So, nowadays, if I write the text... if I would work in the communication department, I send it out and it is full of discrimination, then I am responsible. If I use Gen AI to generate something and I don't-

49

PM: Yes, yes.

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F11: -Approve if it's free of discrimination. I'm in charge. Even though I use a tool, so therefore, as long as we don't use it automated it is the same mechanisms that that that we have today implemented. This is mainly-

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PM: Yes.

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F11: -Four eyes' principles, things like that, that that we say, "Well, we have some clearance policy", how we check texts that go public. But they're not done because of AI.

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PM: They're just general.

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F11: They're here because we want to ensure that we have discrimination-free texts in the web or in communication.

55

PM: Yes. Do you think that this is enough, or do you think that some more aspect might be added to this kind of strategy? Also considering the field is kind of quickly developing?

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F11: For the moment, I think it's enough. The question would be if you use agentic AI elements, I mean fully automated process is in our production case. So, meaning that we won't have enough resources to check the texts, but I absolutely say this is not the strategy we follow.

57

PM: Yes. Yes.

58

F11: We still want to have people that that approve, and in communications I don't see that we have currently use cases that really are in need of full automation. Yeah.

59

PM: OK, so basically as long as people are in charge then it shouldn't be that big of an issue because you can always have people in charge, and if something happens it is the person who is responsible.

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F11: It is no issue as long as we have people that are able to edit these texts.

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PM: Yes.

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F11: This is probably a problem that might come up, say, but this is a challenge in education. We have...I mean, how do people learn to write discrimination free texts if they only generate stuff? But that is not a problem we have nowadays, that might be an issue if, for example, academic teaching isn't having the effect that people know what they would do, if they would do it themselves. You understand what I mean? And at the moment we have these people aboard and if we hire somebody,

we want to see their personal competences. We don't say, "Well, the most important is that you can prompt, you don't need to be able to really check the text quality". I mean that would be that. Yeah. I mean if we were a tech company, maybe we say "Well, we won't have enough people in our communications department" then this might be a question, but at the moment this is not something we follow strategically as long as we say it's the human in the loop approach.

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PM: Then. I think the main aspect of my guidelines for this interview have been covered. I've added some other questions; I changed some of them as per usual. Before closing it off, I would like to ask you if there is a concrete example or something that you have experienced that you might want to share with me. That kind of summarises what you have told me until now.

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F11: I think I tried to summarize what I have told you also in the beginning.

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PM: Mm hmm. Oh yes, it's more like...

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F11: What I really honestly can say is that we are quite positive that this helps us to better texts, to do better communication in the end with the help of generative AI adoption, we're quicker. So, it's an efficiency element. So, this means we have more time to check on quality. And with that we will have, also better future texts if I bring it to simplicity. I mean, we generated content, you have this this new Pareto principle, I would say you can do good texts with no effort. But to be really good you can invest more time in making really great texts. As long as you have enough people.

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PM: Yes. The question that I was going to ask you, actually, and then I kind of worded it weirdly, I was sorry, but it's great that you said that because it's a great add is that if you have kind of an act of Tor story that basically shows OK, yes, what we did was successful and this is a concrete story of.

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F11: Sorry. Ah, sure, yeah. I mean, the example of shortening text. For example, if you have a press text having 6000 characters and the newspaper says, "Well, we don't take more than 3000." This is a job no one loves, shortening something you have developed already. And if you have a good proposal, this makes the job more

fun, and you get more time for the stuff that really needs human interaction. So, I really am happy if people come to me and say well, this really helps me to do the shitty stuff more fast, in a good quality, and I can invest my time in in things where I really can make a difference. That is a sample of this short you of the small use case of shortening stuff, but.

69

PM: Yes. Yes, yes, but thank you. I feel that we have covered all the aspects that I wanted to. If you have anything else that you want your hand would like to add, feel free to do so. Otherwise, for me I think everything is covered for today.

70

F11: Mm hmm. Right. And if you have any further questions, just let me know. I'm looking forward to your paper.

71

PM: Perfect then. Yes, I will provide it to you as soon as I am done with everything in summer, so.

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F11: I love love to read it.

73

PM: Perfect. Then for me, it is everything for today. Thank you very much for your time. And yes, I will wait for your document and then we will. I will write you again in July. I think with the daisies. Perfect.

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F11: You're absolutely welcome. Perfect. All the best for for your work and thanks for the questioner and I'll send you the the document with my signing just in a few minutes. Have a great time.

Appendix F: [Interview Transcript_FI2]

1	Interview Transcript – FI2
2	March 12th, 2025, h.15.00, Interview on Microsoft Teams
3	<p>PM: Also. Die Aufnahme ist gestartet, super. Ich würde dann sehr gerne starten, dass es wie eine Art «common ground» gibt, wie wir Ethik in diesem Zusammenhang verstehen können. Das wäre für den Zweck dieses Interviews eine Schnittmenge aus ethischer KI, Unternehmensethik und auch Ethik in der Unternehmenskommunikation.</p> <p>In diesem Zusammenhang bedeutet Ethik Verantwortungsbewusstes Handeln, um Innovation und gesellschaftliche Auswirkungen in Einklang zu bringen, also Risiken zu minimieren und Fairness und Respekt gegenüber sozialen und menschlichen Werten zu fördern .Ist das für Sie auch sinnvoll oder haben sie etwas, das sie noch anpassen möchten, basierend aus Ihrer Erfahrung? Oder ist das für Sie auch okay so?</p>
4	<p>FI2: Nein, das kann ich unterschreiben. So also bei uns natürlich branchenbezogen sehr wichtig noch medizinische Faktoren, die hier natürlich auch noch reinspielt.</p>
5	<p>PM: Ja. Ja, das versteh ich 100%.</p>
6	<p>FI2: Aber sonst absolut einverstanden, ja.</p>
7	<p>PM: Super, dann würde ich auch gerne mit ein paar lockeren Fragen starten. Also, wie lange arbeiten Sie in Unternehmenskommunikation?</p>
8	<p>FI2: In diesem Unternehmen oder ganz allgemein?</p>
9	<p>PM: Allgemein.</p>

10

FI2: Ah. 14 Jahre.

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PM: 14 Jahre, das ist schon viel, und in diesem Unternehmen?

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FI2: Seit eineinhalb Jahren.

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PM: Ja, und woran besteht ihre Arbeit jetzt also in Ihrer Position bei diesem Unternehmen?

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FI2: Ich leite den die gesamte Abteilung Corporate Communication von [COMPANY'S NAME].

15

PM: Mhm.

16

FI2: Das umfasst die Unternehmenskommunikation, aber auch Public Affairs und die Übersetzungsdienste sind mir unterstellt.

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PM: Ja. Ja, alles klar. Also, jetzt würde ich gerne direkt zum Thema KI sprechen, und meine erste Frage wäre: Wie oft nutzen Sie, oder auch ihre Kolleg:Innen, generativen KI für Kommunikationsaufgaben, also mit welcher Frequenz?

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FI2: Das ist sehr unterschiedlich in unserem Team, es gibt Leute, die nutzen das so gut wie gar nicht und es gibt Leute, die das nutzen mehrmals täglich, also das ist... ich habe festgestellt, dass das sehr generationenabhängig ist.

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PM: Mhm, ja, Mhm. OK.

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FI2: Wir haben Leute bei uns im Team, die sind 50 plus, die verwenden das teilweise nur sehr sporadisch, und wir haben Leute frisch ab Kommunikationsstudium, und für die ist das ein tägliches Werkzeug.

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PM: Mhm. OK ja. Mhm ja und Sie persönlich?

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FI2: Ich persönlich, ich würde jetzt mal sagen... mehrmals wöchentlich, aber nicht täglich.

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PM: Ja nicht täglich, ja, alles klar. Und welche KI-Tools verwenden Sie am meisten? Und auch warum haben sie vielleicht bestimmte Tools ausgewählt und andere nicht?

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FI2: Was ganz klar am häufigsten angewendet wird, sind Übersetzungstools.

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PM: Mhm ja.

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FI2: Da haben wir ein eigenes Tool aus Datenschutzgründen.

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PM: Ja.

28

FI2: Das nennt sich [COMPANY'S NAME] Translator, ist aber eigentlich wie DeepL mit dem Unterschied, dass die Daten nicht ins World Wide Web rausgehen zu Trainingszwecken.

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PM: Ja. Ja, alles klar.

30

FI2: Wir haben ein eigenes [COMPANY'S NAME] GPT, das wie Chat GPT funktioniert, auch mit der gleichen Einschränkung, dass die Daten nicht zu Trainingszwecken rausgehen. Auch das verwenden wir. Ja, das sind so die häufigsten im Moment.

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PM: Aha ja, und welche Vorteile sehen Sie hier, wenn Sie diese Tools nutzen oder wieso brauchen sie oder nutzen Sie diese?

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FI2: Einerseits Effizienz bei so Routinetätigkeiten das ist sicher der grösste Vorteil.

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PM: Mhm ja.

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FI2: Manchmal auch, um sich schnell eine Übersicht über ein Thema, das man noch nicht so gut kennt, zu verfassen, so die wichtigsten Quellen wichtigsten ja... welche Punkte dreht sich eine Debatte. Oder um längere komplexe Themen zusammenzufassen, wenn man nicht 150-seitiges Dokument lesen möchte.

35

PM: Ja. Alles klar. Und dann die Aufgaben, bei denen Sie diese Tools einsetzen, sind dann eben Übersetzung, haben Sie gesagt... Zusammenfassungen... und gibt es sonst etwas, dass Sie damit machen?

36

FI2: Ja, also, es gibt Kolleginnen und Kollegen im Team, die verwenden diese Tools auch für wirkliche, für Schreibaarbeiten, dass sie beispielsweise einen längeren Text zu einem Thema schreiben und dann die Kurzversion für die für die einzelnen Social-Media-Kanäle von KI schreiben lassen, explizit mit dem Prompt, so dass es für uns... in unserem Tone of Voice kommt. Wir haben auch ein Tool, das wird aber vor allem vom Marketing, teilweise aber auch von der Unternehmenskommunikation genutzt. Das ist trainiert auf die Tone of Voice von [COMPANY'S NAME], wo wir Texte durchlaufen lassen können, beispielsweise für employer branding. Dass es immer im gleichen Tonfall daherkommt und nach [COMPANY'S NAME] klingt, da werden die Texte mit KI in die richtige Tone of Voice gebracht, auch das wird kommt häufig zur Anwendung bei uns.

37

PM: Ja. Jetzt sind sie auch negative KI für Bildgenerierung oder Videogenerierung oder nur Texte?

38

FI2: Bildgenerierung noch sehr beschränkt, wir haben viele Kommunikationskanäle eben, wo es um Gesundheits-, Ernährungs- und Bewegungsthema Themen geht-

39

PM: Mhm.

40

FI2: -Wo man traditionell auf Stockbilder zurückgegriffen hat, um das zu illustrieren, und da wird teilweise mit KI gearbeitet, um etwas Passendes zu generieren. Videos bis jetzt noch gar nicht.

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PM: Das nicht, ja OK. Und wenn Sie diese Tools auch in Ihrer Arbeit integrieren, wie wird das gemacht? Gibt es zum Beispiel Menschen, die diese kontrollieren müssen? Oder wie sieht das aus allgemein bei Ihnen?

42

FI2: Ja, das ist bei unserer Branche sicher speziell, wir haben sehr strenge Auflagen seitens der regulierenden Behörde, weil wir sehr hochsensible Gesundheitsdaten bei uns verarbeiten, auch die Kunden-Kommunikation enthält natürlich teilweise sehr sensible Informationen über die psychische oder physische Gesundheit dieser Kundinnen und Kunden.

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PM: Ja.

44

FI2: Und die dürfen natürlich keinesfalls irgendwie ins World Wide Web gelangen.

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PM: Ah ja.

46

FI2: Und deshalb müssen wir diese abgegrenzten Lösungen verwenden, und auch dort dürfen die sensiblen Sachen... die dürfen gar nicht hochgeladen werden. Es ist natürlich schwierig, das zu kontrollieren, vor allem, weil wir eine sehr dezentrale Organisation sind. Mit etwa 60 Standorten in der Schweiz.

47

PM: Ja.

48

FI2: Und da können wir nicht allen über die Schultern schauen, wir wissen nicht, was auf den einzelnen Agenturen was gemacht wird, aber wir suchen das so gut wie möglich mit Weisungen und Kontrollen in den Griff zu bekommen, dass der Datenschutz auch wirklich eingehalten wird.

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PM: Ja. Ausser Datenschutz, wenn wir ganz allgemein über die Outcomes sprechen, manchmal sind diese mehr zuverlässig als anderen, zum Beispiel werden diese auch kontrolliert von Experten?

50

FI2: Ähm ja, wir veröffentlicht sehr viel Content zum Thema, eben wie Gesundheitstipps, medizinisches Wissen, und da haben wir ein klares, ein 4 Augen Prinzip, das mindestens 2 Menschen den Text noch durchgelesen und kontrolliert haben müssen, bevor er veröffentlicht wird.

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PM: Mhm.

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FI2: Das ist Standard bei uns.

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PM: Wenn wir dagegen mehr über die ethischen Herausforderungen sprechen, ich würde gerne fragen, wo sehen Sie die grössten ethischen Herausforderungen beim Einsatz von KI in Unternehmenskommunikation, also allgemein in diesem Umfeld?

54

FI2: Mhm. Ja, da müsste... das ist ein bisschen ein Blick in die Glaskugel, oder? Aber ich höre natürlich von gewissen Kollegen, dass die Prozesse schon viel, viel automatisierter sind.

55

PM: Ja.

56

FI2: Und ja, um den gewissen Effizienzgewinn zu erzielen, muss man natürlich immer mehr auch vertrauen, dass sie diese Sachen so produziert. Und ja, man muss ja den Kauf, den Controlleraufwand dann irgendwann zurückfahren können, und ich habe dieses Vertrauen noch nicht so ganz muss ich ehrlich sagen.

57

PM: OK.

58

FI2: Ich glaube, es braucht es diese menschliche Kontrolle unbedingt, um sicherzustellen, dass nicht etwas kommuniziert wird, dass am Schluss nicht Unternehmenswerten entspricht, und ja, ich meine, es ist sehr schwer einzuschätzen, mit welchen Daten also eine solche KI dann nach wirklich trainiert worden ist, und ob da nicht doch etwas einfließen, dass man vielleicht nicht drin haben will.

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PM: Mhm.

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FI2: Und die Schwierigkeit, die ich in Zukunft sehe, ist...die Kleine, die jetzige Generation von Leuten, die in der Unternehmenskommunikation arbeitet, die hat das alles noch selber gelernt, das zu formulieren, sich zu überlegen, jedes Wort auf die Goldwaage zu legen.

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PM: Ja.

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FI2: Und die kann einen von der KI verfassten Text auch entsprechend einordnen und bewerten.

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PM: Ja.

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FI2: Wenn man aber schon von Grunde auf damit gelernt hat, mit KI-Texte zu schreiben, oder verfassen zu lassen, ja... dann mache ich mich etwa Sorgen, ob man in Zukunft diese Fähigkeit, ob die irgendwann verloren geht, oder? Ob sie das auch wirklich einschätzen und gewichten können.

65

PM: Das verstehe ich. Und wenn Sie vielleicht mehr spezifisch an Ihren Branchen denken, dann wo sehen Sie die grössten Herausforderungen? Wir haben vorher ein bisschen über Datenschutz gesprochen.

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FI2: Ja.

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PM: Gibt es sonst etwas anderes, dass für Sie wichtig ist?

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FI2: Ja ein sehr hoher Wert ist natürlich, dass die Leute uns vertrauen, dass wir medizinische Informationen, die wir veröffentlichen, dass es sich hundertprozentig darauf verlassen können, dass diese auch wirklich stimmen, also Tipps zu Impfungen, zu Medikamenten und so weiter, dass diese wirklich genauso gut sind, wie wenn sie von einem Arzt kommen.

69

PM: Mhm. Ja.

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FI2: Wir haben intern auch einen medizinischen Dienst mit Fachleuten, die diese Sachen geglesen und kontrollieren und ja, diese Qualität, die dürfen wir einfach nicht verlieren.

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PM: Aha.

72

FI2: Und die können wir auch nicht an eine KI zumindest vorläufig nicht an eine KI delegieren.

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PM: Ja. Und Sie haben zum Beispiel gesagt, dass Sie vertrauen KI noch nicht ganz, ist das so bei jedem in ihrem Team oder gibt es Menschen, die dagegen ein bisschen mehr Vertrauen haben, oder eine andere Sichtweise haben? Oder ist das homogen?

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FI2: Ja, die Faustregel ist je jünger eine Mitarbeiterin ein Mitarbeiter ist, desto höheres Vertrauen hat in diese Tools. Da geht es natürlich teilweise auch noch darum, ja, wenn man einen Beitrag produziert, oder? Hat die noch auch eine persönliche Handschrift? Also, wenn wir einen Autorenbeitrag, die man dann auch mit Namen zeichnet, in einem Kundenmagazin oder so, ist das wirklich noch selbst geschrieben oder nicht?

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PM: Ja.

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FI2: Und da prüfen wir natürlich teilweise auch nach und teilweise sieht man dann halt auch ja, gewisse Abschnitte wurden selbst geschrieben. Gewisse Abschnitte wurden mit KI generiert. Passt im Stil dann vielleicht nicht ganz zusammen und so. Da müssen wir teilweise schon noch korrigierende eingreifen. Und im Moment dann auch noch ein bisschen mit den entsprechenden Leitlinien, wie man mit diesen Tools wie frei mal mit diesen umgehen soll.

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PM: Ja. Genau das wäre auch meine nächste Frage gewesen, was denn ihre Strategien sozusagen, um diese Herausforderung zu vermeiden. Ich finde schon spannend, dass sie schon ihre eigenen Tools nutzen. Ich glaube, das vermeidet schon ein bisschen, das Risiko, aber sonst haben sie Leitlinien, haben sie gesagt, wir sehen Sie aus?

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FI2: Ja.

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PM: Welche Leitlinien haben Sie also? Was umfassen diese?

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FI2: Also bis jetzt gibt es nur Leitlinien bezüglich Datenschutzes.

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PM: OK, nur Datenschutz?

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FI2: Was jetzt für die Kommunikationsarbeit betrifft, sind wir noch daran, diese zu erstellen. Wir hatten da intern schon Workshops gemacht und eben da habe ich festgestellt, dass die Haltungen im Team auch ziemlich noch auseinander gehen.

83

PM: Ja.

84

FI2: Und ja, wir werden wir werden sicher differenzieren, je nach Art von Kommunikation, wie stark KI zum Einsatz kommen kann. Also ich habe vorhin schon angesprochen, beispielsweise zur Generierung von Kurztexen für Social Media ist sicher ein sehr effizientes Werkzeug und da haben wir.... das ist klar.... da kann man es anwenden, hingegen für längere Beiträge, Fachbeiträge, die Autorentexte sind und dann auch ins gedruckte Kundenmagazin kommen da besteht schon die

Erwartung, dass man die auch wirklich noch selber schreibt. Und KI dort vielleicht mehr als Inspiration nutzen? Für Formulierungsvorschläge, für Rechercheaufgaben, für Themen zu meinem Thema gesamtheitlich zu erfassen, ist man es... für diese Zwecke mehr einsetzt und weniger jetzt für die Schreibearbeit an sich.

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PM: Ja das das versteh ich auch schon. Sie haben auch zum Beispiel gesagt, dass Sie überprüfen, ob Texte von Menschen oder KI geschrieben wurden. Habe ich das richtig verstanden?

86

F12: Ich mach das nicht standardmässig, aber wenn ich einen Text redigiere, also redaktionell noch mal überarbeite und mir fällt auf, dass der der Stil wechselt-

87

PM: Aha.

88

F12: -Von einem Abschnitt zum anderen dann lass ich das durch ein entsprechendes Kontrolltool laufen und meistens sieht man dann recht schnell.

89

PM: Ja. Haben sie auch interne Kontrolltools oder sind diese öffentliche Kontrolltools, dass Sie nutzen?

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F12: Das da können wir, da verwenden wir öffentliche, dafür haben wir keine eigenes, bis jetzt.

91

PM: OK.

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F12: Vielleicht ändert sich das noch.

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PM: Ja dann.

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FI2: Aber ich hoffe eigentlich nicht, dass ich den Leuten noch lange immer so hinterherrennen und kontrollieren muss.

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PM: Ja.

96

FI2: Ich vertraue den Leuten eigentlich, und ich denke, wenn die Standards mal etabliert sind, dann spielt sich das relativ rasch ein, wie man das verwenden soll.

97

PM: Ja, dann würden Sie sagen, ist den Ansatz jetzt bei Ihrem Unternehmen mehr präventiv? Also, versuchen sie am meisten ein Problem oder ein Risiko zu vermeiden oder versuchen sie meistens, reaktive Lösungen zu haben? Also es gibt schon ein Problem, ein Problem ist aufgetreten, dann versuchen wir eine Lösung zu finden, also welchen Ansatz hatten sie präventiv oder reaktiv? Was würden Sie sagen?

98

FI2: Beim Datenschutz sicher eher präventiv, das müssen wir bei allem anderen eher reaktiv, weil wir schon die Haltung haben, die Leute sollen das ausprobieren, um überhaupt herauszufinden, was für Möglichkeiten, dass das bietet, wie sie das integrieren können, ihre tägliche Arbeit, das ist auch gewünscht, so von unserem CEO, der selber sehr technikaffin ist, und deshalb ja lassen wir die Leute ausprobieren und dann, wenn wir sehen, «Hey, da tauchen Probleme auf»-.

99

PM: Mhm ja. Ja.

100

FI2: -Erst dann schränken wir ein, und vorher schränken wir euch lieber nicht ein, das ist so.

101

PM: OK. Haben sie auch ein Teil zum Beispiel der Risikokommunikation speziell auf KI ausgerichtet? Oder es ist mehr wirklich eine Art auch Lösung, also «Schauen wir je nach Fall, was wir machen»? Oder haben sie auch standardisierte Prozesse in diesem Fall?

102

F12: Wie meinen Sie das mit der Risikokommunikation?

103

PM: Also ich meine, wenn etwas mit KI passiert, sagen wir mal, dass etwas publiziert wird, der mit KI geschrieben wurde und deswegen ist das nicht genau standardmässig.

104

F12: Aha.

105

PM: Die Qualität ist vielleicht niedriger, so in dieser Richtung.

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F12: Ja.

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PM: Dann haben Sie sich schon etwas geplant für dieses Szenario, oder müssten Sie theoretisch eine Lösung speziell für den Fall finden?

108

F12: Na, ich denke, dass wir können das mit unserem 4 Augen Prinzip können wir diesen Fall eigentlich ausschliessen.

109

PM: Mhm ja, OK ja.

110

F12: Das wird auch regelmässig überprüft, ob das so eingehalten wird im Team, das ja das ist das interne Risk Management hat da schon das Auge drauf.

111

PM: Ja. OK super und allgemein sind Sie zufrieden mit diesen Lösungen und diese Strategien, die Sie mir erzählt haben? Diesen Workshops und Leitlinien. Oder würden Sie sich etwas anderes wünschen oder mehr vielleicht?

112

F12: Ähm, ganz ehrlich, wir sind da noch etwas in der Findungsphase. Ich denke, dieser Prozess ist noch länger nicht abgeschlossen, auch weil das das komplette

Potenzial dieser neuen Technologien noch gar nicht so ganz abschliessend abschätzbar ist.

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PM: Mhm.

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FI2: Ich denke, das ist ein ongoing process, und das wird uns noch die nächsten Jahre ganz sicher beschäftigen, und ich denke auch eine Lösung, die jetzt vielleicht für dieses Jahr gut ist, muss nächstes Jahr vielleicht schon wieder überdacht werden, weil man neue Möglichkeiten...

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PM: Ja. Ja, Mhm.

116

FI2: Erst da muss man sehr flexibel bleiben, glaub ich.

117

PM: Gibt es etwas Spezielles, dass sie für die Kommunikationsabteilung haben möchten? Also ein Wunsch speziell für ihre Abteilung oder für ihr Team?

118

FI2: Was noch können sollte für uns?

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PM: Ja, oder was man noch implementieren könnte... Prompt zum Beispiel... ja, spezielle Leitlinie also ganz allgemein, es ist eine ganz offene Frage.

120

FI2: Ja eben auch, so smarte Leitlinien zu formulieren für die einzelnen Kommunikationskanäle ist für uns sicher. Ist sicher sehr wichtig, und das ist eine Arbeit, die Moment an dran sind. Und dann geht es sicher darum, auch die Leute, die mit diesen Tools arbeiten, möglichst alle auf einen guten Wissensstand zu bringen eben gesagt, eben zum Beispiel Weiterbildungen in Sachen wie «Wie prompte ich richtig», «Wie setze ich diese Ergebnisse richtig ein?», «Wie kann ich es auch einschätzen, was ist qualitativ gut, was ist weniger gut, wo kann ich das Maximum rausholen aus den Tools?», und «Wie nutze ich sie effizient?» Da braucht es sicher noch eine, da müssen wir noch ein 2 Stufen weiterkommen, das ist klar.

121

PM: Ja, OK. Ich wollte auch fragen: Haben Sie vielleicht noch ein Beispiel, wie Sie... also, ein konkretes Beispiel oder auch eine Anekdote, wie Sie KI nutzen, etwas, was vielleicht sie in Ihrer Karriere gesehen haben? Das für Sie jetzt eine Rolle spielt? Also ganz allgemein etwas, das für Sie relevant ist, ein Fall.

122

FI2: Also die grössten Fortschritte sehe ich natürlich bei der Effizienz in Sachen Übersetzungen bei uns, das ist dort geht es am schnellsten vorwärts.

123

PM: Mhm.

124

FI2: Dort investieren wir auch massiv in die neuesten Tools. Und ja, wir erhoffen uns von dort deutlich mehr Geschwindigkeit, gute Qualität und gleichzeitig deutlich tiefere Kosten. Da sind wir im Moment intensiv sehr intensiv dran.

125

PM: Mhm ja. Wie würden... Sie haben eben Qualität erwähnt, deswegen wollte ich fragen, wie beurteilen Sie die heutige Qualität von KI, generierten Texten in Ihrem Bereich konkret?

126

FI2: Und ja. Die sind oft... inhaltlich eigentlich schon recht gut, wenn man sie mit den richtigen Grundlagen füttert. Ähm, vom Sprachstil her werde ich noch nicht so glücklich, bin ich noch nicht so glücklich für gewisse Textsorten schon sehr gut, wenn es so rein faktische Texte sind, aber wenn man so ein gewisses-

127

PM: OK.

128

FI2: -Ja, so etwas, ich weiss gar nicht, wie ich das ausdrücken soll. Das ist so authentisch klingt so eine gewisse Handschrift hat, oder?

129

PM: Ja, klingt schon ein bisschen... ja.

130

F12: Und man ja, das kennen Sie ja sicher auch, gewisse Autoren liest man lieber als andere und generierte Texte-

131

PM: Mhm.

132

F12: Ja, die öden mich noch einer gewissen Zeit einfach an, weil sie immer so ein bisschen die gleichen Abläufe verwenden. Ja, ich lese das nicht so gerne, aber das wird vielleicht noch besser, wer weiss?

133

PM: Jetzt kann es sein, das kann es sein. Also ich möchte sagen, wir sind schon durch, also wir haben alle Frage schon schnell beantwortet, aber ich glaube, ich konnte schon die wichtigsten Punkte sammeln.

134

F12: OK.

135

PM: Ich habe Notizen geschrieben und natürlich habe ich noch meine Transkation hier dabei, und ich habe das Gefühl ich habe schon alles gehört, was ich für meine Masterarbeit brauche, deswegen super. Wir waren sehr schnell heute, aber aus diesem Grund ist für mich alles gut. Haben Sie sonst noch Fragen, oder etwas, das Sie gerne wissen möchten oder auch hinzufügen möchten?

136

F12: Natürlich noch Unternehmen. Mit welchen anderen Unternehmen Sie auch noch Interviews führen?

137

PM: Ja. Genau also, ich habe unterschiedliche Unternehmen ausgewählt, ich kann leider Ihnen nicht sagen genau mit wem ich gesprochen habe wegen dieser Anonymität ja, aber ich habe ansonsten weitere Versicherungen kontaktiert und Banken und Unternehmen aus dem Food and Beverage Industry, also Lebensmittelproduktion.

138

F12: Ja, das ist mir klar. Ja. Ja.

139

PM: Dann habe ich noch Engineering Sektor, also das war Ingenieurin allgemein und dann noch zum Schluss habe ich noch Pharmaceutical Sector, also medizinischen Sektor auch. Ja, Unternehmen die Medikamente produzieren. Das ist auch sehr spannend, weil natürlich der medizinische Bereich ist sehr stark reglementiert und dort gibt es am wenigsten Freiheit, wenn man KI-Tools nutzt.

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FI2: Ja.

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PM: Gut.

156

FI2: Vielen Dank für diese Fragen.

157

PM: Danke ihnen auch und dann ja, falls Sie möchten, würde ich Ihnen gerne die Maske arbeiten. Nächsten Monat zur Verfügung stellen, so können Sie noch die Ergebnisse schauen, aber ich glaube jetzt ja, aber für heute dann ist alles vielen Dank.

158

FI2: Würde ich sehr gerne ja, es würde mich sehr interessieren Mhm. OK, ich danke Ihnen und wünsche sehr viel Erfolg mit dem Abschluss in dem Fall.

159

PM: Danke, wünsche Ihnen auch einen ganz schönen Tag noch.

160

FI2: Merci schönen Abend und wiederschauen Frau Pellegrino.

161

PM: Danke, schönen Abend.

162

Appendix G: [Interview Transcript_FB1]

1	Interview Transcript – FB1
2	February 28th,2025, h. 14.00, Interview on Microsoft Teams
3	PM: Yes, perfect. So, the first thing I would like to do now that we have started officially, the interview is to provide you with a sort of understanding of what ethics is for this project. Of course, you already have your knowledge about it or so because you have a fairly theoretical background as well as experience, but for this specific purpose of the thesis, ethics is understood as an intersection... or so if I you see me looking up, it's because I have another screen with my notes. I will be also taking notes.
4	FB1: OK.
5	PM: So, as I was saying, ethics in my case is understood as an intersection of ethical AI, business ethics and corporate communication ethics, meaning that ethics entails acting responsibly to balance innovation and societal impact, mitigate risks, and promote fairness and respect. Sword, social and human values. So, we basically have this idea that being ethical means that we are acting with fairness and respect towards people in general, so society and human values.
6	FB1: Mm hmm.
7	PM: Does this resonates with you, or if you have anything else to add to this definition, then feel free to do so.
8	FB1: Sounds good to me for now.
9	PM: Perfect. And then I would start with very easy questions. How long have you been into this field? So how long have you been working in the corporate communication field?
10	FB1: Well, around 13 years.

11

PM: 13 yes, and now you're working in an agency you said. Can you tell me what your job consists of?

12

FB1: Well, I have different mandates, different clients.

13

PM: Yes.

14

FB1: Where I do corporate communication, crisis communication, social media, consult on the issues. That is kind of... write texts, articles...

15

PM: Basically everything.

16

FB1: Everything, yes. I have clients. Well, I have had clients from the finance industry, specifically payments. If you can anonymize the company, I'm going to tell you, but so you for your understanding, which was...maybe I will talk more about it later because it's a technology company, [COMPANY'S NAME].

17

PM: Yes.

18

FB1: People think, oh, credit cards. No, they provide the technology.

19

PM: Yes.

20

FB1: And so yeah, AI was quite a big subject there as well.

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PM: Sure.

22

FB1: I have clients from the infrastructure projects where I do project communication more and other communications... for Switzerland. It's [COMPANY'S NAME], yeah.

23

PM: I know it.

24

FB1: I have small banks. [COMPANY'S NAME]. Well, this is actually what I've had in the past three years. Well and little others, yeah.

25

PM: So, you have kind of an overview of different fields I would say.

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FB1: Yes.

27

PM: And perfect. This works very well... and then so this were the first questions, and now I would like to understand a bit more... how you personally use AI or how does your team use the AI. So, in my case it would be: How often do you use it? And also, you... I mean, and also your colleagues. So how often do you use AI to complete your tasks?

28

FB1: Mm hmm. So, I would say everybody in the agency works on a daily basis with DeepL and ChatGPT. We work in three, sometimes four languages. Not everyone is fluent in every language, so, to control ourselves...we do work very strongly with those. So, you know, we need to, as an agency, we need to provide perfect language, no typos, no grammar problems. So yeah.

29

PM: And why do you choose these tools specifically? Because for example, also to ChatGPT, there are also other programs, for example Gemini... What are the specific advantages that you see when using these exact tools?

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FB1: Well, to be very honest, I haven't tried Gemini because for me at the moment.

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PM: Mm hmm. OK.

32

FB1: If I'm not happy with DeepL I always consult ChatGPT as well. I mean how many tools can you use? I mean, let's, let's be honest, I've tried Copilot. Copilot is the one in the Edge browser.

33

PM: Yeah.

34

FB1: We don't work well together, but I've seen others like my bosses, they sometimes use Copilot. Yeah. And also, we have a license. We have a license for ChatGPT. Like we buy the license to have to use it more profoundly so-

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PM: Yes.

36

FB1: -That's the reason we work with, yeah.

37

PM: So, it's you're basically happy with the quality that you're receiving. So, you feel satisfied with the quality, yes.

38

FB1: Yes. Yes, although me personally, I like to try new stuff also on teams. You have a lot of-

39

PM: Yes.

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FB1: -New AI tools and from time to time I try them out, but as long as I don't see the value of really optimizing my work with it. There is no point using it, but I would say once, twice a year I test new stuff. I take the time I test new stuff and if I see it provides benefits, then I will start using it. Otherwise, I said "You're not there yet".

41

PM: Makes sense. Yeah.

42

FB1: And not no... I just want to say another platform we use very much...

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PM: Yes, no, you can go on. No problem.

44

FB1: Is Airtable.

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PM: OK.

46

FB1: Which is actually a database, but it works also with AI on the background, and it provides a platform... it's like it's like a development of Excel, yeah... but you

can share with your clients. As we're not in the same company, we don't have a shared-

47

PM: Yes.

48

FB1: - Files so on Airtable, we've built a database for media planning. And also media monitoring. We use it actually almost now for everyone and it's. Yeah, we're very happy with that. We've created our own basis.

49

PM: Sounds really nice. The other question I was about to ask you is: In which tasks are AI implemented? So, you said you have a variety of tasks such as social media, writing texts... in which tasks do you use AI? It may be some of them more than others, or maybe all of them equally...

50

FB1: Well, I would say. When I have a task that we need to work on a strategy or a new concept for some PR. Let's say there is an anniversary from a company. Yeah. And we always do brainstorming in the team first and then one is in charge to work out the process. Like a first draft and we do also brainstorm with ChatGPT.

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PM: OK, so it is sort of a starting the process and brainstorm if I understood you correctly.

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FB1: Yeah, yeah, I also brainstorm... I've always preferred to brainstorm with my colleagues.

53

PM: Yeah.

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FB1: But then in a second, you know, maybe it has a good idea to another good idea we didn't think of. Normally not. But you know, it's always good to have like different options. So that's what I use it for.

55

PM: Yes. Do you also use it to maybe correct or improve text or to generate text for example?

56

FB1: Yes and no.

57

PM: OK.

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FB1: Yes and no, because you cannot trust ChatGPT to write you a full text. It writes a lot of nonsense. I think ChatGPT works much better if you ask for short texts. For social media posts, for example, but also every company has its own style. So, you can't... I mean, to tell ChatGPT what it needs to know about a company and to write it the way it's supposed to... in the meantime, you wrote it yourself, right? So, I think you really need to... one needs to find out where it works. I mean, I've also started to prompt. I just did a CAS at the ZHAW in political communication and I did a research on a lot of articles, which in the short time I had it's by hand I would not have been able to analyze all these articles if it wasn't for ChatGPT, so I did a lot of prompting to perfect the analysis because it's something you know he can do if you-

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PM: OK. Yep.

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FB1: -If you work with short term, if you give him 100 pages and say analyze, then he will not do it well. But short things with a good prompt that that works. I... depending on what kind of social media, I also use it for social media. I have my written prompts. Don't tell our clients. Sometimes the output is really good. Sometimes not and I have to rewrite so yeah, I and you cannot try. You always need to control. It's like a small child. You always need to control because you never know.

61

PM: OK. Yeah. Understandable.

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FB1: If they're going to invent, it's going to invent something. So, I have my trust issues.

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PM: My next question, which you kind of already answered, is...I was asking how do you implement these tools, but you basically already told me, you basically share ideas with these AI tools so that you can have a little brainstorm. But mostly you write your own text or maybe some shorter text than you can give it to AI. But the most important thing for you is control, which was part of my question, the sort of human in the loop process. Is implemented in your case?

64

FB1: Yes, because I don't know how you say that in English...In German we call it "Geschwurbel". It's like a lot of hot air. Like, it sounds fantastic. But once you read, it's not saying anything. So ChatGPT is really good at that.

65

PM: OK. Yep.

66

FB1: And you can't... you can't get real specific and good texts from ChatGPT.

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PM: Yeah, I can understand what you mean.

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FB1: Which is actually... I'm very happy about that. So, we are still needed. You still need us.

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PM: It's obvious, I am happy as well.

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FB1: Yes.

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PM: That's fine.

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FB1: So yeah, I always say, "Every tool is as good as you know how to use it. But you can't use it for everything".

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PM: Yes, knowing when to use them. That's important. And if you think a bit more about ethical challenges in itself, where do you see these main challenges? So, if you think about using AI, what do you think would be an ethical issue that comes up? In your experience, as we have mentioned before. We can focus this aspect on the food and beverage industry. If you think this is possible for you, or even generally, what do you think?

74

FB1: I personally think you know, I am older. I already wrote a lot of papers. I grew up without computers.

75

PM: Yes.

76

FB1: So, I had to go through this process of having to read and having to write. Yeah, I think young people don't go through that process anymore because you have ChatGPT at hand. There are so many ways to take a shortcut, which I personally think for developing young minds... it's really bad because I think it's very

important for a young mind to go through... I'm repeating myself... through the process of reading, thinking, processing, and writing. It's a whole... it's a whole process which is not existent if you start using AI.

77

PM: If you think more specifically about the field of corporate communication you are working in, do you think there is something which is really specific to this kind of job when you start using AI?

78

FB1: Well, it goes into the same if you don't have the experience and you know how supposed to be, and you rely on GPT or on AI.

79

PM: Yes.

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FB1: How will you know that the output is correct? You... like when I was telling you, I can control it. I know how to control it. But because I learned it from scratch, I am very much afraid that we are growing into a society who doesn't really know. Or think enough for themselves and relies only on the output of ChatGPT, which makes people very manipulative [*probably meaning "manipulated"*] to whoever runs the AI.

81

PM: To think about manipulation. Are you maybe thinking about sharing false information? I mean, not on purpose because simply you do not check enough your sources or... just... it's more of an understanding question to understand your point of view. When you talk about people, I mean that, or is it kind of AI can become manipulative? Then it's this in this sense that you can just share and provide false information. So, for example, if you work in corporate communication, writing a text with something which does... It's not true.

82

FB1: You just don't know any better. Which I think is the biggest danger, and it might take another generation, but, you know when my kind dies out. Yeah.

83

PM: Yeah. Do you ever.

84

FB1: So yeah, that's I think one of the biggest challenges.

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PM: Sure. Yeah. And do you talk about these about AI in general and about these issues specifically with your department or the agency that you're working for, do you discuss these aspects as well or is it more your opinion, your experience?

86

FB1: Yeah. Well, we discuss, we discuss a lot at work, this problem of AI. We are kind of teaching AI by consulting AI... and many people are getting the same output, it's kind of. Even if it's a mistake or it's not a mistake, it's like you're reproducing the same storyline over and over again. Which is very dangerous and that's where my other point of view comes back in. You don't have enough knowledge to criticize it. Because you don't have, you haven't accumulated enough knowledge to be able to criticize it.

87

PM: Do you think this is a shared sort of shared concern that it's not your only concern? Yes and-

88

FB1: Yes, yes, it is a shared concern within our agency. Not only for our work but like in general.

89

PM: Yes, in general.

90

FB1: A general concern of people in my agency with AI, yeah.

91

PM: Yes. And so, considering that it is something that you all share, do you sort of have a specific approach in the way you use AI within your agency, a sort of...it might be rules or even unwritten rules, or sort of behavior that you adopt in within your agency when you start using AI.

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FB1: I think we're too small-

93

PM: Yes.

94

FB1: -To invoke rules, our boss always says to use human sense. Common sense.

95

PM: OK.

96

FB1: Which as you know, 10 people, 10 common senses.

97

PM: Yes.

98

FB1: My experience... I would say in our company is knowledge on the AI, how to use AI, are those people who use it more. I hadn't finished...we also use it a lot too... for example, to transcribe. Maybe you're gonna use it as well.

99

PM: Yes, definitely. I will double-check but I will use it.

100

FB1: So. It has; it has... But also there, I've had really bad experiences that I was like... reading... because . I put an audio in the... we use TransTurbo [*probably meaning: TurboScribe*] I think it's called-

101

PM: Yes.

102

FB1: -And then I use ChatGPT PT and tell him "Write me a protocol". And then I read the protocols and I'm like "That's not how it went down. And something is missing". So, at the end I still need to listen in, but generally, yeah, it works 70/30%.

103

PM: So, you can still use it.

104

FB1: It has accelerated the process of writing protocols so. So that's another, yeah.

105

PM: So, you said, I think it's very interesting that in your small group you use common sense or sort of common knowledge when it comes to these kinds of things.

106

FB1: Mm hmm.

107

PM: Would you know how to react in case of a crisis which is related to the use of AI. So, we made the example of writing something without double checking because you just do not know any better. You were talking about it. Would you know

what to do in case something goes out that you have produced, but it's not reliable information, for example?

108

FB1: That's a good question which I haven't been confronted with because I would say that all the senior consultants...I'm like the only one mainly using AI, the others, not that digitalized. So, they do not rely that much. On AI. And the young ones too. But their texts never go out without us checking it. So, I would say that's automatically. We have control of what goes out.

109

PM: OK. So, you kind of have a strategy of having people controlling the text before they go out?

110

FB1: Yes.

111

PM: I don't. I mean, is it a strategy that was, I mean you do it either way. It's not only if people use AI, you still double check the text?

112

FB1: Exactly, exactly. It doesn't matter if it's AI or not AI. We have four to six [people]... I control and review of texts. Always.

113

PM: Do you think this is enough? Or if you think about it, would you wish to have a more or a different approach or something more that makes you think "OK" I don't know... "if I add this part and I'm sure the work which is going out is going to be perfect" or do you think for your context and the kind of job that you're doing then this is already what you need?

114

FB1: I think you always need the human touch because at the end... let's give you an example with [COMPANY'S NAME]. Yeah, I talked to the people of [COMPANY'S NAME].. I have meetings with them. I mail them. So, I have a lot of context.

115

PM: Yes.

116

FB1: ChatGPT doesn't have all this context. I can't feed all this information for it to have the context. Because you... it's like I would have to teach him and then next time he forgot everything already. So, there will always have to be this human control of proof reading and adding context to it, that's what I was telling you before. I never ever just take a text from ChatGPT, 99% of the time I have to rewrite it, but it

still gives me an idea. It's like more of brainstorming, you know, like, "OK, this is not OK. This is not how I want to do" it or "OK, that's a good structure. It helps me". And then I start rewriting. It does not work without... I call it human touch now.

117

PM: Now, yeah, yeah, it might understand what you mean.

118

FB1: I forgot your question.

119

PM: No, but I think you answered because I was saying if you are happy with your current sort of strategy and by saying that human touch is always needed, that is what you're doing, then I would say it kind of aligns. So, you are satisfied with how you are doing it?

120

FB1: Yes. Yes.

121

PM: One last question which goes more, as I've mentioned before, we have said it a couple of times, I was focusing now on what might be food and beverage industry when working with these kinds of companies in this sector. Did you find anything which was specific for them which might be relevant for the topic? The conversations we are having now. So maybe they have some specific concern about the use of AI related to their industry or something that they need more than others.

122

FB1: This is very interesting. Cause the only customer I've ever talked with about AI and how to use AI has been [COMPANY'S NAME] because they are a technology company, so they are pushing AI. They are using Copilot they're also recording meetings and then transcribing them, I think it's Copilot as well in in Teams, yeah.

123

PM: Yes, Copilot.

124

FB1: So, they have initiated this conversation, even though they never...they never talk to us about using it for our work or to accelerate our work, you know, to say budget, for example, by using AI. It's not a topic.

125

PM: OK.

126

FB1: I personally think that it's not a topic because we work with communication people as well. So, if we would say we will use it, they have to use it then suddenly companies may say, "Ah, we don't need as many people anymore."

127

PM: Yes.

128

FB1: So this is a conversation that just doesn't happen yet.

129

PM: So, it's not really...

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FB1: We're... we as an agency are certainly not gonna start the conversation.

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PM: Yes, OK. That's fair.

132

FB1: Ethical or not ethical? I mean, we need to work so...

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PM: Yeah. So, you'll kind of avoid maybe, something that could...

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FB1: I mean, I don't avoid using it and especially with budgets that you know, you know we've we have optimized. That's what I told you. We optimize by not using Excel anymore and transferring it. You know you, like project management, we through AI, we have managed to reduce hours and instead using use it for more measurements in PR. So that's not a loss of budget.

135

PM: Right, I see you.

136

FB1: You know, so I think this conversation could be a good conversation, you know? But as I said, I'm not gonna start it, but we use it. Yeah.

137

PM: I think we covered the main aspect that I wanted to which are AI's implementation ethical challenge and how you deal with them. So, I think to summarize, AI's implementation is basically in every aspect of your job, but I find it very interesting, you do not use it very much for text generation, which is probably the main reason tools like ChatGPT were created. And you said that an ethical challenge that you

see in it is that when you let AI generate your text, you can never know exactly, or I mean you can may think that the outputs are really good, but you need to be able to understand them and to evaluate them. And the way you make sure that you do that is by having someone with expertise checking the results. Basically, I think this summarizes these are the main points of our discussion today.

138

FB1: Yes. Yes.

139

PM: Before ending the interview, I would like to ask you if you have a sort of story or challenge or something that you have encountered in your years of experience which might think is a good example of what you we have discussed until now. Or sort or anything else, anything that you want to share. Which things could be a good way to close it off?

140

FB1: Looking into the future and bringing it back to where I started. I start to wonder if ChatGPT or certain AI should have, like an age, like what? At what age? You should be able to start using it, and in universities and school. Because otherwise ..., as "man auf Deutsch sagen würde, schaffen wir uns selbst ab" but not in a good way, because ChatGPT can pretend to be to have humanity and be social. But that's bullshit. It's just programmed to do it. It can switch in another direction just as quickly, if you program it. So having to rely on AI without questioning it, without being critical about it ... I think that's a real big danger and I think many people don't know how to use it properly. Because it seems so easy.

141

PM: Yes.

142

FB1: So, these would be my final words on the topic.

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PM: Yes. I asked you already all my questions, some of them I have changed. I want to thank you very much for your time and your valuable insights and I think I can now stop the recording... wait.

Appendix H: [Interview Transcript_FB2]

1	Interview Transcript – FB2
2	March 21st, 2025, h. 14.00, Interview on Microsoft Teams
3	PM: The recording is starting.
4	FB2: OK. Normally for that, when we do that here if somebody hits record, the camera and mic might go off and putting them on is funny enough, your acceptance that you're being recorded both visually and audio...
5	PM: Yeah, I understand.
6	FB2: Yeah.
7	PM: Yeah. So, I would like to start, but in order to do that, I would like to explain to you how we can understand ethics for this specific interview and for thesis. So, I would like to read you a definition. I am in another setting today; therefore, I had to print out a document because I couldn't use two screens as I usually can. Therefore, I am just going to read it out to you-
8	FB2: Oh yeah.
9	PM: -And not share the screen, but I think it's still possible to understand. So the ethics definition they I'm going to use today is that ethics is understood as an intersection of ethical AI, business ethics and ethics in corporate communication. In this context, ethics entails acting responsibly to balance innovation and societal impact, mitigate risks, and promote fairness and respect towards social and human values. Now the first question, would you agree with these or is? Is there anything else that is important for you, or can you work with this definition as well?

10

FB2: That's fine, it's fine. It's pretty standard.

11

PM: Then I would like to start with a couple of easy questions. How long have you been working in the field of corporate communication?

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FB2: So corporate communications. That's been since 2006 or seven. So, it's been about two decades. Before that I was a journalist actually.

13

PM: Mm. OK.

14

FB2: So, then I went into PR which is which is corporate comms essentially, and and yeah, I'm still here today.

15

PM: And now, what does your job consist of? What are your tasks or your responsibility in your current position?

16

FB2: So, I take care of the corporate communications for the [COMPANY'S NAME] and this includes... it's predominantly internal comms, because [COMPANY'S NAME] is a relatively conservative company.

17

PM: Mm hmm. Yep. Mm hmm.

18

FB2: So, it's important to add that when I joined the company, there was no corporate communications function on a group level. And I built the whole structure from virtually nothing.

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PM: OK.

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FB2: The task is internal communication as I said, via a number of channels: broadcast, Internet Viva Engage, which used to be called Yammer, and it's essentially to keep people informed, to make their life easier at work and help people understand things like our mission, our vision and our strategy. Because knowing these will of course make their work easier. So that's on the internal level. There's other things, for example event organizing. It is an important part of comms because that's where you meet up as groups of people and you share, and in cross-functional teams we share the work which you're doing. On the external side, I take care of all the external comms for the for the company that goes from social media, especially platforms like LinkedIn and Instagram.

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PM: Mm hmm.

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FB2: And also, the corporate website is my responsibility. I take care of press relations today, we'll publish our annual report. For example, why prepare the press release? I spoke with journalists who have questions, and I dealt with any media inquiries, also sharing through our teams across the across the world because we do have each of our countries and there are about 15 countries, each of them has their own their own-

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PM: Mm hmm.

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FB2: -Setting, let's say of corporate communications. Managers will probably be responsible. I also take care of things like crisis management. So, if we do a crisis, I will also handle that myself. It's pretty much the whole thing. Yeah, it's a whole package, exactly. I also must add that I am the corporate communications team. So. So yes, I'm alone and-

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PM: OK, OK. Yeah. Yes, the whole package. That you're alone, yeah.

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FB2: -Which is OK, of course within limits, but. You know, it might help you at least to understand some limitations there are within my role.

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PM: I can understand. Now if we talk more closely about the way you use AI tools, how often would you say that you use them? I mean, I'm talking about generative AI tools. How often are they implemented in your tasks?

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FB2: OK, so it's important to explain one thing with regards to the implementation of AI within [COMPANY'S NAME]. So we... like other companies as well, we have a lot of things which are confidential, which we don't want to share with a wider audience. I mean if you take the annual report, we could not have shared it yesterday, we couldn't share it. Today it's public and so we can share if we can put it on ChatGPT, whatever it may be because it's public knowledge but a lot of other things-

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PM: Mm hmm.

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FB2: -Contracts, recipes, whatever, whatever it may be, those are confidential, and we don't want to share them. So, this is where you get a little bit of a dilemma whereby you want your people, you want your staff to use AI because it's a great tool, or great tools I should say. But you also are a little bit... you know, you need to be able to care for. So, we use Microsoft Copilot as our tool and when using it of course we keep it within our own Microsoft encrypted environment.

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PM: Yes. Yeah. Mm hmm.

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FB2: So, so that's our provider. Does that mean that people don't use external AI? But of course, they do. And we do have our list of do's and don'ts on what you should use, what you should and shouldn't share with them with the external world, and the thing is if you if you can't speak to your friend's neighbour about it, well don't then use it on that. Oh, I'm sorry on AI. Personally, I'm a little bit older so it takes me a little bit more time maybe to pick up. I'm also extremely busy and this is why.

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PM: OK. Yeah.

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FB2: I am a one-man team, so I tend to be putting out fires a lot as I go along and having to deal with many different things. So I don't use it as much as I should. That's probably the best answer, but do I use it? I'm trying to, you know, to get more used to it. I'm also encouraging people to use it and I'm and I what I mean by this is-

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PM: Yeah. Yes.

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FB2: -Run the Intranet of the company. And I write. I was a journalist, after all. And I write all...literary all the articles. And to be honest, it doesn't take me too long to write. I've written so many articles that, you know, in 15 or 20 minutes I can write an article from zero to complete.

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PM: OK. OK.

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FB2: But the thing is, when you have 20 of them, 20 times 15 minutes is of course a long time. So, I'm encouraging people to use AI to send me articles which are more or less complete. You see. So even if I don't use it directly myself, others are using it and sending me material and even images for example. So, they'd send me an article and an image and I can just post it on Intranet.

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PM: Mm hmm. Yep.

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FB2: My use of AI...you know, again I do...I am trying to use it a lot. I'm part of a Copilot team and we're supposed to meet every Thursday. I've missed every single one so far to be honest with you, but next Thursday I should have a meeting. I have a meeting, but I should be able to actually join, because that's the key thing, actually, learning how to do it. But how to do it properly? You know, that's the key.

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PM: OK. Yes, that's important. If you were to give that, I mean a frequency, would you say it like one per week, one per day, once per month?

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FB2: No, I would. I would. I would say it's three times a day.

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PM: Yeah. So, it's still daily. It's still a daily use, yeah.

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FB2: Yes, it's daily use, yes, absolutely. Even because with Copilot is everywhere, so it's on teams. It's on PowerPoint, Word, and the icon keeps following you around, which is a bit annoying to be honest. But it keeps following you, which means that it's actually very easy to use.

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PM: Mm hmm, that's true, yeah.

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FB2: Because it's there. All you have to do is move the mouse literally a centimeter to the left and you can click on it and have it there. And so, you know when there's a, when there's a gap between things and I'm doing something and then I still say, "OK, let's see what AI would do".

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PM: Mm hmm.

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FB2: It is one of the most difficult things to have... and we have corporate visuals. We buy a lot of visuals as well, but sometimes you need a really, really specific thing.

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PM: Yes. And then you can use the AI generated images and videos. For example, you can generate, yeah...

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FB2: Exactly, exactly. And in fact, we organized a webinar for our colleagues. I was running the webinar at the back, so I didn't really follow much, but one thing was really simple. We... the guy who was running it, the colleague I spoke to, basically he showed on the webinar how to create a video and he said, you know, take I want a photo of a... it was a flower in the middle of the road with it. And then he did created it to be nice, to be nicer, nicer. And than a bee had to land on the flower, because bees are very important for us. We use fruits and vegetables. No bees, no

fruits and vegetables. So, you know that sort of thing. And then he came up with this really great image which is, which is fantastic.

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PM: And then, OK and other than generating videos images, what are the other tasks in which you decide to use AI? So, for example maybe correct your texts, or maybe you're writing them in some instances. I mean which are the main areas in which you feel like you need AI systems, or do you want to use it?

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FB2: For me, it's what you mentioned. Really. It's tech. I didn't use it directly for proofing, but we just have as I mentioned earlier, we just had our annual report out and the colleague who I was working with on the annual report, I did send his text through AI to prove it.

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PM: Yeah. Mm hmm yes.

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FB2: To be honest, when I proved it, I still had a lot of work to do, but I'm reasonably sure that if he hadn't done that, I would have had double the work to do so that helps. That helps quite a bit.

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PM: Yes. Yep, you've mentioned that you will still proof write the text after your colleague put it through AI. This means that you are always the one controlling the outputs, so there's still a human person which is in charge of it?

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FB2: Yes, and that works for everything, and I can give you an actually good example which I spoke to my colleague about. This is something which most companies are using now. There's... it's in CVs, curriculum which come in... by the way, my function falls within the HR department, and that's why it's a bit related to me, so you have AI that checks the CVs, but you also need the human element.

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PM: Yes. Yes.

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FB2: Because when you input something in AI, you have to be a little bit careful of unconscious bias. And it's really easy to have these biases without knowing. So, for

example, if you write in the prompts, “He has to have 10 years of experience and he has to have this and he has to have that”, AI might assume that because you wrote “he” all the time... and you know, we write “he” just to write something. You could also write “she”, doesn't matter as long as you're consistent. And then the machine might just say, “OK-

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PM: Yes. Yes, yes, yes, yes.

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FB2: If it's a woman, then out, because this person wants a male, obviously”, even though you might not want that, you know. So, AI of course is great. I mean, a great tool and it will be, I was going to say it will be the future, but it's actually now the present. But you still have to keep an eye on it because one of the most difficult things to do is what prompts to give to AI so how can you make it that-

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PM: I see.

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FB2: -AI doesn't misunderstand. It's a little bit like I don't... have you watched the film? I think it's just called “I robot.”

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PM: I think so. I think I've watched it.

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FB2: I mean it's quite some time back. So, the main actor, I think it was Will Smith, he hates robots, and one of the reasons why he hated robots is that... you don't see it, but then he explains, what is going along... is that the robots, they were... there was a car accident and there was a child, and there was an adult Will Smith and the robot jumped in to save them and the robot calculated-

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PM: Mm hmm.

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FB2: -That it's more possible that the adult male survives than another child. And so, he saved Will Smith and the child died. Sorry. It's a bit of a spoiler alert, but you know what I mean. And the thing is, the robot is probably right. But of course, anyone, any human, if there's a choice, you know, save the child or save myself-

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PM: No, I understand.

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FB2: -Any normal person would say save the child, but the robot of course doesn't know that. And this is where you have a little bit of a, you know you need the human elements to come into it.

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PM: I think it's great that you mentioned this aspect already, because my next set of questions would have been about the ethical challenges that you see when using AI, and you already mentioned a few of them, so I'm going to basically tell you now what I could note. So, the first thing you told me is about prompting. So, the fact that even the information you put on AI in can have biases.

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FB2: Absolutely.

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PM: And then also we were talking about these differences in mentality. So, for example the robot thinking that males, sorry adults have a higher chance of surviving than children and therefore choosing them first. So, I think I have these two main aspect written down which are important for you, something like a different mindset. Do you have any other concerns when it comes to AI? Especially when it comes down to the field of corporate communication, something which is making you worried about how AI could be used.

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FB2: Yes, and I'm. going over the notes as well.

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PM: Yes.

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FB2: Well, profiling and bias, those are two of the biggest issues.

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PM: Yeah.

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FB2: You also have to t be a little bit on the on the, on the careful side when it comes to jobs.

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PM: Mm hmm.

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FB2: So do you get a chatbot to replace the customer service reception? Because a chatbot will do an equally good job. And this is where you have to look at things. I was in the UK a very long time ago. With this, I mean there was a colleague. I was sitting down saying someone was in the back. I could hear a colleague, and she was speaking to a customer.

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PM: Mm hmm.

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FB2: And this customer had a problem which wasn't directly related to the products, but she helped her anyway, and it was a bit more of a personal thing, which I was quite happily surprised about, because it was, it turned out... it was an old woman, and she couldn't do something.

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PM: Yes.

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FB2: -Which was only semi-related and of course a chatbot wouldn't do that. So, would you, you know?, be OK with job losses to replace them with chabots, is that is that a good thing ethically, but also the term of the service that is provided? You've been on... I'm sure because of probably what you're studying on these chatbots, sometimes you have to go through 1000 [*of chatbots, referring to customer service-related situations*] in some companies, a 1000 of really annoying-

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PM: Yes.

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FB2: -Well, chatbots. Sorry. Before you actually get to a human, and most times you say, "Well, I'm never going to get it anywhere". So. So there's also that, that part which we need to, to, look into.

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PM: Mm hmm. There is. Are you afraid that AI is going to be able to take over communication jobs entirely, or is it going to sort of mess it up? Is it something that worries you?

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FB2: You know, the thing is in communications, like in any other jobs you have what's called donkey work. In other words, work whereby you don't really need to think too much.

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PM: Yes.

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FB2: And one of the biggest problems I have currently is I don't have time to think... to stop and say "OK, how can we solve this problem" or "how can we do this that and the other". So, if AI does these menial tasks, I mean menial, it sounds bad by menial I mean things like writing an article for example, and if that saves me time, that's not only-

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PM: Mm hmm.

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FB2: -That's going to help me a lot to do my job better.

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PM: Yes.

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FB2: Would it? Would it take over my job? It's possible, you know, because you could get the system to write an article and even post it. It's possible, of course, the job is so wide and so varied that that it would be it would be very, very-

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PM: Mm hmm. Yeah.

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FB2: -Hard. So, is it possible? Absolutely it is, will it? Will it really happen? I am not quite sure if it will, because you still need to have that human touch to know what to do.

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PM: Mm hmm. Sure.

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FB2: So, I can give you an example which is also about writing.

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PM: Mm hmm.

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FB2: We have a colleague who retired, and he is not with the company, he's been here for 20 years. Usually, the normal announcement I would write is like "Dear colleagues, we regret to inform you that Marta Pellegrino is leaving the company, she found a job elsewhere... in her time with the company Marta did this and that... Thank you very much for your service. Wish you good luck" and whatever. But with people who've been there for 20 years, for example, and everyone knows, it can be a little bit more personal even because you know the person, and you could put prompts in, of course, to AI. But unless you know the person, it is going to be very difficult to do that. And this is the personal sort of touch you would need to be able to have not a good communications toolbox, but a very good one, you see. So, there is that difference-

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PM: Yes.

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FB2: -In quality the same as the annual report that was proofread-

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PM: Yes, yes.

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FB2: -By AI, but then I found many mistakes. Maybe this guy did them later. I don't know. It could also be...by the way, I don't... I mean I don't do... I think AI is a great, great tool. But it does, it does... It's still not quite there yet. I mean, is huge compared to three years ago, two years ago. My goodness, I mean incredible. But we still need a little bit more time.

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PM: Yes. It Improves. Yes. So, this is the reason why you still feel free and still check everything. I mean, you wouldn't simply publish something that AI had written without looking at it before. So, you still feel like you had to add something to it?

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FB2: I mean you could, and it'll be OK. That's what I'm saying. It would be. It would be good, but it wouldn't be great. So, then it depends where you put the bar and-

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PM: Yeah.

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FB2: -For me it would be... there are certain things which it's OK if they're not great. If you have, you know, "Some colleagues planted 10 trees outside the office to celebrate World Earth Day". Great. You don't need to have a superb thing. But if you speak about the annual report, for example, if you think about a long-term colleague leaving, then you really need to make sure it is great and I don't know if you know, for example LinkedIn.

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PM: Yes.

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FB2: LinkedIn, if you have even very few followers. If the content is great, the content will spread like wildfire. If it's a video, you call it going viral. Same, you know, and this is the same thing internally if you... or when you... when I write something like this which comes from the heart, it's really, really great. People come back and say, wow, it was amazing, but of course they don't do it for everything because, you know, you need to do it for certain things. That's why I'm saying you could publish it, it would work. It's not wrong.

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PM: Yes.

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FB2: But it depends on where you put the put the ball.

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PM: There is something that maybe worries you other than the quality of the work. So, we we've mentioned before biases, I mean, are you worried that something

that you put out which is written by AI and maybe not proofread correctly or anything is going to really backfire and create... I mean if we go down to that, if there's is there something other than quality that really makes you think "I need to take a look at it before publishing it"?

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FB2: I mean, yes. As a supervisor... so if it's something which could have a big impact, it will always be checked and generally we check multiple times by different people because it's very, very easy to get something on. Of course, even for humans, which is why... if you, if you do a job like mine... I would write something and then I would leave it and then I'd go back to it and check it again.

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PM: Mm hmm.

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FB2: And then you know it was a hugely critical thing. I would print it out and read it on paper because reading on a screen and reading on paper is different. Of course, the last step [*reading on paper*], which is the most critical one, AI cannot do, logically, but what's is a bit more of a concern for me is that people wouldn't know how to use AI properly. So, to back the bias idea, it's back to what prompt you and that is because you could also get a wrong picture.

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PM: Mm hmm mm.

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FB2: If you, if you, if you look at things like, what's it called the Elon Musk AI? Croc or something like that? Grock, no.

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PM: I think so. I think so. Now that you've mentioned it, I got confused for a second, but it yeah, I think it should be correct.

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FB2: I think it's cool. Yeah, I'm not. I'm not a big fan of that person. But so, I don't even... I've never even used it and then I won't. And one reason why I wouldn't use that for example, is because that has no restrictions.

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PM: Yeah, me neither.

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FB2: It will give you the answer, however racist, however morally and ethically wrong it will give you the answer, and you won't say, "Well, that's good for freedom of-

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PM: Mm hmm. Mm hmm.

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FB2: -Of I don't know what of speech or or something or another".

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PM: Yeah.

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FB2: Of course. You know there are limitations. That's why we don't in today's world, we don't use the N word for example, because it's just wrong to do it. But that system probably... I don't know, it probably would, because it doesn't... it's not told "Hey, you can't use these words". So, the thing is-

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PM: Mm hmm. Yeah.

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FB2: -You know, getting our people to learn how to use the AI tools properly and also... of course this goes for myself too, when I'm prompting I'm not very politically correct, to be honest with you. Maybe because I'm a bit older and that's OK. But you know, in certain cases it's not OK. So, then you need to be careful. So, you need to educate people and yourself in using these tools properly and as they're meant to be used and it's good to you know, do a bit of a trial-and-error thing till you get it together but that is a concern. That is a quite a big concern. Because people could also go outside and share things which are not supposed to share, you know.

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PM: What I mean... I am moving a bit to the concept of the strategies that you might use to prevent a series of challenges and problems with AI. And if you think about the way you, I mean, I would say you're a department, but it's just you. So, talking about communication in your company in general, which is still going to be you, how would you say that you're navigating issues and things possible problem that can be caused by the use of AI?

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FB2: If there's an overreliance on AI you could go into issues.

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PM: Mm hmm.

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FB2: So again, you need... it's down to education. So, in corporate comms as *[COMPANY'S NAME]* it's... there are... all companies have their own. In many cases it's not actually comms people. So, HR people would also take on role, or the marketing people would take on. Which means that very often people are not really trained in using it. So, when you speak about strategy... it's really one thing for all.

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PM: Mm hmm.

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FB2: So, one of the main... there's two pillars. One of them is personal productivity. So in other words, your job is made easier by AI, that's the task of AI. The other one would be it would be a more marketing thing and how can the tool help in in pack-design, for example, that that's quite specific. I'm sorry, that is quite specific and quite restricted, I would say, but for us, for here, the main strategy at the moment is personal productivity.

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PM: Yeah. Mm hmm.

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FB2: And again, it's there to help you do your do your job more efficiently.

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PM: Yes.

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FB2: And actually, even before AI, we had those, we still have this program called "Personal effectiveness program" whereby you teach people how to use things like teams. This was 20, I think 19 *[years ago]* when we launched it. So, it's the same. The same theory works with AI.

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PM: Yes. So, you have this sort of trainings programs, I would say sort of trainings.

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FB2: Absolutely, it's still at the beginning. So, for example, I have the webinar to tell "Listen", you know for a start, before that even where the things say, "Listen we know about AI, this is what you can and can't do". Then there's a webinar saying, "OK, look, this is how it works", and we will have more webinars as we as we go along again it's purely a matter of time. I'm using my notes and... fine enough... one of the one of the greatest things of AI for example is, and you'll probably do it after the meeting is...you can have a summary of what the meeting is all about. So, when you go and do your you when you do your writing.It's very simple. You have a nice, lovely summary. I didn't have that when I did my master's not very long ago actually, but just ten years ago. But it would have helped a lot to be able to actually press a button, which is what I did with the meeting I had. And I have a whole list of meeting roles-

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PM: Yeah, yeah, yes.

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FB2: -To divide into AI strategy, marketing, AI policy, et cetera, et cetera. That's great because then you share that and it's nice and easy. I mean, before this you'd have to type in. "Now this person said this, and that person said that", and that would take you an hour, an hour and a half. I'm going to make an assumption that maybe you have some interest in this, but you haven't... you don't have a job. I guess when you have a job, you need to make sure that things are documented.

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PM: Yes, that's for sure.

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FB2: Because, you know, I could say "No, no, Marta didn't tell me that I have to do the job, she's supposed to do it." And he said no. But we spoke in the meeting. And. No, no, no. But if you have the meeting notes done and ready, they're there. And it's very, very easy to use. And even if you forget what was said you meeting and I was OK. Martin said this. Well fine.

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PM: You can check it, yeah.

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FB2: You see, this is the idea of productivity. I don't need to waste an hour and a half to type the notes. I have them there. It's fantastic actually.

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PM: You train... I mean the people in your company are trained for using AI effectively or also for not using AI the wrong way?

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FB2: Both.

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PM: Both yes. Do you have any other strategies? I'm thinking maybe... I wrote as examples of handbooks or maybe guidelines prompting guidelines, anything which is a very specific and not just the general use of the AI, but specific to a certain use case or certain scenario.

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FB2: Yes. So, for example in marketing, they use it specifically for content creation. They also use it for insights generation. So, the generation of graphs and. Sales figures and nest of things.

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PM: Sure.

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FB2: I maybe don't have an example per se.

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PM: OK.

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FB2: Other than the ones in my own department, which is what I'm interested in.

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PM: OK. Yeah, that's perfect. Yeah, I mean, your department, do you have anything like that? I mean, just for you, just for corporate com, anything, which is a guideline or a handbook telling you...?

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FB2: We do. And the thing is, it's two things. So, I have already created a lot of guidelines and policies. Man, we got a manuals, handbook. Same things.

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PM: Yes.

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FB2: Etcetera, etcetera. But this was this was before and now I need to read, not redo them. I need to update them, let's say.

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PM: Yeah.

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FB2: There's that one. And the second thing is position papers.

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PM: Mm hmm yeah.

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FB2: So, you have to w have a position on everything. What's... that for example, of breastfeeding, which is an obvious one, and I mentioned it's specific as people think that we are against breastfeeding [*because of the company also selling baby formula*] On the contrary, you know, we strongly, you know, urge any new mothers to breastfeed because it's the best you can have. Period. We do have milk.

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PM: Mm hmm.

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FB2: Baby milk from zero months old and it's very simple. If you can't breastfeed for whatever reason, well, you need to have something to give your baby. And I have three kids. And none of them breastfed, none, they just didn't want to do it. So, my wife had to pump. But when you pump, I mean, again you probably... I'm assuming you don't have any kids by the assumption, but anyways, I'm sorry about the assumption. But you know when you pump, it takes a very long time for a very small amount of milk, which is not enough by a mile. So, you need to have this milk.

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PM: Yeah.

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FB2: But people think you kill babies with our products. Which makes me laugh because if there was and this was before my time at [*COMPANY'S NAME*], because my youngest is 16, you can imagine.

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PM: Yeah, yeah.

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FB2: If there wasn't milk, we would have had a massive, massive problem, but you need to have a position paper on that which says yes, we, you know, we need to. We were pro breastfeeding, blah blah blah, you know, and my thinking is rather than me going on all our documents and seeing what people said, is to feed it with our internal documents and some external as well [*into AI*].

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PM: Yes.

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FB2: And then see what it spits out. Essentially what is AI going to give me? And then I can get that and use that as a base, as a very good base by the way, to create things because for a person like me who's a one-man team... you have to take all the help you can get and having tools like that would be super helpful so. Yes, position papers. Manuals. Articles. Visuals. All these elements absolutely.

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PM: These are things that you have or that you think they would help?

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FB2: It's things for the last two, it's things which are already happening. For the others, I hope to do them. But I've been again.

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PM: OK. Yes, yes.

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FB2: It's putting out first.

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PM: You're trying, yeah. Yeah, they are good. Not to pressure you to do something more.

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FB2: Yeah, it's, it's, it's funny because it's a little bit like chicken and egg. You know, you need to do one, but you have to do the other. But if you did this one, you could, you know, just keep on going around.

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PM: Mm hmm. Yeah, it's the circle.

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FB2: But absolutely, this is... and that's why it's great actually, because generally in in summer and in the last weeks of December usually it's very quiet and that's when normally I do things like that you know, but it has to be a quiet period.

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PM: So, you've mentioned to me that you have some, I mean we're talking about it right now, the manuals and the articles and everything. I'm assuming this is sort of to prevent that anything wrong happens when people use AI, am I right?

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FB2: Oh yeah, yeah. For AI specifically, we have a policy, and we have our do's and don'ts.

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PM: Mm hmm. Ah, perfect. You have them? Yep.

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FB2: It gives you the scope or...I'm just reading, it gives you a scope of what to do.

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PM: Yeah, yeah.

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FB2: What is it, compliance with laws? So of course, anything we do needs to be within the law. You, you know you can't do anything which is outside the law.

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PM: Are any of these do's and don'ts specifically related to corporate com or are they more general for the company general? Yes.

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FB2: It's general for the company.

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PM: Do you wish to have something more which is very specific to your role? Or do you think that general guidelines still work?

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FB2: No, the general ones work, because you have things like... the dos is that...they're to legal and ethical standards. Ensure data privacy and security report issues. Seek advice in case of doubt. They don't avoid sensitive data and open AI systems. Prevent unauthorized AI usage. Circumvent legal compliance or unreflected use. You know. So, I mean, I can't think of anything which would have you could use AI to write your [?], but that's a little bit obvious.

187

PM: Yes, but you wouldn't. Mm hmm. Yeah, yeah.

188

FB2: So you wouldn't, you wouldn't really. You wouldn't really do that. I think most, most are related. One one thing is that...we meet the communication teams individually and as a team. And these are things which come out. And although again, I don't really have any great examples, but-

189

PM: Yes.

190

FB2: -What I'm trying to do with the team is to see where we have strengths and where we have weaknesses. So, if you're good in AI then you can help the rest. If I'm good at creating and cutting videos, then I'll do it for you. You see that sort of thing. I haven't gotten there yet, but that's the.

191

PM: Yes. That's it.

192

FB2: That's the general. You know, thinking. We're still very young, or immature, when it comes to AI. So, it's a very steep learning curve, but still, I mean again like most companies really we're still relatively young. We do have thought and again it's this guy who I spoke to earlier.

193

PM: Yes. Mm hmm. Hmm. Yes.

194

FB2: We have a team who is very actively working on how to best implement it, how to best take advantage of it, but again not specific for comms though.

195

PM: OK, it's more general. There are two questions that I'm thinking of considering what you've told me until now. The first one is that you said that you're also working on crisis communication. I am wondering if you have anything in your mind or anything that you have strategically prepared for if a crisis were to happen which is related to the use of AI?

196

FB2: Right. No, but that's very good, that's a very good idea actually. So, we it's not specific to AI, but again it's generic. So, we have a very, very robust crisis communications manual.

197

PM: Mm hmm.

198

FB2: Which takes into consideration... it does take into consideration specific aspects, but it's very generic at the same time.

199

PM: Yes.

200

FB2: I don't think we've had any AI related crises. The thing is, it only comes to me if it's, you know, goes beyond borders, and if the, for example, the name of the company, the reputation could be affected. So, so, I mean, I don't know if there were any on a country level.

201

PM: Mm hmm. No. Mm hmm.

202

FB2: It's a good idea. I'll speak to our quality director, who's in charge of crisis and let her know that maybe we should think about that.

203

PM: Yes, perfect. And the second question I was thinking of is that I was gathering basically companies from different fields and their company was... basically, for my thesis it is part of the food and beverage industry and. Do you feel that there are specific challenges or specific topics which are related to this sort of industry, to us-

ing AI in the food and beverage industry? That might not be relevant for other industries or other fields. I mean, do you? Do you have any concerns or anything to say which you think yet to the specific core tips industry?

204

FB2: I mean, as I was mentioning before, there is the marketing AI and there we have to be very, very careful, you know, because it's a very, very highly regulated area, especially with regards to baby food. So, what goes on the label even for food in general, what goes on the label is hugely important and.

205

PM: Mm hmm. Yes. Yes.

206

FB2: Would you? Would you trust AI? I'm. I'm not sure. I don't know. The thing is, you know, there are certain things you have to put on. For example, contents of anything that could be people could be allergic to.

207

PM: Mm hmm.

208

FB2: Or whatever. Whatever preservatives or additives you use.

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PM: Yes.

210

FB2 Incidentally, it might also be even better maybe than humans in in doing it, because you have, you know, as soon as there's a human element usually there's also always a risk of error.

211

PM: Yeah, but basically, yeah. It's technical communication, I would say also like if you. Yeah. Mm hmm.

212

FB2: Logically. Exactly, absolutely. And this is where, you know, and we're undergoing at the moment where we've been for quite some time because it's huge project. Digitalization project which involves the use of the SAP HANA 4 platform, so that all our production units especially are connected. So, before everything is to be

done manually. And I mean the, the chances of errors were so high. So now it's all within the system. And that means that because it's within our closed system and we have a closed AI, we can use AI to our benefit. I don't know the extent to which they use it to be honest with you, but I'm pretty sure that they do use it to make these...the content creation, for example, the package-details, especially because in many cases we try and do packs which are good for many countries, so you know you always get... in fact, I've seen this here, for example, this, I'm seeing in it here, you have it in German.

213

PM: Mm hmm.

214

FB2: In French, in Italian, in English, I thought because Switzerland, the three languages, so we have to add on about nine other languages.

215

PM: Yes, sure.

216

FB2: And I wonder if this is, you know, and even just doing that you need to make sure that, you know, things are done properly. I don't know if you see some of the Chinese product translations sometimes. It's comical. But the thing is if you if you're dealing with whatever it is, I don't know, a pen knife it's one thing. But if you're dealing with baby food, it's another thing you can't mess around you. You know, you can't have some of the-.

217

PM: Yeah, yeah. There was no one, yes. Yes.

218

FB2: -Own products descriptions which I mean this is terrible, you know? So. So I assume that's where it would go.

219

PM: Yes, perfect I think you have actually answered to all of my questions. Definitely everything that I had planned and prepared for today. I asked you a couple more questions that as I mentioned weren't in my script, but basically come up as we speak.

220

FB2: Good.

221

PM: So yes, we've talked we you have told me everything that I needed, but before closing it, I would like to ask you if there is anything else that you would like to add, something you feel that we haven't touched upon, but you think it's very important for today. I mean, I mean anything, I would just give you free space now.

222

FB2: Yeah, I'm. I'm again looking at the at the notes.

223

PM: Yes.

224

FB2: So one thing which I mentioned was that automating business processes, in other words, looking at the potential of, but it's not communication. So, so maybe it's not relevant, but anyway.

225

PM: That's correct, yes.

226

FB2: The potential of having multiple AI models come up with a more holistic outcome.

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PM: Hmm.

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FB2: So, so again it's, it's the same thing generating summaries, graphs, automating tasks and this this. Especially would impact people's work. He actually also spoke of the importance of engaging with younger people, especially because people like you are the ones who essentially are growing up and writing theses, which are very important on on these topics. Last Wednesday I gave a talk to about 20 or 30 ethics students who came to our office.

229

PM: Sure. Yes.

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FB2: This was a chat about the company itself. But The thing is, they had such great questions and, you know, they are the future of of of the, the the industry. So it's it's really good to engage with them and see how how they use AI and how they could improve it.

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PM: Yes.

232

FB2: We're still in our early, as I mentioned before, we're still in the early stages of AI.

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PM: Yes, yes, yeah.

234

FB2: Yeah, that that seems to be the most most of the other things we we we we covered.

Yeah, most of the things we covered.

235

PM: I think we have everything. I mean, they were really nice insights. I think I got a very nice overview of how you work, especially the thinking processes that goes beyond doing certain things. So, I think this is going to be very helpful when writing my thesis. So, thank you very much for giving me such great insights and for your time today.

236

FB2: My pleasure, if you have any questions... because you know how thesis you're writing something you want to put something there and you don't have that information. If you just send me a question and I'll either know it myself or check with my boss and then he can help out to fill in some gaps, which are usually very annoying.

237

PM: Yes. Yeah, if looking back, I see a gap or something that I'm missing or something that I don't understand, I will definitely go back at you and ask you for support, but.

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FB2: You know just.

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PM: Thankfully, we have the video and the audio, so I think something might mean yeah, but anyways, it's great to know that they can, and they can contact you. And yes, I will still have to contact you regarding the forms so.

240

FB2 Yeah, absolutely. And it will be also good when you finally finish your thesis in about a year, I guess.

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PM: Yes, I think it's going to be later in the summer that I can be telling you something not early to summer, but later on probably August.

242

FB2 Yeah. Yeah, it would be. It would be of course, if possible. Of course it would be quite interesting to.

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PM: Mm hmm.

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FB2 To read it because you know if I assume when you speak to other comms people and it always great to see what others are doing because you can, you can or I can learn. In this case it will be, it will be great for me to do so.

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PM: Yes. Yeah. Yes, definitely. So thank you very much. I think I will stop the recording right now. If I manage to find it because the little window with the recording thing disappeared.

Appendix I: [Interview Transcript_HR1]

1	Interview Transcript – HR1
2	February 18th, 2025, h.09.30, Interview on Microsoft Teams
3	PM: The recording started so I will switch to English to start to explain the project to you. So, as you might have read already in my e-mail, I am investigating the use of artificial intelligence in corporate communication and especially I am interested in the ethical challenges that communication professionals have when using artificial intelligence.
4	HR1: Wonderful.
5	PM: As you will read in the form that I sent you the interview will be recorded. However, in the thesis itself, only a transcription will be provided, and all the data will be made anonymous. So not your name, the name of third people, or the name of your company will be provided. Even if it happens that you say something that you shouldn't have said during the interview., for example, a name, you can tell me, and I will just change it or blur it so that not anyone will see it.
6	HR1: OK, perfect.
7	PM: Another thing that I would like to tell you is the definition of ethics that we are going to be using for this interview, and it is basically the base for my thesis. So, for the purpose of the interview ethic is understood as an intersection of ethical AI, business ethics and ethics in a corporate communication. In this context, ethics entails acting responsibly to balance innovation and societal impact, mitigate risks, and promote fairness and respect towards social and human values. I would ask you if there is anything else that you would like to add to the definition, or if you think that also resonates with you.
8	HR1: It makes sense. It's like, well, I think it should be the same definition in all areas and environment. If it's communication company or yeah, whatever.
9	PM: I will just start with an easy question. So how long have you been working in the field of corporate communication? I think you are an expert now.

- 10 **HR1:** Oh, wow. So well, I've always worked in corporate communication, corporate communication and also marketing. But I started in 2006, so well, yeah, quite a lot.
- 11 **PM:** It's quite a lot of experience, so I think you have already seen a lot of changes happening in the field.
- 12 **HR1:** Yes. Yes.
- 13 **PM:** And I know that now you are the head of your department. So, what does your job mostly consist of at your company?
- 14 **HR1:** OK. Well, you know, I'm seven years with [COMPANY NAME]. So, I always had different jobs. I started with heading communication. Then I took over marketing and now I'm responsible for comms in Switzerland, but also globally, about 30%. So financial communication as well, but also partnerships and other projects. So, it's both.
- 15 **PM:** Mm hmm. Quite the whole package, let's say. Then I would like to start with the questions that go more in depth about AI in itself. And so, the most logical question would be how often do you use... actually, you or your colleagues use AI to complete communication test?
- 16 **HR1:** Mm hmm. OK, so it depends on what is AI, right? If you start with DeepL or ChatGPT or Perplexity, all these tools, but also, we have tools in our CRM, in Salesforce, that help us write better job ads, and we have different Utools for our sales team to help them also improve communication and writing. So, mostly is really generative AI, so, written. So, this is used like daily from I would say most in the company, in communication also daily because we are responsible for whole Switzerland. So, we are communicating more than 4 languages. So, it's like also English right and we use those tools regularly. DeepL very, very often for example.
- 17 **PM:** Regularly.
- 18 **HR1:** Yeah, ChatGPT as well, I think it's just important to know the source when you do this.

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PM: That's true. So, you kind of already answered to my second question, which would have been which are the specific tools that you use. So, you already mentioned that you use ChatGPT and DeepL especially, and that you also have some tools that are already incorporated in your CRM tools. So, this is basically the tools that you use. Is there anything else?

20

HR1: Exactly. But we also have some other tools like an AI toolbox for ourselves that are just like links, separate links not included in our ... or not yet integrated in our Salesforce because it was just written, because every country has a different IT landscape and it's not that easy to build in everything that fast. So that's why -

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PM: Mm hmm. Of course.

22

HR1: - We also have like tools apart to integrate, you know, to help you with the distribution correctly in the countries.

23

PM: Is there any specific reason why you decide to use certain tools, so are there tools that you might find very effective, for example, or particularly fast, or that you think that are particularly reliable? So, what is the main reason why you decide on using these kinds of tools?

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HR1: Well, on the first-hand side, everybody already used those tools, so we had to kind of make it officially. So, we really made sure that we officially can use ChatGPT and did also trainings on the other hand side, we're also doing pilots with Copilot for Microsoft to include it in our daily work. But at the moment it's just a selected audience that has it and not yet all because we really want to make sure we have -

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PM: Yes.

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HR1: - Use cases that make sense because it's very expensive -

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PM: Yes.

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HR1: - And that really bring added value because you can spend so much and at the end you really think... need to fist find out what is that and value. If not, people maybe are unproductive, lose time, do not really know what to do, just play around. You know it's really a trying out sometimes and it's not always efficient. So, we really

want to make sure that we know exactly the use cases before we introduce it to everybody.

29

PM: Do you notice any advantages in using these tools compared to when you weren't using them some years ago? So, for example, people completing the work faster or maybe feeling more secure when you complete a certain task because you have a sort of answer from the machine telling you that the work is well done or just anything else?

30

HR1: Well, I think it's it. There are different ways, right on. On the one hand side, I think many people are faster. But on the other hand, also the quality is getting worse if it's not corrected right? So, you see that many just research with these tools, with AI tools and do not research, do the Google Research anymore. So, without really checking the sources -

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PM: OK.

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HR1: - And I think this is dangerous. So sometimes it's also the quality that is not guaranteed. And I think it's super important that also if you use AI tools, you check the sources and you make sure that you own the message and you own the AI tool or not that the AI tool owns you because it's dangerous because, yeah, you still should be in control -

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PM: Yes.

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HR1: -And what I would like to introduce for comes is tool that, based on certain sources that I choose, gives me some answers for media, for example. Studies. Past answers. Official talk tracks. And based on that gives me some answers and I don't want, you know, uncontrolled searches. I really want to define based on what the machine gives me the answer and for example this is not possible or not yet possible with Copilot because you can't just have so much uploaded and then search through because it doesn't have a memory. So, you really need, in my opinion the AI to be more serious and better, and to be really that we are on top of the AI and not vice versa. It's really important to be able to adapt those to the needs and to choose the sources to make sure the result is really thorough.

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PM: Yes. And so, you said that basically you think, or you see that your employees or yourself are working faster, but there are some problems related to the fact that you cannot control the sources and if you're not very serious or if not pay a lot of at-

tention to what you're doing, then equality might be worse. In what tasks is AI implemented the most, so which are the daily tasks in which you find yourself using AI the most?

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HR1: Well, let's say for example, we have a speech for someone, and I formulated it, or somebody formulated it in a in a text, right? And then I'm saying "oh, wow. This is not really nice, not really practical for the speaker, so let's make bullets out of it." So, I put it into Copilot for example, and ask "hey, please rewrite this speech, but in bullet points." And then it's very fast. It's done and it would take me like half an hour or 15 minutes to do it myself and like that, it's done. Let's say I still need like these 10 minutes because I have to review it. The thing is, if I don't review it, I think I really need to be transparent and tell "OK this is the original text and this is the DeepL translation, or this is the DeepL or ChatGPT or Copilot short version". Like, I think it's important to say, "OK I can translate, I don't have time, but I can send you the AI generated version so please check it". Yeah.

37

PM: Yes. And another thing that it wasn't in my questionnaire, but you mentioned it. The thing you use is transparency. So, if you use AI for example, for translation, you tell that to the person who is receiving the translation. For example, you tell them that is AI generated?

38

HR1: No, not always. So, let's see. You know, if you do like a translation, for example, for an internal communication -

39

PM: OK, no problem.

40

HR1: - You know, you put it into DeepL. And DeepL is also AI generated, right?

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PM: Yes.

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HR1: - And then this is one on. There are no sources involved, so I don't see a need to tell them "Was it a manual translation or was it AI generated?" If I go then and translate and correct it myself and for example my German is good enough or French is good enough to read through it and make sure it's correct then I don't see the necessity. If you generated a text fully with -

43

PM: OK.

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HR1: - ChatGPT or copilot without really knowing the source of it, then yes. Then I tell, but it's if it's just a translation, I think also the translation agency used DeepL to do the translation, so it really depends. As soon as sources are included, I think yes. And if it's for example a very long text and I had no time to correct it or I don't have the skills to correct this language. If it's Japanese, then of course, yes.

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PM: Yes.

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HR1: It depends.

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PM: And so, I think this was also partly already covered, but the way in which these tools are implemented, it is mainly done with a sort of human in the loop in the process, which is basically what you are describing. I am translating a text into English because I do not have time, but I can like evaluate the text by myself or does it happen that it's just the AI doing all the work? I mean, how is the way in which you usually use the tools?

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HR1: No, it's never the AI just going to work. It's not... it's not possible yet. You know. Sometimes it helps to give some ideas if you have to be creative and write something. But at the end you need to generate value for the person that you have in front of you, and you have to think about what could be interesting and you have to do the basic work yourself and maybe it can give you an-

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PM: Yes.

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HR1: - Additional idea, what could be interesting, it can help you formulate a little bit differently. It can give you variations and more creativity sometimes, but I think it's still super important that we don't let us drive by AI, but first think ourselves detached from AI and make a concept and think of what, what makes sense and yeah.

51

PM: OK. Now I would like to go to the ethical challenges that we find when using AI. So, the main broad question would be where do you see the main ethical challenges regarding the use of AI in the field of corporate communication?

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HR1: Well. You know, and they at [COMPANY NAME], the ethical challenge is mainly in the HR recruitment field. It's not directly communications. It's really about if you have an AI that goes through applications, how much can be automated and how not. And I think they're the principle is the same as in communication is super important that that there is a human involved, and that human leads the tool. And

you need really to have an ideal collaboration between tool and human to have a good outcome. So, AI can always be biased, can always be based on past learnings that can be wrong. So, if you have an AI supporting you in the recruitment processes, it's important to own it. And in communication... well. Let's see. I think it's dangerous if you have like an AI tool getting independent that is not controlled anymore by humans. So, a chat bot or an AI answering machine. But you can always build it in a way that is fine, right? If you say, OK, these are the sources based on those, the machine can answer, then it's fine if you just insert a Q&A and it's based on that or some additional sources. Then it's fine, but as long as you own the content and know what it's based on it's fine. And in communication, you know there will be also more and more tools to improve. Images. Videos. All this stuff and the question is "What is authenticity and what is not so?" There are many photo shootings' costs that you can save if you have just 1-2 pictures and the rest is like AI, generate the background. I think it's super important that then you name the source and tell "OK, this was based on a shooting and yeah, that's the background". I think Mango *[clothing brand, not related to HR1's company]* generated some.

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PM: Yes.

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HR1: - Pictures with the AI that, but officially, you know, transparently announced it. But also I have... we have employees that have like privately this ChatGPT 4 or other image AI tools and generate pictures for their social media posts with AI that they use for you know advertising jobs, and you know it's always difficult there is no real reason to say why it's not OK because it's sometimes really fun right? I think it's for example they put it in a, let's say it's a brand from Schaffhausen and they put it like with the Rhine in the background, with the Munot, you know some local recognizable assets and then at the it's a marketing job. Then you see some marketing formula or things like that. So, it's cool, why not? But then you see some details that are completely wrong and then you need... then I tell "OK, maybe just make sure that here there is a mistake that this is not because this AI generation doesn't always, alright, hit all the spots. So, you have to be attentive. But I think it's fun. But I always tell, "OK, if you do this, please write <It has been AI generated> and also include the tool you have been generated. This was so it has been included. It has been done with ChatGPT4 or something like that.

55

PM: And do you think that this view would... the thing that you describe, this idea that it might be dangerous if AI is not accurate enough, but you can always control it, is it shared by people working in your team or people that you have met in your experience? Or do you think that your view is more unique and other people that you have met may think something different?

56

HR1: It's difficult, so in communication we had like AI workshop and the company that completely forbid to use AI in communication, for example in videos, because you can have tools that go over videos and cut out the ähms, oohs, or you know and

it's quite cool. So, the question is how much it needs to be perfect, how much does it need to be authentic. And I think some authenticity-

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PM: Mm hmm. Yes.

58

HR1: - Helps to be credible. So, it's always difficult to do the right decision, right? So, I think people think a lot of it. They're not that I think everybody has a... someone is a little bit hesitant about AI and has some concerns. We're really at the beginning of it. So, but for me it's just the next step in digitalization we have like you know, machines. Calculators that are faster and faster and faster and faster, and now the next step is just that instead of numbers machines can also work with words and letters, so that's kind of the normal process. It's just we need to own it, and we need to put the formula in correctly and we need to control it. I know I don't think that everybody is very conscious about it, but in communication, yes, I think we are.

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PM: Yes, that's good to hear.

60

HR1: Mm hmm.

61

PM: And considering this specific case of your company and the way you in particular use AI that we have talked about, is there a specific ethical challenge or concern that you might think of that you might have, for example, already encountered or that you fear in particular or not? Maybe not fear exactly, but just you think is something that might be prevalent for your particular case.

62

HR1: Not that I can think of. You know, it's really based on generative AI. It's just, for example, we have on social media, or you know if you have people that don't speak all languages, they use it more and more, also ChatGPT to translate. And where I am concerned is if we start to use this thing for internal data and you cannot control this. The system puts it in a machine that learns and... if the competition does it as well, maybe it will help us as well, but it's not, you know, it's just you cannot control it 100%. You will never be able to, but AI is such a fast thing and its tonnes of maybe internal data that land in those counts that you cannot control anymore. This is something that makes me afraid because I think... I'm convinced that many people put in, also at work, a lot of things that they shouldn't and that they don't even know they shouldn't.

63

PM: How do you deal with his concerns of these ethical issues you might found? Do you maybe have a strategy within your company or sort of guidelines that would follow?

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HR1: Yes, yes. We just set up like AI responsible toolkits and ethics that we communicated and now every employee need to do an AI training, so it's mandatory, so it has just rolled out now. So, this training start now I have not done it myself yet so. It's starting now, but we have evaluated a toolkit and also some ethics, some standards. And now everybody needs to go through training, I think this is super important. It's about, yeah, using AI correctly in a work environment.

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PM: I would say that this part of your approach is sort of preventive. So, try to avoid the issue before it comes. So, you basically... yes, try to avoid it. Would you agree?

66

HR1: Yes. Well, yes, it's prevention because you cannot hinder people in using it, so it's like I don't know, you can maybe try to make your children not watch TV, not watch a cell phone, whatever. But at a certain point they will learn, and they will do it yourself. Even you learn it early when you know when they still are in initial stage and listen to you or the new to it. Too late, too late, and then it's... They might already have learned some patterns that are completely wrong or there might be some damage. So, it's better to prevent and to do something. To go into the right direction because you never, you can never stop the progress and this is progress.

67

PM: You, on the other hand, have a strategy or something that you have already thought of in the case of an issue that comes... an ethical issue that comes that you could not prevent, or even with your toolkit, if you say "OK, this is not working. Something has come up." Do you have a plan, for example, for that situation?

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HR1: Yeah, what we did is also sensible eyes for phishing. So, what we had is like, there are some AI made videos-

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PM: Mm hmm.

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HR1: - For example, there were some off of you know that were sent around and it's like phishing mail. It tries to get the data and to do [headering?] attacks. And we did some sensibilisation of those internal comps and things like that. But this is coming more and more. So, people need to be very aware that many things can be fake.

71

PM: And generally speaking, are you satisfied with your current strategy and the way you are dealing the situation? Would you wish something more, something different for now or the future, or maybe even the past? Or are you generally satisfied? What is your feeling?

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HR1: I think it's fine. We are doing like we also found AI departments where we focus on this and really make sure that we drive it. In general, yes, I think we do the right thing. On the other hand, I must say, companies sometimes... you know, you like to see the nice AI story, but what we often forget is everything is based on data and everything that is in the company. And to introduce AI, you should have a database, a digital database that is solid that you have a single source of truth that you know where is what, and in a global company with so many different countries it's super important that you first get the basics before you introduce AI. So, I always think AI is like it makes visible what you have on data, maybe sometimes forgotten. But it doesn't prevent you... you really need to control the base as well the database.

73

PM: Yes. Do you think that there would be it? I mean, I have the impression that you feel that you have already all the elements you need to be secure when using AI or would you say that maybe you wish you could have something more? So maybe we were talking about a set of data that you can't control. Do you feel that something is missing that you could need for navigating the AI in itself, an issue that may come with it?

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HR1: I think we would need more tools that people can create themselves in a sense of getting the source you know for example. I think people should be enabled to use AI, but in a safe way and at the moment we just let them use the unsafe AI, right? Because but we need to give an alternative that is safe.

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PM: Yes, yes.

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HR1: And that safe alternative will be to build per department, for example AI tools based on the use case and needs that the department has. So, in my opinion, AI should be much more about how AI in certain departments can be implemented, and we should, you know, focus on department for department and then start to work there. It's there is not one tool that fits all one. One fits all.

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PM: Mm hmm.

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HR1: I think it's more complicated that we think, and I think we're just at the beginning and but I think they're very well equipped and we are very advanced. If I speak to other companies, we are very much doing progress and are exactly doing this strategy. But of course, it takes time and yeah, you still have to do your job and sell, right.

79

PM: Yes, that's true. So, I want to inform you that we have touched upon the main three points that was interested about. To close the interview, I would like to ask you if in general there something is more that you feel like it would be useful to share, or if you maybe have a concrete example that you would or that you might find interesting to provide. So basically, if you have something that you think is important to close off the interview.

80

HR1: No, it's all good. Thank you very much. I think I said everything.

81

PM: Thank you to you.

82

HR1: Yeah, it will be just interesting if you could send me the thesis when it's finished. I would be very interested to what's the title.

83

PM: For sure. I do not have an official title yet, but the main topic would be AI and Swiss communication department and the ethical issues. So, I will be analysing the ethical issues and also how companies are dealing with it. So yes, the official interview is done. So, thank you very much for your time. It was interesting, as you might have heard, I did not comment a lot on what you were saying because this is part of the interview process, but I find it really-

84

HR1: OK.

85

PM: -Interesting and eye opening. For students to see how reality is going. So, thank you very much.

86

HR1: Thank you. And you will not mention the company in the thesis, OK.

87

PM: No, no, I will. So, this is a company in HR and this is the first company in HR that I am interviewing. So, your name will probably be HR1.

88

HR1: Wonderful.

89

PM: Thank you.

90

HR1: Yeah, this is my new e-mail.

91

PM: Yes. Perfect. Perfect. Thank you. It will be in July. So, thank you very much and I wish you all the best for your new job. Thank you very much. Bye.

92

HR1: Wonderful. Thank you. Thank you. Bye, bye.

Appendix J: [Interview Transcript_HR2]

1	Interview Transcript – HR2
2	March 10th, 2025, h.15.05, Interview on Microsoft Teams
3	PM: OK, now I started the recording, so I kind of switched to English.
4	HR2: OK.
5	PM: And to start, I would like to give you a definition which is going to have to give us a sort of common ground for the interview. So, for the purpose of this interview, I think ethics is understood as an intersection of ethical AI, business ethics and ethics in a corporate communication. In this context, ethics entails acting responsibly, balancing innovation and societal impact, mitigate risks and promote fairness and respect towards social and human values. Does it resonate with you, or do you have anything else that you would like to change or to add to the definition?
6	HR2: No. Sounds about right, yeah.
7	PM: Perfect. So, I would like to start with a couple of more relaxed questions. The first one being how long have you been working in the corporate communication field? So how long have you been...yeah.
8	HR2: I've been working in the corporate communication field for about 3 years now. Before that I was working in an agency, also in communications and as an editor. So, kind of the other side. Yeah, in corporate for three years.
9	PM: Yeah. And what does your job consist of right now at your position?
10	HR2: I'm responsible for the whole content strategy and also for the content creation of course basically text creation, video creation, but also in very general external

communication, partnerships, collaboration, media collaborations, internal communication, event management, live comms... everything connected to communications, yes, yeah.

11

PM: Hmm. Basically, the whole package So now I would go to a is implementation and I would like to ask you how often is AI used in your department? So, by you and your colleagues to complete communication tasks.

12

HR2: I would say daily.

13

PM: OK.

14

HR2: Yeah.

15

PM: And which specific tools do you use? And also, why did you choose them exactly?

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HR2: We tested some. We started at the very beginning with Jasper and of course ChatGPT, but then there were policies of course, and in global corporate field we have policies from the holding.

17

PM: Mm hmm.

18

HR2: And so, we use ChatGPT of course on more not so data secure topics and then we developed our own AI. So, the [COMPANY'S NAME AI] now actually, since working with Google, Google Chrome that we just today actually got the implementation of Gemini. So, we are testing that now and we really have to say ChatGPT is the most intuitive and the fastest for us.

19

PM: Mm hmm. Perfect. Yes.

20

HR2: And gives the best basis for building up on that, because we don't copy paste, but we really use it as a base creator, and this is something to wrap. Yeah, as a as a sparing partner. So, we figured that ChatGPT for a lot of things is delivering the best base.

21

PM: In which tasks are the AI tools mainly implemented?

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HR2: For me and in communications a lot for translations. We use it a lot for that and then give it to a translation task force. We call it for people who really speak the language within the company to make it really perfect. And of course, for brainstorming, we use it for a lot of things and for research.

23

PM: Hmm.

24

HR2: Of course, carefully for research, but yeah, to get ideas to brainstorm and I have to say I don't use it for creation that much. But it happens. Of course, if we have like automations and-

25

PM: OK.

26

HR2: -Yeah, really standardized things that we have to create all the time, then we use it for that too.

27

PM: What would be an example of these standardized things that you might create with ChatGPT?

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HR2: For example, SEO texts.

29

PM: Yep.

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HR2: We have that, but we also just detected the limits on AI there on SEO texts, because of course AI learns from what's online and if you always create a text, it learns from itself. So, it kind of creates a loop that makes the quality really bad right now. And the algorithm also sees the problem and they detect and of course and then it's not really working for SEO texts anymore.

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PM: OK.

32

HR2: So yeah, bit of challenge there.

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PM: Yes, mm hmm. And so, you mentioned that you have people maybe correctly translating texts. So how would it be the process of creating with together with AI? Would it always be that you have someone checking it, or other standardized options that might go out?

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HR2: So, the process how we start... basically I mean... we always create a text depending maybe in German or sometimes in English. If we get something from the holding, we have it in English and then we translate it or we see what we need, what languages we need. But usually we need French, German, Italian and English. The other four languages, so I say, "hey ChatGPT", but I prove first that there's no confidential data in it. If there's something that's not supposed to go online or we are working in a people's business. So, we always have to be very careful about the data of the people. So we check if we can go out. And then I really implement into ChatGPT and say, "Hey, can you please translate it please?" Be aware that there are special needs in the Swiss German language, and I'm also the French and Switzerland is different. Please take that into consideration." So always also a bit of training-

35

PM: Mm hmm.

36

HR2: - With the tool and then it spits out the text and the translation and then I take the text and translation. And then I give it into our group and then they know that it's based on ChatGPT.

37

PM: Mm hmm.

38

HR2: And then a native Italian speaker, native French speaker, a native English speaker, reads through the text, scans if it makes sense, if the sentences are right. Sometimes it uses some weird abbreviations and so on, or it translates things in our corporate language that are not supposed to be translated. They *[proofreaders]* know what they are, they are taught to check that and then they make their corrections and then I can use AI and human collaboration translation.

39

PM: And for example, when you have the SEO text that you were mentioned before, it's kind of the same process I'm assuming.

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HR2: Yeah. Mostly we let it be created by AI too, and for the other texts mostly it's created by me or by colleagues. Or by the holding, but for the SEO text we have a longer process. We let it create by AI. Then I have the first check, so we'll let it be created in English or in German. Then I have the first check and see OK. Does it make sense? Does it have all the blocks inside because we also figured that ChatGPT likes to skip things that we have in the task so-

41

PM: Yes.

42

HR2: - We check that. If the basic texts really works and then we... 'cause we of course put it into an SEO tool and see if it does make sense and works for our purposes, and if that all is the case, then we start the translation process and then we give it to the task force again and that we are again.

43

PM: And what are the main reasons why you use these kinds of tools? What are the main advantages that they provide for you?

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HR2: The main thing is definitely speed.

45

PM: Mm hmm.

46

HR2: AI makes things much faster, much more cost efficient. Before that we were working with agencies, we still are, and the agencies are knowingly using AI too. But it saves us time. It saves us effort. We can focus on other things on more strategic topics. That's really to make our everyday lives more efficient and also... to be honest, more fun because they can be very, in communications, very repetitive tasks that are really nice to have a tool to take off our shoulders.

47

PM: OK. Yes. I can understand that. So now that I got an overview of how you use it, I would like to move more concretely to the ethical challenges. So, in this case, where do you see the main ethical challenges regarding the use of AI in corporate communication? What might be some issues for you?

48

HR2: Mm hmm. Yeah, sure. One of the main things is that we basically see it as enrichment, right? We see it as an opportunity to really elevate communication to a new level and to... just as I said, simplify routine tasks and yeah, focus more on the strategic work, but we definitely see a challenge in transparency, transparency and responsibility? Definitely. Also how you... Yeah. How you want to position yourself as company, of course. I mean, we are in the people's business as an HR company,

and we are using tools and not people. What we really claim for is what we stand for, right? That we want to give people work and now we use AI to replace people's work so. That is, of course, something that is always in discussion and that we always look into, and we see... I have to say that we don't, we don't lose people, but we see how people can transform.

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PM: OK.

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HR2: And that's really something that is nice to see. But of course, it's a responsibility where you have to look into and that you don't replace, that you also don't lose your quality standards there.

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PM: Yeah.

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HR2: And yeah, that you really make sure that the job security is still given that you don't say, "Hey, we have ChatGPT now and we don't need you anymore."

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PM: Yes.

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HR2: So yeah, that's definitely something. And also with the content itself, trustworthiness. That's something at the confidentiality.

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PM: Yes.

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HR2: That's definitely something. Yeah, that you have to be aware of and... yeah.

57

PM: Since we have mentioned a few of them [*ethical issues*], which of them do you believe is more relevant for your work in particular or for the field you are in for the HR field? Since we've mentioned quite a lot, is there any that is prevalent, or are all of them equally important to you?

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HR2: Well, the most important thing is really the thing about the job. Security the job transformation, yeah.

59

PM: OK.

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HR2: And in second place, I would say transparency and trustworthiness.

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PM: Transparency. What do you mean more specifically?

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HR2: With the content for me, for my standards, and that's what I try to go out with them, also for the company and the brand of course-

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PM: Mm hmm.

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HR2: -I want to go out with high quality information. I want to inform the people our target group is used to content that really gives them-

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PM: Yes.

66

HR2: -How do you say Mehrwert? Yes, exactly gives them value and-

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PM: Yeah, more value, yeah.

68

HR2: -Teaches them things in the best case and shows them that we have expertise that we can transform. And if I now give that responsibility to AI and then go out with maybe information that is not on that level, and I am still claiming that the brand is known for something on a high level and people trust us. I think we have to keep that standard up and with AI of course you have to have guidelines and everything in place that this is still given. So that's also something what I mean with transparency, if you if you say "We use AI tools to create content". Yes, you can say that, and you have to claim that on websites, right? You have to say "Hey, this is created by AI", but I think that's a bit of an easy way out. So, for me it's also-

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PM: Yes.

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HR2: -An ethical thing that I'm honest and say, "Hey, yeah, we use it, but we still check it. There's the humans behind it. That's our standard." and we want to give

you the feeling which is also sometimes the case that people think you don't take enough effort anymore. You don't put enough work into it anymore because you give it to tech. So yeah, that's yeah, yeah.

71

PM: Yes, this is what you mean, OK. Is this view as you shared with me right now, also shared by people in your department or in your, I mean, in your surroundings, or have maybe some people seen some other issues or maybe seeing less issues that you're currently seeing or do you think is it sort of homogeneous?

72

HR2: I think there are different viewpoints for sure in in my department, especially in in communications we-

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PM: OK.

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HR2: Mostly agree. Some people use it more randomly and I would say less carefully, but then they know that there will be a review process by me so.

75

PM: OK, they trust you.

76

HR2: They can rely on that. That's perfectly fine. I'm fine with that rule. And in general, we do have guidelines in the company that are really going along with our values, with our company values and that is-

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PM: Yes.

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HR2: -Of course, we are trying to be a very human focused and that we, yeah, take our values very seriously. So, there are already the baseline is already in that direction. So, people have the same mindset. But of course, you still see mailings that are created completely by AI and then it's going out and you say, "OK, yes, but maybe next time-

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PM: OK.

80

HR2: Have a look at it again and yeah, people will notice that it's written by AI" and maybe not find it so.

81

PM: Yes.

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HR2: But mostly I would say we all agree on align, yeah.

83

PM: OK, you've mentioned already the guidelines, so my it is part of the interview now, would it be around the strategies? So, in your department, how do you deal with these ethical concerns or these ethical issues that might arise? What are the things that you are doing?

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HR2: We created guidelines.

85

PM: Perfect.

86

HR2: So, first of all, I mean when it came up, it came up really fast. So, we were kind of the first in marketing, the first group to test it really. And we also said, "Hey, yeah, we are really we are *[A BIG HR COMPANY - changed otherwise identifiable]* So it takes too long for us to wait for something to come from the holding. So, the holding, the main company also said in our... in every country they said "Hey, try it out yourself, you are responsible of what you're doing. You know your market best and try it out. Be creative, use it. Be careful. And then be aware that there will be something coming." So, we created guidelines, we got guidelines, general guidelines and then we specialized them on the Swiss market and looked at what would make sense for us. Mostly everything makes sense for us. That makes sense for global, but then we have some specific things, of course, and yeah. Details. It's... but yeah, exactly. And then we offered also trainings from our IT department. We have trainings for people who are being on boarded that we included. "Hey, that's how we use AI. That's what our principles are. Please take into consideration that maybe in your former company that was not important or something else was important. So, we make people aware. And yeah.

87

PM: Yes. The guidelines... are they more about maybe how to use prompts or how to use the tools in itself or what are the main aspects of these guidelines that you've mentioned?

88

HR2: Yeah. Mm hmm, definitely how to how to use it technically, of course. And what are the perks and what you can do, but also data privacy. That's a very big topic for us. Definitely. And then also... yeah. How to check the outcomes, really. How you can trust that you have really have a review process afterwards and don't believe everything ChatGPT or whatever tool you use.

89

PM: Yes.

90

HR2: It says that's definitely in it and also what tools we are allowed to use. We are not allowed to use all the tools definitely. Yeah, and mainly since we are not that really strict and we give a frame where we don't give like really hard borders. So, we always apply to people's sense of responsibility. Everybody has a chance to really try and do it on their own best knowing and will. But we really make the people aware. "Hey, that's how we use it. That's how you're supposed to use it". But also feel free within those frames to try things out and yeah.

91

PM: Do you have anything in your strategy which is also reactive, so sort of an issue already occurred when using AI. So now we have a plan on what to do afterwards, sort of crisis strategy in this sense or is it always like trying to avoid the issue before it happens? How?

92

HR2: Well, perfect would be proactive, but we are very aware that's not always the case. And in the rush of the business, then you have to be of course reactive too. And we had those situations. We did of course have them already that there are processes in place when something happens, about what we can do. Of course more general, at communication level... Very often, it is not that hot for us, so we can quickly de-escalate since we have really low hierarchies here and be very free and open about the answers there, but yeah, we also have reactive.

93

PM: OK, you also have...

94

HR2: Yeah.

95

PM: Would you say that you are currently satisfied with TS guidelines and strategies that you have, or do you feel like something more could be added to them or there are some blind spots that you might have? Or do you think you have already covered?

96

HR2: I think there are some blind spots. I think with some things.

97

PM: Mm hmm.

98

HR2: You know, in my opinion, can be more strict and maybe you have to be more strict because we're really different levels of profiles and people working for us. I mean, our core business is consulting and recruiting. That of course doesn't match what is going on in our head functions here, like finance, marketing administration-

99

PM: Yeah.

100

HR2: -What we have, and it would be great to have a clearer definition on what job you have, on how to use the tools, because I think. Maybe we could be more free to use them, but the guidelines are very to the core business, especially as to the core business which limits us in in cases where we could be more free.

101

PM: Yes, I understand. I would like to go back for a second to your sort of reactive strategy or reactive guidelines. Is this something that is only in the hands of communication, since crisis communication is usually for the department or is it something that covers the whole group or the other functions? Since you mentioned right now, of course you have finance and administration. Is it covered only by your department, or each department has its own thing?

102

HR2: It's, it's a work together. It's basically... Mainly actually coming from IT in our case, because it's really about security there and-

103

PM: OK.

104

HR2: -I well, in communications, not me in that case, but the global communications department of course, has the finger on it and say, "Hey, OK, what how do we react after what happened?" But IT is riding the worst-case scenario. Let's say that and we're coming up with the solutions communication wise because then communication steps in, right?

105

PM: Yes. OK.

106

HR2: To fix wrong.

107

PM: OK. OK, so I have to say that now I have cover covered already the three main aspects of my interviews that would have been AI's implementation, the ethical challenges and the strategies. So now that my questions are over, I would like to ask you if there is anything else that you find interesting or nice to share with us. It might be a thought or maybe.

108

HR2: OK.

109

PM: A story or anecdote that you have seen in your experience in the company. I will just let you free to tell me whatever.

110

HR2: An anecdote. Well, I have something funny. Well, actually...I don't know if you can use it for anything, but we really and that's the nice thing about the AI we have, we created a Christmas song. For our CEO with AI last year and it was so funny because it could really, I don't remember which tool we used for that. A colleague did it. She used it and she created it and she could really take the voices of some of our employees and make it sound like somebody is really singing it. And then they went through the whole company and went viral, basically. And it was a really fun story and people thought it was real. And there was also a part where we said, "OK, now it's becoming a bit scary. Now we have to really..." And now the ethical part comes in again. And we said, "OK, are we transparent now, are we telling people <Hey? It's not real is it's actually AI or don't we?>" And then we decided of course to make it a fun joke. And at the Christmas party.

111

PM: OK, OK.

112

HR2: We sang at all and then we said "Hey, and if you listen closely, our voices are not that nice. So, you know, now we created an AI. AI makes everything more per-

fect. But if you want to have a real person in place, then maybe make it more personal. Then you can also listen to the real song now.” So, we made it a bit of a fun situation and also to make people aware.

113

PM: OK.

114

HR2: Don't be tricked by AI so.

115

PM: Yeah, it's a very nice story and thank you for telling me.

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HR2: Was very funny.

117

PM: Yes. So, I'm actually done if you are OK with it. Of course, we have time if you have any more questions or anything else that you would like to add. But for my part everything has been covered already.

Appendix K: [Interview Transcript_P1]

1	Interview Transcript – P1:
2	March 10th, 2025, h 10.00, Interview on Microsoft Teams
3	PM: OK, so the recording started, so I will switch to English and to start my interview... perfect. To start my interview, I would like to provide you with a definition of ethical AI which can be used to understand or to have a sort of common ground when it comes to this interview.
4	P1: Sure.
5	PM: So, for the purpose of this interview, ethics is understood as an intersection of ethical AI, business ethics, and ethics in corporate communication. In this context, ethics entails acting responsibly to balance innovation and societal impact, mitigate risks, and promote fairness and respect towards social and human values. Does this definition resonate with you, or do you feel you have something more to add or that would like to change?
6	P1: No, that's OK, that's perfect. Perfectly fine for me.
7	PM: Perfect. I'm sorry, I have a cat, and you don't see it right now, but she is playing in the background, so if you hear noises or see something, it's the cat.
8	P1: And it's OK. It's I see. An interview with entertainment. Great.
9	PM: Yes, exactly.
10	P1: But you can present your cat. You know that's not a problem. I like cats. You know. I'm. I'm. I'm a-

11

PM: -But this is the main reason she's the main reason why I have a background, because she's always...

12

P1: You know I'm a cat...man. I'm a cat man.

13

PM: Perfect. OK. So, going back, I would like to start with some more easy question, the first one being: How long have you been working in corporate communication? How long have you been in the field?

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P1: Hmm. So, I'm now close to 10 years. Yeah, in this base of communication. First of all, in the role of a spokesperson.

15

PM: Mm hmm. Perfect. And how long have you been working for the company you are currently in?

16

P1: Close to 10 years as well, yeah.

17

PM: As well, so. And may I ask you what your job consists of at your company right now? So, what are your main tasks?

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P1: It's a communication focus, capital market, communications. I'm in charge of investor relations.

19

PM: Mm hmm.

20

P1: As well as well as the role of the spokesperson. General purposes.

21

PM: Now I would like to switch to AI's implementation, and I would like to start by asking you how often do you and your colleagues use generative AI to complete the communication tasks?

22

P1: Yep. Yes, I think this will be a very short interview. Because we are not using AI in a very significant way, and I would like to explain and to deepen this.

23

PM: Yes.

24

P1: Our company is active in a very, very highly regulated environment. So, and of course this regulation is different in every country-

25

PM: Yes.

26

P1: -In every territory we are active, so have to compliant with a huge number of different jurisdictions, and this of course is a challenge for the whole communication team, to generate content. So, we are rely...So, first we have to be, as a principle, very limited in our communication. So especially I think we have to distinguish between financial or nowadays non-financial disclosures we are obliged to do, and then of course next to this there's corporate communication in terms of PR and marketing and promotion. And as I said, as we are active in a highly regulated environment...so, it's the space of Medtech and healthcare, we have to rely very much on expertise on subject experts.

27

PM: Yes.

28

P1: And therefore, that's basically the reason why we are not, in terms of communication, using AI, of course, maybe there are other technical areas and spaces in our company and in finance and maybe in development and then technology and R&D and operations, of course, we have plenty of efforts to increase efficiency. But communication, our communication is really reduced to...first, limited because we obliged to do so, and then very much focused on facts. Yeah, on medical evidence. That's the that's the most important term. We have to be super safe that we don't promote any information, so, if we're allowed at all, without any or there is without-

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PM: Mm hmm. Yes.

30

P1: -Medical evidence to this. So, it's really, it's very science-based communication as you know. And to every quote, there must be a reference to a medical evidence document, yeah.

31

PM: I assume when it comes to internal communication then you might be more relaxed.

Is it possible for you to, for example, use AI for internal communication or internal projects or anything like that?

32

P1: Yeah, maybe I have to be more precise, OK. I think there might be one area where we are in fact using artificial intelligence, let's say the indirect way. And this is using translation tools. So, if you use directly translation tools or even if you go to an agency, a translation agency, each agency is now using tools.

33

PM: Mm hmm.

34

P1: And probably they are AI based. So, we are a company... in our corporate communication, we are still bilingual. Our leading language is still German, but of course our international reach, our reach out is English. So, we still have to cover any major external communication post languages at minimum. And then of course we have... we are active in more than 25 countries. That means we are... we have to cover more than 20 different languages. So, we have a huge workload of translation, as a very basic LinkedIn or any social media post of course has to be translated in 20 different languages, and always we have to be super safe to do it the correct way because a small change in content and meaning can... could be very harmful for us. And in internal communication I would put it that way. So, next to text, I would say translation task or maybe text improvement tools. We use it for, let's say basic content generation. And so, it gives you... or give ourselves maybe some impulse or some starting point to start from, but then of course we elaborate, we improve, we continue the very traditional way, and then you may assume also in a very complex system.

35

PM: Mm hmm.

36

P1: With the with the highest priority to be compliant and to be compliant with any kind of regulation. So, we have the communication team which is generating content, then we have...to every content there is a subject matter experience, matter experts assigned, and he has to prove it. And then it's even reviewed by the management and every task, most of these tasks, the most relevant tasks are even done in an audit trail or audit proven system. So, we manage this based on... on an SAP tool so that we can really show and prove... so we are compliant.

37

PM: I understand that. For the little AI that you use, for example translation and this basic content generation that you mentioned. Are there any specific tools that you prefer to use for any reasons, something that is more common?

38

P1: Yep. Let's say translation. And really, so we are active from Spain to China, from Sweden to Australia and now also going to the US so we have more than 20 very, very different languages. We have... as a corporate tool, we have selected DeepL.

39

PM: Mm hmm.

40

P1: And I have to say, I'm super content with the features and quality. And for the purpose, for other purposes. So, this is now ongoing to have here a proper solution. So, this is an ongoing task. I would say everybody's using... it for the time being, which is definitely not satisfying, a different tool on a very individual base, I would say most probably use ChatGPT.

41

PM: Yes.

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P1: But we are now putting this on a solid foundation, and this is a task ongoing, this is a work stream. So, we will define, we will establish, and we will implement, and this is now, these days. I just got a notification that we will reach... and it will roll out rather soon in the next couple of days, a proper... let's say company-based, company-specific AI tool-

43

PM: Mm.

44

P1: -Also, to secure cybersecurity and data privacy and data protection, so that the business and the content we are generating and all these requests we are sending to this tool are within protected boundaries.

45

PM: That's something I understand. So, we talked a bit already about the fact that you use it for inputs, use AI. Sorry, for having some starting points and input and translation. If I understood you correctly, this is mainly for internal communication or also for starting projects. Because my next question would have been in which tasks are the tools implemented? Now in your case I feel this question is a bit less relevant since you mentioned you prefer to do things in a traditional way, but if you were to answer the question, are there tasks where AI is mostly used? I'm thinking maybe of correcting a text or maybe writing a newsletter, I don't know.

46

P1: I would say... so, everything that is highly relevant to our products and the safety of our products and the safety of our users... so, we should not rely on AI based content or information. Outside of this or next to this, I think especially in the field of capital market communication, so we could. So, we are using it. As I said, to make some high-level analysis to generate also, to analyze maybe a sentiment, so what's going out? What's going on in our industry? What is happening? -

47

PM: Yeah.

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P1: -Left and right to our company. So, what's going on in our space? Most of our peers are as well equity listed, that means a lot of information is available, there's a lot of content generated around the globe, and of course we try to generate some benefit of this information and to extract value added to shape our equity story, to address certain topics to be... maybe to be ready also in the context of Q&A So, what are the hot topics? What is the elephant in the room? What could be what we have to address actively? What do we have to prepare proactively? And maybe for this we also... we are going to work with another tool. Maybe I should mention it. And this is really very much focused on capital market. This is called Alphasense, this is pure AI using... that it's highly unstructured. But I think quite powerful, yeah.

49

PM: OK, so I think now I have got a better understanding of how your department uses AI... you have mentioned that anyway, when you use AI, you still have a person and an expert which is in charge of proving the quality of the content and making

sure that it is compliant with your regulations and also with your medical information that you are required to always have in mind and have in your documentation, basically. If we now talk about ethical challenges. Where do you see the main use the main risks when it comes to the use of AI?

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P1: I think there are plenty of risks, first of all the risk of giving some insights outside, for what reason ever...there the tools are very powerful but quite... let's say... you know generic and universal platforms, that of course could misuse every entry, data entry. Second of course we have to be aware of is... as a very responsible company and value-based company, the footprint behind it, it is a super energy intensive business, at least the technology available today. Hopefully we still see improvement, but basically one data centre requires one nuclear power plant, which is tremendous.

51

PM: Mm hmm.

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P1: And then of course, we have to be aware that AI is, in terms of output dangerous., Yeah. So of course, depending on the tool and depending on specification and of course and also depending on the on the prompt and the data input... but yeah there is no, you don't have any safety or security about the output. So you have always to challenges, especially in terms of communications, yeah.

53

PM: Yes, you have this particular view of how AI might be dangerous. Is it a sort of a view which is shared within your communication department, or there are different opinions? People who believe it might be used more or maybe even less than what you're already doing? Or is it something that...your concerns are shared within your community? How do you do feel?

54

P1: I think I think AI is here to stay. This is clear. The big question is what's the optimal way to use it to get the optimal value out of it. And so, it's the of course it is increasing efficiency, it makes a couple of tasks much easier. So, a lot of information in principle is available at your fingertip. So, it is saving, any hours of formal paperwork. I think this is understood and this is clear. This is common opinion. The big question is really to do it the right way to do it, to do the right things and do it right, and so to be lean means also you have to take care about the output, the quality of

the output, the reliability of the output and I think therefore it's also it. It is very important, and this is also the, I would say common sense in our company, but also I would say in in the conversation with some peers-

55

PM: Mm hmm.

56

P1: -Outside. We have to be very reflected for which and what purpose we are using it.

Therefore, for the time being...I'm quite happy about how we handle it and how we do it, because it is limited. We try to take benefit, but on the other hand we are not... we don't want to be depending on AI, and I think this is again a big challenge.

57

PM: What would be for you the highest ethical concern if AI was implemented more in your field, or generally the main risk since we mentioned data leaks or misuse of data entries, what would be for you like the worst-case scenario for your field specifically?

58

P1: Of course, privacy, data privacy and so, if anything, if any, legal data breach might be... can be very painful for us. And we are handling very private information. So, we are active in the in the Medtech industry, and Medtech today of course is connected. So, we are offering our devices are connected to cloud solutions, so.... and cybersecurity is key to us. I think this is one very major concern, one major concern. And... of course, exchange compliance. Maybe any data that should be... that could be considered as an insider information...get outside and I would say first maybe finally data, data ownership. You know data ownership.

59

PM: Yes.

60

P1: Any bug or any inconsistency, or any failure or any misleading information across all communication channels can end up very badly.

61

PM: Yes. So, because it's the part related to the ethical challenge, which I think we have concluded. My last part would be about the strategies implemented. I think we have discussed already a bit of it or that I could get some insights already from your

answers. So, my question would have been, can you describe how your department deal with these ethical concerns? I think in your case the answer that I could already get from you. Your discussion is that you basically try to limit the use, but do you also have other? Other strategies, such as... it might be a handbook or a concrete written down strategy or like discussions other than using it as little as possible.

62

P1: Mm hmm. Yes, I think that's, you know... and this is of course the core of our business-

63

PM: Mm hmm.

64

P1: Is. We this is our daily business and we do this in every process and our processes. We have to be able to validate it. And I think that this is the same for AI. And of course this is difficult because by definition AI is not based on rules. So, an AI process is... I don't know, from from a theoretical point of view, how it would be possible to validate? But I would say, to take this on a corporate level is very important. Instead of every department or every person, every individual has AI, I don't know... a different way to deal with it and using apps on a personal smartphone instead of working, so working outside the system. I think this we should minimise... maybe we should block it, we should avoid it at all. And we should... we have to force the people to work within the system with tools that are at least maybe in in, in a sense, validated. That means we establish... we approve certain systems, and everybody has to use it. And then of course, then we can add certain processes and documentation and handbooks. I think this is definitely the way we should go. I don't know by heart if this is already foreseen, but by the way, this is an excellent input, and I will pass it on.

65

PM: But for the moment, then you are not having this kind of work done at the moment is more on individual basis, yeah.

66

P1: This is ongoing. This is ongoing. As I said, there is a this is ongoing, and we want to stop this... every person use its own personal apps unguided, and we have to centralised it and we have to control it. We have to get the grip on this, and I think the first step is now to establish the corresponding technical backbones or the IT solution and once this is place, of course, we have to deal the governance around it, yeah.

67

PM: Yes. So, I would... I'd feel like your approach now and the approach which we're trying to pursue is more preventive. So, sort of trying to avoid any possible issue beforehand. If it comes, I mean, first, do you agree with my sentence?

68

P1: Yes, it's good. Given our industry, I would say this is very reasonable.

69

PM: Yes. Do you have anything on the other hand which is more reactive? So, in the case of something with AI was going to happen, do you have a sort of reaction strategy that tells you, "OK, it has already happened, this is how we're going to handle the situation from now on?"

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P1: So, as I said, from a corporate perspective, of course we recognise and have identified that AI is very important.

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PM: Mm hmm.

72

P1: And this was the reason why we decided to establish a work task force and to and to and to install certain corporate wide solutions. But maybe we are not. We are not a front runner. We are not the front runner, so these are recognised but we have to, we have everything we do must be risk based.

73

PM: Mm hmm. OK. Yep. So, you have sort of a risk strategy in general.

74

P1: Exactly. Exactly. Exactly. And so, this is given our industry and they're highly regulated, and the regulation that is in place.

75

PM: Well, yeah. So, are you happy with the strategy that you are implementing? So, this idea that you bring AI to a corporate level, or do you feel that something more could be done or could be discussed in the next future to like be 100% secure with what how you use AI or are you satisfied with it?

76

P1: I'm happy. So maybe we are not super front running on this topic, yeah.

77

PM: OK. Mm hmm.

78

P1: But on the other hand, I think we are aware about risks related to this topic. And so, we tried really to balance risk and benefit.

79

PM: OK. So I think. This kind of answers all my main points for this interview in order to close off the interview, I would like to ask you if you have something significant that you would like to share with me. Or maybe something that you have experienced which is related to the use of AI in your company which you think is a sort of anecdote or an example like anything. Basically, you are really I will just give it to you the possibility to tell me anything.

80

P1: Yeah. Thanks. But I think we take it all relevant points. So, thanks for the good list of questions for me this is fine. We can leave it there.

81

PM: OK. Yeah, that's perfect. Perfect. Perfect. Then my questions have been answered. I think your answers gave me a really nice insight on how your field tackles these challenges. Of course, AI is challenging for all of us right now.

82

P1: Yeah, for the university, I think it's a big challenge. It's a bad, that's a good. That's a good example.

83

PM: OK. Yes, exactly. Definitely. So, I will stop recording now.

Appendix L: [Interview Transcript_P2]

1	Interview Transcript – P2
2	March 17th, 2025, h. 15.00, Interview on Microsoft Teams
3	P2: The whole file with the confirmation and the signature. [<i>talking about signing the consent form</i>]
4	PM: Yes, I need to ask for the signature. It's no worry. You can send it also the next day. It's not that urgent. It's just your signature, perfect.
5	P2: OK. Very good. Yeah, because now I have nothing to easily sign, so I will do that later.
6	PM: No, no. Yes, that's no problem. Also, the next days, no worries. So. Before we start with the questions, I would like to give you a definition of how ethics is understood for this project. So, we're talking about using AI in corporate communication and doing this ethically. So, I would like to have a common understanding of what this means. So, for the purpose of this interview ethic is understood as an intersection of ethical AI, business ethics and ethics in corporate communication. In this context, ethics entails acting responsibly to balance innovation and societal impact, mitigate risks, and promote fairness and respect towards social and human values. So does this definition work for you. Is there anything that you would like to add or that you feel should be included?
7	P2: It was a bit fast now. Maybe you can show it to me.
8	PM: Yes, no problem. I think I can maybe share with you directly the screen, so that you can read it.
9	P2: That would be the easiest because otherwise I...

10

PM: No worries.

11

P2: It's more difficult to answer that question because this is... I mean, yeah, I can see it. It's a bit small still maybe you can.

12

PM: So, I hope you see what I'm doing. I will make it bigger.

13

P2: Yeah.

14

PM: Yes, this is the sentence I was recently reading to you.

15

P2: Yeah, that's for sure a good way, a good definition for the interview. It's just for the intro, right? It's not that you're asking for any additional content to it, OK?

16

PM: No, no, no. It's just for the interview. Exactly. So now that we have the definition, I would like to start with a couple of relaxed questions. So how long have you been working in corporate communication?

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P2: I have been working since 2010 in corporate communication. So, it's 15 years now.

18

PM: Yes. And how long have you been working for the company you are currently working for now?

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P2: Only one year, so I started one year ago.

20

PM: Yes. And what do you do now? I mean, I've seen that you are the chief of communication. So, what does your job merely consist of? What are your tasks?

21

P2: Yeah, I mean, corporate communication for [COMPANY'S NAME], we are a listed company. So, a big part of the task is shareholder communication and employee communication. And yeah, positioning also the company towards internal and external stakeholders.

22

PM: Mm hmm.

23

P2: And yeah, a big part nowadays is always, also, about reputation. So that we take care of the reputation of the company, and that means there is a lot of consulting within the company-

24

PM: Yes.

25

P2: -To have the right messages. Yeah, to communicate at the end.

26

PM: Perfect. And if we now go more specifically about artificial intelligence, how often do you use it? Or do people in your department, in the communication department use it?

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P2: Yeah, we have implemented Copilot. So, I have been using it since... bit more than half a year now. As it is still pretty new tool but also implemented by our IT department, so we can use both sides, so topics within the company...so, there is Copilot for within the company, but also for outside of the company, with the research... and we are testing that also in our department, yeah, to find out how we can use it best for us.

28

PM: Do you use it frequently or only for specific tasks? Or is it something you do every day? I mean, how do you use it?

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P2: If you ask myself personally, I use it often within texts, documents or writing, but not that Copilot writes me the texts. It's more that I have a text, and I let it correct.

30

PM: Yes.

31

P2: Or I'll let it I ask if, if Copilot can make it better or has something to add. And of course, I think almost everyone in the team also uses it for inspiration. So, for research. And. We also use AI for translation, so there is, I mean we are using Microsoft, so also... Viva Engage for example... there is the automatic translation. I think this is AI based as well and we have a translation provider called *[COMPANY'S NAME, unrelated to the interviewee's company]* This is a company that is well known.

32

PM: Yeah.

33

P2: And within this environment, we can also use the AI tool for example. Of course, also we can use Copilot but all day, I too, love the translation partner.

34

PM: Yes. So, you've mentioned already a couple of tools that you are using, so maybe Copilot, *[COMPANY'S Software]* and Viva Engage software. Why do you use them? So where do you see the main benefits? What sort of value do these tools give to your work?

35

P2: So, we are a very small team, only 12 employees, and this is for a company of 8000 people, for corporate communication that's pretty lean. And we also have to aim to be lean because we are... most of the content producing ourselves, all the videos.

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PM: Yep.

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P2: Texts and so on. So, of course, it makes us more efficient. It makes us faster and it's just an additional tool to help our daily productivity as a team.

38

PM: I understand. And so, you've mentioned you use it for text production inspiration. What are like the main tools? I'm sorry, the main tasks? Or the main

aspect where you see “Yes, this is the area in which we implement these tools the most”.

39

P2: Yes, I said. I guess it's text production content. And I cannot speak for all of our, of my team members because they are of course also creative in using it. I know that I have two people. One is a multimedia producer, one is a media video producer, and I think they have, they have the official tools of-

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PM: Yes.

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P2: -Of Adobe and also within Adobe you have certain functions that help them to be faster. For example, in post-production.

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PM: Yes. When do you use them is there a specific way in which we implement them? Do you have the human in the loop kind of reasoning, so that people are always checking it? Or are there scenarios in which the output can be used as it comes?

43

P2: Actually, we do not have... we have not, so we are still, let's say in a testing phase.

44

PM: Mm hmm.

45

P2: The rule for sure is that in Viva Engage and so on, it's automatically written if you use the translation function so that people are aware, OK, this is a machine translation, another human translation. I think this is very important also for the quality standard we have.

46

PM: OK.

47

P2: And otherwise, all the content we produce, we share, is always checked by human beings. So, we use it as an efficient productivity enhancement. We are

testing it, but we are not yet there so that we delegate things like... for example summaries or something like that. What you could also offer, obviously as we can see in the daily newspapers, they sometimes have these AI summaries. So, we are not doing that yet. So does that help you a little bit, but we do not have big guidelines yet. I mean we have the data department but yeah, so this is a bit what we are building up now.

48

PM: OK. Yes, that, sure. That's perfect. Do you maybe use it for video generation and picture generation or is it still mainly text?

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P2: No, it's mainly text, and we think it it's it also needs to be authentic. So, we want to show employees in our videos, and we also have our picture database for the corporate design and corporate identity. This is produced with real human beings and real photographers.

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PM: Yes. Mm hmm. Yes.

51

P2: Still, I need to say of course there are also ways of producing them differently. For sure, companies will do that to save costs maybe as well, but we are there still in the yeah, in the normal setting, we used to do that in the past.

52

PM: So now that I have an overview of how you use AI, I would like to move to the ethical challenges, and I would like to ask you, where do you see the main ethical challenges when it comes to using AI in our field? So, in corporate communication and maybe more, also specifically to the medical field in which you are working for now.

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P2: Yeah, I think of course in in terms of intellectual property, so.

54

PM: Mm hmm.

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P2: I think there are tools like Perplexity for example.

56

PM: Yeah.

57

P2: Where you always have to source. Also, Copilot is giving you the source, so I think it's extremely important that we are not stealing-

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PM: Yes.

59

P2: -Content from...that is protected, for example, and reusing that and then taking this as yours. That's one of the yeah, of the risks there is.

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PM: Mm hmm.

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P2: And I think of course also, yeah, if you if you use it in pictures and so on, so... are you are you flagging it, so saying, "OK, this is AI, fine". I think this is absolutely necessary that you do that. I mean there is also... I just read an article today in the "Persönlich" do you know that? Yeah. And there was about the Tagesanzeiger, how they do it now, they do this testing also with summaries. And there were two links to the guidelines, also that and I think this is very important. So, the most important guidelines are written there, and it will be the next task for sure, also for us to see if we comply to these guidelines or not, or if we have to implement something further.

62

PM: Is it something like... the ideas that you've shared with me right now. So, it is idea of intellectual property and being careful with pictures and videos. Is it something that is shared among your department? Do you see people having maybe different concerns about the use of AI or would you say that you are on the same line, on the same page?

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P2: I think this is something where we did awareness. We need to build up still. Of course, there are guidelines also for the usage of AI tools. So, we are not allowed to use ChatGPT and so on.

64

PM: Right.

65

P2: This is a corporate guideline we have there because this is also dangerous when we share data about our company that is confidential, for example. So, yeah, there are huge guidelines about that from our data governance team. So, this we have, which is common sense, and we also educate all the employees, including the communication department-

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PM: Mm hmm. Yes.

67

P2: -With awareness, learnings about that.

68

PM: Are these trainings more related to how you use the data or also related to how you can use the tools?

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P2: How to use the data. Because the tools I mean this is yeah this is developing so fast.

70

PM: Yes, it's new. Mm hmm.

71

P2: And you cannot forbid to use every tool. Our approach is more to offer as fast as possible a secure environment where people can use it without... yeah, without feeling always in danger. Can they use it or not? So, I think Copilot with Microsoft is a very good solution.

72

PM: Yes. Do you feel that Copilot is safer than ChatGPT when it comes to corporate settings?

73

P2: Well, this is a good question I cannot answer right now. But I mean, at least I trust there also our IT department that tested that. And when I choose the internal-

74

PM: Yeah, OK.

75

P2: -That it is running on my laptop for internal usage, that works more or less the same a it also works when I do a standard work file. Yeah.

76

PM: Considering that you use. I mean, you're not using that much AI in the moment, you're using it, but more for inspiration and some kind of translation and text. There are any specific concerns that you have regarding using AI in a specific way, or do you feel that is a pretty safe way of using AI?

77

P2: No, I think we always need to be aware that this is.

78

PM: Mm hmm.

79

P2: We still need to use our capabilities, the human factor is very important in checking the content, in requesting...Is it true? Is it not true? Because of course everyone that uses it finds out very quickly, OK, there is also a lot of-

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PM: Yes.

81

P2: -Rights or wrongs. That is, yeah, it's a machine at the end, and the content comes from somewhere and it can be pretty much wrong. Even though Copilot tells you it's right. So.

82

PM: Yes. Yes, you always have to.

83

P2: Is the risk. Yeah.

84

PM: So now I would like to talk to you about the strategies that you have. You've told me in the beginning that it is a developing phase for you. However,

I feel that you still have some regulations. So, for example, not using a ChatGPT being careful about data. So could you maybe explain in more details how you regulate your AI usage in your department or in your company?

85

P2: Yeah. So it in the company, it's the data governance department. So that is also taking care of that. I mean it's not only data based on AI, it's also other kind of data. So, I think there we have... as a as a listed company anyway a huge... how do you say? Awareness that we need implement that in a proper way, and the people have to learn and need to find where they can do that. I mean I'm not the head of that department.

86

PM: Yeah, sure.

87

P2: I Cannot tell you all the details. Within our team, we also have... so, this is a nice thing that the company does, so that in all the teams there is also kind of experts or ambassadors.

88

PM: Mm hmm.

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P2: For cybersecurity, data security and so on. So also, we in our team, we have two ambassadors, and we do regular feedback and awareness. In the sense that we talk about the topics, "What can we do better? How do we use it?" So, I think that we are... we have a good way of dialogue in in the team.

90

PM: And also, I understood that you have regulated which AI tools you can use and what not. So, you have regulations in that sense.

91

P2: Yeah, more or less exactly. Or when using it, what people need to make sure.

92

PM: OK, So... Sorry, I have my cat, which is kind of showing. Yes, she is now...she decided that she wants to move up my chair. OK.

93

P2: Yeah, with the usage of it. Oh, I see it's a cute one.

94

PM: I will let her do her own thing now.

95

P2: It's fine, it's fine.

96

PM: Yes, I was thinking you said that you have to kind of be aware of what you can sort of put in your AI. If I understood you correctly, I mean being aware of what you can and cannot do in a sense. Is it something that you discuss in the meetings or that you have written down or I mean how?

97

P2: Uh huh. It's written down in the company regulations we discussed about it within the team and there is regular awareness programs running, where we do our E-learnings about topics as well.

98

PM: Perfect. Are there important takeaways learning that you have done recently that you find particularly interesting?

99

P2: Using AI or...?

100

PM: Yes, yes. Anything that came up in his sessions.

101

P2: Yeah, I think it's to learn from each other. People are. also creative. Some people use it more for inspiration, others more for productivity. And there is day by day, there is coming out something you can do with it, you can try it out and yeah we want to do the this this this right this part joyful for the people so that they inspire each other also in the usage.

102

PM: You still have, so this kind of training and kind of regulations, but it's not a real gAI guideline you mentioned, or do you have a real AI guideline?

103

P2: The AI guideline, yeah, this is from the data governance department.

104

PM: Oh yes, perfect. And does it contain anything specific to corporate communication or is it more general?

105

P2: General, yeah. It is for everyone in the company.

106

PM: Mm hmm. OK, yes. I have another question for you. I would like to ask you if you think that your AI approach right now is more preventive, so try to avoid having an issue beforehand, or more reactive, in the sense that you are planning how to deal with an issue after it occurred? So, if you try to avoid the issue or solve it afterwards.

107

P2: Our approach... I guess it's both, you tried to avoid it and when it happens, I think this is with every damage you cause. You always try to avoid it, and you implement as I said with awareness campaigns and so on.

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PM: Yes.

109

P2: But if it happens, you need to have an action plan, a crisis management, or a task-force management and we have that all implemented.

110

PM: Perfect. Yes. Are you currently satisfied with all these methods that you described to me or would you wish to have something more, something that makes you feel more secure in certain aspects?

111

P2: No, I think we have a good measure in place.

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PM: Yes.

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P2: This is important, and we are continuously...yeah, bringing effort into these topics to get better, to learn from the newest possibilities that there are in this environment. As I said, it is developing so fast that you continuously need to be on track on that and we have...also, specific teams that are collaborating with each other among the company and they are very diverse so that they are from all the departments.

114

PM: I think I wanted to ask you one last question which does not have to do with the strategies anymore, but it came to my mind. Of course, since you are working in the pharmaceutical sector, I believe that you kind of have a highly regulated system so that you have all these data departments trying to tell you how to how what is the best way to use this data. Do you think that this has an influence on the way you are using AI right now?
Coming from this field, which is highly regulated, or do you think it would be the same if you were working in another field?

115

P2: I don't know, I mean. I think it's yeah; it is highly regulated. So, you need to be aware of how you use it. But I think this is also in other sectors. So, I was working before in the energy sector, it was very similar.

116

PM: OK, so it's not, I mean specific to your sector, it's more, yeah.

117

P2: Yeah, in the communication I I cannot speak about the communication department and not for all.... I mean, of course, all the operational departments, they have very specific guidelines.

118

PM: Yes.

119

P2: But communication is more or less similar as in other industries.

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PM: Yes, similar. Perfect. So, I think I've collected all the information that I wanted to collect.
With this interview, therefore, I would like to conclude the interview by asking you if you have anything else that you would like to add, something that I didn't

ask, but you wanted to tell or a story, anecdote, anything. I will just leave you free right now to.

Tell me if you have something.

121

P2: That's fine. So, if I if you can send me the into when you did write it.

122

PM: Yes, that's right.

133

P2: OK. Very good. Thank you for your time and good luck with your thesis.

134

PM: Thank you. Good luck to you as well for your work and have a nice evening.

Thank you. Bye bye. Ciao.

Appendix M: [Editorial annotations]

Editorial Annotation	Function	Use
[COMPANY'S NAME]	Anonymisation of company's name	Common
The whole file with the confirmation and the signature [<i>talking about signing the consent form</i>]	Implicit reference in conversation	Specific, interview with P2
I think Mango [<i>clothing brand, unrelated to HR1's company</i>]	Reference clarification	Specific, interview with HR1
[<i>headering?</i>] attacks.	Unintelligible word	Specific, interview with HR1
[COMPANY'S Software]	Anonymisation of company's name	Common
They [<i>proofreaders</i>]	Implicit reference in conversation	Specific, interview with HR2
we are really we are [<i>A BIG HR COMPANY - changed otherwise identifiable</i>]	Anonymisation of company's name	Specific, interview with HR2
We have mentioned a few of them [<i>ethical issues</i>]	Implicit reference in conversation	Specific, interview with HR2
you have to go through 1000 [<i>of chatbots, referring to customer service-related situations</i>]	Implicit reference in conversation	Specific, interview with FB2
Of course, the last step [<i>reading on paper</i>], which is the most critical one	Implicit reference in conversation	Specific, interview with FB2
This was 20, I think 19 [<i>years ago</i>] when we launched it.	Implicit reference in conversation	Specific, interview with FB2
People think that we are against breastfeeding [<i>because of the company also selling baby formula</i>]	Contextualisation	Specific, interview with FB2
I can't think of anything which would have you could use AI to write your [?]	Unintelligible word	Specific, interview with FB2
To feed it with our internal documents and some external as well [<i>into AI</i>].	Implicit reference in conversation	Specific, interview with FB2
which makes people very manipulative [<i>probably meaning "manipulated"</i>]	Intended meaning	Specific, interview with FB1
we use TransTurbo [<i>probably meaning: TurboScribe</i>]	Intended meaning	Specific, interview with FB1
Give me a text for [meaning: <i>about</i>] a person	Intended meaning	Specific, interview with F11
"If you don't redigate [meaning: <i>edit</i>] the text mostly	Intended meaning	Specific, interview with F11
[COMPANY'S NAME] GPT is an internal tool	Anonymisation of company's name	Specific, interview with E1
You know about fingers [<i>in AI's image generation</i>]	Implicit reference in conversation	Specific, interview with E1
That is great to say [<i>ironic</i>]	Clarification of tone	Specific, interview with E1
I use LinkedIn [meaning: <i>AI</i>] as my counter partner	Intended meaning	Specific, interview with E2
<i>the opening of a new site in [COMPANY'S LOCATION].</i>	Anonymisation of company's name and location	Specific, interview with E2
<i>The division where I'm sitting is [NAME OF THE COMPANY'S DIVISION].</i>	Anonymisation of company's division	Specific, interview with E2

Appendix N: [Coding Notes]

HR1:

Tasks in which AI is implemented:

- Writing texts, ads
- Brainstorming, generating ideas

AI advantages

- Faster
- Cost efficiency
- Fun
- Creative

AI disadvantages

- Unknown/ unreliable sources
- Quality loss in text production or image generation
- Inaccurate production (e.g. things that are not actually there, hallucinations)

Ethical challenges:

- Biases
- Unclear sources of the outputs
- Difficulty in rationalizing why something is wrong → could also hint to an area in which training is required
- Data security
- Employees' lack of knowledge

Possible solutions to the ethical challenges:

- Personalized AI tools/ features that can only draw on a pool of previously selected information to control the sources
- Clearly stating that the content is AI generated
- Own the machine
- Humans being in control of the machine or the tools
- Teaching the basics before introducing AI

Common views in the department

- Hesitancy
- Next technological step
- Consciousness (I think in communication we actually are).

Strategies implemented to deal with ethical issues

- AI trainings
- AI responsible kit tools and ethics

AI's regulations

- No video or image generation in communication

Approaches

Preventive

- It is impossible to use prohibit AI's use
- It is impossible to stop progress

Satisfaction with the current strategy -> Although satisfied, they mentioned things that could be done to prevent problems that are not currently set in place by their company

Positive

- IT department that takes care of the issues

Negative

- We tend to only see the positives

What could be added:

- Company or department specific tools with controlled sources

General impressions of AI

- We are at the beginning of a process

HR2**Frequency of AI use:**

- Daily

AI tools most frequently implemented:

- ChatGPT
- Gemini
- Internal AI tools

Tasks in which AI is used:

- Translation
- Brainstorming
- Research
- Creation (although not that much)
- Standardized texts like SEO texts

Problems with generative AI

- Bad quality (especially texts being similar, sort of a loop)
- Other algorithms (e.g. Research engines) recognizing the use of AI and downgrading the content
- ChatGPT ignoring the instructions
- Losing quality standards
- AI not being able to provide content as high as the company promises to deliver it (?)

Human in the loop or AI working alone

- Human in the loop

Ethical Issues

- Data security
- Transparency
- Responsibility
- AI replacing people (because in the HR sector you should be employing people and not machines)
- Losing quality standards → also having the necessity to provide high quality information
- Confidentiality
- Loss of trust (people don't think that you put effort in your work anymore, people believe that you just use AI)
- People using it less carefully/ only relying on someone else for double checking → Not framed as a problem by HR2, but could be a problem especially if we considered the ECRM 2023's results that show that communication professionals do not have enough competencies to deal with AI. Only relying on someone means the other are not able to check AI use for themselves?
- Trusting everything that tools tell you

Solutions to AI problems or ethical issues

- People correcting and double-checking, human in the loop as a form of solution
- Declaring that the content is AI generated
- Guidelines → coming from IT, no department specific guidelines
- Spreading awareness with trainings and country-specific guidelines → regarding data privacy, but communication checks the guidelines and if something happens they are required to step in
- Applying to people's sense of responsibility
- Having an internal AI (already implemented in the case of HR2)

Advantages when using AI

- Speed
- Efficiency
- Fun
- Enrichment
- Opportunity to simplify things

Opinions/ Attitudes within the communication department

- Some troubles
- People using AI differently
- General alignment

Preventive or proactive

- Preventive

Satisfaction with their current guidelines

- More strict
- Could be different depending on department/ position

E1:**Frequency when using AI:**

- Every day (even every hour)

AI tools

- ChatGPT
- Internal GPT
- Copilots

Most used AI tools

- Internal GPT
- ChatGPT

Problems when using AI

In case of image generation, quality is still low and people are able to detect it

AI generated content in terms of images does not land well on all audiences

Advantages when using AI

- Helping with creativity
- Giving new ideas quickly
- Time-efficient

Tasks in which AI is used

- Rewriting e-mails
- Brainstorming (slides, presentations, creative idea generation)
- Writing copies for social media -> Especially if they already have an idea of what to write
- Newsletter
- Booklets
- Summaries

Ethical issues related to AI use

- Not knowing the source of information
- Faulty information in outputs
- AI generation (unknown origin of the pictures used to generate the new one)
- Copyright
- Data security (personal data, inputs)

Solutions to AI problems or ethical issues

- **Guidelines** (in forms of wiki with different prompts and different guidelines, suggestions related to data security)
- Not using AI generate images and videos
- Global generation AI team → staying in contact with different regions, implementing new tools
- Human in the loop, human proofreading (different in every department, but implemented in communication department)
- Fact-checking
- Biweekly GenAI calls with the global team where people can ask questions and learn about the newest updates
- Different tools with different classifications
- Social media team leading AI meetings with communication team

Satisfaction with guidelines

- Currently satisfied, clear guidelines/ tools regarding image generation and presentation are missing

Preventive or reactive

- Preventive, very careful to not cause any trouble
- Issues related to the use of AI are unlikely because not everyone use AI, and texts are always double-checked.

Personal stories or attitudes

- Shared beliefs in team, discussions about faulty outputs and information origin
- Used AI to generate a Christmas story regarding Santa Clause with pictures, but Photoshop was needed to improve the quality of the pictures
- People in communication are open to new things and are not resisting change/ AI

E2:

Frequency when using AI:

- Not often, only for limited tasks
- Other people in the team use it more frequently for slides creation, content creation generally

Tasks in which AI is mainly used

- Generating social media content
- Generating LinkedIn content
- Video and image creation, especially to provide a concrete idea of technologically advanced products without showing the real one (so that the competition does not see them)
- Writing summaries and bullet points
- Sorting pros and cons
- Writing notes
- Creating slides

AI tools

- ChatGPT
- Perplexity (only some coworkers)
- Copilot
- Shutterstock (image and video generation function)

Problems when using AI

- Sometimes it is quicker to just write things yourself
- Quality loss → all texts and in general content being very similar, being always the same
- Reducing language level

Advantages when using AI

- Cutting costs by doing things internally
- Employees have to provide the communication department with their own content, AI help them

- Privacy and hiding confidential information (hiding highly technologically advanced products from competitors)
- Showing high confidential products by showing AI's generated prototypes
- Having a counterpart
- Reducing meetings
- Saving time

Ethical issues related to AI use

- False information
- Unknown sources
- Fake news
- Data security

Solutions to AI problems or ethical issues

- Human in the loop, always double-checking
- Long internal approving process (which happens regardless of AI)
- Intranet guidelines about the opportunities and limitations of AI
- Limitations, sharing ideas and thoughts about ChatGPT with colleagues, be responsible when using it
- Not sharing private data or confidential information on ChatGPT
- Compliance trainings that sometimes touch upon AI

Satisfaction with guidelines

- **Satisfied**
- **Something more could be done regarding video creation**

Preventive or reactive

- Preventive
- Not reactive because they are very careful and crisis or issues related to AI's use are unlikely

Personal stories or attitudes

- A field where correctness is extremely important, they are very cautious with what they publish regardless of it being AI generated or not
- Important topic for everyone in the field
- "I am thrilled to announce" → clearly AI written
- AI is a threat but we need to see it as a chance
- Communication job will change and we have to understand which skills will be required
- People ignoring the change will have problems in the future

FB1:

Frequency when using AI:

- Daily

Tasks in which AI is mainly used

- Providing good texts and content in different languages
- Media planning and monitoring
- Planning PR activities
- Brainstorming
- Hearing a second opinion
- Researching
- Social media
- Transcribing
- Project management

AI tools

- DeepL
- ChatGPT
- Airtable
- Copilot (other people)

Problems when using AI

- Not all tools bring concrete benefits to the daily tasks
- Writing nonsense
- Losing time by prompting detailed information into ChatGPT
- Quality inconsistencies
- Always having to control
- Low trust
- Saying «nice sounding» things, but no real content
- AI does not go to deep, not going specific
- Producing the same outputs for different people or prompts, always the same content
- AI does not know all the context and it can forget it

Advantages when using AI

- Satisfaction with quality (short texts, short material), although inconsistent
- Internal decision making (providing employees with the license and encouraging them to use it)
- Especially good for shorter texts
- Analyzing a small quantity of data
- Making processes faster

Ethical issues related to AI use

- People tend to rely more on ChatGPT than on their own experience
- Critical especially for young people who do not have experience → losing valuable professionals?
- Unknown sources
- The spread of false information can turn into manipulation
- People not being able to evaluate ChatGPT's outputs

Solutions to AI problems or ethical issues

- Common sense
- People always double checking

Satisfaction with guidelines

- Satisfied
- Human touch is always needed

Preventive or reactive

- Not really a strategy

Personal stories or attitudes

- Is better to discuss and brainstorm with colleagues, but AI can still provide valuable insights and second opinions
- It's good that AI still has not reached the best quality, because it means that we are still needed
- They are being asked to consult people regarding AI
- They feel like they have the control over what goes out
- Being afraid of telling clients that they use AI because they could not be hired anymore

FB2:

Frequency when using AI:

- Not as much as he could
- Everyday, three times a day

Tasks in which AI is mainly used

- Generating images and videos that are very specific
- Helping other employees to produce texts which will be adapted by communication
- Correcting texts (although there's the need to still adapt them afterwards)
- Writing position papers (that the company has to write about political and social topics such as breastfeeding, since they also sell baby formula), visuals, manuals

AI tools

- Copilot
- Flash?

Problems when using AI

- Not perfect, you still have to correct the outputs
- AI misunderstands things depending on how you write prompts
- Quality loss: "It's good, but it's not great"
- Cannot be used for all tasks equally

Advantages when using AI

- Makes things faster
- Reducing workload
- Doing repetitive tasks and leaving creative tasks to humans
- Quickly documenting tasks and information
- Systematic work can reduce human error

Ethical issues related to AI use

- Risks related to confidential information
- Unconscious bias
- Incorrect prompting (machines can misunderstand what you want and it might lead to ethical issues, such as writing "he" when you do not necessarily mean a male)
- AI does not have "human morality", it cannot distinguish right from wrong the way we would do
- Profiling
- People not knowing how to use it properly → putting in things that they should not – data security?
- AI not being politically correct, for example using discriminatory language
- Over-reliance
- In food and beverage they have a highly regulated field and they have to be very attentive of what they put in labels
- Product descriptions in different languages need to be perfect

Solutions to AI problems or ethical issues

- Using Copilot in the company's Microsoft encrypted environment
- Rule of thumb: "If you cannot talk about it with your friend's neighbor, then do not put it on AI"
- Human in the loop, having a human person controlling the outputs/ anything that goes out
- AI in itself needs regulation (for example, Elon Musk's AI does not have any and the person would not feel comfortable using it)
- AI replacing jobs → not very likely that it will take over communication because you still need the human touch → Same expression used by FB1
- Always checking multiple times, but also in human-generated content, because it could also backfire
- Trial-and-error
- Webinars
- Policies with dos and don'ts

Satisfaction with guidelines

- Generally satisfied, needs maybe more exchange with colleagues

Preventive or reactive

- Preventive
- No reactive strategies planned but it could be a good idea

Personal stories or attitudes

- After having a lot of experience in the field, the person does not see a lot of advantages in using AI → after 20 years of writing articles, you can do it pretty fast and you do not need AI to help you
- The most important thing is learning how to properly use AI

F11:

Frequency when using AI:

- Daily

Tasks in which AI is mainly used

- Brainstorming
- Kick-off ideas, giving hints
- Challenging texts
- Shortening press releases
- Internal communication, Intranet
- Website
- Translation

AI tools

- Only Copilot officially
- Privately, people are also using other tools
- Azure (used to manage AI implementation and use cases)
- Third party providers that give them AI focused on specific use cases → specific prompts and information which are really specific to the use cases and tone of voice of the company, otherwise Copilot would not be accurate enough

Problems when using AI

- Inaccuracy or inconsistency when it comes to company's specific information or tone of voice, especially when it comes to

Advantages when using AI

- Copilot has data protection from Microsoft so it feels more secure
- Flexibility
- Fastening processes, efficiency
- People have more time to check for texts' quality

Ethical issues related to AI use

- Data protection
- Biases, discrimination
- Not many issues as they communicate mostly about numbers and they have trained people who proofread everything
- Marks stating that the content has been created by generative AI

Solutions to AI problems or ethical issues

- Use cases and prompts specially tailored to the company's and communication department's needs
- Human in the loop, always having humans controlling AI's outputs
- Regulations about data protection and biases
- Prompts library

Satisfaction with guidelines**Preventive or reactive**

- Preventive
- Reaction would not be needed because humans have the ultimate responsibility, therefore they do not need specific measures for AI-related crisis

F12:**Frequency when using AI:**

- Some people daily and some people almost never
- The interviewer personally multiple times a week

Tasks in which AI is mainly used

- Translation
- Getting a quick overview on a topic
- Summarizing

- Social Media texts
- Sometimes image generation (limited to adapting already existing images)

AI tools

- Sweet Translator, internal AI-based translation tool
- Internal GPT tool

Problems when using AI

- Very peculiar field with very sensitive information and strong regulations, AI must be used more carefully
- Medical information needs to be extremely accurate, AI is not
- Lacks personal touch
- Not suitable for longer texts, customer magazines, or specialists' texts
- AI style is not really good yet

Advantages when using AI

- Efficiency
- Time saving
- Good content

Ethical issues related to AI use

- Data security
- Uncertainty regarding output's quality
- Very high risk when it comes to medical or health topics
- Detecting AI (in case of ambiguity) with public AI detection tools

Solutions to AI problems or ethical issues

- Internal translation tool
- Internal GPT tool → both good because data cannot be put on Internet as training data, there is more privacy and because they can reproduce the company's tone of voice
- Always controlling data security is being respected
- Four eyes principles, someone always checks what is being published
- Guidelines for data security
- Workshops
- Will prepare guidelines that are more specific for communication

Satisfaction with guidelines

- Cannot really judge considering that they are only at the beginning of the process
- The AI landscape develops quickly, therefore solutions that might work this year could be already outdated this year
- Could include smart guidelines for the different communication channels
- People should really be trained regarding prompting, evaluation of AI generated content and efficiency

Preventive or reactive

- Preventive in case of data security
- Reactive, they usually tell people to stop using AI in a certain way when they notice it could be problematic

Personal stories or attitudes

- Fear that the next generations might not be able to do the job
- In the future there should be better regulations or a better understanding of how AI should be used so one has to control people's production less
- Different opinions about AI use in team

P2:

Frequency when using AI:

- Very often

Tasks in which AI is mainly used

- Correcting texts
- Research
- Inspiration
- Translation
- Video-post editing

AI tools

- Copilot
- Translation software provided by another company

Problems when using AI

- Tools are developing very fast, so it is difficult to develop guidelines about how to use them

Advantages when using AI

- Efficiency
- Boosting productivity

Ethical issues related to AI use

- Intellectual property
- Needing to know the source of information (no stealing, copywriting issues)
- Publishing AI generated content without declaring it (intellectual honesty?), especially in image and video generation
- Data security
- Uncertainty regarding the correctness of AI's outputs

Solutions to AI problems or ethical issues

- Only translations are entirely automated and people within the company are aware
- Human in the loop, someone is always checking the outputs
- Guidelines, especially regarding data security
- Use of ChatGPT is not allowed
- Trainings focusing on data security
- Cybersecurity ambassadors that do feedback & awareness sessions with the team

Preventive or reactive

- Mainly preventive, but they have crisis management in place in case something happens

Satisfaction with guidelines

- They work as they are

Personal stories or attitudes

- The human factor is always going to be necessary
- Not many difference when it comes to AI usage in communication, similar situations in every industry

P1:**Frequency when using AI:**

- Not often

Tasks in which AI is mainly used

- Translation
- Giving input or ideas

AI tools

- DeepL
- Privately, people are using their own tools, probably ChatGPT
- AlphaSense (project management, not generative AI)

Problems when using AI

- They operate in a highly regulated environment where every word is extremely important, and inaccuracy can be very dangerous. AI cannot keep up with that.

Advantages when using AI

- Efficiency
- Can take over monotone tasks

Ethical issues related to AI use

- Putting confidential data on AI tools
- Outputs are not accurate and do not have a good quality
- Ecological footprint
- Data security

Solutions to AI problems or ethical issues

- Limiting AI use
- Using corporate-based AI
- Prohibiting employees from using other AI tools privately

Preventive or reactive

- Preventive

Satisfaction with guidelines

- Satisfied with the ongoing process

Personal stories or attitudes

- AI is here to stay, so we need to learn to live with it
- They are not front runners, but they are very aware of the risks

Appendix O: [MAXQDA Statistical data]

Perceptions on provided AI

		Segments	Percentage
Positive views		9	90,0
Further elements needed		1	10,0
TOTAL		10	100,0

Frequency of AI implementation

		Segments	Percentage
Everyday		4	30,8
Varied use within team members		3	23,1
Rarely		2	15,4
Multiple times a day		2	15,4
Often		1	7,7
Multiple times a week		1	7,7
TOTAL		13	100,0

AI tools implemented

		Segments	Percentage
Copilot		7	17,5
Internal GPT/ internal tools		6	15,0
ChatGPT		6	15,0
DeepL		4	10,0
Varied use within team members		3	7,5
Perplexity		2	5,0
Azure OpenAI		2	5,0
Adobe AI		1	2,5
Gemini		1	2,5
Shutterstock		1	2,5
TurboScribe		1	2,5
Airtable		1	2,5
Partners' AI softwares		1	2,5
DeepSeek		1	2,5
InferenceCloud		1	2,5
Synthesia.IO		1	2,5
CopyAI		1	2,5
TOTAL		40	100,0

Tasks in which AI is implemented

		Segments	Percentage
Language and text work		16	30,8
Text enhancement		15	28,8
Ideation support		10	19,2
Visual and multimedia ...		7	13,5
Strategic work		3	5,8
Media relations		1	1,9
TOTAL		52	100,0

Strategic work

		Segments	Percentage
Distribution and adaptation in ...		1	33,3
PR concepts		1	33,3
Trend Monitoring		1	33,3
TOTAL		3	100,0

Media relations

		Segments	Percentage
Media monitoring and media ...		2	100,0
TOTAL		2	100,0

Language and text work

		Segments	Percentage
Translation		8	42,1
Formal texts		5	26,3
Copywriting		5	26,3
Notetaking		1	5,3
TOTAL		19	100,0

Copywriting

		Segments	Percentage
Social media copywriting		3	37,5
Booklets and brochures		2	25,0
SEO Texts		1	12,5
Intranet and Webepages		1	12,5
Newsletter		1	12,5
TOTAL		8	100,0

Formal texts

		Segments	Percentage
Presentations		2	40,0
Transcriptions		1	20,0
Protocols		1	20,0
Speeches		1	20,0
TOTAL		5	100,0

Text enhancement

Code: ← Text enhancement →		
	Segments	Percentage
Summarising and combining ...	7	38,9
Writing improvement	4	22,2
Text editing	3	16,7
Text challenging	2	11,1
Bullet points creation	2	11,1
TOTAL	18	100,0

Ideation support

Code: ← Ideation support →		
	Segments	Percentage
Input/Inspiration	7	63,6
Brainstorming	3	27,3
Overview generation	1	9,1
TOTAL	11	100,0

Visual and multimedia production

Code: ← Visual and multimedia production →		
	Segments	Percentage
Video and image generation	5	55,6
Visual prototypes	2	22,2
Social media content generation	2	22,2
TOTAL	9	100,0

Perceived AI advantages/ Reasons for use

Code: ← Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use →		
	Segments	Percentage
Increased efficiency	19	46,3
Satisfaction with results	9	22,0
Creative support	7	17,1
Transformative impact in the ...	3	7,3
Organisational reasons	3	7,3
TOTAL	41	100,0

Increased efficiency

Code: ← Increased efficiency →		
	Segments	Percentage
Time saving	14	43,8
Optimised workflows and ...	7	21,9
Shifting routine focus to qualit...	4	12,5
Effort reduction	4	12,5
Cost reduction	2	6,3
Reducing potential for human ...	1	3,1
TOTAL	32	100,0

Satisfaction with results

		Segments	Percentage
Good features and quality		6	75,0
Consistency with company's ...		2	25,0
TOTAL		8	100,0

Creative support

		Segments	Percentage
Inspiration and idea generation		6	75,0
Fun and enjoyment		2	25,0
TOTAL		8	100,0

Organisational reasons

		Segments	Percentage
Increased data security and ...		4	80,0
Formalization of AI use		1	20,0
TOTAL		5	100,0

Perceived AI disadvantages

		Segments	Percentage
Inaccurate or unreliable outputs		14	50,0
Inefficiency		10	35,7
Incompatibility with complex o...		3	10,7
Audience rejection of AI's ...		1	3,6
TOTAL		28	100,0

Inefficiency

		Segments	Percentage
Inefficiency in certain tasks or ...		5	50,0
Inefficiency due to users' lack ...		2	20,0
Time inefficiency due to ...		2	20,0
Slow and costly solutions		1	10,0
TOTAL		10	100,0

Inaccurate on unreliable outputs

		Segments	Percentage
Poor text quality		7	63,6
Incomplete outputs		3	27,3
Poor video and image quality		1	9,1
TOTAL		11	100,0

Ethical risks and issues

Code: ← Ethical risks and issues →		
	Segments	Percentage
Unreliability of outputs	14	16,9
Lack of control	13	15,7
Data security and cybersecurity	11	13,3
Perceived authenticity of AI ...	10	12,0
Copyright issues and unclear ...	8	9,6
Manipulation and ...	7	8,4
Biases	6	7,2
Overreliance on AI tools	5	6,0
Legal compliance	5	6,0
Job security	2	2,4
Environmental issues	1	1,2
Lack of empathy or human ...	1	1,2
TOTAL	83	100,0

Unreliability of outputs

Code: ← Unreliability of outputs →		
	Segments	Percentage
Faulty outputs	8	57,1
Outputs' incompatibility with ...	3	21,4
Superficial and repetitive ...	3	21,4
TOTAL	14	100,0

Biases

Code: ← Biases →		
	Segments	Percentage
Sexism	2	50,0
Discriminatory language	2	50,0
TOTAL	4	100,0

Lack of control

Code: ← Lack of control →		
	Segments	Percentage
Unknown source of information	4	26,7
Difficulty in determining future...	4	26,7
Difficulty in controlling AI use ...	3	20,0
AI lacking necessary structural ...	2	13,3
Uncertainty regarding AI use	2	13,3
TOTAL	15	100,0

Solutions and mitigation strategies

	Segments	Percentage
Corporate-level solutions	19	34,5
Human in the loop	16	29,1
Limiting AI use	13	23,6
Disclosure of AI implementation	5	9,1
AI control tools	1	1,8
Common sense	1	1,8
TOTAL	55	100,0

Human in the loop

	Segments	Percentage
Four eyes principle	5	62,5
Experts review	3	37,5
TOTAL	8	100,0

Limiting AI use

	Segments	Percentage
Using company owned tools ...	6	42,9
Only using company approved...	5	35,7
Banning AI video and/ or imag...	2	14,3
Banning AI completely	1	7,1
TOTAL	14	100,0

Corporate-level solutions

	Segments	Percentage
Guidelines	12	35,3
AI internal workshops and ...	9	26,5
Involvement of AI or IT ...	5	14,7
Department or company-base...	4	11,8
Strict AI workflows	3	8,8
Internal task forces	1	2,9
TOTAL	34	100,0

Guidelines

	Segments	Percentage
Rules and recommendations	8	57,1
Handbooks and manuals	2	14,3
Prompting lists	2	14,3
Position papers	1	7,1
AI toolkits	1	7,1
TOTAL	14	100,0

Evaluation of current strategies

Code: Evaluation of current strategies		
	Segments	Percentage
Partially satisfied	6	30,0
Preventive approach	6	30,0
Satisfied	5	25,0
Both preventive and reactive ...	3	15,0
TOTAL	20	100,0

Partially satisfied

Code: Partially satisfied		
	Segments	Percentage
Further improvements needed	5	83,3
Complicated or inefficient ...	1	16,7
TOTAL	6	100,0

Spontaneous reflections and opinions

Code: Spontaneous reflections and opinions		
	Segments	Percentage
Need for AI education	5	15,2
Inevitability of AI use	4	12,1
Communication sector's ...	4	12,1
Need for communication ...	4	12,1
Risk for overreliance in younge...	3	9,1
Low likelihood of AI - related ...	3	9,1
Peer learning and inspiration i...	2	6,1
AI is a dilemma: Great tools wit...	2	6,1
AI friendliness in communicati...	2	6,1
External perception of ...	1	3,0
Reduction of ethical risks than...	1	3,0
Failed internal AI use cases	1	3,0
Successful internal AI use cases	1	3,0
TOTAL	33	100,0

Appendix P: [MAXQDA Code system]

Codes		973
▼	● Perceptions on provided AI ethics' definition	10
	● Positive views	9
	● Further elements needed	1
▼	● Frequency of AI implementation	13
	● Rarely	2
	● Often	1
	● Multiple times a week	1
	● Everyday	4
	● Multiple times a day	2
	● Varied use within team members	3
▼	● AI tools implemented	26
	● Varied use within team members	3
	● Adobe AI	1
	● Gemini	1
	● Shutterstock	1
	● Perplexity	2
	● TurboScribe	1
	● Airtable	1
	● DeepL	4
	● Partners' AI softwares	1
	● Azure OpenAI	2
	● DeepSeek	1
	● InferenceCloud	1
	● Synthesia.IO	1
	● CopyAI	1
	● Internal GPT/ internal tools	6
	● ChatGPT	6
	● Copilot	7
▼	● Tasks in which AI is implemented	40
	▼ ● Strategic work	3
	● Distribution and adaptation in different countries	1
	● PR concepts	1
	● Trend Monitoring	1
	▼ ● Media relations	1
	● Media monitoring and media planning	2
	▼ ● Language and text work	16
	▼ ● Formal texts	5
	● Transcriptions	1
	● Protocols	1
	● Speeches	1
	● Presentations	2
	● Translation	8
	● Notetaking	1
	▼ ● Copywriting	5
	● SEO Texts	1
	● Social media copywriting	3
	● Booklets and brochures	2
	● Intranet and Webpages	1
	● Newsletter	1
	▼ ● Text enhancement	15
	● Text editing	3
	● Text challenging	2
	● Summarising and combining information	7
	● Writing improvement	4
	● Bullet points creation	2
	▼ ● Ideation support	10
	● Overview generation	1
	● Input/Inspiration	7
	● Brainstorming	3
	▼ ● Visual and multimedia production	7
	● Visual prototypes	2
	● Social media content generation	2
	● Video and image generation	5

▼	● Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use	43
	● Transformative impact in the workplace	3
▼	● Increased efficiency	19
	● Reducing potential for human error	1
	● Shifting routine focus to quality focus	4
	● Cost reduction	2
	● Time saving	14
	● Effort reduction	4
	● Optimised workflows and productivity	7
▼	● Satisfaction with results	9
	● Consistency with company's style and tone of voice	2
	● Good features and quality	6
▼	● Creative support	7
	● Inspiration and idea generation	6
	● Fun and enjoyment	2
▼	● Organisational reasons	3
	● Increased data security and control (in specific cases)	4
	● Formalization of AI use	1
▼	● Perceived AI disadvantages	24
▼	● Inefficiency	10
	● Slow and costly solutions	1
	● Inefficiency in certain tasks or areas	5
	● Inefficiency due to users' lack of knowledge or improper use of AI	2
	● Time inefficiency due to prompting and explaining	2
▼	● Inaccurate or unreliable outputs	14
	● Incomplete outputs	3
	● Poor text quality	7
	● Poor video and image quality	1
	● Incompatibility with complex or experts' content	3
	● Audience rejection of AI's generated content	1
▼	● Ethical risks and issues	70
▼	● Unreliability of outputs	14
	● Outputs' incompatibility with company's values	3
	● Faulty outputs	8
	● Superficial and repetitive outputs	3
▼	● Biases	6
	● Sexism	2
	● Discriminatory language	2
▼	● Lack of control	13
	● AI lacking necessary structural restrictions	2
	● Difficulty in controlling AI use within team members	3
	● Uncertainty regarding AI use	2
	● Unknown source of information	4
	● Difficulty in determining future challenges	4
	● Manipulation and disinformation	7
	● Overreliance on AI tools	5
	● Legal compliance	5
	● Environmental issues	1
	● Data security and cybersecurity	11
	● Copyright issues and unclear content ownership	8
	● Perceived authenticity of AI generated content	10
	● Lack of empathy or human touch	1
	● Job security	2

▼ Solutions and mitigation strategies	63
▼ Human in the loop	16
Four eyes principle	5
Experts review	3
AI control tools	1
▼ Limiting AI use	13
Only using company approved tools	5
Using company owned tools that operate on known internal sources	6
Banning AI video and/ or image generation	2
Banning AI completely	1
▼ Corporate-level solutions	19
Strict AI workflows	3
AI internal workshops and trainings	9
Involvement of AI or IT departments	5
Department or company-based use cases	4
Internal task forces	1
▼ Guidelines	12
Position papers	1
Rules and recommendations	8
Handbooks and manuals	2
Prompting lists	2
AI toolkits	1
Common sense	1
Disclosure of AI implementation	5
▼ Evaluation of current strategies	20
Satisfied	5
▼ Partially satisfied	6
Complicated or inefficient strategy	1
Further improvements needed	5
Preventive approach	6
Both preventive and reactive approach	3
▼ Spontaneous reflections and opinions	31
External perception of replaceability of communication professionals	1
Peer learning and inspiration in AI usage	2
AI is a dilemma: Great tools with many risks	2
Need for AI education	5
Inevitability of AI use	4
Communication sector's awareness of AI risks	4
Risk for overreliance in younger generations	3
Need for communication professionals	4
Reduction of ethical risks thanks to human involvement	1
Low likelihood of AI - related ethical crisis	3
AI friendliness in communication sector	2
Failed internal AI use cases	1
Successful internal AI use cases	1
Sets	0

Appendix P: [Codebook]

Code	Definition	Example
1. Perceptions on provided AI ethics' definition	Interviewees' opinions on the ethic definition provided by the interviewer	"Yeah, that's for sure a good way, a good definition for the interview" (Interview with P2)
1.1. Positive views	Interviewees manifest positive opinions on the ethic definition provided by the interviewer	"I think it's a good, very good definition" (Interview with E2)
1.2. Further elements needed	Interviewees address missing aspects on the ethic definition provided by the interviewer	"Das kann ich unterschreiben. So also bei uns natürlich branchenbezogen sehr wichtig noch medizinische Faktentreue, die hier natürlich auch noch reinspielt" (Interview with F12)
2. Frequency of AI implementation	Information about the frequency in which AI tools are implemented by the interviewees	"So, this is used like daily from I would say most in the company, in communication also daily" (Interview with HR1)
2.1. Rarely	Interviewees declare to rarely implement AI tools	"I would say not a lot" (Interview with E2)
2.2. Often	Interviewees declare to often implement AI tools	"If you ask myself personally, I use it often" (Interview with P2)
2.3. Multiple times a week	Interviewees declare to implement AI tools multiple times a week	"ich würde jetzt mal sagen... mehrmals wöchentlich" (Interview with F12)
2.4. Everyday	Interviewees declare to daily implement AI tools	"I would say daily" (Interview with HR2)
2.5. Multiple times a day	Interviewees declare to implement AI tools multiple times a day	"I would say it's three times a day" (Interview with FB2)
2.6. Varied use within team members	Interviewees declare that the frequency of AI implementation varies within team members	"Das ist sehr unterschiedlich in unserem Team" (Interview with F12)
3. AI tools implemented	Information about the AI tools implemented by the interviewees	"So, I would say everybody in the agency works on a daily basis with DeepL and ChatGPT" (Interview with FB1)
3.1. Varied use within team members	Interviewees declare that the AI tools implemented vary within team members	"We know that some people use, on their private computers, they use other tools" (Interview with F11)
3.2. Adobe AI	Interviewees declare to use Adobe AI	"They have the official tools of Adobe" (Interview with P2)
3.3. Gemini	Interviewees declare to use Gemini	"We just today actually got the implementation of Gemini" (Interview with HR2)

3.4.	Shutterstock	Interviewees declare to use Shutterstock	<i>"We're using Shutterstock"</i> (Interview with E2)
3.5.	Perplexity	Interviewees declare to use Perplexity	<i>"They're also using Perplexity"</i> (Interview with E2)
3.6.	TurboScribe	Interviewees declare to use TurboScribe	<i>"we use TransTurbo [probably meaning: TurboScribe]"</i> (Interview with FB1)
3.7.	Airtable	Interviewees declare to use Airtable	<i>"I just want to say another platform we use very much...Is Airtable"</i> (Interview with FB1)
3.8.	DeepL	Interviewees declare to use DeepL	<i>"As a corporate tool, we have selected DeepL"</i> (Interview with P1)
3.9.	Partner's AI softwares	Interviewees declare to use partners' AI softwares	<i>"We work together with some partners that provide us with concrete implementations"</i> (Interview with F11)
3.10.	Azure OpenAI	Interviewees declare to use Azure OpenAI	<i>"We currently work primarily with Azure"</i> (Interview with F11)
3.11.	DeepSeek	Interviewees declare to use DeepSeek	<i>"We also have like DeepSeek"</i> (Interview with E1)
3.12.	InferenceCloud	Interviewees declare to use InferenceCloud	<i>"So, we use [...] InferenceCloud"</i> (Interview with E1)
3.13.	Synthesia.IO	Interviewees declare to use Synthesia.IO	<i>"So, we use OK, it starts with [...] Synthesia.IO"</i> (Interview with E1)
3.14.	CopyAI	Interviewees declare to use CopyAI	<i>"So, we use OK, it starts with CopyAI"</i> (Interview with E1)
3.15.	Internal GPT/ internal tools	Interviewees declare to use internal GPT systems or internal AI-based tools	<i>"A proper... let's say company-based, company-specific AI tool"</i> (Interview with P1)
3.16.	ChatGPT	Interviewees declare to use ChatGPT	<i>"We use ChatGPT of course"</i> (Interview with HR2)
3.17.	Copilot	Interviewees declare to use Copilot	<i>"We have implemented Copilot"</i> (Interview P2)
4.	Tasks in which AI is implemented	Information about the tasks in which AI tools are implemented by the interviewees	<i>"I think there might be one area where we are in fact using artificial intelligence"</i> (Interview with P1)
4.1.	Strategic work	Interviewees declare to implement AI in tasks fulfilling strategic goals	<i>"We are using it. As I said, to make some high-level analysis"</i> (Interview with P1)
4.1.1.	Distribution and adaptation in different countries	Interviewees declare to implement AI to distribute and adapt content in international locations	<i>"We also have like tools [...] to help you with the distribution correctly in the countries"</i> (Interview with HR1)
4.1.2.	PR concepts	Interviewees declare to implement AI to develop PR concepts	<i>"I have a task that we need to work on a strategy or a new concept for some PR"</i> (Interview with FB1)

4.1.3. Trend Monitoring	Interviewees declare to use AI for trend monitoring	<i>“As I said, to make some high-level analysis to generate also, to analyze maybe a sentiment, so what's going out? What's going on in our industry? What is happening Left and right to our company?”</i> (Interview with P1)
4.2. Media relations	Interviewees declare to use AI for tasks related to media relations activities	<i>“We've built a database for media planning. And also media monitoring”</i> (Interview with FB1)
4.2.1. Media monitoring and media planning	Interviewees declare to use AI for media monitoring and media planning activities	<i>“We've built a database for media planning. And also media monitoring”</i> (Interview with FB1)
4.3. Language and text work	Interviewees declare to use AI for language and text production activities	<i>“Es gibt Kolleginnen und Kollegen im Team, die verwenden diese Tools auch für wirkliche, für Schreibarbeiten“</i> (Interview with FI2)
4.3.1. Formal texts	Interviewees declare to use AI to compose formal, standardised, or structured text types	<i>“And then I use ChatGPT PT and tell him “Write me a protocol”</i> (Interview FB1)
4.3.1.1. Transcriptions	Interviewees declare to use AI to compose transcriptions	<i>“We also use it a lot too... for example, to transcribe”</i> (Interview with FB1, Pos. 98)
4.3.1.2. Protocols	Interviewees declare to use AI to compose protocols	<i>“And then I use ChatGPT PT and tell him “Write me a protocol”</i> (Interview FB1)
4.3.1.3. Speeches	Interviewees declare to use AI to compose speeches	<i>“Like creating speeches”</i> (Interview with E1)
4.3.1.4. Presentations	Interviewees declare to use AI to compose presentations	<i>“I think also for all the slides”</i> (Interview with E2)
4.3.2. Translation	Interviewees declare to use AI for translations	<i>“We also use AI for translation”</i> (Interview with P2)
4.3.3. Notetaking	Interviewees declare to use AI for notetaking	<i>“Do like meeting notes as well”</i> (Interview with E2)
4.3.4. Copywriting	Interviewees declare to use AI for copywriting tasks, meaning creative and persuasive text genres	<i>“I think that's mostly for [...]Writing copy for social media”</i> (Interview with E1)
4.3.4.1. SEO Texts	Interviewees declare to use AI to compose Software Engine Optimisation texts	<i>“For example, SEO texts”</i> (Interview with HR2)
4.3.4.2. Social media copywriting	Interviewees declare to use AI for social media related copywriting activities	<i>“I also use it for social media. I have my written prompts”</i> (Interview with FB1)
4.3.4.3. Booklets and brochures	Interviewees declare to use AI to compose texts for booklets and brochures	<i>“We do a lot of, I don't know, leaflets, brochures”</i> (Interview with E2)
4.3.4.4. Intranet and Webpages	Interviewees declare to use AI to compose texts for Intranet and Webpages	<i>“To draft internal use for the Intranet, or maybe even for the Webpage”</i> (Interview with FI1)

4.3.4.5. Newsletter	Interviewees declare to use AI to compose newsletters	<i>"I think mostly to write copy. So, if it's for a newsletter" (Interview with E1)</i>
4.4. Text enhancement	Interviewees declare to use AI for enhancing previously written texts	<i>"I use it often within texts, documents or writing, but not that Copilot writes me the texts. It's more that I have a text, and I let it correct" (Interview with P2)</i>
4.4.1. Text editing	Interviewees declare to use AI to edit and correct already written text	<i>"I mean, on the other hand we have we have like... but this is more on the pilot phase, things to edit" (Interview with F11)</i>
4.4.2. Text challenging	Interviewees declare to use AI to enhance text that can be considered difficult due to their content or complexity. AI enhances their intelligibility and functionality	<i>"They often use it as a hint giver or to start with something, or to challenge some texts" (Interview with F11)</i>
4.4.3. Summarising and combining information	Interviewees declare to use AI to summarise or combine content or information	<i>"Oder um längere komplexe Themen zusammenzufassen" (Interview with F12)</i>
4.4.4. Writing improvement	Interviewees declare to use AI for general writing support, such as improving phrasing, clarity, and flow	<i>"I ask if, if Copilot can make it better" (Interview with P2)</i>
4.4.5. Bullet points creation	Interviewees declare to use AI to group information into bullet points	<i>"I put it into Copilot for example, and ask "hey, please rewrite this speech, but in bullet points" (Interview with HR1)</i>
4.5. Ideation support	Interviewees declare to use AI for support in ideation processes	<i>"I insert all the information I have and wait for some inspiration" (Interview with E2)</i>
4.5.1. Overview generation	Interviewees declare to use AI to generate overviews of a specific topic	<i>"Manchmal auch, um sich schnell eine Übersicht über ein Thema, das man noch nicht so gut kennt, zu verfassen" (Interview with F12)</i>
4.5.2. Input/Inspiration	Interviewees declare to use AI to obtain first inputs or inspiration	<i>"I think almost everyone in the team also uses it for inspiration" (Interview with P2)</i>
4.5.3. Brainstorming	Interviewees declare to use AI for brainstorming activities	<i>"We do also brainstorm with ChatGPT" (Interview with FB1)</i>
4.6. Visual and multimedia production	Interviewees declare to use AI to produce visual or multimedia content	<i>"We will be able to do image generation with [COMPANY'S NAME] internal pictures" (Interview with E1)</i>
4.6.1. Visual prototypes	Interviewees declare to use AI to generate visual product or content prototypes	<i>"We for example use AI to generate ideas on how we could make some kind of communication on the visual side" (Interview with F11)</i>

4.6.2. Social media content generation	Interviewees declare to use AI to generate multimedia content for social media which is not exclusively text	<i>"I use it, for the moment, just for my LinkedIn content creation"</i> (Interview with E2)
4.6.3. Video and image generation	Interviewees declare to use AI to generate videos or images	<i>"Da wird teilweise mit KI gearbeitet, um etwas Passendes zu generieren"</i> (Interview with F12)
5. Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use	Information about the advantages that interviewees perceive when implementing AI tools	<i>"You see, this is the idea of productivity. I don't need to waste an hour and a half to type the notes. I have them there. It's fantastic actually"</i> (Interview with FB2)
5.1. Transformative impact in the workplace	Interviewees perceive AI tools to deeply transform the workplace	<i>"I think it's life changing when it comes to work"</i> (Interview with E1)
5.2. Increased efficiency	Advantages related to increased efficiency and productivity, creation and organisational support	<i>"So, of course, it makes us more efficient"</i> (Interview with P2)
5.2.1. Reducing potential for human error	Interviewees declare that AI implementation minimise risk for human based mistakes	<i>"It might also be even better maybe than humans in in doing it, because [...] as soon as there's a human element usually there's also always a risk of error"</i> (Interview with FB2)
5.2.2. Shifting routine focus to quality focus	Interviewees note that delegating routine tasks to AI allows them to focus on quality-oriented tasks	<i>"As I said, simplify routine tasks and yeah, focus more on the strategic work"</i> (Interview with HR2)
5.2.3. Cost reduction	Interviewees declare that AI implementation reduces expenses	<i>"AI makes things [...] much more cost efficient"</i> (Interview with HR2)
5.2.4. Time saving	Interviewees declare that AI implementation increases time efficiency	<i>"It makes us faster"</i> (Interview with P2)
5.2.5. Effort reduction	Interviewees declare that AI implementation reduces cognitive or physical effort required to complete certain tasks	<i>"It makes a couple of tasks much easier"</i> (Interview with P1)
5.2.6. Optimised workflows and productivity	Interviewees declare that AI implementation improves work organisation, processes and productivity	<i>"It's just an additional tool to help our daily productivity as a team"</i> (Interview with P2)
5.3. Satisfaction with results	Advantages related to high satisfaction with AI generated outputs	<i>"We figured that ChatGPT for a lot of things is delivering the best base"</i> (Interview with HR2)
5.3.1. Consistency with company's style and tone of voice	Interviewees perceive AI generated outputs to be aligned with the company's communication standards	<i>"But (it) still keep the tone of voice of [COMPANY'S NAME] and the way we communicate"</i> (Interview with F11)
5.3.2. Good features and quality	Interviewees express satisfaction with quality and functionality of AI generated outputs and AI tools	<i>"I'm super content with the features and quality"</i> (Interview with P1)

5.4. Creative support	Advantages related to AI's ability to support and stimulate creative processes	"It's kind of a counterpart, [...] you insert your ideas and your thoughts, and you have an immediate reply." (Interview with E2)
5.4.1. Inspiration and idea generation	Interviewees use AI as a source for creative input	"Sometimes it helps to give some ideas if you have to be creative and write something" (Interview with HR1)
5.4.2. Fun and enjoyment	Interviewees describe AI as enjoyable or entertaining	"That's really to make our everyday lives [...] to be honest, more fun" (Interview with HR2)
5.5. Organisational reasons	Advantages related to AI related organisational improvement	"Everybody already used those tools, so we had to kind of make it officially" (Interview with HR1)
5.5.1. Increased data security and control (in specific cases)	Interviewees declare that specific AI implementation increase the company's data security	we currently have Copilot. This is some kind of ChatGPT adoption which is secure [...] and is provided by Microsoft with all this data protection possibilities (Interview with FI1)
5.5.2. Formalization of AI use	Interviewees apply specific AI implementations to regulate and formalize AI use within the company	"Everybody already used those tools, so we had to kind of make it officially" (Interview with HR1)
6. Perceived AI disadvantages	Information about the disadvantages that interviewees perceive when implementing AI tools	"AI learns from what's online and if you always create a text, it learns from itself. So, it kind of creates a loop that makes the quality really bad right now" (Interview with HR2)
6.1. Inefficiency	Disadvantages related to time consumptions, poor performance or workflow disruption caused by the implementation of AI tools	"The big question is what's the optimal way to use it to get the optimal value out of it." (Interview with P1)
6.1.1. Slow and costly solutions	Interviewees complain about AI slow and costly implementation	"wir erhoffen uns von dort deutlich mehr Geschwindigkeit, gute Qualität und gleichzeitig deutlich tiefere Kosten" (Interview with FI2)
6.1.2. Inefficiency in certain tasks or areas	Interviewees complain about the unsuccessful implementation of AI in particular tasks or areas	"I always say, "Every tool is as good as you know how to use it. But you can't use it for everything" (Interview with FB1)
6.1.3. Inefficiency due to users' lack of knowledge or improper use of AI	Interviewees complain about AI unsuccessful implementation caused by users' lack of knowledge regarding AI or improper use	"People maybe are unproductive, lose time, do not really know what to do, just play around" (Interview with HR1)
6.1.4. Time inefficiency due to prompting and explaining	Interviewees complain about inefficiency caused by the time spent prompting and providing AI with the necessary context	"In formulating all the things I would like ChatGPT to create, I am sometimes quicker in just writing it down myself" (Interview with E2)

6.2. <i>Inaccurate or unreliable outputs</i>	Disadvantages related to poor AI generated outputs	<i>"You have to take care about the output, the quality of the output, the reliability of the output"</i> (Interview with P1)
6.2.1. Incomplete outputs	Interviewees complain about the AI generated outputs missing information or aspects of a task	<i>"We also figured that ChatGPT likes to skip things that we have in the task"</i> (Interview with HR2)
6.2.2. Poor text quality	Interviewees complain about the poor textual quality of AI generated outputs	<i>"But on the other hand, also the quality is getting worse if it's not corrected right?"</i> (Interview with HR1)
6.2.3. Poor video and image quality	Interviewees complain about the poor visual quality of AI generated images and videos	<i>"But then you see some details that are completely wrong [...] because this AI generation doesn't always, alright, hit all the spots"</i> (Interview with HR1)
6.3. Incompatibility with complex or experts' content	Interviewees note that AI struggles to handle highly specialized or complex topics	<i>"Would you trust AI? I'm. I'm not sure. I don't know. The thing is, you know, there are certain things you have to put on. For example, contents of anything that could be people could be allergic to"</i> (Interview with FB2)
6.4. Audience rejection of AI's generated content	Interviewees report that certain audiences respond negatively to AI generated content	<i>"It was very creative in a sense, but also it didn't land that well with our audience"</i> (Interview with E1)
7. Ethical risks and issues	Information related to ethical concern linked to the use of AI by interviewees	<i>"That type of thing is a is a huge problem and I think that's where ethical discussions have to go or already are happening"</i> (Interview with E1)
7.1. <i>Unreliability of outputs</i>	Ethical concerns related to the unreliability of AI generated outputs	<i>"You can use a prompt [...] but [it] does it in a manner which is not reliable"</i> (Interview with E1)
7.1.1. Outputs' incompatibility with company's values	Interviewees report that AI generated outputs do not align with the corporate identity, values, or communication style	<i>"Es braucht es diese menschliche Kontrolle unbedingt, um sicherzustellen, dass nicht etwas kommuniziert wird, dass am Schluss nicht Unternehmenswerten entspricht"</i> (Interview with FI2)
7.1.2. Faulty outputs	Interviewees mention the presence of incorrect, misleading, or factually wrong information in AI generated content	<i>"Well the output and the information that you sometimes receive is faulty"</i> (Interview with E1)
7.1.3. Superficial and repetitive outputs	Interviewee note that AI generated outputs lack depth and originality, and are often repetitive	<i>"Like, it sounds fantastic. But once you read, it's not saying anything. So ChatGPT is really good at that."</i> (Interview with FB1)
7.2. <i>Biases</i>	Ethical concerns related to the presence of social and cultural biases in AI generated outputs	<i>"So, AI can always be biased"</i> (Interview with HR1)
7.2.1. Sexism	Interviewees report the presence of sexist assumptions in AI generated outputs	<i>"The machine might just say, "OK, if it's a woman, then out"</i> (Interview with FB2)

7.2.2. Discriminatory language	Interviewees report the presence of discriminatory or marginalizing and offensive language in AI generated outputs	<i>"We don't use the N word for example, because it it's just wrong to do it. But that system probably... I don't know, it probably would"</i> (Interview with FB2)
7.3. Lack of control	Ethical concerns related to the perceived difficulty in governing, supervising, and ensuring the responsible use of AI systems	<i>"So, one of the things is always "How? How well do we know at all?" [...] What's happening with our data? What's happening with our inputs?"</i> (Interview with E1)
7.3.1. AI lacking necessary structural restrictions	Interviewees note the absence of built-in constraints that could prevent inappropriate use of AI tools	<i>"And one reason why I wouldn't use that for example, is because that has no restrictions"</i> (Interview with FB2)
7.3.2. Difficulty in controlling AI use within team members	Interviewees describe challenges ensuring a responsible and consistent AI use within the organisation	<i>"Some people use it more randomly and I would say less carefully"</i> (Interview with HR2)
7.3.3. Uncertainty regarding AI use	Interviewees express doubts or lack of clarity about how to correctly use AI tools	<i>"So, an AI process is... I don't know, from a theoretical point of view, how it would be possible to validate?"</i> (Interview with P1)
7.3.4. Unknown source of information	Interviewees note the danger of AI generated outputs being based on unverifiable, opaque, or low-quality sources	<i>"If we use ChatGPT or AI to really be aware that we...do not trust the source"</i> (Interview with E2)
7.3.5. Difficulty in determining future challenges	Interviewees express uncertainty regarding the unpredictable developments of AI	<i>"Das ist ein bisschen ein Blick in die Glaskugel, oder?"</i> (Interview with F12)
7.4. Manipulation and disinformation	Interviewees note that AI tools can intentionally or unintentionally be used to spread manipulative and misleading content	<i>"I think it's always a challenge to avoid misinformation, false information"</i> (Interview with E2)
7.5. Overreliance on AI tools	Interviewees highlight the risk of becoming excessively depending on AI	<i>"I think it's still super important that we don't let us drive by AI, but first think ourselves"</i> (Interview with HR1)
7.6. Legal compliance	Interviewees mention difficulties in ensuring that AI use complies with laws and regulations	<i>"So of course, anything we do needs to be within the law. You, you know you can't do anything which is outside the law".</i> (Interview with FB2)
7.7. Environmental issues	Interviewees express concern about the environmental impact of AI	<i>"The footprint behind it, it is a super energy intensive business, at least the technology available today"</i> (Interview with P1)
7.8. Data security and cybersecurity	Interviewee express concern about the handling sensitive data by AI and the potential vulnerability to cybersecurity related risks	<i>"This is also dangerous when we share data about our company that is confidential, for example"</i> (Interview P2)

7.9.	Copyright issues and unclear content ownership	Interviewees note ambiguity around copyright and content ownership of AI generated content	<i>"Copyright infringement, that type of thing is a huge problem and I think that's where ethical discussions have to go or already are happening"</i> (Interview with E1)
7.10.	Perceived authenticity of AI generated content	Interviewees express concerns about the authenticity of AI generated content, especially related to human voice, brand image, and credibility	<i>"It also needs to be authentic. So, we want to show employees in our videos, and we also have our picture database for the corporate design and corporate identity"</i> (Interview with P2)
7.11.	Lack of empathy or human touch	Interviewees reflect AI's lack of emotional intelligence or empathy	<i>"You need the human elements to come into it"</i> (Interview with FB2)
7.12.	Job security	Interviewees concern that the increasing use of AI might lead to job losses	<i>"You really [need to] make sure that the job security is still given"</i> (Interview with HR2)
8.	Solutions and mitigation strategies	Action, practices and policies adopted by the interviewees or their organisations to reduce ethical risks and issues	<i>"Well, this is up to every team, but we have the policy in our team that we look over it"</i> (Interview with E1)
8.1.	Human in the loop	Interviewees describe the importance of human review of AI generated content	<i>"There are always men in the loop. A human, I mean, not just men"</i> (Interview with F11)
8.1.1.	Four eyes principle	Interviewees note that a second person needs to review and approve AI generated content before publication	<i>"Da haben wir ein klares, ein 4 Augen Prinzip, das mindestens 2 Menschen den Text noch durchgelesen und kontrolliert haben müssen, bevor er veröffentlicht wird"</i> (Interview with F12)
8.1.2.	Experts review	Interviewees declare that subject matters experts need to review and approve AI generated content before publication	<i>"To every content there is a subject matter experience, matter experts assigned, and he has to prove it"</i> (Interview with E2)
8.2.	AI control tools	Interviewees declare to use tools to monitor AI usage within team members	<i>"Dann lass ich das durch ein entsprechendes Kontrolltool laufen"</i> (Interview with F12)
8.3.	Limiting AI use	Action and practices adopted by the interviewees or their organisation to mitigate AI ethical risks and issues by limiting AI implementation	<i>"So, we are not allowed to use ChatGPT and so on."</i> (Interview with P2)
8.3.1.	Only using company approved tools	Interviewees declare that the use of AI has been limited to officially approved tools	<i>"It says [...] what tools we are allowed to use. We are not allowed to use all the tools, definitely"</i> (Interview with HR2)
8.3.2.	Using company owned tools that operate on known internal sources	Interviewees declare that the use of AI has been limited to internal AI systems that draw from secure internal data sources	<i>"We use Microsoft Copilot as our tool [...] we keep it within our own Microsoft encrypted environment"</i> (Interview with FB2)

8.3.3.	Banning AI video and/ or image generation	Interviewees declare that image or video generation has been completely prohibited	<i>"The company completely forbid to use AI in communication, for example in videos"</i> (Interview with HR1)
8.3.4.	Banning AI completely	Interviewees contemplate the possibility of completely prohibiting the use of AI tools	<i>"I think this we should minimise... maybe we should block it, we should avoid it at all"</i> (Interview with P1)
8.4.	Corporate-level solutions	Structural and organisational strategies developed to support and regulate AI use within the organisation	<i>"That's why we do a lot of literacy, so that people understand what they can expect"</i> (Interview with F1)
8.4.1.	Strict AI workflows	Interviewees declare that fixed processes for AI implementation have been established	<i>"We have developed like a more strict workflow in in use cases like this"</i> (Interview with F1)
8.4.2.	AI internal workshops and trainings	Interviewees declare that learning opportunities to increase AI literacy have been provided	<i>"We have biweekly Gen AI calls that are led by the global team, so everyone's able to join them, ask questions, get the newest updates"</i> (Interview with E1)
8.4.3.	Involvement of AI or IT departments	Interviewees declare that communication departments collaborate with AI or IT departments to develop ethical approaches for AI implementation	<i>"That's not something we are dealing with. That's something in our IT department"</i> (Interview with E2)
8.4.4.	Department or company-based use cases	Interviewees declare that AI implementation is regulated or allowed within specific use cases for the company or the communication department	<i>"At our company currently this is a catalogue of around 450 use cases which we know of"</i> (Interview with F1)
8.4.5.	Internal task forces	Interviewees note the presence of specialised task forces responsible for monitoring and guiding AI implementation	<i>"We decided to establish a work task force"</i> (Interview with P1)
8.4.6.	Guidelines	Documental resources to support responsible AI use	<i>"There are guidelines also for the usage of AI tools"</i> (Interview with P2)
8.4.6.1.	Position papers	Interviewees note the presence of official documents outlining the company's stance and policy regarding AI implementation	<i>"And the second thing is position papers. So, you have to have a position on everything"</i> (Interview with FB2)
8.4.6.2.	Rules and recommendations	Interviewees note the presence of official dos and don'ts regarding AI implementation	<i>"We put on a small set of rules which we defined in a in a cross functional team"</i> (Interview with F1)
8.4.6.3.	Handbooks and manuals	Interviewees note the presence of reference material offering detailed instructions regarding AI implementation	<i>"Then we can add certain processes and documentation and handbooks"</i> (Interview with P1)
8.4.6.4.	Prompting lists	Interviewees note the presence of promoting lists to support efficient AI implementation	<i>"We have a whole wiki online with different prompts"</i> (Interview with E1)
8.4.6.5.	AI toolkits	Interviewees note the presence of written resources that provide guidance on AI ethical implementation	<i>"We just set up like AI responsible toolkits and ethics"</i> (Interview with HR1)

8.5.	Common sense	Interviewees note that emphasis is put on personal judgement and reflection when implementing AI tools	<i>"Our boss always says to use human sense. Common sense"</i> (Interview with FB1)
8.6.	Disclosure of AI implementation	Interviewees declare that a transparent disclosure of AI generated content is encouraged and expected within the company	<i>"I really need to be transparent and tell "OK this is the original text and this is the DeepL translation, or this is the DeepL or ChatGPT or Copilot short version"</i> (Interview with HR1)
9. Evaluation of current strategies			
Interviewees' opinions about the approaches and strategies in place aiming at reducing AI ethical risks and issues			<i>"I think we have a good measure in place"</i> (Interview with P2)
9.1.	Satisfied	Interviewees express overall satisfaction with the current AI implementation strategy	<i>"I'm quite happy about how we handle it and how we do it"</i> (Interview with P1)
9.2.	Partially satisfied	Interviewees express satisfaction with the current AI strategy while highlighting limitations and improvement potential	<i>"I think there are some blind spots. I think with some things [...] can be more strict"</i> (Interview with HR2)
9.2.1.	Complicated or inefficient strategy	Interviewees describe their strategy as overly complex and overall inefficient	<i>"Prompts are a lot of the time, very over engineered. They're a bit complicated sometimes"</i> (Interview with E1)
9.2.2.	Further improvements needed	Interviewees express the need of refinement or addition to the current strategy	<i>"Maybe another topic would be the video creations"</i> (Interview with E2)
9.3.	Preventive approach	Interviewees describe the strategy as mainly focused on preventing potential ethical risks or issues	<i>"It's prevention because you cannot hinder people in using it"</i> (Interview with HR1)
9.4.	Both preventive and reactive approaches	Interviewees note that the strategy includes both preventive measures and reactive strategies to handle ethical risks and issues	<i>"Our approach... I guess it's both"</i> (Interview with P2)
10. Spontaneous reflections and opinions			
Unsolicited thoughts, general impressions or viewpoints shared by the interviewees during the conversation.			<i>"I would say they're more optimistic or I don't see that they're so scared or they see challenges"</i> (Interview with E2)
10.1.	External perception replaceability of communication professionals	Interviewees reflect how other professionals may view communication professionals as easily replaceable by AI	<i>"So, if we would say we will use it, [...] suddenly companies may say, "Ah, we don't need as many people anymore"</i> (Interview with FB1)
10.2.	Peer learning and inspiration in AI usage	Interviewees describe gaining knowledge or inspiration to use AI by observing colleagues	<i>"I think it's to learn from each other. People are also creative."</i> (Interview with P2)
10.3.	AI is a dilemma: Great tools with many risks	Interviewees express ambivalence towards AI, as it is described as a powerful but dangerous tool	<i>"You get a little bit of a dilemma whereby you want your people [...] to use AI because it's a great tool [...]. But you also [...] need to be able to care for [it]"</i> (Interview with FB2)

10.4.	Need for AI education and literacy	Interviewees emphasize the importance of educating current and future communication professionals on AI	<i>“So, you need to educate people and yourself in using these tools properly”</i> (Interview with FB2)
10.5.	Inevitability of AI use	Interviewees express the idea that AI implementation in communication is unavoidable and will keep growing	<i>“I think AI is here to stay”</i> (Interview with P1)
10.6.	Communication sector’s awareness of AI risks	Interviewees express the idea that communication professionals is already aware of ethical risks pose by AI implementation	<i>“I don’t think that everybody is very conscious about it, but in communication, yes, I think we are”</i> (Interview with HR1)
10.7.	Risk for overreliance in younger generations	Interviewees express concern that younger professionals may rely too heavily on AI tools	<i>“Die jetzige Generation von Leuten, die in der Unternehmenskommunikation arbeitet, die hat das alles noch selber gelernt, das zu formulieren, sich zu überlegen, jedes Wort auf die Goldwaage zu legen”</i> (Interview with FI2)
10.8.	Need for communication professionals	Interviewees argue that human communicators are still essential to the field	<i>“So, we are still needed. You still need us.”</i> (Interview with FB1)
10.9.	Reduction of ethical risks thanks to human involvement	Interviewees express the belief that human oversight can help reduce ethical risks associated with AI implementation	<i>“It is no issue as long as we have people that are able to edit these texts”</i> (Interview with FI1)
10.10.	Perception of AI-related ethical crisis as unlikely	Interviewees express the belief that ethical crisis related to AI implementation in communication is improbable	<i>“I don’t think we’ve had any AI related crises. The thing is, it only comes to me if it’s, you know, goes beyond borders”</i> (Interview with FB2)
10.11.	AI friendliness in communication sector	Interviewees describe the communication field as open and curious towards AI	<i>“I think communications is very open to new tools in general, so we were very open”</i> (Interview with E1)
10.12.	Failed internal AI use cases	Interviewees share example of failed AI implementation	<i>“It was very fun to see what is possible with image generation, but then we also noticed how much work it will be used afterwards”</i> (Interview with E1)
10.13.	Successful internal AI use cases	Interviewees share example of successful AI implementation	<i>“So, we made it a bit of a fun situation and also to make people aware”</i> (Interview with HR2)

Appendix R: [Summaries with coded segments]

Code	Coded segments	Summary
Perceptions on provided AI ethics' definition	<p>HR2: No. Sounds about right, yeah.</p> <p>Transcript_HR2: 6 - 6 (0)</p>	
	<p>t makes sense. It's like, well, I think it should be the same definition in all areas and environment.</p> <p>Transcript_HR1: 8 - 8 (0)</p>	
	<p>P2: Yeah, that's for sure a good way, a good definition for the interview. It's just for the intro, right? It's not that you're asking for any additional content to it, OK?</p> <p>Transcript_P2: 15 - 15 (0)</p>	
	<p>P1: No, that's OK, that's perfect. Perfectly fine for me.</p>	

Transcript_P1: 6 - 6 (0)

FB2: That's fine, it's fine. It's pretty standard.

Transcript_FB2: 10 - 10 (0)

FB1: Sounds good to me for now.

Transcript_FB1: 8 - 8 (0)

FI2: Nein, das kann ich unterschreiben. So also bei uns natürlich branchenbezogen sehr wichtig noch medizinische Faktoren, die hier natürlich auch noch reinspielt.

Transcript_FI2: 4 - 4 (0)

FI1: Mm hm. No. So yeah, it works for me.

Transcript_FI1: 4 - 4 (0)

E2: I think it's a good, very good definition, very complex and therefore, yeah, I think a lot of aspects are already touched. Mm hmm.

Transcript_E2: 5 - 5 (0)

No, absolutely.

Transcript_E1: 6 - 6 (0)

Perceptions on provided AI ethics' definition > Positive views

HR2: No. Sounds about right, yeah.

Transcript_HR2: 6 - 6 (0)

HR1: It makes sense. It's like, well, I think it should be the same definition in all areas and environment. If it's communication company or yeah, whatever.

Transcript_HR1: 8 - 8 (0)

hat's for sure a good way, a good definition for the interview.

Transcript_P2: 15 - 15 (0)

OK, that's perfect. Perfectly fine for me.

Transcript_P1: 6 - 6 (0)

FB2: That's fine, it's fine. It's pretty standard.

Transcript_FB2: 10 - 10 (0)

FB1: Sounds good to me for now.

Transcript_FB1: 8 - 8 (0)

F11: Mm hm. No. So yeah, it works for me.

Transcript_F11: 4 - 4 (0)

E2: I think it's a good, very good definition, very complex and therefore, yeah, I think a lot of aspects are already touched. Mm hmm.

Transcript_E2: 5 - 5 (0)

No, absolutely.

Transcript_E1: 6 - 6 (0)

Perceptions on provided AI ethics' definition > Further elements needed

Nein, das kann ich unterschreiben. So also bei uns natürlich branchenbezogen sehr wichtig noch medizinische Faktoren, die hier natürlich auch noch reinspielt.

Transcript_FI2: 4 - 4 (0)

Frequency of AI implementation

HR2: I would say daily.

Transcript_HR2: 12 - 12 (0)

HR1: Mm hmm. OK, so it depends on what is AI, right? If you start with DeepL or ChatGPT or Perplexity, all these tools, but also, we have tools in our CRM, in Salesforce, that help us write better job ads, and we have different Utools for our sales team to help them also improve communication and writing. So, mostly is really generative AI, so, written. So, this is used like daily from I would say most in the company, in communication also daily because we are responsible for whole Switzerland. So, we are communicating more than 4 languages. So, it's like also English right and we use those tools regularly. DeepL very, very often for example.

Transcript_HR1: 16 - 16 (0)

P2: If you ask myself personally, I use it often within texts, documents or writing, but not that Copilot writes me the texts. It's more that I have a text, and I let it correct.

Transcript_P2: 29 - 29 (0)

P1: Yep. Yes, I think this will be a very short interview. Because we are not using AI in a very significant way, and I would like to explain and to deepen this.

Transcript_P1: 22 - 22 (0)

FB2: No, I would. I would. I would say it's three times a day.

Transcript_FB2: 42 - 42 (0)

FB1: Mm hmm. So, I would say everybody in the agency works on a daily basis with DeepL and ChatGPT. We work in three, sometimes four languages. Not everyone is fluent in every language, so, to control ourselves...we do work very strongly with those. So, you know, we need to, as an agency, we need to provide perfect language, no typos, no grammar problems. So yeah.

Transcript_FB1: 28 - 28 (0)

F12: Das ist sehr unterschiedlich in unserem Team, es gibt Leute, die nutzen das so gut wie gar nicht und es gibt Leute, die das nutzen mehrmals täglich, also das ist... ich habe festgestellt, dass das sehr generationenabhängig ist.

Transcript_F12: 18 - 18 (0)

F12: Ich persönlich, ich würde jetzt mal sagen... mehrmals wöchentlich, aber nicht täglich.

Transcript_F12: 22 - 22 (0)

F11: Well, I would say today it's on a daily base, but we need to differ on... on one hand we have a really open tool, like we currently have Copilot. This is some kind of ChatGPT adoption which is secure, which is currently based on GPT 4.0 model, and is provided

by Microsoft with all this data protection possibilities, which enables us to use more than just public data. And I'd say I know of my colleagues at the communication department, that they often use it as a hint giver or to start with something, or to challenge some texts. And so... therefore this approach... and we enable that also with an intense program at [*COMPANY'S NAME*] and, and I'd say, and I know from these colleagues, that they often use it.

Transcript_FI1: 12 - 12 (0)

E2: -Not a lot. Also, sometimes I still stick to creating my own texts because in... yeah, how can I say? In formulating all the things I would like ChatGPT to create, I am sometimes quicker in just writing it down myself.

Transcript_E2: 19 - 19 (0)

E2: Yeah. Yeah, I think I am one of the of the people who are less using it for the moment. I see more and more people having ChatGPT open.

Transcript_E2: 21 - 21 (0)

E1: How often... very often I think, personally I think I use it every hour at least, like two or three times.

Transcript_E1: 14 - 14 (0)

know that some of my older colleagues use it a little bit less, but just because they're not that used to it yet

Transcript_E1: 16 - 16 (0)

Frequency of AI implementation >
Rarely

we are not using AI in a very significant way

Transcript_P1: 22 - 22 (0)

Not a lot.

Trancript_E2: 19 - 19 (0)

Frequency of AI implementation >
Often

If you ask myself personally, I use
it often

Transcript_P2: 29 - 29 (0)

Frequency of AI implementation >
Multiple times a week

mehrmals wöchentlich

Transcript_FI2: 22 - 22 (0)

Frequency of AI implementation >
Everyday

HR2: I would say daily.

Transcript_HR2: 12 - 12 (0)

this is used like daily from I would
say most in the company, in com-
munication also daily

Transcript_HR1: 16 - 16 (0)

I would say everybody in the agency works on a daily basis with DeepL and ChatGPT

Transcript_FB1: 28 - 28 (0)

today it's on a daily base

Transcript_FI1: 12 - 12 (0)

Frequency of AI implementation >
Multiple times a day

FB2: No, I would. I would. I would say it's three times a day.

Transcript_FB2: 42 - 42 (0)

I think I use it every hour at least, like two or three times

Transcript_E1: 14 - 14 (0)

Frequency of AI implementation >
Varied use within team members

FI2: Das ist sehr unterschiedlich in unserem Team, es gibt Leute, die nutzen das so gut wie gar nicht und es gibt Leute, die das nutzen mehrmals täglich, also

das ist... ich habe festgestellt, dass das sehr generationenabhängig ist.

Transcript_FI2: 18 - 18 (0)

E2: Yeah. Yeah, I think I am one of the of the people who are less using it for the moment. I see more and more people having ChatGPT open.

Trancript_E2: 21 - 21 (0)

know that some of my older colleagues use it a little bit less, but just because they're not that used to it yet

Transcript_E1: 16 - 16 (0)

AI tools implemented

HR2: And so, we use ChatGPT of course on more not so data secure topics and then we developed our own AI. So, the [COMPANY'S NAME AI] now actually, since working with Google, Google Chrome that we just today

actually got the implementation of Gemini. So, we are testing that now and we really have to say ChatGPT is the most intuitive and the fastest for us.

Transcript_HR2: 18 - 18 (0)

HR1: Mm hmm. OK, so it depends on what is AI, right? If you start with DeepL or ChatGPT or Perplexity, all these tools, but also, we have tools in our CRM, in Salesforce, that help us write better job ads, and we have different Utools for our sales team to help them also improve communication and writing. So, mostly is really generative AI, so, written. So, this is used like daily from I would say most in the company, in communication also daily because we are responsible for whole Switzerland. So, we are communicating more than 4 languages. So, it's like also English right and we use those tools regularly. DeepL very, very often for example.

Transcript_HR1: 16 - 16 (0)

HR1: Exactly. But we also have some other tools like an AI

toolbox for ourselves that are just like links, separate links not included in our ... or not yet integrated in our Salesforce because it was just written, because every country has a different IT landscape and it's not that easy to build in everything that fast. So that's why -

Transcript_HR1: 20 - 20 (0)

HR1: Well, on the first-hand side, everybody already used those tools, so we had to kind of make it officially. So, we really made sure that we officially can use ChatGPT and did also trainings on the other hand side, we're also doing pilots with Copilot for Microsoft to include it in our daily work. But at the moment it's just a selected audience that has it and not yet all because we really want to make sure we have -

Transcript_HR1: 24 - 24 (0)

P2: Yeah, we have implemented Copilot. So, I have been using it since... bit more than half a year now. As it is still pretty new tool

but also implemented by our IT department, so we can use both sides, so topics within the company...so, there is Copilot for within the company, but also for outside of the company, with the research... and we are testing that also in our department, yeah, to find out how we can use it best for us.

Transcript_P2: 27 - 27 (0)

-Of Adobe and also within Adobe you have certain functions that help them to be faster. For example, in post-production

Transcript_P2: 41 - 41 (0)

P1: Yep. Let's say translation. And really, so we are active from Spain to China, from Sweden to Australia and now also going to the US so we have more than 20 very, very different languages.

We have... as a corporate tool, we have selected DeepL.

Transcript_P1: 38 - 38 (0)

P1: And I have to say, I'm super content with the features and quality. And for the purpose, for other purposes. So, this is now ongoing to have here a proper solution. So, this is an ongoing task. I would say everybody's using... it for the time being, which is definitely not satisfying, a different tool on a very individual base, I would say most probably use ChatGPT.

Transcript_P1: 40 - 40 (0)

P1: But we are now putting this on a solid foundation, and this is a task ongoing, this is a work stream. So, we will define, we will establish, and we will implement, and this is now, these days. I just

got a notification that we will reach... and it will roll out rather soon in the next couple of days, a proper... let's say company-based, company-specific AI tool-

Transcript_P1: 42 - 42 (0)

P1: -Left and right to our company. So, what's going on in our space? Most of our peers are as well equity listed, that means a lot of information is available, there's a lot of content generated around the globe, and of course we try to generate some benefit of this information and to extract value added to shape our equity story, to address certain topics to be... maybe to be ready also in the context of Q&A So, what are the hot topics? What is the elephant in the room? What could be what we have to address actively? What do we have to prepare proactively? And maybe for this we also... we are going to work with another tool. Maybe I should

mention it. And this is really very much focused on capital market. This is called Alphasense, this is pure AI using... that it's highly unstructured. But I think quite powerful, yeah.

Transcript_P1: 48 - 48 (0)

FB2: -Contracts, recipes, whatever, whatever it may be, those are confidential, and we don't want to share them. So, this is where you get a little bit of a dilemma whereby you want your people, you want your staff to use AI because it's a great tool, or great tools I should say. But you also are a little bit... you know, you need to be able to care for. So, we use Microsoft Copilot as our tool and when using it of course we keep it within our own Microsoft encrypted environment.

Transcript_FB2: 30 - 30 (0)

FB2: So, so that's our provider. Does that mean that people don't use external AI? But of course, they do. And we do have our list of do's and don'ts on what you should use, what you should and shouldn't share with them with the external world, and the thing is if you if you can't speak to your friend's neighbour about It, well don't then use it on that. Oh, I'm sorry on AI. Personally, I'm a little bit older so it takes me a little bit more time maybe to pick up. I'm also extremely busy and this is why.

Transcript_FB2: 32 - 32 (0)

FB1: Mm hmm. So, I would say everybody in the agency works on a daily basis with DeepL and ChatGPT. We work in three, sometimes four languages. Not everyone is fluent in every language, so, to control ourselves...we do work very strongly with those. So, you know, we need to, as an agency, we need to provide perfect language, no

typos, no grammar problems. So yeah

Transcript_FB1: 28 - 28 (0)

FB1: We don't work well together, but I've seen others like my bosses, they sometimes use Copilot. Yeah. And also, we have a license. We have a license for ChatGPT. Like we buy the license to have to use it more profoundly so-

Transcript_FB1: 34 - 34 (0)

FB1: And not no... I just want to say another platform we use very much...

PM: Yes, no, you can go on. No problem.

FB1: Is Airtable.

Transcript_FB1: 42 - 44 (0)

FB1: So. It has; it has... But also there, I've had really bad experiences that I was like... reading...

because . I put an audio in the...
we use TransTurbo [*probably
meaning: TurboScribe*] I think it's
called-

Transcript_FB1: 100 - 100 (0)

FI2: Da haben wir ein eigenes
Tool aus Datenschutzgründen.

Transcript_FI2: 26 - 26 (0)

FI2: Ja, also, es gibt Kolleginnen
und Kollegen im Team, die ver-
wenden diese Tools auch für
wirkliche, für Schreibaarbeiten,
dass sie beispielsweise einen län-
geren Text zu einem Thema
schreiben und dann die Kurzver-
sion für die für die einzelnen
Social-Media-Kanäle von
KI schreiben lassen, explizit mit
dem Prompt, so dass es für uns...
in unserem Tone of Voice kommt.
Wir haben auch ein Tool, das wird
aber vor allem vom Marketing,
teilweise aber auch von der Un-

ternehmenskommunikation genutzt. Das ist trainiert auf die Tone of Voice von [COMPANY'S NAME], wo wir Texte durchlaufen lassen können, beispielsweise für employer branding. Dass es immer im gleichen Tonfall daherkommt und nach [COMPANY'S NAME] klingt, da werden die Texte mit KI in die richtige Tone of Voice gebracht, auch das wird kommt häufig zur Anwendung bei uns.

Transcript_FI2: 36 - 36 (0)

FI1: Well, I would say today it's on a daily base, but we need to differ on... on one hand we have a really open tool, like we currently have Copilot. This is some kind of ChatGPT adoption which is secure, which is currently based on GPT 4.0 model, and is provided by Microsoft with all this data protection possibilities, which enables us to use more than just public data. And I'd say I know of my

colleagues at the communication department, that they often use it as a hint giver or to start with something, or to challenge some texts. And so... therefore this approach... and we enable that also with an intense program at [*COMPANY'S NAME*] and, and I'd say, and I know from these colleagues, that they often use it.

Transcript_F11: 12 - 12 (0)

F11: We primarily for the flexible usage, we use Copilot. We know that some people use, on their private computers, they use other tools, but from the official side at our company it is Copilot, for the for the chat functionality versus an LLM feature. We certainly also have quite a journey behind us in identifying concrete use cases where you need a more strict implementation, and where you also use cloud resources. We currently work primarily with Azure,

and there we have an AI foundation developed which can be used to implement specific use cases. Or we work together with some partners that provide us with concrete implementations, for example, one use case in communication is to shorten a press text. Often you need to provide different newspapers with more shorter information than we edited, and therefore we have developed a hardened prompt setting, or agents, which really shorten the text but still keep the tone of voice of [COMPANY'S NAME] and the way we communicate the essential information we want to provide in this text and therefore we have developed like a more strict workflow in use cases like this.

Transcript_F11: 14 - 14 (0)

E2: -Not a lot. Also, sometimes I still stick to creating my own texts because in... yeah, how can I say? In formulating all the things I

would like ChatGPT to create, I am sometimes quicker in just writing it down myself.

Transcript_E2: 19 - 19 (0)

E2: Yes, it's ChatGPT. And me personally not, but I learned that they're also using Perplexity.

Transcript_E2: 27 - 27 (0)

E2: You're welcome. There's another one. We are also using Copilot in Microsoft Edge.

Transcript_E2: 33 - 33 (0)

E2: I'm just using ChatGPT for the moment I started using also...there is a possibility... we are using for example for images and video, stock images and

stock videos. We're using Shutterstock and in Shutterstock there is the possibility-

Transcript_E2: 35 - 35 (0)

E1: So, we use OK, it starts with CopyAI, Synthesia.IO, then obviously Copilot, so Microsoft 365 Copilots, Copilot studio. AI attack which is Azure OpenAI basically. InferenceCloud and *[COMPANY'S NAME]* GPT, and *[COMPANY'S NAME]* GPT is an internal tool we developed that combines-

Transcript_E1: 20 - 20 (0)

E1: - All the different... yeah, all the different models we kind of know, I think we also have like DeepSeek on there... ChatGPT and we basically get to use all the models as well, yeah.

Transcript_E1: 22 - 22 (0)

AI tools implemented > Varied
use within team members

different tool on a very individual
base, I w

Transcript_P1: 40 - 40 (0)

Does that mean that people don't
use external AI? But of course,
they do.

Transcript_FB2: 32 - 32 (0)

We know that some people use,
on their private computers, they
use other tools,

Transcript_FI1: 14 - 14 (0)

AI tools implemented > Adobe AI

-Of Adobe and also within Adobe
you have certain functions that
help them to be faster. For exam-
ple, in post-production

Transcript_P2: 41 - 41 (0)

AI tools implemented > Gemini

e just today actually got the implementation of Gemini

Transcript_HR2: 18 - 18 (0)

AI tools implemented > Shutterstock

We're using Shutterstock

Trancript_E2: 35 - 35 (0)

AI tools implemented > Perplexity

Perplexity

Transcript_HR1: 16 - 16 (0)

Perplexity

Trancript_E2: 27 - 27 (0)

AI tools implemented > TurboScribe

I put an audio in the... we use TransTurbo [*probably meaning: TurboScribe*]

Transcript_FB1: 100 - 100 (0)

AI tools implemented > Airtable**FB1: Is Airtable.**

Transcript_FB1: 44 - 44 (0)

AI tools implemented > DeepL

DeepL

Transcript_HR1: 16 - 16 (0)

DeepL

Transcript_HR1: 16 - 16 (0)

DeepL.

Transcript_P1: 38 - 38 (0)

DeepL

Transcript_FB1: 28 - 28 (0)

**AI tools implemented > Partners'
AI softwares**

Or we work together with some partners that provide us with concrete implementations

Transcript_FI1: 14 - 14 (0)

AI tools implemented > Azure
OpenAI

We currently work primarily with
Azure

Transcript_FI1: 14 - 14 (0)

Azure OpenAI

Transcript_E1: 20 - 20 (0)

AI tools implemented >
DeepSeek

DeepSeek

Transcript_E1: 22 - 22 (0)

AI tools implemented > Infer-
enceCloud

InferenceCloud

Transcript_E1: 20 - 20 (0)

AI tools implemented > Synthe-
sia.IO

Synthesia.IO

Transcript_E1: 20 - 20 (0)

AI tools implemented > CopyAI

CopyAI,

Transcript_E1: 20 - 20 (0)

AI tools implemented > Internal
GPT/ internal tools

our own AI. So, the *[COMPANY'S
NAME AI]*

Transcript_HR2: 18 - 18 (0)

like an AI toolbox for ourselves
that are just like links, separate
links not included in our ... or not
yet integrated in our Salesforce

Transcript_HR1: 20 - 20 (0)

let's say company-based, com-
pany-specific AI tool-

Transcript_P1: 42 - 42 (0)

FI2: Da haben wir ein eigenes
Tool aus Datenschutzgründen.

Transcript_FI2: 26 - 26 (0)

Wir haben auch ein Tool, das wird aber vor allem vom Marketing, teilweise aber auch von der Unternehmenskommunikation genutzt. Das ist trainiert auf die Tone of Voice von [COMPANY'S NAME],

Transcript_FI2: 36 - 36 (0)

[COMPANY'S NAME] GPT

Transcript_E1: 20 - 20 (0)

AI tools implemented > ChatGPT

we use ChatGPT of course on more not so data secure topics

Transcript_HR2: 18 - 18 (0)

ChatGPT

Transcript_HR1: 16 - 16 (0)

I would say most probably use
ChatGPT

Transcript_P1: 40 - 40 (0)

ChatGPT.

Transcript_FB1: 28 - 28 (0)

ChatGPT

Trancript_E2: 19 - 19 (0)

ChatGPT

Transcript_E1: 22 - 22 (0)

AI tools implemented > Copilot

we're also doing pilots with Copi-
lot for Microsoft to include it in our
daily work.

Transcript_HR1: 24 - 24 (0)

we have implemented Copilot.

Transcript_P2: 27 - 27 (0)

So, we use Microsoft Copilot as
our tool

Transcript_FB2: 30 - 30 (0)

Copilot.

Transcript_FB1: 34 - 34 (0)

Copilot

Transcript_FI1: 12 - 12 (0)

Copilot

Trancript_E2: 33 - 33 (0)

Copilot

Transcript_E1: 20 - 20 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented

HR2: For me and in communications a lot for translations. We use it a lot for that and then give it to a translation task force. We call it for people who really speak the language within the company to make it really perfect. And of course, for brainstorming, we use it for a lot of things and for research.

Transcript_HR2: 22 - 22 (0)

HR2: For example, SEO texts.

Transcript_HR2: 28 - 28 (0)

HR1: Mm hmm. OK, so it depends on what is AI, right? If you start with DeepL or ChatGPT or Perplexity, all these tools, but also, we have tools in our CRM, in Salesforce, that help us write better job ads, and we have different tools for our sales team to help them also improve communication and writing. So, mostly is really generative AI, so, written. So, this is used like daily from I would say most in the company, in communication also daily because we

are responsible for whole Switzerland. So, we are communicating more than 4 languages. So, it's like also English right and we use those tools regularly. DeepL very, very often for example.

Transcript_HR1: 16 - 16 (0)

HR1: - We also have like tools apart to integrate, you know, to help you with the distribution correctly in the countries.

Transcript_HR1: 22 - 22 (0)

HR1: Well, let's say for example, we have a speech for someone, and I formulated it, or somebody formulated it in a in a text, right? And then I'm saying "oh, wow. This is not really nice, not really practical for the speaker, so let's make bullets out of it." So, I put it into Copilot for example, and ask "hey, please rewrite this speech, but in bullet points." And then it's very fast. It's done and it would take me like half an hour or 15 minutes to do it myself and like that, it's done. Let's say I still need like these 10 minutes because I

have to review it. The thing is, if I don't review it, I think I really need to be transparent and tell "OK this is the original text and this is the DeepL translation, or this is the DeepL or ChatGPT or Copilot short version". Like, I think it's important to say, "OK I can translate, I don't have time, but I can send you the AI generated version so please check it". Yeah.

Transcript_HR1: 36 - 36 (0)

HR1: - Pictures with the AI that, but officially, you know, transparently announced it. But also I have... we have employees that have like privately this ChatGPT 4 or other image AI tools and generate pictures for their social media posts with AI that they use for you know advertising jobs, and you know it's always difficult there is no real reason to say why it's not OK because it's sometimes really fun right? I think it's for example they put it in a, let's say it's a brand from Schaffhausen and they put it like with the Rhine in the background, with the Munot, you know some local recognizable assets and then at the it's a marketing job. Then you see some marketing formula or things

like that. So, it's cool, why not? But then you see some details that are completely wrong and then you need... then I tell "OK, maybe just make sure that here there is a mistake that this is not because this AI generation doesn't always, alright, hit all the spots. So, you have to be attentive. But I think it's fun. But I always tell, "OK, if you do this, please write <It has been AI generated> and also include the tool you have been generated. This was so it has been included. It has been done with ChatGPT4 or something like that.

Transcript_HR1: 54 - 54 (0)

P2: If you ask myself personally, I use it often within texts, documents or writing, but not that Copilot writes me the texts. It's more that I have a text, and I let it correct.

PM: Yes.

P2: Or I'll let it I ask if, if Copilot can make it better or has something to add. And of course, I think

almost everyone in the team also uses it for inspiration. So, for research. And. We also use AI for translation, so there is, I mean we are using Microsoft, so also... Viva Engage for example... there is the automatic translation. I think this is AI based as well and we have a translation provider called *[COMPANY'S NAME, unrelated to the interviewee's company]* This is a company that is well known.

Transcript_P2: 29 - 31 (0)

P1: Yeah, maybe I have to be more precise, OK. I think there might be one area where we are in fact using artificial intelligence, let's say the indirect way. And this is using translation tools. So, if you use directly translation tools or even if you go to an agency, a translation agency, each agency is now using tools.

Transcript_P1: 32 - 32 (0)

P1: And probably they are AI based. So, we are a company... in our corporate communication, we are still bilingual. Our leading language is still German, but of course our international reach, our reach out is English. So, we still have to cover any major external communication post languages at minimum. And then of course we have... we are active in more than 25 countries. That means we are... we have to cover more than 20 different languages. So, we have a huge workload of translation, as a very basic LinkedIn or any social media post of course has to be translated in 20 different languages, and always we have to be super safe to do it the correct way because a small change in content and meaning can... could be very harmful for us. And in internal communication I would put it that way. So, next to text, I would say translation task or maybe text improvement tools. We use it for,

let's say basic content generation. And so, it gives you... or give ourselves maybe some impulse or some starting point to start from, but then of course we elaborate, we improve, we continue the very traditional way, and then you may assume also in a very complex system.

Transcript_P1: 34 - 34 (0)

P1: I would say... so, everything that is highly relevant to our products and the safety of our products and the safety of our users... so, we should not rely on AI based content or information. Outside of this or next to this, I think especially in the field of capital market communication, so we could. So, we are using it. As I said, to make some high-level analysis to generate also, to analyze maybe a sentiment, so what's going out? What's going

on in our industry? What is happening? -

PM: Yeah.

P1: -Left and right to our company. So, what's going on in our space? Most of our peers are as well equity listed, that means a lot of information is available, there's a lot of content generated around the globe, and of course we try to generate some benefit of this information and to extract value added to shape our equity story, to address certain topics to be... maybe to be ready also in the context of Q&A So, what are the hot topics? What is the elephant in the room? What could be what we have to address actively? What do we have to prepare proactively? And maybe for this we also... we are going to work with another tool. Maybe I should mention it. And this is really very much focused on capital market. This is called Alphasense, this is

pure AI using... that it's highly unstructured. But I think quite powerful, yeah

Transcript_P1: 46 - 48 (0)

FB2: It is one of the most difficult things to have... and we have corporate visuals. We buy a lot of visuals as well, but sometimes you need a really, really specific thing.

PM: Yes. And then you can use the AI generated images and videos. For example, you can generate, yeah...

FB2: Exactly, exactly. And in fact, we organized a webinar for our colleagues. I was running the webinar at the back, so I didn't really follow much, but one thing was really simple. We... the guy who was running it, the colleague I spoke to, basically he showed on the webinar how to create a video and he said, you know, take I want a photo of a... it was a flower in the middle of the road

with it. And then he did created it to be nice, to be nicer, nicer. And than a bee had to land on the flower, because bees are very important for us. We use fruits and vegetables. No bees, no fruits and vegetables. So, you know that sort of thing. And then he came up with this really great image which is, which is fantastic.

Transcript_FB2: 48 - 50 (0)

FB2: For me, it's what you mentioned. Really. It's tech. I didn't use it directly for proofing, but we just have as I mentioned earlier, we just had our annual report out and the colleague who I was working with on the annual report, I did send his text through AI to prove it.

Transcript_FB2: 52 - 52 (0)

FB2: Absolutely, it's still at the beginning. So, for example, I have the webinar to tell "Listen", you know for a start, before that even where the things say, "Listen we know about AI, this is what you can and can't do". Then there's a webinar saying, "OK, look, this is how it works", and we will have more webinars as we as we go along again it's purely a matter of time. I'm using my notes and... fine enough... one of the one of the greatest things of AI for example is, and you'll probably do it after the meeting is...you can have a summary of what the meeting is all about. So, when you go and do your you when you do your writing. It's very simple. You have a nice, lovely summary. I didn't have that when I did my master's not very long ago actually, but just ten years ago. But it would have helped a lot to be able to actually press a button, which is what I did with the meeting I had. And I have a whole list of meeting roles-

Transcript_FB2: 138 - 138 (0)

FB2: And then see what it spits out. Essentially what is AI going to give me? And then I can get that and use that as a base, as a very good base by the way, to create things because for a person like me who's a one-man team... you have to take all the help you can get and having tools like that would be super helpful so. Yes, position papers. Manuals. Articles. Visuals. All these elements absolutely.

Transcript_FB2: 168 - 168 (0)

FB1: Mm hmm. So, I would say everybody in the agency works on a daily basis with DeepL and ChatGPT. We work in three, sometimes four languages. Not everyone is fluent in every language, so, to control ourselves...we do work very strongly with those. So, you know, we need to, as an agency, we need to provide perfect language, no

typos, no grammar problems. So yeah.

Transcript_FB1: 28 - 28 (0)

FB1: - Files so on Airtable, we've built a database for media planning. And also media monitoring. We use it actually almost now for everyone and it's. Yeah, we're very happy with that. We've created our own basis.

Transcript_FB1: 48 - 48 (0)

FB1: Well, I would say. When I have a task that we need to work on a strategy or a new concept for some PR. Let's say there is an anniversary from a company. Yeah. And we always do brainstorming in the team first and then one is in charge to work out the process. Like a first draft and we do also brainstorm with ChatGPT.

Transcript_FB1: 50 - 50 (0)

FB1: -If you work with short term, if you give him 100 pages and say

analyze, then he will not do it well. But short things with a good prompt that that works. I... depending on what kind of social media, I also use it for social media. I have my written prompts. Don't tell our clients. Sometimes the output is really good. Sometimes not and I have to rewrite so yeah, I and you cannot try. You always need to control. It's like a small child. You always need to control because you never know.

Transcript_FB1: 60 - 60 (0)

FB1: My experience... I would say in our company is knowledge on the AI, how to use AI, are those people who use it more. I hadn't finished...we also use it a lot too... for example, to transcribe. Maybe you're gonna use it as well.

Transcript_FB1: 98 - 98 (0)

FB1: -And then I use ChatGPT and tell him "Write me a protocol". And then I read the protocols and I'm like "That's not how it

went down. And something is missing". So, at the end I still need to listen in, but generally, yeah, it works 70/30%.

Transcript_FB1: 102 - 102 (0)

FI2: Was ganz klar am häufigsten angewendet wird, sind Übersetzungstools.

Transcript_FI2: 24 - 24 (0)

FI2: Manchmal auch, um sich schnell eine Übersicht über ein Thema, das man noch nicht so gut kennt, zu verfassen, so die wichtigsten Quellen wichtigsten ja... welche Punkte dreht sich eine Debatte. Oder um längere komplexe Themen zusammenzufassen, wenn man nicht 150-seitiges Dokument lesen möchte.

Transcript_FI2: 34 - 34 (0)

F12: Ja, also, es gibt Kolleginnen und Kollegen im Team, die verwenden diese Tools auch für wirkliche, für Schreibaarbeiten, dass sie beispielsweise einen längeren Text zu einem Thema schreiben und dann die Kurzversion für die für die einzelnen Social-Media-Kanäle von KI schreiben lassen, explizit mit dem Prompt, so dass es für uns... in unserem Tone of Voice kommt. Wir haben auch ein Tool, das wird aber vor allem vom Marketing, teilweise aber auch von der Unternehmenskommunikation genutzt. Das ist trainiert auf die Tone of Voice von [COMPANY'S NAME], wo wir Texte durchlaufen lassen können, beispielsweise für employer branding. Dass es immer im gleichen Tonfall daherkommt und nach [COMPANY'S NAME] klingt, da werden die Texte mit KI in die richtige Tone of Voice gebracht, auch das wird kommt häufig zur Anwendung bei uns.

Transcript_FI2: 36 - 36 (0)

FI2: -Wo man traditionell auf Stockbilder zurückgegriffen hat, um das zu illustrieren, und da wird teilweise mit KI gearbeitet, um etwas Passendes zu generieren. Videos bis jetzt noch gar nicht.

Transcript_FI2: 40 - 40 (0)

FI1: Well, I would say today it's on a daily base, but we need to differ on... on one hand we have a really open tool, like we currently have Copilot. This is some kind of ChatGPT adoption which is secure, which is currently based on GPT 4.0 model, and is provided by Microsoft with all this data protection possibilities, which enables us to use more than just public data. And I'd say I know of my colleagues at the communication department, that they often use it as a hint giver or to start with something, or to challenge some

texts. And so... therefore this approach... and we enable that also with an intense program at [*COMPANY'S NAME*] and, and I'd say, and I know from these colleagues, that they often use it.

Transcript_F11: 12 - 12 (0)

F11: We primarily for the flexible usage, we use Copilot. We know that some people use, on their private computers, they use other tools, but from the official side at our company it is Copilot, for the for the chat functionality versus an LLM feature. We certainly also have quite a journey behind us in identifying concrete use cases where you need a more strict implementation, and where you also use cloud resources. We currently work primarily with Azure, and there we have an AI foundation developed which can be used to implement specific use cases. Or we work together with some

partners that provide us with concrete implementations, for example, one use case in in communication is to shorten a press text. Often you need to provide different newspapers with more shorter information than we edited, and therefore we have developed a hardened prompt setting, or agents, which really shorten the text but still keep the tone of voice of [COMPANY'S NAME] and the way we communicate the essential information we want to provide in this text and therefore we have developed like a more strict workflow in in use cases like this.

Transcript_F11: 14 - 14 (0)

F11: Yeah, there is. There's quite some, I mean, what we did, we did make an intense business analysis where we collected all the use cases, primarily focusing on generative AI adoption. At our company currently this is a catalogue of around 450 use cases

which we know of, and some of them are worth to be implemented in the way that we say “Well this needs to be implemented”, the more reliable approach. But those are most are mostly not in the communications environment because in communications, well, I'd say with copilot itself you have quite a good tool set to use. And sure, with this example of shortening text, this is a good sample which helps us to communicate. I mean, on the other hand we have we have like... but this is more on the pilot phase, things to edit or to-

Transcript_F11: 22 - 22 (0)

F11: -To draft internal use for the Intranet, or maybe even for the Webpage, where we provide some tools and where we try to find out if this shortens the process to develop these kinds of text.

Transcript_F11: 24 - 24 (0)

F11: This is like a set of predeveloped prompts that we provide or that employees develop and share with us, and we share it with the whole company. So, where we say “Well, this is this is basically approved, it works this prompt”, but this is more in the usage and adoption of a tool like Copilot. For example, if someone has translation of text. We say, “Well, principally we have a standard approach where we currently are switching from a language model to element-based translation with a partner and still use the glossary feature”, for example. We also have a prompt but here using the glossary, which is in our case a set of...I mean we communicate in in three languages officially. And there we have a set of words or phrases that need to be translated in a proven manner and with open prompting. This is not so reliable,

so therefore we have there translation tool which is being switched because we've seen that the quality with LLM based translation is better than with the historic approaches we used. But yeah-

Transcript_F11: 28 - 28 (0)

F11: There are issues but, but I think it's not ones that are more relevant because we are a financial institution and as I say it, it depends on the kind of text you do. I mean, what's the, what's the public and who is at adressant, and is there no biases in it, or...yeah, things like these questions need to be posed. I mean, there's just something, but it's just this is more... Well, it might be addressed in the ethical part. We say to our employees "If you don't redigate [meaning: *edit*] the text mostly, if you don't change a lot of things we expect you to put in a remark saying this has been created with the help of AI. This is

this is mainly relevant in sense of using images, I mean this is not in the field of communication primarily, but yeah if we would use... but we don't... we for example clearly decided not to use AI generated pictures of humans because we we're a company saying we want to be close to the people. So, we want to show real people but we for example use AI to generate ideas-

Transcript_F11: 40 - 40 (0)

E2: I would say... I use it, for the moment, just for my LinkedIn content creation. For example, I have to create a post, and the business gives me input regarding a new product we are launching, and I get some bullet points or some information or a brochure and out of this I try to create appealing content post for LinkedIn or yeah and therefore I use LinkedIn [meaning: AI] as my counter partner, I insert all the information I have

and wait for some inspiration. But I would say-

Transcript_E2: 17 - 17 (0)

E2: And I think also for all the slides and content creation. We do a lot of, I don't know, leaflets, brochures and before we were, we outsourced this completely with our agency. But now the more and more we have to cut costs. So, we are doing this internally.

Transcript_E2: 23 - 23 (0)

E2: I'm just using ChatGPT for the moment I started using also...there is a possibility... we are using for example for images and video, stock images and stock videos. We're using Shutterstock and in Shutterstock there is the possibility-

Trascript_E2: 35 - 35 (0)

2: Yeah. Yes. Correct, because [COMPANY'S NAME] or the division where I'm sitting is [NAME OF THE COMPANY'S DIVISION]. It's one of three divisions, and my division is mainly creating, producing applications and products for end-customers which then, for example, produce pharmaceutical products or they do plastic and so we provide them the machines. So, each you can imagine each customer has a different scenario. So, all the products we create are really, really-

PM: Yeah.

E2: -Specific for these customers, so they don't want to have competitors know what they are doing because of course they want to be competitive and that's why it's always an issue. I think it's the biggest challenge we are facing in marketing communication in this

kind of area. You want to share, but you cannot share. So, we have a big success project and we want to share it with the world and show “look what we can do”.

Transcript_E2: 47 - 49 (0)

E2: -Yeah, long meetings. And you, you have also for idea creation or like brainstorming. It's amazing or there are even people... they're recording with ChatGPT. I never did it, but it's possible. I heard they're recording a meeting and then they entered the prompt “Please, what are... What do you think are the points? Are there more pros or more cons?”

Transcript_E2: 61 - 61 (0)

E2: Or are people more into it or not based on the recording, so they kind of resume or yeah...

Compile the OR do like meeting notes as well... yeah...

Transcript_E2: 63 - 63 (0)

E1: Yep. Yep, absolutely. So, I think the one I use the most is [COMPANY'S NAME] GPT. In this case, I mostly use ChatGPT 4.0 at the moment, and I think that's mostly for rewriting my emails. Writing copy for social media. Giving me ideas for slides and presentations. New ideas for or just like creative idea generation, which most of the time it's not that great at because it's not creative in a sense, but it will just give me a little bit of help if I have some kind of blockage in my brain. So, I think that's the one I used the most. Yeah.

Transcript_E1: 24 - 24 (0)

E1: Yes, I think mostly to write copy. So, if it's for a newsletter or

for a booklet that we publish for our customers or copy for social media, I think we use it a lot, especially if we already have some type of idea on what we want to write. It's good at summarizing certain content and like, really, yeah, helping us there to combine everything, yeah.

Transcript_E1: 26 - 26 (0)

E1: Yeah. Yeah, we don't at the moment, we have an internal policy that we don't, I think, and this maybe comes into like the ethical perspective of a lot because it is using pictures that are not our own. But we are working on a tool that will be doing it. So, we will be able to do image generation with [COMPANY'S NAME] internal pictures. So, it is in progress. We don't know when it's going to start, but we have seen some results, and it looks fantastic. So, if

that's going to work soon, I'm very excited, yeah.

Transcript_E1: 28 - 28 (0)

E1: Summarizing, yeah, maybe. I mean, is that copywriting again, like creating speeches, like presentations like bullet points, I think that is another big thing.

Transcript_E1: 104 - 104 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Strategic work

HR1: - We also have like tools apart to integrate, you know, to help you with the distribution correctly in the countries.

Transcript_HR1: 22 - 22 (0)

So, we are using it. As I said, to make some high-level analysis to generate also, to analyze maybe a sentiment, so what's going out? What's going on in our industry? What is happening? -

PM: Yeah.

P1: -Left and right to our company. So, what's going on in our space? Most of our peers are as well equity listed, that means a lot of information is available, there's a lot of content generated around the globe, and of course we try to generate some benefit of this information and to extract value added to shape our equity story, to address certain topics to be... maybe to be ready also in the context of Q&A So, what are the hot topics? What is the elephant in the room? What could be what we have to address actively? What do we have to prepare proactively

Transcript_P1: 46 - 48 (0)

work on a strategy or a new concept for some PR.

Transcript_FB1: 50 - 50 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Strategic work > Distribution and adaptation in different countries

HR1: - We also have like tools apart to integrate, you know, to help you with the distribution correctly in the countries.

Transcript_HR1: 22 - 22 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Strategic work > PR concepts

a new concept for some PR

Transcript_FB1: 50 - 50 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Strategic work > Trend Monitoring

So, we are using it. As I said, to make some high-level analysis to generate also, to analyze maybe a sentiment, so what's going out? What's going on in our industry? What is happening? -

PM: Yeah.

P1: -Left and right to our company. So, what's going on in our space? Most of our peers are as well equity listed, that means a lot of information is available, there's a lot of content generated around the globe, and of course we try to

generate some benefit of this information and to extract value added to shape our equity story, to address certain topics to be... maybe to be ready also in the context of Q&A So, what are the hot topics? What is the elephant in the room? What could be what we have to address actively? What do we have to prepare proactively

Transcript_P1: 46 - 48 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Media relations

FB1: - Files so on Airtable, we've built a database for media planning. And also media monitoring. We use it actually almost now for everyone and it's. Yeah, we're very happy with that. We've created our own basis.

Transcript_FB1: 48 - 48 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Media relations > Media monitoring and media planning

we've built a database for media planning

Transcript_FB1: 48 - 48 (0)

And also media monitoring

Transcript_FB1: 48 - 48 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Language and text work

HR2: For me and in communications a lot for translations. We use it a lot for that and then give it to a translation task force. We call it for people who really speak the language within the company to make it really perfect. And of course, for brainstorming, we use it for a lot of things and for research.

Transcript_HR2: 22 - 22 (0)

HR2: For example, SEO texts.

Transcript_HR2: 28 - 28 (0)

d. So, we are communicating more than 4 languages. So, it's like also English right and we use those tools regularly. DeepL very, very often for example.

Transcript_HR1: 16 - 16 (0)

We also use AI for translation, so there is, I mean we are using Microsoft, so also... Viva Engage for example... there is the automatic translation. I think this is AI based as well and we have a translation provider called *[COMPANY'S NAME, unrelated to the interviewee's company]* This is a company that is well known.

Transcript_P2: 31 - 31 (0)

. And this is using translation tools

Transcript_P1: 32 - 32 (0)

We use it for, let's say basic content generation

Transcript_P1: 34 - 34 (0)

. I... depending on what kind of social media, I also use it for social media.

Transcript_FB1: 60 - 60 (0)

to transcribe.

Transcript_FB1: 98 - 98 (0)

FB1: -And then I use ChatGPT PT and tell him "Write me a protocol". And then I read the protocols and I'm like "That's not how it went down. And something is missing". So, at the end I still need to listen in, but generally, yeah, it works 70/30%.

Transcript_FB1: 102 - 102 (0)

FI2: Was ganz klar am häufigsten angewendet wird, sind Übersetzungstools.

Transcript_FI2: 24 - 24 (0)

s gibt Kolleginnen und Kollegen im Team, die verwenden diese Tools auch für wirkliche, für

Schreibarbeiten, dass sie beispielsweise einen längeren Text zu einem Thema schreiben und dann die Kurzversion für die für die einzelnen Social-Media-Kanäle

Transcript_FI2: 36 - 36 (0)

To draft internal use for the Intranet, or maybe even for the Webpage,

Transcript_FI1: 24 - 24 (0)

For example, if someone has translation of text. We say, "Well, principally we have a standard approach where we currently are switching from a language model to element-based translation with a partner and still use the glossary feature", for example. We also have a prompt but here using the glossary, which is in our case a set of...I mean we communicate in in three languages officially.

And there we have a set of words or phrases that need to be translated in a proven manner and with open prompting. This is not so reliable, so therefore we have there translation tool which is being switched because we've seen that the quality with LLM based translation is better than with the historic approaches we used. But yeah-

Transcript_F11: 28 - 28 (0)

slides

Trancript_E2: 23 - 23 (0)

E2: Or are people more into it or not based on the recording, so they kind of resume or yeah... Compile the OR do like meeting notes as well... yeah...

Trancript_E2: 63 - 63 (0)

like creating speeches, like presentations

Transcript_E1: 104 - 104 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Language and text work > Formal texts

HR2: For example, SEO texts.

Transcript_HR2: 28 - 28 (0)

to transcribe.

Transcript_FB1: 98 - 98 (0)

I use ChatGPT PT and tell him
"Write me a protocol"

Transcript_FB1: 102 - 102 (0)

slides

Trancript_E2: 23 - 23 (0)

like creating speeches, like presentations

Transcript_E1: 104 - 104 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Language and text work > Formal texts > Transcriptions
to transcribe.

Transcript_FB1: 98 - 98 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Language and text work > Formal texts > Protocols
I use ChatGPT PT and tell him
"Write me a protocol"

Transcript_FB1: 102 - 102 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Language and text work > Formal texts > Speeches
like creating speeches, like
presentations

Transcript_E1: 104 - 104 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Language and text work > Formal texts > Presentations
slides

Trancript_E2: 23 - 23 (0)

like creating speeches, like
presentations

Transcript_E1: 104 - 104 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented

> Language and text work >
Translation

a lot for translations. We use it a lot for that and then give it to a translation task force. We call it for people who really speak the language within the company to make it really perfect

Transcript_HR2: 22 - 22 (0)

d. So, we are communicating more than 4 languages. So, it's like also English right and we use those tools regularly. DeepL very, very often for example.

Transcript_HR1: 16 - 16 (0)

this is the DeepL translation

Transcript_HR1: 36 - 36 (0)

We also use AI for translation, so there is, I mean we are using Microsoft, so also... Viva Engage for example... there is the automatic translation. I think this is AI based as well and we have a translation provider called [COMPANY'S

NAME, unrelated to the interviewee's company] This is a company that is well known.

Transcript_P2: 31 - 31 (0)

. And this is using translation tools

Transcript_P1: 32 - 32 (0)

Not everyone is fluent in every language, so, to control ourselves...we do work very strongly with those

Transcript_FB1: 28 - 28 (0)

FI2: Was ganz klar am häufigsten angewendet wird, sind Übersetzungstools.

Transcript_FI2: 24 - 24 (0)

For example, if someone has translation of text. We say, "Well, principally we have a standard

approach where we currently are switching from a language model to element-based translation with a partner and still use the glossary feature”, for example. We also have a prompt but here using the glossary, which is in our case a set of...I mean we communicate in in three languages officially. And there we have a set of words or phrases that need to be translated in a proven manner and with open prompting. This is not so reliable, so therefore we have there translation tool which is being switched because we've seen that the quality with LLM based translation is better than with the historic approaches we used. But yeah-

Transcript_F11: 28 - 28 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented

> Language and text work > do like meeting notes as well
Notetaking

Trancript_E2: 63 - 63 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented

> Language and text work > Copywriting

. I... depending on what kind of social media, I also use it for social media.

Transcript_FB1: 60 - 60 (0)

Social-Media-Kanäle

Transcript_FI2: 36 - 36 (0)

Intranet, or maybe even for the Webpage

Transcript_FI1: 24 - 24 (0)

We do a lot of, I don't know, leaflets, brochures

Trancript_E2: 23 - 23 (0)

Writing copy for social media. Giving me ideas for slides and presentations. New ideas for or just like creative idea generation, which most of the time it's not that

great at because it's not creative in a sense, but it will just give me a little bit of help if I have some kind of blockage in my brain. So, I think that's the one I used the most. Yeah.

PM: So, you were telling me already a bit about the tasks. Are there generally speaking in your department tasks in which your tools are used more frequently? How do you mainly use AI?

E1: Yes, I think mostly to write copy. So, if it's for a newsletter or for a booklet that we publish for our customers

Transcript_E1: 24 - 26 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Language and text work > Copywriting > SEO Texts

HR2: For example, SEO texts.

Transcript_HR2: 28 - 28 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Language and text work > Copywriting > Social media copywriting

. I... depending on what kind of social media, I also use it for social media.

Transcript_FB1: 60 - 60 (0)

Social-Media-Kanäle

Transcript_FI2: 36 - 36 (0)

Writing copy for social media.

Transcript_E1: 24 - 24 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Language and text work > Copywriting > Booklets and brochures

We do a lot of, I don't know, leaflets, brochures

Transcript_E2: 23 - 23 (0)

or for a booklet

Transcript_E1: 26 - 26 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Language and text work > Copywriting > Intranet and Webpages

Intranet, or maybe even for the Webpage

Transcript_FI1: 24 - 24 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented

> Language and text work > Copywriting > Newsletter

Transcript_E1: 26 - 26 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented

> Text enhancement

that help us write better job ads

Transcript_HR1: 16 - 16 (0)

This is not really nice, not really practical for the speaker, so let's make bullets out of it." So, I put it into Copilot for example, and ask "hey, please rewrite this speech, but in bullet points." And then it's very fast. It's done and it would take me like half an hour or 15 minutes to do it myself and like that, it's done. Let's say I still need like these 10 minutes because I have to review it. The thing is, if I don't review it, I think I really need to be transparent and tell "OK this is the original text and this is the DeepL translation, or this is the DeepL or ChatGPT or Copilot short version". Like, I think it's important to say, "OK I can translate, I don't have time, but I can send you the AI generated version so please check it". Yeah.

Transcript_HR1: 36 - 36 (0)

P2: If you ask myself personally, I use it often within texts, documents or writing, but not that Copilot writes me the texts. It's more that I have a text, and I let it correct.

PM: Yes.

P2: Or I'll let it I ask if, if Copilot can make it better or has something to add.

Transcript_P2: 29 - 31 (0)

maybe text improvement tools.

Transcript_P1: 34 - 34 (0)

FB2: For me, it's what you mentioned. Really. It's tech. I didn't use it directly for proofing, but we just have as I mentioned earlier, we just had our annual report out and the colleague who I was

working with on the annual report, I did send his text through AI to prove it.

Transcript_FB2: 52 - 52 (0)

d you'll probably do it after the meeting is...you can have a summary of what the meeting is all about. So, when you go and do your you when you do your writing.It's very simple. You have a nice, lovely summary.

Transcript_FB2: 138 - 138 (0)

Oder um längere komplexe Themen zusammenzufassen, wenn man nicht 150-seitiges Dokument lesen möchte.

Transcript_FI2: 34 - 34 (0)

Ja, also, es gibt Kolleginnen und Kollegen im Team, die verwenden diese Tools auch für wirkliche, für Schreibarbeiten, dass sie beispielsweise einen längeren Text zu einem Thema schreiben und dann die Kurzversion für die für die einzelnen Social-Media-Kanäle von KI schreiben lassen

Transcript_FI2: 36 - 36 (0)

or to challenge some texts

Transcript_FI1: 12 - 12 (0)

for example, one use case in in communication is to shorten a press text. Often you need to provide different newspapers with more shorter information than we edited, and therefore we have developed a hardened prompt setting, or agents, which really shorten

Transcript_FI1: 14 - 14 (0)

ings to edit or to-

Transcript_FI1: 22 - 22 (0)

so they kind of resume or yeah

Trancript_E2: 63 - 63 (0)

for rewriting my emails

Transcript_E1: 24 - 24 (0)

It's good at summarizing certain content and like, really, yeah, helping us there to combine everything, yeah

Transcript_E1: 26 - 26 (0)

bullet points

Transcript_E1: 104 - 104 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Text enhancement > Text editing

I have to review it. The thing is, if I don't review it, I think I really need to be transparent and tell

Transcript_HR1: 36 - 36 (0)

have a text, and I let it correct.

Transcript_P2: 29 - 29 (0)

ings to edit or to-

Transcript_FI1: 22 - 22 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Text enhancement > Text challenging

FB2: For me, it's what you mentioned. Really. It's tech. I didn't use it directly for proofing, but we just have as I mentioned earlier, we just had our annual report out and the colleague who I was working with on the annual report, I did send his text through AI to prove it.

Transcript_FB2: 52 - 52 (0)

or to challenge some texts

Transcript_F11: 12 - 12 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Text enhancement > Summarising and combining information

this is the DeepL or ChatGPT or Copilot short version

Transcript_HR1: 36 - 36 (0)

d you'll probably do it after the meeting is...you can have a summary of what the meeting is all about. So, when you go and do your you when you do your writing.It's very simple. You have a nice, lovely summary.

Transcript_FB2: 138 - 138 (0)

Oder um längere komplexe Themen zusammenzufassen, wenn man nicht 150-seitiges Dokument lesen möchte.

Transcript_FI2: 34 - 34 (0)

Ja, also, es gibt Kolleginnen und Kollegen im Team, die verwenden diese Tools auch für wirkliche, für Schreibarbeiten, dass sie beispielsweise einen längeren Text zu einem Thema schreiben und dann die Kurzversion für die für die einzelnen Social-Media-Kanäle von KI schreiben lassen

Transcript_FI2: 36 - 36 (0)

for example, one use case in in communication is to shorten a press text. Often you need to provide different newspapers with more shorter information than we edited, and therefore we have developed a hardened prompt setting, or agents, which really shorten

Transcript_FI1: 14 - 14 (0)

so they kind of resume or yeah

Transcript_E2: 63 - 63 (0)

ummarizing certain content and
like, really, yeah, helping us there
to combine everything

Transcript_E1: 26 - 26 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Text enhancement > Writing im-
provement

that help us write better job ads

Transcript_HR1: 16 - 16 (0)

Or I'll let it I ask if, if Copilot can
make it better or has something to
add.

Transcript_P2: 31 - 31 (0)

maybe text improvement tools.

Transcript_P1: 34 - 34 (0)

for rewriting my emails

Transcript_E1: 24 - 24 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented

> Text enhancement > Bullet points creation

This is not really nice, not really practical for the speaker, so let's make bullets out of it." So, I put it into Copilot for example, and ask "hey, please rewrite this speech, but in bullet points.

Transcript_HR1: 36 - 36 (0)

bullet points

Transcript_E1: 104 - 104 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented

> Ideation support

nd of course, for brainstorming, we use it for a lot of things and for research

Transcript_HR2: 22 - 22 (0)

I think almost everyone in the team also uses it for inspiration

Transcript_P2: 31 - 31 (0)

or give ourselves maybe some impulse or some starting point to start from

Transcript_P1: 34 - 34 (0)

FB2: And then see what it spits out. Essentially what is AI going to give me? And then I can get that and use that as a base, as a very good base by the way, to create things because for a person like me who's a one-man team... you have to take all the help you can get and having tools like that would be super helpful so. Yes, position papers. Manuals. Articles. Visuals. All these elements absolutely.

Transcript_FB2: 168 - 168 (0)

Like a first draft and we do also brainstorm with ChatGPT

Transcript_FB1: 50 - 50 (0)

Manchmal auch, um sich schnell eine Übersicht über ein Thema, das man noch nicht so gut kennt, zu verfassen, so die wichtigsten Quellen wichtigsten ja... welche Punkte dreht sich eine Debatte

Transcript_FI2: 34 - 34 (0)

they often use it as a hint giver or to start with something

Transcript_FI1: 12 - 12 (0)

but we for example use AI to generate ideas-

Transcript_FI1: 40 - 40 (0)

I insert all the information I have and wait for some inspiration

Transcript_E2: 17 - 17 (0)

E1: Yep. Yep, absolutely. So, I think the one I use the most is [COMPANY'S NAME] GPT. In this case, I mostly use ChatGPT 4.0 at the moment, and I think that's mostly for rewriting my emails. Writing copy for social media. Giving me ideas for slides and presentations. New ideas for or just like creative idea generation, which most of the time it's not that great at because it's not creative in a sense, but it will just give me a little bit of help if I have some kind of blockage in my brain. So, I think that's the one I used the most. Yeah.

Transcript_E1: 24 - 24 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Ideation support > Overview generation

Manchmal auch, um sich schnell eine Übersicht über ein Thema, das man noch nicht so gut kennt, zu verfassen, so die wichtigsten

Quellen wichtigsten ja... welche Punkte dreht sich eine Debatte

Transcript_FI2: 34 - 34 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Ideation support > Input/Inspiration

I think almost everyone in the team also uses it for inspiration

Transcript_P2: 31 - 31 (0)

or give ourselves maybe some impulse or some starting point to start from

Transcript_P1: 34 - 34 (0)

FB2: And then see what it spits out. Essentially what is AI going to give me? And then I can get that and use that as a base, as a very good base by the way, to create things because for a person like me who's a one-man team... you have to take all the help you can get and having tools like that would be super helpful so. Yes,

position papers. Manuals. Articles. Visuals. All these elements absolutely.

Transcript_FB2: 168 - 168 (0)

Like a first draft

Transcript_FB1: 50 - 50 (0)

they often use it as a hint giver or to start with something

Transcript_F11: 12 - 12 (0)

I insert all the information I have and wait for some inspiration

Trancript_E2: 17 - 17 (0)

Giving me ideas for slides and presentations. New ideas for or just like creative idea generation

Transcript_E1: 24 - 24 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented

> Ideation support > Brainstorming

nd of course, for brainstorming, we use it for a lot of things and for research

Transcript_HR2: 22 - 22 (0)

brainstorm

Transcript_FB1: 50 - 50 (0)

like brainstorming. It's amazing or there are even people... they're recording with ChatGPT. I never did it, but it's possible. I heard they're recording a meeting and then they entered the prompt "Please, what are... What do you think are the points? Are there more pros or more cons?"

Trancript_E2: 61 - 61 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented

> Visual and multimedia production

we have employees that have like privately this ChatGPT 4 or other image AI tools and generate pictures for their social media posts

with AI that they use for you know advertising jobs

Transcript_HR1: 54 - 54 (0)

FB2: It is one of the most difficult things to have... and we have corporate visuals. We buy a lot of visuals as well, but sometimes you need a really, really specific thing.

PM: Yes. And then you can use the AI generated images and videos. For example, you can generate, yeah...

FB2: Exactly, exactly. And in fact, we organized a webinar for our colleagues. I was running the webinar at the back, so I didn't really follow much, but one thing was really simple. We... the guy who was running it, the colleague I spoke to, basically he showed on the webinar how to create a video and he said, you know, take I want a photo of a... it was a flower in the middle of the road with it. And then he did created it

to be nice, to be nicer, nicer. And than a bee had to land on the flower, because bees are very important for us. We use fruits and vegetables. No bees, no fruits and vegetables. So, you know that sort of thing. And then he came up with this really great image which is, which is fantastic.

Transcript_FB2: 48 - 50 (0)

und da wird teilweise mit KI gearbeitet, um etwas Passendes zu generieren

Transcript_FI2: 40 - 40 (0)

I use it, for the moment, just for my LinkedIn content creation. For example, I have to create a post,

Trancript_E2: 17 - 17 (0)

E2: I'm just using ChatGPT for the moment I started using

also...there is a possibility... we are using for example for images and video, stock images and stock videos. We're using Shutterstock and in Shutterstock there is the possibility-

Transcript_E2: 35 - 35 (0)

So, each you can imagine each customer has a different scenario. So, all the products we create are really, really-

PM: Yeah.

E2: -Specific for these customers,

Transcript_E2: 47 - 49 (0)

So, we will be able to do image generation with [COMPANY'S NAME] internal pictures.

Transcript_E1: 28 - 28 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented

> Visual and multimedia production
> Visual prototypes

but we for example use AI to generate ideas-

PM: Yes.

F1: -On how we could make some kind of communication on the visual side.

Transcript_F1: 40 - 42 (0)

So, each you can imagine each customer has a different scenario. So, all the products we create are really, really-

PM: Yeah.

E2: -Specific for these customers,

Trancript_E2: 47 - 49 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented

> Visual and multimedia production
> Social media content generation

we have employees that have like privately this ChatGPT 4 or other image AI tools and generate pictures for their social media posts with AI that they use for you know advertising jobs

Transcript_HR1: 54 - 54 (0)

I use it, for the moment, just for my LinkedIn content creation. For example, I have to create a post,

Trancript_E2: 17 - 17 (0)

Tasks in which AI is implemented
> Visual and multimedia production
> Video and image generation

we have employees that have like privately this ChatGPT 4 or other image AI tools and generate pictures for their social media posts with AI that they use for you know advertising jobs

Transcript_HR1: 54 - 54 (0)

FB2: Exactly, exactly. And in fact, we organized a webinar for our colleagues. I was running the webinar at the back, so I didn't really follow much, but one thing was really simple. We... the guy who was running it, the colleague I spoke to, basically he showed on the webinar how to create a video and he said, you know, take I want a photo of a... it was a

flower in the middle of the road with it. And then he did created it to be nice, to be nicer, nicer. And than a bee had to land on the flower, because bees are very important for us. We use fruits and vegetables. No bees, no fruits and vegetables. So, you know that sort of thing. And then he came up with this really great image which is, which is fantastic.

Transcript_FB2: 50 - 50 (0)

und da wird teilweise mit KI gearbeitet, um etwas Passendes zu generieren

Transcript_FI2: 40 - 40 (0)

we are using for example for images and video, stock images and stock videos

Trancript_E2: 35 - 35 (0)

But we are working on a tool that will be doing it. So, we will be able to do image generation with [COMPANY'S NAME] internal pictures. So, it is in progress

Transcript_E1: 28 - 28 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use

HR2: And gives the best basis for building up on that, because we don't copy paste, but we really use it as a base creator, and this is something to wrap. Yeah, as a as a sparing partner. So, we figured that ChatGPT for a lot of things is delivering the best base.

Transcript_HR2: 20 - 20 (0)

HR2: The main thing is definitely speed.

Transcript_HR2: 44 - 44 (0)

HR2: AI makes things much faster, much more cost efficient. Before that we were working with agencies, we still are, and the

agencies are knowingly using AI too. But it saves us time. It saves us effort. We can focus on other things on more strategic topics. That's really to make our everyday lives more efficient and also... to be honest, more fun because they can be very, in communications, very repetitive tasks that are really nice to have a tool to take off our shoulders.

Transcript_HR2: 46 - 46 (0)

HR2: Mm hmm. Yeah, sure. One of the main things is that we basically see it as enrichment, right? We see it as an opportunity to really elevate communication to a new level and to... just as I said, simplify routine tasks and yeah, focus more on the strategic work, but we definitely see a challenge in transparency, transparency and responsibility? Definitely. Also how you... Yeah. How you want to position yourself as company, of course. I mean, we are in the people's business as an HR company, and we are using tools and not people. What we really claim for is what we stand for, right? That we want to give people work and now we use AI to replace people's work so. That is, of

course, something that is always in discussion and that we always look into, and we see... I have to say that we don't, we don't lose people, but we see how people can transform.

Transcript_HR2: 48 - 48 (0)

HR1: Well, on the first-hand side, everybody already used those tools, so we had to kind of make it officially. So, we really made sure that we officially can use ChatGPT and did also trainings on the other hand side, we're also doing pilots with Copilot for Microsoft to include it in our daily work. But at the moment it's just a selected audience that has it and not yet all because we really want to make sure we have -

Transcript_HR1: 24 - 24 (0)

HR1: - And that really bring added value because you can spend so much and at the end you really think... need to fist find out what is that and value. If not, people maybe are unproductive, lose time, do not really know what to do, just play around. You know it's

really a trying out sometimes and it's not always efficient. So, we really want to make sure that we know exactly the use cases before we introduce it to everybody.

Transcript_HR1: 28 - 28 (0)

HR1: Well, I think it's it. There are different ways, right on. On the one hand side, I think many people are faster. But on the other hand, also the quality is getting worse if it's not corrected right? So, you see that many just research with these tools, with AI tools and do not research, do the Google Research anymore. So, without really checking the sources -

Transcript_HR1: 30 - 30 (0)

HR1: Well, let's say for example, we have a speech for someone, and I formulated it, or somebody formulated it in a in a text, right? And then I'm saying "oh, wow. This is not really nice, not really practical for the speaker, so let's make bullets out of it." So, I put it into Copilot for example, and ask

“hey, please rewrite this speech, but in bullet points.” And then it's very fast. It's done and it would take me like half an hour or 15 minutes to do it myself and like that, it's done. Let's say I still need like these 10 minutes because I have to review it. The thing is, if I don't review it, I think I really need to be transparent and tell “OK this is the original text and this is the DeepL translation, or this is the DeepL or ChatGPT or Copilot short version”. Like, I think it's important to say, “OK I can translate, I don't have time, but I can send you the AI generated version so please check it”. Yeah.

Transcript_HR1: 36 - 36 (0)

HR1: No, it's never the AI just going to work. It's not... it's not possible yet. You know. Sometimes it helps to give some ideas if you have to be creative and write something. But at the end you need to generate value for the person that you have in front of you, and you have to think about what could be interesting and you have to do the basic work yourself and maybe it can give you an-

Transcript_HR1: 48 - 48 (0)

HR1: - Pictures with the AI that, but officially, you know, transparently announced it. But also I have... we have employees that have like privately this ChatGPT 4 or other image AI tools and generate pictures for their social media posts with AI that they use for you know advertising jobs, and you know it's always difficult there is no real reason to say why it's not OK because it's sometimes really fun right? I think it's for example they put it in a, let's say it's a brand from Schaffhausen and they put it like with the Rhine in the background, with the Munot, you know some local recognizable assets and then at the it's a marketing job. Then you see some marketing formula or things like that. So, it's cool, why not? But then you see some details that are completely wrong and then you need... then I tell "OK, maybe just make sure that here there is a mistake that this is not because this AI generation doesn't always, alright, hit all the spots. So, you have to be attentive. But I think it's fun. But I always tell, "OK, if you do this,

please write <It has been AI generated> and also include the tool you have been generated. This was so it has been included. It has been done with ChatGPT4 or something like that.

Transcript_HR1: 54 - 55 (0)

P2: Texts and so on. So, of course, it makes us more efficient. It makes us faster and it's just an additional tool to help our daily productivity as a team.

Transcript_P2: 37 - 37 (0)

P2: And you cannot forbid to use every tool. Our approach is more to offer as fast as possible a secure environment where people can use it without... yeah, without feeling always in danger. Can they use it or not? So, I think Copilot with Microsoft is a very good solution.

Transcript_P2: 71 - 71 (0)

P1: And I have to say, I'm super content with the features and quality. And for the purpose, for other purposes. So, this is now ongoing to have here a proper solution. So, this is an ongoing task. I would say everybody's using... it for the time being, which is definitely not satisfying, a different tool on a very individual base, I would say most probably use ChatGPT.

Transcript_P1: 40 - 40 (0)

P1: I think I think AI is here to stay. This is clear. The big question is what's the optimal way to use it to get the optimal value out of it. And so, it's the of course it is increasing efficiency, it makes a couple of tasks much easier. So, a lot of information in principle is available at your fingertip. So, it is

saving, any hours of formal paperwork. I think this is understood and this is clear. This is common opinion. The big question is really to do it the right way to do it, to do the right things and do it right, and so to be lean means also you have to take care about the output, the quality of the output, the reliability of the output and I think therefore it's also it. It is very important, and this is also the, I would say common sense in our company, but also I would say in in the conversation with some peers-

Transcript_P1: 54 - 54 (0)

FB2: But the thing is, when you have 20 of them, 20 times 15 minutes is of course a long time. So, I'm encouraging people to use AI to send me articles which are more or less complete. You see. So even if I don't use it directly myself, others are using it and sending me material and

even images for example. So, they'd send me an article and an image and I can just post it on Intranet.

Transcript_FB2: 38 - 38 (0)

FB2: To be honest, when I proved it, I still had a lot of work to do, but I'm reasonably sure that if he hadn't done that, I would have had double the work to do so that helps. That helps quite a bit.

Transcript_FB2: 54 - 54 (0)

FB2: And one of the biggest problems I have currently is I don't have time to think... to stop and say "OK, how can we solve this problem" or "how can we do this that and the other". So, if AI does these menial tasks, I mean menial, it sounds bad by menial I mean things like writing an article

for example, and if that saves me time, that's not only-

PM: Mm hmm.

FB2: -That's going to help me a lot to do my job better.

Transcript_FB2: 88 - 90 (0)

FB2: -To divide into AI strategy, marketing, AI policy, et cetera, et cetera. That's great because then you share that and it's nice and easy. I mean, before this you'd have to type in. "Now this person said this, and that person said that", and that would take you an hour, an hour and a half. I'm going to make an assumption that maybe you have some interest in this, but you haven't... you don't have a job. I guess when you have a job, you need to make sure that things are documented.

PM: Yes, that's for sure.

FB2: Because, you know, I could say “No, no, Marta didn't tell me that I have to do the job, she's supposed to do it.” And he said no. But we spoke in the meeting. And. No, no, no. But if you have the meeting notes done and ready, they're there. And it's very, very easy to use. And even if you forget what was said you meeting and I was OK. Martin said this. Well fine.

PM: You can check it, yeah.

FB2: You see, this is the idea of productivity. I don't need to waste an hour and a half to type the notes. I have them there. It's fantastic actually.

Transcript_FB2: 140 - 144 (0)

FB2 Incidentally, it might also be even better maybe than humans in in doing it, because you have, you know, as soon as there's a

human element usually there's also always a risk of error.

PM: Yeah, but basically, yeah. It's technical communication, I would say also like if you. Yeah. Mm hmm.

FB2: Logically. Exactly, absolutely. And this is where, you know, and we're undergoing at the moment where we've been for quite some time because it's huge project. Digitalization project which involves the use of the SAP HANA 4 platform, so that all our production units especially are connected. So, before everything is to be done manually. And I mean the, the chances of errors were so high. So now it's all within the system. And that means that because it's within our closed system and we have a closed AI, we can use AI to our benefit. I don't know the extent to which they use it to be honest with you, but I'm pretty sure that they do use it to make these...the content creation, for example, the package-

details, especially because in many cases we try and do packs which are good for many countries, so you know you always get... in fact, I've seen this here, for example, this, I'm seeing in it here, you have it in German.

Transcript_FB2: 210 - 212 (0)

FB1: Yes. Yes, although me personally, I like to try new stuff also on teams. You have a lot of-

PM: Yes.

FB1: -New AI tools and from time to time I try them out, but as long as I don't see the value of really optimizing my work with it. There is no point using it, but I would say once, twice a year I test new stuff. I take the time I test new stuff and if I see it provides benefits, then I will start using it. Otherwise, I said "You're not there yet".

Transcript_FB1: 38 - 40 (0)

FB1: But then in a second, you know, maybe it has a good idea to

another good idea we didn't think of. Normally not. But you know, it's always good to have like different options. So that's what I use it for.

Transcript_FB1: 54 - 54 (0)

FB1: Yes and no, because you cannot trust ChatGPT to write you a full text. It writes a lot of nonsense. I think ChatGPT works much better if you ask for short texts. For social media posts, for example, but also every company has its own style. So, you can't... I mean, to tell ChatGPT what it needs to know about a company and to write it the way it's supposed to... in the meantime, you wrote it yourself, right? So, I think you really need to... one needs to find out where it works. I mean, I've also started to prompt. I just did a CAS at the ZHAW in political communication and I did a research on a lot of articles, which in the short time I had it's by hand I would not have been able to analyze all these articles if it wasn't for ChatGPT, so I did a lot of prompting to perfect the analysis because it's something you know he can do if you-

Transcript_FB1: 58 - 58 (0)

FB1: I mean, I don't avoid using it and especially with budgets that you know, you know we've we have optimized. That's what I told you. We optimize by not using Excel anymore and transferring it. You know you, like project management, we through AI, we have managed to reduce hours and instead using use it for more measurements in PR. So that's not a loss of budget.

Transcript_FB1: 134 - 134 (0)

nennt sich [*COMPANY'S NAME*] Translator, ist aber eigentlich wie DeepL mit dem Unterschied, dass die Daten nicht ins World Wide Web rausgehen zu Trainingszwecken

Transcript_FI2: 28 - 28 (0)

F12: Einerseits Effizienz bei so Routinetätigkeiten das ist sicher der grösste Vorteil.

Transcript_F12: 32 - 32 (0)

F12: Manchmal auch, um sich schnell eine Übersicht über ein Thema, das man noch nicht so gut kennt, zu verfassen, so die wichtigsten Quellen wichtigsten ja... welche Punkte dreht sich eine Debatte. Oder um längere komplexe Themen zusammenzufassen, wenn man nicht 150-seitiges Dokument lesen möchte.

Transcript_F12: 34 - 34 (0)

F12: Ja, also, es gibt Kolleginnen und Kollegen im Team, die verwenden diese Tools auch für wirkliche, für Schreiarbeiten, dass sie beispielsweise einen längeren Text zu einem Thema

schreiben und dann die Kurzversion für die für die einzelnen Social-Media-Kanäle von KI schreiben lassen, explizit mit dem Prompt, so dass es für uns... in unserem Tone of Voice kommt. Wir haben auch ein Tool, das wird aber vor allem vom Marketing, teilweise aber auch von der Unternehmenskommunikation genutzt. Das ist trainiert auf die Tone of Voice von [COMPANY'S NAME], wo wir Texte durchlaufen lassen können, beispielsweise für employer branding. Dass es immer im gleichen Tonfall daherkommt und nach [COMPANY'S NAME] klingt, da werden die Texte mit KI in die richtige Tone of Voice gebracht, auch das wird kommt häufig zur Anwendung bei uns.

Transcript_FI2: 36 - 36 (0)

FI2: Und ja, wir werden wir werden sicher differenzieren, je nach Art von Kommunikation, wie stark

KI zum Einsatz kommen kann. Also ich habe vorhin schon angesprochen, beispielsweise zur Generierung von Kurztönen für Social Media ist sicher ein sehr effizientes Werkzeug und da haben wir... das ist klar... da kann man es anwenden, hingegen für längere Beiträge, Fachbeiträge, die Autorentexte sind und dann auch ins gedruckte Kundenmagazin kommen da besteht schon die Erwartung, dass man die auch wirklich noch selber schreibt. Und KI dort vielleicht mehr als Inspiration nutzen? Für Formulierungsvorschläge, für Rechercheaufgaben, für Themen zu meinem Thema gesamtheitlich zu erfassen, ist man es... für diese Zwecke mehr einsetzt und weniger jetzt für die Schreibe an sich.

Transcript_FI2: 84 - 84 (0)

FI2: Also die grössten Fortschritte sehe ich natürlich bei der Effizienz in Sachen Übersetzungen bei

uns, das ist dort geht es am schnellsten vorwärts.

Transcript_FI2: 122 - 122 (0)

FI2: Und ja. Die sind oft... inhaltlich eigentlich schon recht gut, wenn man sie mit den richtigen Grundlagen füttert. Ähm, vom Sprachstil her werde ich noch nicht so glücklich, bin ich noch nicht so glücklich für gewisse Textsorten schon sehr gut, wenn es so rein faktische Texte sind, aber wenn man so ein gewisses-

Transcript_FI2: 126 - 126 (0)

FI1: Well, I would say today it's on a daily base, but we need to differ on... on one hand we have a really open tool, like we currently have Copilot. This is some kind of ChatGPT adoption which is secure, which is currently based on GPT 4.0 model, and is provided

by Microsoft with all this data protection possibilities, which enables us to use more than just public data. And I'd say I know of my colleagues at the communication department, that they often use it as a hint giver or to start with something, or to challenge some texts. And so... therefore this approach... and we enable that also with an intense program at [*COMPANY'S NAME*] and, and I'd say, and I know from these colleagues, that they often

Transcript_F11: 12 - 12 (0)

F11: We primarily for the flexible usage, we use Copilot. We know that some people use, on their private computers, they use other tools, but from the official side at our company it is Copilot, for the for the chat functionality versus an LLM feature. We certainly also have quite a journey behind us in identifying concrete use cases

where you need a more strict implementation, and where you also use cloud resources. We currently work primarily with Azure, and there we have an AI foundation developed which can be used to implement specific use cases. Or we work together with some partners that provide us with concrete implementations, for example, one use case in in communication is to shorten a press text. Often you need to provide different newspapers with more shorter information than we edited, and therefore we have developed a hardened prompt setting, or agents, which really shorten the text but still keep the tone of voice of [COMPANY'S NAME] and the way we communicate the essential information we want to provide in this text and therefore we have developed like a more strict workflow in in use cases like this.

Transcript_F11: 14 - 14 (0)

F11: -To draft internal use for the Intranet, or maybe even for the Webpage, where we provide some tools and where we try to find out if this shortens the process to develop these kinds of text.

Transcript_F11: 24 - 24 (0)

F11: What I really honestly can say is that we are quite positive that this helps us to better texts, to do better communication in the end with the help of generative AI adoption, we're quicker. So, it's an efficiency element. So, this means we have more time to check on quality. And with that we will have, also better future texts if I bring it to simplicity. I mean, we generated content, you have this this new Pareto principle, I would say you can do good texts with no effort. But to be really good you can invest more time in making

really great texts. As long as you have enough people.

Transcript_FI1: 66 - 66 (0)

E2: So, the people from the business, actually the engineers, have to provide the content. So, they are using and working a lot with AI, yeah.

Transcript_E2: 25 - 25 (0)

E2: -I think in the future we will rely more there on the AI pictures and videos to kind of show what it is but hide at the same time the confidential parts.

Transcript_E2: 45 - 45 (0)

E2: I think it's. It's so nice because in my opinion, it's kind of a counterpart, so instead of scheduling a meeting with a work colleague,

you just go to ChatGPT, you insert your ideas and your thoughts, and you have an immediate reply. I think it's kind of replacing-

Transcript_E2: 59 - 59 (0)

E2: -Yeah, long meetings. And you, you have also for idea creation or like brainstorming. It's amazing or there are even people... they're recording with ChatGPT. I never did it, but it's possible. I heard they're recording a meeting and then they entered the prompt "Please, what are... What do you think are the points? Are there more pros or more cons?"

Transcript_E2: 61 - 61 (0)

E2: Then, ChatGPT maybe responds based on outdated or biased data. Number two, share the

insights, share your ideas and insights about ChatGPT with your colleagues. And number three, be responsible, use ChatGPT to increase your productivity, but be mindful how you use AI generated content. Number four learn and experiment. Use ChatGPT as a tool for learning and experimentation. So, there are also some don'ts. AI can be wrong. Point 1. Point two. proper permission.

Transcript_E2: 115 - 115 (0)

E1: I know that some of my older colleagues use it a little bit less, but just because they're not that used to it yet, but we did recently have a little course that we hosted in our team as well to get everyone on board and really like make them want to use it because I think it's life changing when it comes to work.

Transcript_E1: 16 - 16 (0)

E1: Yep. Yep, absolutely. So, I think the one I use the most is [COMPANY'S NAME] GPT. In this case, I mostly use ChatGPT 4.0 at the moment, and I think that's mostly for rewriting my emails. Writing copy for social media. Giving me ideas for slides and presentations. New ideas for or just like creative idea generation, which most of the time it's not that great at because it's not creative in a sense, but it will just give me a little bit of help if I have some kind of blockage in my brain. So, I think that's the one I used the most. Yeah.

Transcript_E1: 24 - 24 (0)

E1: Yeah. Yeah, we don't at the moment, we have an internal policy that we don't, I think, and this maybe comes into like the ethical perspective of a lot because it is using pictures that are not our

own. But we are working on a tool that will be doing it. So, we will be able to do image generation with [COMPANY'S NAME] internal pictures. So, it is in progress. We don't know when it's going to start, but we have seen some results, and it looks fantastic. So, if that's going to work soon, I'm very excited, yeah.

Transcript_E1: 28 - 28 (0)

E1: I think it helps with brain blockages, especially features needed fast input to start working on something. I think it is very quick. I think it helps save massive amounts of time. Especially if you have material and you just need the material in another format, it's fantastic. Yeah, I think saving time is the biggest one.

Transcript_E1: 106 - 106 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use > Transformative impact in the workplace

One of the main things is that we basically see it as enrichment, right? We see it as an opportunity to really elevate communication to a new level

Transcript_HR2: 48 - 48 (0)

that really bring added value

Transcript_HR1: 28 - 28 (0)

I think it's life changing when it comes to work.

Transcript_E1: 16 - 16 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use > Increased efficiency

HR2: The main thing is definitely speed.

Transcript_HR2: 44 - 44 (0)

HR2: AI makes things much faster, much more cost efficient. Before that we were working with agencies, we still are, and the agencies are knowingly using AI

too. But it saves us time. It saves us effort. We can focus on other things on more strategic topics. That's really to make our everyday lives more efficient and also... to be honest, more fun because they can be very, in communications, very repetitive tasks that are really nice to have a tool to take off our shoulders.

Transcript_HR2: 46 - 46 (0)

just as I said, simplify routine tasks and yeah, focus more on the strategic work,

Transcript_HR2: 48 - 48 (0)

HR1: Well, I think it's it. There are different ways, right on. On the one hand side, I think many people are faster. But on the other hand, also the quality is getting worse if it's not corrected right? So, you see that many just research with these tools, with AI tools and do not research, do the Google Research anymore. So, without really checking the sources -

Transcript_HR1: 30 - 30 (0)

, it makes us more efficient. It makes us faster and it's just an additional tool to help our daily productivity as a team.

Transcript_P2: 37 - 37 (0)

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Transcript_P1: 54 - 54 (0)

FB2: To be honest, when I proved it, I still had a lot of work to do, but I'm reasonably sure that if he hadn't done that, I would have had double the work to do so that helps. That helps quite a bit.

Transcript_FB2: 54 - 54 (0)

FB2: And one of the biggest problems I have currently is I don't have time to think... to stop and say "OK, how can we solve this problem" or "how can we do this that and the other". So, if AI does these menial tasks, I mean menial, it sounds bad by menial I mean things like writing an article for example, and if that saves me time, that's not only-

PM: Mm hmm.

FB2: -That's going to help me a lot to do my job better

Transcript_FB2: 88 - 90 (0)

FB2: -To divide into AI strategy, marketing, AI policy, et cetera, et cetera. That's great because then you share that and it's nice and easy. I mean, before this you'd

have to type in. "Now this person said this, and that person said that", and that would take you an hour, an hour and a half. I'm going to make an assumption that maybe you have some interest in this, but you haven't... you don't have a job. I guess when you have a job, you need to make sure that things are documented.

PM: Yes, that's for sure.

FB2: Because, you know, I could say "No, no, Marta didn't tell me that I have to do the job, she's supposed to do it." And he said no. But we spoke in the meeting. And. No, no, no. But if you have the meeting notes done and ready, they're there. And it's very, very easy to use. And even if you forget what was said you meeting and I was OK. Martin said this. Well fine.

PM: You can check it, yeah.

FB2: You see, this is the idea of productivity. I don't need to waste

an hour and a half to type the notes. I have them there. It's fantastic actually.

Transcript_FB2: 140 - 144 (0)

FB2 Incidentally, it might also be even better maybe than humans in in doing it, because you have, you know, as soon as there's a human element usually there's also always a risk of error.

PM: Yeah, but basically, yeah. It's technical communication, I would say also like if you. Yeah. Mm hmm.

FB2: Logically. Exactly, absolutely. And this is where, you know, and we're undergoing at the moment where we've been for quite some time because it's huge project. Digitalization project which involves the use of the SAP HANA 4 platform, so that all our production units especially are connected. So, before everything

is to be done manually. And I mean the, the chances of errors were so high. So now it's all within the system. And that means that because it's within our closed system and we have a closed AI, we can use AI to our benefit. I don't know the extent to which they use it to be honest with you, but I'm pretty sure that they do use it to make these...the content creation, for example, the package-details, especially because in many cases we try and do packs which are good for many countries, so you know you always get... in fact, I've seen this here, for example, this, I'm seeing in it here, you have it in German.

Transcript_FB2: 210 - 212 (0)

F12: Einerseits Effizienz bei so Routinetätigkeiten das ist sicher der grösste Vorteil.

Transcript_F12: 32 - 32 (0)

um sich schnell

Transcript_FI2: 34 - 34 (0)

FI2: Also die grössten Fortschritte sehe ich natürlich bei der Effizienz in Sachen Übersetzungen bei uns, das ist dort geht es am schnellsten vorwärts.

Transcript_FI2: 122 - 122 (0)

we try to find out if this shortens the process to develop these kinds of text.

Transcript_FI1: 24 - 24 (0)

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Transcript_F11: 66 - 66 (0)

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Trascript_E2: 25 - 25 (0)

E2: -Yeah, long meetings.

Trascript_E2: 61 - 61 (0)

use ChatGPT to increase your productivity

Transcript_E2: 115 - 115 (0)

I think it is very quick. I think it helps save massive amounts of time. Especially if you have material and you just need the material in another format, it's fantastic. Yeah, I think saving time is the biggest one.

Transcript_E1: 106 - 106 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use > Increased efficiency > Reducing potential for human error

FB2 Incidentally, it might also be even better maybe than humans in in doing it, because you have, you know, as soon as there's a human element usually there's also always a risk of error.

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Transcript_FB2: 210 - 212 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/
Reason for use > Increased efficiency
> Shifting routine focus to quality
focus

We can focus on other things on more strategic topics

Transcript_HR2: 46 - 46 (0)

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Transcript_HR2: 48 - 48 (0)

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Transcript_FB2: 88 - 90 (0)

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Transcript_F11: 66 - 66 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use > Increased efficiency
> Cost reduction

Transcript_HR2: 46 - 46 (0)

especially with budgets that you know, you know we've we have optimized

Transcript_FB1: 134 - 134 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use > Increased efficiency > Time saving

HR2: The main thing is definitely speed.

Transcript_HR2: 44 - 44 (0)

On the one hand side, I think many people are faster

Transcript_HR1: 30 - 30 (0)

And then it's very fast. It's done and it would take me like half an hour or 15 minutes to do it myself and like that, it's done

Transcript_HR1: 36 - 36 (0)

It makes us faster

Transcript_P2: 37 - 37 (0)

increasing efficiency, it makes a couple of tasks much easier. So, a lot of information in principle is available at your fingertip. So, it is saving, any hours of formal paperwork.

Transcript_P1: 54 - 54 (0)

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Transcript_FB2: 54 - 54 (0)

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Transcript_FB1: 58 - 58 (0)

Effizienz bei so Routinetätigkeiten

Transcript_FI2: 32 - 32 (0)

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Transcript_E1: 106 - 106 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/
Reason for use > Increased efficiency
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It saves us effort.

Transcript_HR2: 46 - 46 (0)

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Transcript_P1: 54 - 54 (0)

Effizienz bei so Routinetätigkeite

Transcript_FI2: 32 - 32 (0)

you can do good texts with no effort

Transcript_FI1: 66 - 66 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/
Reason for use > Increased efficiency
> Optimised workflows and
productivity

help our daily productivity as a team

Transcript_P2: 37 - 37 (0)

FB2: But the thing is, when you have 20 of them, 20 times 15 minutes is of course a long time. So, I'm encouraging people to use AI to send me articles which

are more or less complete. You see. So even if I don't use it directly myself, others are using it and sending me material and even images for example. So, they'd send me an article and an image and I can just post it on Intranet.

Transcript_FB2: 38 - 38 (0)

FB2: -To divide into AI strategy, marketing, AI policy, et cetera, et cetera. That's great because then you share that and it's nice and easy. I mean, before this you'd have to type in. "Now this person said this, and that person said that", and that would take you an hour, an hour and a half. I'm going to make an assumption that maybe you have some interest in this, but you haven't... you don't have a job. I guess when you have a job, you need to make sure that things are documented.

PM: Yes, that's for sure.

FB2: Because, you know, I could say "No, no, Marta didn't tell me that I have to do the job, she's supposed to do it." And he said no. But we spoke in the meeting. And. No, no, no. But if you have the meeting notes done and ready, they're there. And it's very, very easy to use. And even if you forget what was said you meeting and I was OK. Martin said this. Well fine.

PM: You can check it, yeah.

FB2: You see, this is the idea of productivity. I don't need to waste an hour and a half to type the notes. I have them there. It's fantastic actually.

Transcript_FB2: 140 - 144 (0)

ew AI tools and from time to time I try them out, but as long as I don't see the value of really optimizing my work with it

Transcript_FB1: 40 - 40 (0)

. Also ich habe vorhin schon angesprochen, beispielsweise zur Generierung von Kurztexten für Social Media ist sicher ein sehr effizientes Werkzeug und da haben wir.... das ist klar.... da kann man es anwenden, hingegen für längere Beiträge

Transcript_FI2: 84 - 84 (0)

the engineers, have to provide the content. So, they are using and working a lot with AI, yeah.

Transcript_E2: 25 - 25 (0)

use ChatGPT to increase your productivity

Transcript_E2: 115 - 115 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use > Satisfaction with results

So, we figured that ChatGPT for a lot of things is delivering the best base.

Transcript_HR2: 20 - 20 (0)

One of the main things is that we basically see it as enrichment, right? We see it as an opportunity to really elevate communication to a new level

Transcript_HR2: 48 - 48 (0)

And I have to say, I'm super content with the features and quality

Transcript_P1: 40 - 40 (0)

Yes.

Transcript_FB1: 38 - 38 (0)

wir Texte durchlaufen lassen können, beispielsweise für employer branding. Dass es immer im

gleichen Tonfall daherkommt und nach [COMPANY'S NAME] klingt, da werden die Texte mit KI in die richtige Tone of Voice gebracht, auch das wird kommt häufig zur Anwendung bei uns.

Transcript_FI2: 36 - 36 (0)

inhaltlich eigentlich schon recht gut,

Transcript_FI2: 126 - 126 (0)

We primarily for the flexible usage

Transcript_FI1: 14 - 14 (0)

but still keep the tone of voice of [COMPANY'S NAME] and the way we communicate the essential information we want to provide in this text

Transcript_FI1: 14 - 14 (0)

but we have seen some results,
and it looks fantastic

Transcript_E1: 28 - 28 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use > Satisfaction with results > Consistency with company's style and tone of voice

xplizit mit dem Prompt, so dass es für uns... in unserem Tone of Voice kommt. Wir haben auch ein Tool, das wird aber vor allem vom Marketing, teilweise aber auch von der Unternehmenskommunikation genutzt. Das ist trainiert auf die Tone of Voice von [COMPANY'S NAME], wo wir Texte durchlaufen lassen können, beispielsweise für employer branding. Dass es immer im gleichen Tonfall daherkommt und nach [COMPANY'S NAME] klingt, da werden die Texte mit KI in die richtige Tone of Voice gebracht, auch das wird kommt häufig zur Anwendung bei uns.

Transcript_FI2: 36 - 36 (0)

but still keep the tone of voice of [COMPANY'S NAME] and the way we communicate the essential information we want to provide in this text

Transcript_F11: 14 - 14 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use > Satisfaction with results > Good features and quality

So, we figured that ChatGPT for a lot of things is delivering the best base.

Transcript_HR2: 20 - 20 (0)

I'm super content with the features and quality

Transcript_P1: 40 - 40 (0)

Yes.

Transcript_FB1: 38 - 38 (0)

inhaltlich eigentlich schon recht gut,

Transcript_FI2: 126 - 126 (0)

We primarily for the flexible usage

Transcript_FI1: 14 - 14 (0)

but we have seen some results,
and it looks fantastic

Transcript_E1: 28 - 28 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use > Creative support

to be honest, more fun because they can be very, in communications, very repetitive tasks

Transcript_HR2: 46 - 46 (0)

Sometimes it helps to give some ideas if you have to be creative and write something.

Transcript_HR1: 48 - 48 (0)

here is no real reason to say why it's not OK because it's sometimes really fun right?

Transcript_HR1: 54 - 54 (0)

FB1: But then in a second, you know, maybe it has a good idea to another good idea we didn't think of. Normally not. But you know, it's always good to have like different options. So that's what I use it for.

Transcript_FB1: 54 - 54 (0)

Und KI dort vielleicht mehr als Inspiration nutzen? Für Formulierungsvorschläge, für Rechercheaufgaben, für Themen zu meinem Thema gesamtheitlich zu erfassen, ist man es... für diese Zwecke mehr einsetzt und weniger jetzt für die Schreibearbeit an sich.

Transcript_FI2: 84 - 84 (0)

E2: I think it's. It's so nice because in my opinion, it's kind of a counterpart, so instead of scheduling a meeting with a work colleague, you just go to ChatGPT, you insert your ideas and your thoughts, and you have an immediate reply. I think it's kind of replacing-

Transcript_E2: 59 - 59 (0)

I think it helps with brain blockages, especially features needed fast input to start working on something.

Transcript_E1: 106 - 106 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use > Creative support > Inspiration and idea generation

Sometimes it helps to give some ideas if you have to be creative and write something

Transcript_HR1: 48 - 48 (0)

it's always good to have like different options.

Transcript_FB1: 54 - 54 (0)

Und KI dort vielleicht mehr als Inspiration nutzen? Für Formulierungsvorschläge, für Rechercheaufgaben, für Themen zu meinem Thema gesamtheitlich zu erfassen, ist man es... für diese Zwecke mehr einsetzt und weniger jetzt für die Schreibe an sich.

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Trancript_E2: 59 - 59 (0)

it will just give me a little bit of help
if I have some kind of blockage in
my brain

Transcript_E1: 24 - 24 (0)

think it helps with brain block-
ages, especially features needed
fast input to start working on
something.

Transcript_E1: 106 - 106 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/ Reason
for use > Creative support >
Fun and enjoyment

to be honest, more fun because
they can be very, in communica-
tions, very repetitive tasks

Transcript_HR2: 46 - 46 (0)

t's always difficult there is no real
reason to say why it's not OK be-
cause it's sometimes really fun
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put it in a, let's say it's a brand
from Schaffhausen and they put it
like with the Rhine in the back-
ground, with the Munot, you know

some local recognizable assets and then at the it's a marketing job. Then you see some marketing formula or things like that. So, it's cool, why not?

Transcript_HR1: 54 - 54 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use > Organisational reasons

verybody already used those tools, so we had to kind of make it officially. So, we really made sure that we officially can use ChatGPT

Transcript_HR1: 24 - 24 (0)

Das nennt sich [*COMPANY'S NAME*] Translator, ist aber eigentlich wie DeepL mit dem Unterschied, dass die Daten nicht ins World Wide Web rausgehen zu Trainingszwecken.

Transcript_FI2: 28 - 28 (0)

E2: -I think in the future we will rely more there on the AI pictures and videos to kind of show what it

is but hide at the same time the confidential parts.

Transcript_E2: 45 - 45 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use > Organisational reasons > Increased data security and control (in specific cases)

So, I think Copilot with Microsoft is a very good solution

Transcript_P2: 71 - 71 (0)

Das nennt sich [*COMPANY'S NAME*] Translator, ist aber eigentlich wie DeepL mit dem Unterschied, dass die Daten nicht ins World Wide Web rausgehen zu Trainingszwecken.

Transcript_FI2: 28 - 28 (0)

is provided by Microsoft with all this data protection possibilities, which enables us to use more than just public data

Transcript_FI1: 12 - 12 (0)

E2: -I think in the future we will rely more there on the AI pictures and videos to kind of show what it is but hide at the same time the confidential parts.

Transcript_E2: 45 - 45 (0)

Perceived AI advantages/ Reason for use > Organisational reasons > Formalization of AI use

everybody already used those tools, so we had to kind of make it officially

Transcript_HR1: 24 - 24 (0)

Perceived AI disadvantages

HR2: We have that, but we also just detected the limits on AI there on SEO texts, because of course AI learns from what's online and if you always create a text, it learns from itself. So, it kind of creates a loop that makes the quality really bad right now. And the algorithm also sees the problem and they detect and of course and then it's not really working for SEO texts anymore.

Transcript_HR2: 30 - 30 (0)

HR2: Yeah. Mostly we let it be created by AI too, and for the other texts mostly it's created by me or by colleagues. Or by the holding, but for the SEO text we have a longer process. We let it create by AI. Then I have the first check, so we'll let it be created in English or in German. Then I have the first check and see OK. Does it make sense? Does it have all the blocks inside because we also figured that ChatGPT likes to skip things that we have in the task so-

Transcript_HR2: 40 - 40 (0)

HR1: - And that really bring added value because you can spend so much and at the end you really think... need to fist find out what is that and value. If not, people maybe are unproductive, lose time, do not really know what to do, just play around. You know it's really a trying out sometimes and it's not always efficient. So, we really want to make sure that we know exactly the use cases before we introduce it to everybody.

Transcript_HR1: 28 - 28 (0)

HR1: Well, I think it's it. There are different ways, right on. On the one hand side, I think many people are faster. But on the other hand, also the quality is getting worse if it's not corrected right? So, you see that many just research with these tools, with AI tools and do not research, do the Google Research anymore. So, without really checking the sources -

Transcript_HR1: 30 - 30 (0)

HR1: No, it's never the AI just going to work. It's not... it's not possible yet. You know. Sometimes it helps to give some ideas if you have to be creative and write something. But at the end you need to generate value for the person that you have in front of you, and you have to think about what could be interesting and you have to do the basic work yourself and maybe it can give you an-

Transcript_HR1: 48 - 48 (0)

HR1: - Pictures with the AI that, but officially, you know, transparently announced it. But also I have... we have employees that have like privately this ChatGPT 4 or other image AI tools and generate pictures for their social media posts with AI that they use for you know advertising jobs, and you know it's always difficult there is no real reason to say why it's not OK because it's sometimes really fun right? I think it's for example they put it in a, let's say it's a brand from Schaffhausen and they put it like with the Rhine in the background, with the Munot, you know some local recognizable assets and then at the it's a marketing job. Then you see some marketing formula or things like that. So, it's cool, why not? But then you see some details that are completely wrong and then you need... then I tell "OK, maybe just make sure that here there is a mistake that this is not because this AI generation doesn't always, alright, hit all the spots. So, you have to be attentive. But I think it's fun. But I always tell, "OK, if you do this, please write <It has been AI generated> and also include the tool you have been generated. This was so it has been included. It

has been done with ChatGPT4 or something like that.

Transcript_HR1: 54 - 54 (0)

P1: And therefore, that's basically the reason why we are not, in terms of communication, using AI, of course, maybe there are other technical areas and spaces in our company and in finance and maybe in development and then technology and R&D and operations, of course, we have plenty of efforts to increase efficiency. But communication, our communication is really reduced to...first, limited because we obliged to do so, and then very much focused on facts. Yeah, on medical evidence. That's the that's the most important term. We have to be super safe that we don't promote any information, so, if we're allowed at all, without any or there is without-

Transcript_P1: 28 - 28 (0)

P1: I think I think AI is here to stay. This is clear. The big question is what's the optimal way to use it to get the optimal value out of it. And so, it's the of course it is increasing efficiency, it makes a couple of tasks much easier. So, a lot of information in principle is available at your fingertip. So, it is saving, any hours of formal paperwork. I think this is understood and this is clear. This is common opinion. The big question is really to do it the right way to do it, to do the right things and do it right, and so to be lean means also you have to take care about the output, the quality of the output, the reliability of the output and I think therefore it's also it. It is very important, and this is also the, I would say common sense in our company, but also I would say in in the conversation with some peers-

Transcript_P1: 54 - 54 (0)

FB2: We have a colleague who retired, and he is not with the company, he's been here for 20 years. Usually, the normal announcement I would write is like "Dear colleagues, we regret to inform you that Marta Pellegrino is leaving the company, she found a job elsewhere... in her time with the company Marta did this and that...Thank you very much for your service. Wish you good luck" and whatever. But with people who've been there for 20 years, for example, and everyone knows, it can be a little bit more personal even because you know the person, and you could put prompts in, of course, to AI. But unless you know the person, it is going to be very difficult to do that. And this is the personal sort of touch you would need to be able to have not a good communications toolbox, but a very good one, you see. So, there is that difference-

Transcript_FB2: 98 - 98 (0)

FB2: -By AI, but then I found many mistakes. Maybe this guy did them later. I don't know. It could also be...by the way, I don't... I mean I don't do... I think AI is a great, great tool. But it does, it does... It's still not quite there yet. I mean, is huge compared to three years ago, two years ago. My goodness, I mean incredible. But we still need a little bit more time.

Transcript_FB2: 102 - 102 (0)

FB2: And then you know it was a hugely critical thing. I would print it out and read it on paper because reading on a screen and reading on paper is different. Of course, the last step [*reading on paper*], which is the most critical one, AI cannot do, logically, but what's is a bit more of a concern

for me is that people wouldn't know how to use AI properly. So, to back the bias idea, it's back to what prompt you and that is because you could also get a wrong picture.

Transcript_FB2: 114 - 114 (0)

FB2: Would you? Would you trust AI? I'm. I'm not sure. I don't know. The thing is, you know, there are certain things you have to put on. For example, contents of anything that could be people could be allergic to.

Transcript_FB2: 206 - 206 (0)

FB1: Yes and no, because you cannot trust ChatGPT to write you a full text. It writes a lot of nonsense. I think ChatGPT works much better if you ask for short texts. For social media posts, for example, but also every company has its own style. So, you can't... I mean, to tell ChatGPT what it needs to know about a company

and to write it the way it's supposed to... in the meantime, you wrote it yourself, right? So, I think you really need to... one needs to find out where it works. I mean, I've also started to prompt. I just did a CAS at the ZHAW in political communication and I did a research on a lot of articles, which in the short time I had it's by hand I would not have been able to analyze all these articles if it wasn't for ChatGPT, so I did a lot of prompting to perfect the analysis because it's something you know he can do if you-

Transcript_FB1: 58 - 58 (0)

FB1: So yeah, I always say, "Every tool is as good as you know how to use it. But you can't use it for everything".

Transcript_FB1: 72 - 72 (0)

FB1: -And then I use ChatGPT PT and tell him "Write me a protocol". And then I read the protocols and I'm like "That's not how it went down. And something is missing". So, at the end I still

need to listen in, but generally, yeah, it works 70/30%.

Transcript_FB1: 102 - 102 (0)

FB1: ChatGPT doesn't have all this context. I can't feed all this information for it to have the context. Because you... it's like I would have to teach him and then next time he forgot everything already. So, there will always have to be this human control of proof reading and adding context to it, that's what I was telling you before. I never ever just take a text from ChatGPT, 99% of the time I have to rewrite it, but it still gives me an idea. It's like more of brainstorming, you know, like, "OK, this is not OK. This is not how I want to do" it or "OK, that's a good structure. It helps me". And then I start rewriting. It does not work without... I call it human touch now.

Transcript_FB1: 116 - 116 (0)

FI2: Ja ein sehr hoher Wert ist natürlich, dass die Leute uns ver-

trauen, dass wir medizinische Informationen, die wir veröffentlichen, dass es sich hundertprozentig darauf verlassen können, dass diese auch wirklich stimmen, also Tipps zu Impfungen, zu Medikamenten und so weiter, dass diese wirklich genauso gut sind, wie wenn sie von einem Arzt kommen.

Transcript_FI2: 68 - 68 (0)

FI2: Dort investieren wir auch massiv in die neuesten Tools. Und ja, wir erhoffen uns von dort deutlich mehr Geschwindigkeit, gute Qualität und gleichzeitig deutlich tiefere Kosten. Da sind wir im Moment intensiv sehr intensiv dran.

Transcript_FI2: 124 - 124 (0)

FI2: Und ja. Die sind oft... inhaltlich eigentlich schon recht gut,

wenn man sie mit den richtigen Grundlagen füttert. Ähm, vom Sprachstil her werde ich noch nicht so glücklich, bin ich noch nicht so glücklich für gewisse Textsorten schon sehr gut, wenn es so rein faktische Texte sind, aber wenn man so ein gewisses-

Transcript_FI2: 126 - 126 (0)

F11: This is like a set of predeveloped prompts that we provide or that employees develop and share with us, and we share it with the whole company. So, where we say “Well, this is this is basically approved, it works this prompt”, but this is more in the usage and adoption of a tool like Copilot. For example, if someone has translation of text. We say, “Well, principally we have a standard approach where we currently are switching from a language model to element-based translation with a partner and still

use the glossary feature”, for example. We also have a prompt but here using the glossary, which is in our case a set of...I mean we communicate in in three languages officially. And there we have a set of words or phrases that need to be translated in a proven manner and with open prompting. This is not so reliable, so therefore we have there translation tool which is being switched because we've seen that the quality with LLM based translation is better than with the historic approaches we used. But yeah-

Transcript_F11: 28 - 28 (0)

E2: -Not a lot. Also, sometimes I still stick to creating my own texts because in... yeah, how can I say? In formulating all the things I would like ChatGPT to create, I am sometimes quicker in just writing it down myself.

Trancript_E2: 19 - 19 (0)

E2: I would say we always have to double check it, of course. So, in my case it's just the LinkedIn post, but I know that also it's used to create a draft for brochures, for example. But then we always make sure to double-check the content. Of course, we have a procedure of how our content gets approved internally and also externally. So that's a very strong process.

Transcript_E2: 69 - 69 (0)

E2: Yeah. Yeah. I mean, there are some kind of recommendations. For example, the first step, be aware of its limitations there. Now they are talking more about ChatGPT.

Transcript_E2: 113 - 113 (0)

E1: Though it was all about factories and the [COMPANY'S NAME] buildings and Santa Claus, and how we're helping Santa Claus going digital. It was very fun to see what is possible with image generation, but then we also noticed how much work it will be used afterwards. I don't know. You know about fingers [*in AI's image generation*] that don't align and things like that. So, it was a lot of Photoshop after the actual image generation. So yeah, that was one example, but the output was great. It was very creative in a sense, but also it didn't land that well with our audience. I think it was very-

Transcript_E1: 66 - 66 (0)

Perceived AI disadvantages > Inefficiency

HR1: - And that really bring added value because you can spend so much and at the end you really think... need to first find out what is that and value. If not, people maybe are unproductive, lose time, do not really know what to

do, just play around. You know it's really a trying out sometimes and it's not always efficient. So, we really want to make sure that we know exactly the use cases before we introduce it to everybody.

Transcript_HR1: 28 - 28 (0)

HR1: Well, I think it's it. There are different ways, right on. On the one hand side, I think many people are faster. But on the other hand, also the quality is getting worse if it's not corrected right? So, you see that many just research with these tools, with AI tools and do not research, do the Google Research anymore. So, without really checking the sources -

Transcript_HR1: 30 - 30 (0)

But at the end you need to generate value for the person that you have in front of you, and you have to think about what could be interesting and you have to do the basic work yourself and maybe it can give you an-

Transcript_HR1: 48 - 48 (0)

P1: I think I think AI is here to stay. This is clear. The big question is what's the optimal way to use it to get the optimal value out of it. And so, it's the of course it is increasing efficiency, it makes a couple of tasks much easier. So, a lot of information in principle is available at your fingertip. So, it is saving, any hours of formal paperwork. I think this is understood and this is clear. This is common opinion. The big question is really to do it the right way to do it, to do the right things and do it right, and so to be lean means also you have to take care about the output, the quality of the output, the reliability of the output and I think therefore it's also it. It is very important, and this is also the, I would say common sense in our company, but also I would say in in the conversation with some peers-

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FB2: We have a colleague who retired, and he is not with the company, he's been here for 20 years. Usually, the normal announcement I would write is like "Dear colleagues, we regret to inform you that Marta Pellegrino is leaving the company, she found a job elsewhere... in her time with the company Marta did this and that...Thank you very much for your service. Wish you good luck" and whatever. But with people who've been there for 20 years, for example, and everyone knows, it can be a little bit more personal even because you know the person, and you could put prompts in, of course, to AI. But unless you know the person, it is going to be very difficult to do that. And this is the personal sort of touch you would need to be able to have not a good communications toolbox, but a very good

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Transcript_FB2: 98 - 98 (0)

s is a bit more of a concern for me is that people wouldn't know how to use AI properly. So, to back the bias idea, it's back to what prompt you and that is because you could also get a wrong picture.

Transcript_FB2: 114 - 114 (0)

I mean, to tell ChatGPT what it needs to know about a company and to write it the way it's supposed to... in the meantime, you wrote it yourself, right?

Transcript_FB1: 58 - 58 (0)

FB1: So yeah, I always say, "Every tool is as good as you know how to use it. But you can't use it for everything".

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Trancript_E2: 113 - 113 (0)

Perceived AI disadvantages > Inefficiency > Slow and costly solutions

eutlich mehr Geschwindigkeit, gute Qualität und gleichzeitig deutlich tiefere Kosten

Transcript_FI2: 124 - 124 (0)

Perceived AI disadvantages > Inefficiency > Inefficiency in certain tasks or areas

But at the end you need to generate value for the person that you have in front of you, and you have to think about what could be interesting and you have to do the basic work yourself

Transcript_HR1: 48 - 48 (0)

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E2: Yeah. Yeah. I mean, there are some kind of recommendations. For example, the first step, be aware of its limitations there. Now they are talking more about ChatGPT.

Transcript_E2: 113 - 113 (0)

Perceived AI disadvantages > Inefficiency > Inefficiency due to users' lack of knowledge or improper use of AI

f not, people maybe are unproductive, lose time, do not really know what to do, just play around. You know it's really a trying out sometimes and it's not always efficient.

Transcript_HR1: 28 - 28 (0)

s is a bit more of a concern for me is that people wouldn't know how to use AI properly. So, to back the bias idea, it's back to what prompt you and that is because you could also get a wrong picture.

Transcript_FB2: 114 - 114 (0)

Perceived AI disadvantages > Inefficiency > Time inefficiency due to prompting and explaining

I mean, to tell ChatGPT what it needs to know about a company and to write it the way it's supposed to... in the meantime, you wrote it yourself, right?

Transcript_FB1: 58 - 58 (0)

In formulating all the things I would like ChatGPT to create, I am sometimes quicker in just writing it down myself

Transcript_E2: 19 - 19 (0)

Perceived AI disadvantages > Inaccurate or unreliable outputs

it kind of creates a loop that makes the quality really bad right now.

Transcript_HR2: 30 - 30 (0)

oes it have all the blocks inside because we also figured that ChatGPT likes to skip things that we have in the task so

Transcript_HR2: 40 - 40 (0)

HR1: Well, I think it's it. There are different ways, right on. On the one hand side, I think many people are faster. But on the other hand, also the quality is getting worse if it's not corrected right? So, you see that many just research with these tools, with AI tools and do not research, do the Google Research anymore. So, without really checking the sources -

Transcript_HR1: 30 - 30 (0)

because this AI generation doesn't always, alright, hit all the spots

Transcript_HR1: 54 - 54 (0)

But communication, our communication is really reduced to...first, limited because we obliged to do so, and then very much focused on facts. Yeah, on medical evidence. That's the that's the most important term. We have to be super safe that we don't promote

any information, so, if we're allowed at all, without any or there is without-

Transcript_P1: 28 - 28 (0)

you have to take care about the output, the quality of the output, the reliability of the output

Transcript_P1: 54 - 54 (0)

FB2: -By AI, but then I found many mistakes. Maybe this guy did them later. I don't know. It could also be...by the way, I don't... I mean I don't do... I think AI is a great, great tool. But it does, it does... It's still not quite there yet. I mean, is huge compared to three years ago, two years ago. My goodness, I mean incredible. But we still need a little bit more time.

Transcript_FB2: 102 - 102 (0)

It writes a lot of nonsense.

Transcript_FB1: 58 - 58 (0)

That's not how it went down. And something is missing”.

Transcript_FB1: 102 - 102 (0)

FB1: ChatGPT doesn't have all this context. I can't feed all this information for it to have the context. Because you... it's like I would have to teach him and then next time he forgot everything already. So, there will always have to be this human control of proof reading and adding context to it, that's what I was telling you before. I never ever just take a text from ChatGPT, 99% of the time I have to rewrite it, but it still gives me an idea. It's like more of brainstorming, you know, like, “OK, this is not OK. This is not how I want to do” it or “OK, that's a good structure. It helps me”. And then I start rewriting. It does not work without... I call it human touch now.

Transcript_FB1: 116 - 116 (0)

FI2: Ja ein sehr hoher Wert ist natürlich, dass die Leute uns vertrauen, dass wir medizinische Informationen, die wir veröffentlichen, dass es sich hundertprozentig darauf verlassen können, dass diese auch wirklich stimmen, also Tipps zu Impfungen, zu Medikamenten und so weiter, dass diese wirklich genauso gut sind, wie wenn sie von einem Arzt kommen.

Transcript_FI2: 68 - 68 (0)

ute Qualität

Transcript_FI2: 124 - 124 (0)

FI1: This is like a set of predeveloped prompts that we provide or that employees develop and share with us, and we share it with the whole company. So,

where we say “Well, this is this is basically approved, it works this prompt”, but this is more in the usage and adoption of a tool like Copilot. For example, if someone has translation of text. We say, “Well, principally we have a standard approach where we currently are switching from a language model to element-based translation with a partner and still use the glossary feature”, for example. We also have a prompt but here using the glossary, which is in our case a set of... I mean we communicate in in three languages officially. And there we have a set of words or phrases that need to be translated in a proven manner and with open prompting. This is not so reliable, so therefore we have there translation tool which is being switched because we've seen that the quality with LLM based translation is better than with the historic approaches we used. But yeah-

Transcript_F11: 28 - 28 (0)

I would say we always have to double check it, of course. So, in my case it's just the LinkedIn post, but I know that also it's used to create a draft for brochures, for example.

Transcript_E2: 69 - 69 (0)

Perceived AI disadvantages > In-accurate or unreliable outputs > Incomplete outputs

oes it have all the blocks inside because we also figured that ChatGPT likes to skip things that we have in the task so

Transcript_HR2: 40 - 40 (0)

That's not how it went down. And something is missing”.

Transcript_FB1: 102 - 102 (0)

. I can't feed all this information for it to have the context. Because you... it's like I would have to teach him and then next time he forgot everything already.

Transcript_FB1: 116 - 116 (0)

Perceived AI disadvantages > In-accurate or unreliable outputs > Poor text quality

it kind of creates a loop that makes the quality really bad right now.

Transcript_HR2: 30 - 30 (0)

the quality is getting worse if it's not corrected right?

Transcript_HR1: 30 - 30 (0)

FB2: -By AI, but then I found many mistakes. Maybe this guy did them later. I don't know. It could also be...by the way, I don't... I mean I don't do... I think AI is a great, great tool. But it does, it does... It's still not quite there yet. I mean, is huge compared to three years ago, two years ago. My goodness, I mean incredible. But we still need a little bit more time.

Transcript_FB2: 102 - 102 (0)

It writes a lot of nonsense.

Transcript_FB1: 58 - 58 (0)

ute Qualität

Transcript_FI2: 124 - 124 (0)

and with open prompting. This is not so reliable,

Transcript_FI1: 28 - 28 (0)

I would say we always have to double check it, of course. So, in my case it's just the LinkedIn post, but I know that also it's used to create a draft for brochures, for example.

Trancript_E2: 69 - 69 (0)

Perceived AI disadvantages > In-accurate or unreliable outputs > because this AI generation
Poor video and image quality > doesn't always, alright, hit all the spots.

Transcript_HR1: 54 - 54 (0)

Perceived AI disadvantages > Incompatibility with complex or experts' content

But communication, our communication is really reduced to...first, limited because we obliged to do so, and then very much focused on facts. Yeah, on medical evidence. That's the that's the most important term. We have to be super safe that we don't promote any information, so, if we're allowed at all, without any or there is without-

Transcript_P1: 28 - 28 (0)

FB2: Would you? Would you trust AI? I'm. I'm not sure. I don't know. The thing is, you know, there are certain things you have to put on. For example, contents of anything that could be people could be allergic to.

Transcript_FB2: 206 - 206 (0)

FI2: Ja ein sehr hoher Wert ist natürlich, dass die Leute uns vertrauen, dass wir medizinische Informationen, die wir veröffentlichen, dass es sich hundertprozentig darauf verlassen können, dass diese auch wirklich stimmen, also Tipps zu Impfungen, zu Medikamenten und so weiter, dass diese wirklich genauso gut sind, wie wenn sie von einem Arzt kommen.

Transcript_FI2: 68 - 68 (0)

Perceived AI disadvantages >
Audience rejection of AI's generated content

but also it didn't land that well with our audience.

Transcript_E1: 66 - 66 (0)

Ethical risks and issues

HR2: So, the process how we start... basically I mean... we always create a text depending maybe in German or sometimes in English. If we get something from the holding, we have it in English and then we translate it or

we see what we need, what languages we need. But usually we need French, German, Italian and English. The other four languages, so I say, "hey ChatGPT", but I prove first that there's no confidential data in it. If there's something that's not supposed to go online or we are working in a people's business. So, we always have to be very careful about the data of the people. So we check if we can go out. And then I really implement into ChatGPT and say, "Hey, can you please translate it please?"

Be aware that there are special needs in the Swiss German language, and I'm also the French and Switzerland is different. Please take that into consideration." So always also a bit of training-

Transcript_HR2: 34 - 34 (0)

HR2: Mm hmm. Yeah, sure. One of the main things is that we basically see it as enrichment, right? We see it as an opportunity to really elevate communication to a new level and to... just as I said, simplify routine tasks and yeah, focus more on the strategic work, but we definitely see a challenge

in transparency, transparency and responsibility? Definitely. Also how you... Yeah. How you want to position yourself as company, of course. I mean, we are in the people's business as an HR company, and we are using tools and not people. What we really claim for is what we stand for, right? That we want to give people work and now we use AI to replace people's work so. That is, of course, something that is always in discussion and that we always look into, and we see... I have to say that we don't, we don't lose people, but we see how people can transform.

Transcript_HR2: 48 - 48 (0)

HR2: And that's really something that is nice to see. But of course, it's a responsibility where you have to look into and that you don't replace, that you also don't lose your quality standards there.

Transcript_HR2: 50 - 50 (0)

HR2: And yeah, that you really make sure that the job security is

still given that you don't say, "Hey, we have ChatGPT now and we don't need you anymore."

Transcript_HR2: 52 - 52 (0)

HR2: Well, the most important thing is really the thing about the job. Security the job transformation, yeah.

PM: OK.

HR2: And in second place, I would say transparency and trustworthiness.

PM: Transparency. What do you mean more specifically?

HR2: With the content for me, for my standards, and that's what I try to go out with them, also for the company and the brand of course-

PM: Mm hmm.

HR2: -I want to go out with high quality information. I want to inform the people our target group is used to content that really gives them-

PM: Yes.

HR2: -How do you say Mehrwert?
Yes, exactly gives them value
and-

PM: Yeah, more value, yeah.

Transcript_HR2: 58 - 67 (0)

HR2: -Teaches them things in the best case and shows them that we have expertise that we can transform. And if I now give that responsibility to AI and then go out with maybe information that is not on that level, and I am still claiming that the brand is known for something on a high level and people trust us. I think we have to keep that standard up and with AI of course you have to have guidelines and everything in place that this is still given. So that's also something what I mean with transparency, if you if you say "We use AI tools to create content". Yes, you can say that, and you have to claim that on websites, right? You have to say "Hey, this is created by AI", but I think that's a bit of an easy way out. So, for me it's also-

Transcript_HR2: 68 - 68 (0)

HR2: Mostly agree. Some people use it more randomly and I would say less carefully, but then they know that there will be a review process by me so.

Transcript_HR2: 74 - 74 (0)

HR2: -Of course, we are trying to be a very human focused and that we, yeah, take our values very seriously. So, there are already the baseline is already in that direction. So, people have the same mindset. But of course, you still see mailings that are created completely by AI and then it's going out and you say, "OK, yes, but maybe next time-

Transcript_HR2: 78 - 78 (0)

HR1: Well, I think it's it. There are different ways, right on. On the one hand side, I think many people are faster. But on the other hand, also the quality is getting worse if it's not corrected right?

So, you see that many just re-search with these tools, with AI tools and do not research, do the Google Research anymore. So, without really checking the sources -

Transcript_HR1: 30 - 30 (0)

HR1: - And I think this is dangerous. So sometimes it's also the quality that is not guaranteed. And I think it's super important that also if you use AI tools, you check the sources and you make sure that you own the message and you own the AI tool or not that the AI tool owns you because it's dangerous because, yeah, you still should be in control -

Transcript_HR1: 32 - 32 (0)

HR1: Well, let's say for example, we have a speech for someone, and I formulated it, or somebody formulated it in a in a text, right? And then I'm saying "oh, wow. This is not really nice, not really practical for the speaker, so let's make bullets out of it." So, I put it into Copilot for example, and ask

“hey, please rewrite this speech, but in bullet points.” And then it's very fast. It's done and it would take me like half an hour or 15 minutes to do it myself and like that, it's done. Let's say I still need like these 10 minutes because I have to review it. The thing is, if I don't review it, I think I really need to be transparent and tell “OK this is the original text and this is the DeepL translation, or this is the DeepL or ChatGPT or Copilot short version”. Like, I think it's important to say, “OK I can translate, I don't have time, but I can send you the AI generated version so please check it”. Yeah.

Transcript_HR1: 36 - 36 (0)

HR1: - Additional idea, what could be interesting, it can help you formulate a little bit differently. It can give you variations and more creativity sometimes, but I think it's still super important that we don't let us drive by AI, but first think ourselves detached from AI and make a concept and think of what, what makes sense and yeah.

Transcript_HR1: 50 - 50 (0)

HR1: Well. You know, and they at *[COMPANY NAME]*, the ethical challenge is mainly in the HR recruitment field. It's not directly communications. It's really about if you have an AI that goes through applications, how much can be automated and how not. And I think they're the principle is the same as in communication is super important that that there is a human involved, and that human leads the tool. And you need really to have an ideal collaboration between tool and human to have a good outcome. So, AI can always be biased, can always is always based on past learnings that can be wrong. So, if you have an AI supporting you in the recruitment processes, it's important to own it. And in communication... well. Let's see. I think it's dangerous if you have like an AI tool getting independent that is not controlled anymore by humans. So, a chat bot or an AI answering machine. But you can always build it in a way that is fine, right? If you say, OK, these are the sources based on those, the machine can answer, then it's fine if you if you just insert a Q&A and it's based on that or some additional sources. Then it's fine, but

as long as you own the content and know what it's based on it's fine. And in in communication, you know there will be also more and more tools to improve. Images. Videos. All this stuff and the question is "What is authenticity and what is not so?" There are many photo shootings' costs that you can save if you have just 1-2 pictures and the rest is like AI, generate the background. I think it's super important that then you name the source and tell "OK, this was based on a shooting and yeah, that's the background". I think Mango [*clothing brand, not related to HR1's company*] generated some.

Transcript_HR1: 52 - 52 (0)

HR1: - Pictures with the AI that, but officially, you know, transparently announced it. But also I have... we have employees that have like privately this ChatGPT 4 or other image AI tools and generate pictures for their social media posts with AI that they use for you know advertising jobs, and you know it's always difficult there is no real reason to say why it's not OK because it's sometimes

really fun right? I think it's for example they put it in a, let's say it's a brand from Schaffhausen and they put it like with the Rhine in the background, with the Munot, you know some local recognizable assets and then at the it's a marketing job. Then you see some marketing formula or things like that. So, it's cool, why not? But then you see some details that are completely wrong and then you need... then I tell "OK, maybe just make sure that here there is a mistake that this is not because this AI generation doesn't always, alright, hit all the spots. So, you have to be attentive. But I think it's fun. But I always tell, "OK, if you do this, please write <It has been AI generated> and also include the tool you have been generated. This was so it has been included. It has been done with ChatGPT4 or something like that.

Transcript_HR1: 54 - 54 (0)

HR1: It's difficult, so in communication we had like AI workshop and the company that completely forbid to use AI in communication, for example in videos, because you can have tools that go over

videos and cut out the ähms, oohs, or you know and it's quite cool. So, the question is how much it needs to be perfect, how much does it need to be authentic. And I think some authenticity-

Transcript_HR1: 56 - 56 (0)

HR1: Not that I can think of. You know, it's really based on generative AI. It's just, for example, we have on social media, or you know if you have people that don't speak all languages, they use it more and more, also ChatGPT to translate. And where I am concerned is if we start to use this thing for internal data and you cannot control this. The system puts it in a machine that learns and... if the competition does it as well, maybe it will help us as well, but it's not, you know, it's just you cannot control it 100%. You will never be able to, but AI is such a fast thing and its tonnes of maybe internal data that land in those counts that you cannot control anymore. This is something that makes me afraid because I think... I'm convinced that many people put in, also at work, a lot of things that they shouldn't and that

they don't even know they shouldn't.

Transcript_HR1: 62 - 62 (0)

P2: No, it's mainly text, and we think it's it also needs to be authentic. So, we want to show employees in our videos, and we also have our picture database for the corporate design and corporate identity. This is produced with real human beings and real photographers.

Transcript_P2: 49 - 49 (0)

P2: Yeah, I think of course in terms of intellectual property, so.

PM: Mm hmm.

P2: I think there are tools like Perplexity for example.

PM: Yeah.

P2: Where you always have to source. Also, Copilot is giving you the source, so I think it's extremely important that we are not stealing-

PM: Yes.

P2: -Content from...that is protected, for example, and reusing that and then taking this as yours. That's one of the yeah, of the risks there is.

Transcript_P2: 53 - 59 (0)

P2: This is a corporate guideline we have there because this is also dangerous when we share data about our company that is confidential, for example. So, yeah, there are huge guidelines about that from our data governance team. So, this we have, which is common sense, and we also educate all the employees,

including the communication department-

Transcript_P2: 65 - 65 (0)

P2: How to use the data. Because the tools I mean this is yeah this is developing so fast.

Transcript_P2: 69 - 69 (0)

P2: -Rights or wrongs. That is, yeah, it's a machine at the end, and the content comes from somewhere and it can be pretty much wrong. Even though Copilot tells you it's right. So.

Transcript_P2: 81 - 81 (0)

P2: I don't know, I mean. I think it's yeah; it is highly regulated. So, you need to be aware of how you use it. But I think this is also in other sectors. So, I was working

before in the energy sector, it was very similar.

Transcript_P2: 115 - 115 (0)

P1: -In every territory we are active, so have to compliant with a huge number of different jurisdictions, and this of course is a challenge for the whole communication team, to generate content. So, we are rely...So, first we have to be, as a principle, very limited in our communication. So especially I think we have to distinguish between financial or nowadays non-financial disclosures we are obliged to do, and then of course next to this there's corporate communication in terms of PR and marketing and promotion. And as I said, as we are active in a highly regulated environment...so, it's the space of Medtech and healthcare, we have to rely very much on expertise on subject experts.

Transcript_P1: 26 - 26 (0)

P1: And therefore, that's basically the reason why we are not, in terms of communication, using AI, of course, maybe there are other technical areas and spaces in our company and in finance and maybe in development and then technology and R&D and operations, of course, we have plenty of efforts to increase efficiency. But communication, our communication is really reduced to...first, limited because we obliged to do so, and then very much focused on facts. Yeah, on medical evidence. That's the that's the most important term. We have to be super safe that we don't promote any information, so, if we're allowed at all, without any or there is without-

Transcript_P1: 28 - 28 (0)

P1: -Also, to secure cybersecurity and data privacy and data protection, so that the business and the content we are generating and all these requests we are sending to this tool are within protected boundaries.

Transcript_P1: 44 - 44 (0)

P1: I would say... so, everything that is highly relevant to our products and the safety of our products and the safety of our users... so, we should not rely on AI based content or information. Outside of this or next to this, I think especially in the field of capital market communication, so we could. So, we are using it. As I said, to make some high-level analysis to generate also, to analyze maybe a sentiment, so what's going out? What's going on in our industry? What is happening? -

Transcript_P1: 46 - 46 (0)

P1: I think there are plenty of risks, first of all the risk of giving some insights outside, for what reason ever...there the tools are very powerful but quite... let's say... you know generic and universal platforms, that of course could misuse every entry, data entry. Second of course we have to be aware of is.... as a very responsible company and value-based company, the footprint behind it, it is a super energy intensive business, at least the technology available today. Hopefully we still see improvement, but basically one data centre requires one nuclear power plant, which is tremendous.

Transcript_P1: 50 - 50 (0)

P1: And then of course, we have to be aware that AI is, in terms of

output dangerous., Yeah. So of course, depending on the tool and depending on specification and of course and also depending on the on the prompt and the data input... but yeah there is no, you don't have any safety or security about the output. So you have always to challenges, especially in terms of communications, yeah.

Transcript_P1: 52 - 52 (0)

P1: -Outside. We have to be very reflected for which and what purpose we are using it. Therefore, for the time being...I'm quite happy about how we handle it and how we do it, because it is limited. We try to take benefit, but on the other hand we are not... we don't want to be depending on AI, and I think this is again a big challenge.

Transcript_P1: 56 - 56 (0)

P1: Of course, privacy, data privacy and so, if anything, if any, legal data breach might be... can be very painful for us. And we are handling very private information. So, we are active in the in the Medtech industry, and Medtech today of course is connected. So, we are offering our devices are connected to cloud solutions, so.... and cybersecurity is key to us. I think this is one very major concern, one major concern. And... of course, exchange compliance. Maybe any data that should be... that could be considered as an insider information...get outside and I would say first maybe finally data, data ownership. You know data ownership.

Transcript_P1: 58 - 58 (0)

P1: Is. We this is our daily business and we do this in every process and our processes. We have to be able to validate it. And I think that this is the same for AI. And of course this is difficult because by definition AI is not based on rules. So, an AI process is... I don't know, from from a theoretical point of view, how it would be possible to validate? But I would say, to take this on a corporate level is very important. Instead of every department or every person, every individual has AI, I don't know... a different way to deal with it and using apps on a personal smartphone instead of working, so working outside the system. I think this we should minimise... maybe we should block it, we should avoid it at all. And we should... we have to force the people to work within the system with tools that are at least maybe in in, in a sense, validated. That means we establish... we approve certain systems, and everybody has to use it. And then

of course, then we can add certain processes and documentation and handbooks. I think this is definitely the way we should go. I don't know by heart if this is already foreseen, but by the way, this is an excellent input, and I will pass it on.

Transcript_P1: 64 - 64 (0)

FB2: OK, so it's important to explain one thing with regards to the implementation of AI within [COMPANY'S NAME]. So we... like other companies as well, we have a lot of things which are confidential, which we don't want to share with a wider audience. I mean if you take the annual report, we could not have shared it yesterday, we couldn't share it. Today it's public and so we can share if we can put it on ChatGPT, whatever it may be because it's public knowledge but a lot of other things-

Transcript_FB2: 28 - 28 (0)

FB2: Because when you input something in AI, you have to be a little bit careful of unconscious bias. And it's really easy to have these biases without knowing. So, for example, if you write in the prompts, "He has to have 10 years of experience and he has to have this and he has to have that", AI might assume that because you wrote "he" all the time... and you know, we write "he" just to write something. You could also write "she", doesn't matter as long as you're consistent. And then the machine might just say, "OK-

PM: Yes. Yes, yes, yes, yes.

FB2: If it's a woman, then out, because this person wants a male, obviously", even though you might not want that, you know. So, AI of course is great. I mean, a great tool and it will be, I was

going to say it will be the future, but it's actually now the present. But you still have to keep an eye on it because one of the most difficult things to do is what prompts to give to AI so how can you make it that-

Transcript_FB2: 58 - 60 (0)

FB2: -Any normal person would say save the child, but the robot of course doesn't know that. And this is where you have a little bit of a, you know you need the human elements to come into it.

Transcript_FB2: 68 - 68 (0)

FB2: You also have to be a little bit on the on the, on the careful side when it comes to jobs.

PM: Mm hmm.

FB2: So do you get a chatbot to replace the customer service reception? Because a chatbot will do an equally good job. And this is where you have to look at things. I was in the UK a very long time ago. With this, I mean there was a colleague. I was sitting down saying someone was in the back. I could hear a colleague, and she was speaking to a customer.

PM: Mm hmm.

FB2: And this customer had a problem which wasn't directly related to the products, but she helped her anyway, and it was a bit more of a personal thing, which I was quite happily surprised about, because it was, it turned out... it was an old woman, and she couldn't do something.

PM: Yes.

FB2: -Which was only semi-related and of course a chatbot wouldn't do that. So, would you,

you know?, be OK with job losses to replace them with chatbots, is that is that a good thing ethically, but also the term of the service that is provided? You've been on... I'm sure because of probably what you're studying on these chatbots, sometimes you have to go through 1000 [*of chatbots, referring to customer service-related situations*] in some companies, a 1000 of really annoying-

Transcript_FB2: 76 - 82 (0)

FB2: I think it's cool. Yeah, I'm not. I'm not a big fan of that person. But so, I don't even... I've never even used it and then I won't. And one reason why I wouldn't use that for example, is because that has no restrictions.

PM: Yeah, me neither.

FB2: It will give you the answer, however racist, however morally and ethically wrong it will give you

the answer, and you won't might say, "Well, that's good for freedom of-

Transcript_FB2: 118 - 120 (0)

FB2: Of course. You know there are limitations. That's why we don't in today's world, we don't use the N word for example, because it's just wrong to do it. But that system probably... I don't know, it probably would, because it doesn't... it's not told "Hey, you can't use these words". So, the thing is-

Transcript_FB2: 124 - 124 (0)

FB2: -You know, getting our people to learn how to use the AI tools properly and also... of course this goes for myself too, when I'm prompting I'm not very politically correct, to be honest with you. Maybe because I'm a bit older

and that's OK. But you know, in certain cases it's not OK. So, then you need to be careful. So, you need to educate people and yourself in using these tools properly and as they're meant to be used and it's good to you know, do a bit of a trial-and-error thing till you till you actually together but that is a concern. That is a quite a big concern. Because people could also go outside and share things which are not supposed to share, you know.

Transcript_FB2: 126 - 126 (0)

FB2: If there's an overreliance on AI you could go into issues.

Transcript_FB2: 128 - 128 (0)

FB2: What is it, compliance with laws? So of course, anything we do needs to be within the law.

You, you know you can't do anything which is outside the law.

Transcript_FB2: 182 - 182 (0)

FB2: And I wonder if this is, you know, and even just doing that you need to make sure that, you know, things are done properly. I don't know if you see some of the Chinese product translations sometimes. It's comical. But the thing is if you if you're dealing with whatever it is, I don't know, a pen knife it's one thing. But if you're dealing with baby food, it's another thing you can't mess around you. You know, you can't have some of the-.

PM: Yeah, yeah. There was no one, yes. Yes.

FB2: -Own products descriptions which I mean this is terrible, you know? So. So I assume that's where it would go.

Transcript_FB2: 216 - 218 (0)

FB1: If they're going to invent, it's going to invent something. So, I have my trust issues.

Transcript_FB1: 62 - 62 (0)

FB1: Yes, because I don't know how you say that in English...In German we call it "Geschwurbel". It's like a lot of hot air. Like, it sounds fantastic. But once you read, it's not saying anything. So ChatGPT is really good at that.

Transcript_FB1: 64 - 64 (0)

FB1: So, I had to go through this process of having to read and having to write. Yeah, I think young people don't go through that process anymore because you have ChatGPT at hand. There are so many ways to take a shortcut, which I personally think for developing young minds... it's really bad because I think it's very important for a young mind to go through... I'm repeating myself...

through the process of reading, thinking, processing, and writing. It's a whole... it's a whole process which is not existent if you start using AI.

Transcript_FB1: 76 - 76 (0)

FB1: How will you know that the output is correct? You... like when I was telling you, I can control it. I know how to control it. But because I learned it from scratch, I am very much afraid that we are growing into a society who doesn't really know. Or think enough for themselves and relies only on the output of ChatGPT, which makes people very manipulative [*probably meaning "manipulated"*] to whoever runs the AI.

Transcript_FB1: 80 - 80 (0)

FB1: Yeah. Well, we discuss, we discuss a lot at work, this problem of AI. We are kind of teaching AI by consulting AI... and many people are getting the same output, it's kind of. Even if it's a mistake or it's not a mistake, it's like you're

reproducing the same storyline over and over again. Which is very dangerous and that's where my other point of view comes back in. You don't have enough knowledge to criticize it. Because you don't have, you haven't accumulated enough knowledge to be able to criticize it.

Transcript_FB1: 86 - 86 (0)

FB1: Looking into the future and bringing it back to where I started. I start to wonder if ChatGPT or certain AI should have, like an age, like what? At what age? You should be able to start using it, and in universities and school. Because otherwise ..., as "man auf Deutsch sagen würde, schaffen wir uns selbst ab" but not in a good way, because ChatGPT can pretend to be to have humanity and be social. But that's bullshit. It's just programmed to do it. It can switch in another direction just as quickly, if you program it. So having to rely on AI without questioning it, without being critical about it ... I think that's a real big danger and I think many people don't know how to use it

properly. Because it seems so easy.

Transcript_FB1: 140 - 140 (0)

FI2: Ja, das ist bei unserer Branche sicher speziell, wir haben sehr strenge Auflagen seitens der regulierenden Behörde, weil wir sehr hochsensible Gesundheitsdaten bei uns verarbeiten, auch die Kunden-Kommunikation enthält natürlich teilweise sehr sensible Informationen über die psychische oder physische Gesundheit dieser Kundinnen und Kunden.

PM: Ja.

FI2: Und die dürfen natürlich keinesfalls irgendwie ins World Wide Web gelangen

Transcript_FI2: 42 - 44 (0)

FI2: Und deshalb müssen wir diese abgegrenzten Lösungen

verwenden, und auch dort dürfen die sensiblen Sachen... die dürfen gar nicht hochgeladen werden. Es ist natürlich schwierig, das zu kontrollieren, vor allem, weil wir eine sehr dezentrale Organisation sind. Mit etwa 60 Standorten in der Schweiz.

Transcript_FI2: 46 - 46 (0)

FI2: Mhm. Ja, da müsste... das ist ein bisschen ein Blick in die Glaskugel, oder? Aber ich höre natürlich von gewissen Kollegen, dass die Prozesse schon viel, viel automatisierter sind.

Transcript_FI2: 54 - 54 (0)

FI2: Und ja, um den gewissen Effizienzgewinn zu erzielen, muss man natürlich immer mehr auch vertrauen, dass sie diese Sachen so produziert. Und ja, man muss

ja den Kauf, den Control-
leraufwand dann irgendwann
zurückfahren können, und ich
habe dieses Vertrauen noch nicht
so ganz muss ich ehrlich sagen.

PM: OK.

FI2: Ich glaube, es braucht es
diese menschliche Kontrolle un-
bedingt, um sicherzustellen, dass
nicht etwas kommuniziert wird,
dass am Schluss nicht Unterneh-
menswerten entspricht, und ja,
ich meine, es ist sehr schwer ein-
zuschätzen, mit welchen Daten
also eine solche KI dann nach
wirklich trainiert worden ist, und
ob da nicht doch etwas einfließen,
dass man vielleicht nicht drin
haben will

Transcript_FI2: 56 - 58 (0)

FI2: Ja ein sehr hoher Wert ist na-
türlich, dass die Leute uns ver-
trauen, dass wir medizinische In-
formationen, die wir veröffentlichen,

dass es sich hundertprozentig darauf verlassen können, dass diese auch wirklich stimmen, also Tipps zu Impfungen, zu Medikamenten und so weiter, dass diese wirklich genauso gut sind, wie wenn sie von einem Arzt kommen.

Transcript_F12: 68 - 68 (0)

F12: Und ja, wir werden wir werden sicher differenzieren, je nach Art von Kommunikation, wie stark KI zum Einsatz kommen kann. Also ich habe vorhin schon angesprochen, beispielsweise zur Generierung von Kurztönen für Social Media ist sicher ein sehr effizientes Werkzeug und da haben wir.... das ist klar.... da kann man es anwenden, hingegen für längere Beiträge, Fachbeiträge, die Autorentexte sind und dann auch ins gedruckte Kundenmagazin kommen da besteht schon die Erwartung, dass man die auch wirklich noch

selber schreibt. Und KI dort vielleicht mehr als Inspiration nutzen? Für Formulierungsvorschläge, für Rechercheaufgaben, für Themen zu meinem Thema gesamtheitlich zu erfassen, ist man es... für diese Zwecke mehr einsetzt und weniger jetzt für die Schreiarbeit an sich.

Transcript_FI2: 84 - 84 (0)

as komplette Potenzial dieser neuen Technologien noch gar nicht so ganz abschliessend abschätzbar ist.

PM: Mhm.

FI2: Ich denke, das ist ein ongoing process, und das wird uns noch die nächsten Jahre ganz sicher beschäftigen, und ich denke auch eine Lösung, die jetzt vielleicht für dieses Jahr gut ist, muss nächstes Jahr vielleicht

schon wieder überdacht werden,
weil man neue Möglichkeiten

Transcript_FI2: 112 - 114 (0)

Ja, so etwas, ich weiss gar nicht,
wie ich das ausdrücken soll. Das
ist so authentisch klingt so eine
gewisse Handschrift hat, oder?

Transcript_FI2: 128 - 128 (0)

F11: This means that that it is a
controlled ad option. If you use
Copilot, it depends on the prompt
you use...you can use a prompt,
shorten the text and he does it,
but he does it in a manner which
is not reliable. Maybe it might be
good, and you can... I always say
“In Copilot is like... it is absolutely
important from the ethical side to
have a human-

Transcript_FI1: 16 - 16 (0)

F11: I think that there are some challenges that need to be addressed. If we look at the ethical challenges at first and that's how we mitigate principally all the ethical approaches is... we need to control by a human. I mean, depending on the models, models have biases. Because they're trained with historic data, so if historic data, for example, has issues with discrimination, I mean, this is nowadays lived otherwise than it used to be 1020 years ago, but the LLM has texts...historical texts. And we know that that it is the job of a statistical system, with these LLMs, even the new ones that, yeah...they try to mitigate some ethical challenges, but they can't do all of them because yeah, as I said it's statistics. So, if you say for example "Give me a text for [meaning: *about*] a person that is absolutely intelligent". It might be that there are only common examples of men, because historic data is full of these kinds of

texts, and therefore you need to proofread what comes out and to check it on these kinds of elements.

Transcript_F11: 34 - 34 (0)

F11: There are issues but, but I think it's not ones that are more relevant because we are a financial institution and as I say it, it depends on the kind of text you do. I mean, what's the, what's the public and who is at adressant, and is there no biases in it, or...yeah, things like these questions need to be posed. I mean, there's just something, but it's just this is more... Well, it might be addressed in the ethical part. We say to our employees "If you don't redigate [meaning: *edit*] the text mostly, if you don't change a lot of things we expect you to put in a remark saying this has been created with the help of AI. This is this is mainly relevant in sense of using images, I mean this is not in

the field of communication primarily, but yeah if we would use... but we don't... we for example clearly decided not to use AI generated pictures of humans because we we're a company saying we want to be close to the people. So, we want to show real people but we for example use AI to generate ideas-

Transcript_F11: 40 - 40 (0)

F11: We do have for the usage of Copilot. I mean there, there we put on a small set of rules which we defined in a in a cross functional team. And this... is but his is mainly addressing things like data protection. It is things like what kind of information you can use. For example, we don't use any data of persons versus LLMs. We have some information that we say "Well, check on legitimacy and freeing text of discrimination. So, proof on that directly. Yeah, we have some kind of telling them

when to mark, if it's Gen AI generated content. Yes. So, these are some rules we define and which we also train the people.

Transcript_FI1: 44 - 44 (0)

E2: I think it's always a challenge to avoid misinformation, false information. To also, if we use ChatGPT or AI to really be aware that we...do not trust the source, so we have to double check and therefore, I think the use is still limited because you still have to have some experts or professionals double checking the content and also fake news.

Trancript_E2: 75 - 75 (0)

E2: The fake news is a big part, I would say and. Yeah, out of this... sometimes I see ethical challenges. It's not ethical, but also it's a challenge because the texts are very plain and always the same.

So, I think from a language point of view-

Trascript_E2: 77 - 77 (0)

E2: If I see for example, I am thrilled, or we are thrilled to announce I know already that's AI.

Trascript_E2: 87 - 87 (0)

E2: Mm hmm. Yeah, yeah, I think it's. I think they're aware that they will use it more and more and then misuse the data protection. The topic like, yeah, "How we can avoid data getting stolen". That's a big point. I would say which, which is something they have to balance and to find a solution between. Yeah.

Trascript_E2: 107 - 107 (0)

E2: Then, ChatGPT maybe responds based on outdated or biased data. Number two, share the insights, share your ideas and insights about ChatGPT with your colleagues. And number three, be responsible, use ChatGPT to increase your productivity, but be mindful how you use AI generated content. Number four learn and experiment. Use ChatGPT as a tool for learning and experimentation. So, there are also some don'ts. AI can be wrong. Point 1. Point two. proper permission.

Transcript_E2: 115 - 115 (0)

E1: Yeah. Yeah, we don't at the moment, we have an internal policy that we don't, I think, and this maybe comes into like the ethical perspective of a lot because it is using pictures that are not our own. But we are working on a tool that will be doing it. So, we will be able to do image generation with [COMPANY'S NAME] internal

pictures. So, it is in progress. We don't know when it's going to start, but we have seen some results, and it looks fantastic. So, if that's going to work soon, I'm very excited, yeah.

Transcript_E1: 28 - 28 (0)

E1: Mm hmm. I think one of the parts is that, well, it is taking information from somewhere. So, we do know that. And I think when it comes to copy, it's not necessarily the most disturbing part, but I think what I mentioned before with the image generation when you know that the image you now receive is part of many images, I think that's where... yeah, copywriting and copyrights. Copyright infringement, that type of thing is a huge problem and I think that's where ethical discussions have to go or already are happening.

Transcript_E1: 34 - 34 (0)

E1: I think one thing that we discuss a lot is, well the output and the information that you sometimes receive is faulty. I think that it's very important to not trust the information and the output unless you already have put the input in, if that makes sense. There's a lot of mistakes that happen regarding facts and things like that, and I think that's the main part for us. To always fact-check.

Transcript_E1: 40 - 40 (0)

E1: So, one of the things is always "How? How well do we know at all?" I think that that's more on the global perspective though, when they decide on what tools we're able to use specifically. But I do know they always check. What's happening with our data? What's happening

with our inputs? I think that's a big, big part as well. And we're also not able to use all the information and all the tools. I think that's also very important. So, we have different classifications for different tools. So, I think when it comes to scenarios on what we want to work with and not want to work with it? First, yeah, what's happening with our data. Second of all, is it useful for our use case? And how is the output? I think that's the most important ones.

Transcript_E1: 52 - 52 (0)

E1: -It didn't seem real, and I think right now you're still able to tell if an image is AI generated to a certain extent. I know there's like really good models that you wouldn't know, but yeah, it didn't land that well.

Transcript_E1: 68 - 68 (0)

E1: And also, about different companies, I think which is watching very carefully on what's happening in the market as well. I know, like recently with the development of DeepSeek and what that means. Then again for the political environment, I think that is also something we have to watch. Yeah.

Transcript_E1: 72 - 72 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Unreliability of outputs

HR2: And that's really something that is nice to see. But of course, it's a responsibility where you have to look into and that you don't replace, that you also don't lose your quality standards there.

Transcript_HR2: 50 - 50 (0)

HR2: Well, the most important thing is really the thing about the job. Security the job transformation, yeah.

PM: OK.

HR2: And in second place, I would say transparency and trustworthiness.

PM: Transparency. What do you mean more specifically?

HR2: With the content for me, for my standards, and that's what I try to go out with them, also for the company and the brand of course-

PM: Mm hmm.

HR2: -I want to go out with high quality information. I want to inform the people our target group is used to content that really gives them-

PM: Yes.

HR2: -How do you say Mehrwert? Yes, exactly gives them value and-

PM: Yeah, more value, yeah.

Transcript_HR2: 58 - 67 (0)

nd if I now give that responsibility to AI and then go out with maybe information that is not on that level, and I am still claiming that the brand is known for something on a high level and people trust us. I think we have to keep that standard up and with AI of course you have to have guidelines and everything in place that this is still given

Transcript_HR2: 68 - 68 (0)

But then you see some details that are completely wrong and then you need... then I tell "OK, maybe just make sure that here there is a mistake t

Transcript_HR1: 54 - 54 (0)

it can be pretty much wrong.

Transcript_P2: 81 - 81 (0)

P1: And then of course, we have to be aware that AI is, in terms of output dangerous., Yeah. So of course, depending on the tool and

depending on specification and of course and also depending on the on the prompt and the data input... but yeah there is no, you don't have any safety or security about the output. So you have always to challenges, especially in terms of communications, yeah.

Transcript_P1: 52 - 52 (0)

FB1: If they're going to invent, it's going to invent something. So, I have my trust issues.

Transcript_FB1: 62 - 62 (0)

FB1: Yes, because I don't know how you say that in English...In German we call it "Geschwurbel". It's like a lot of hot air. Like, it sounds fantastic. But once you read, it's not saying anything. So ChatGPT is really good at that.

Transcript_FB1: 64 - 64 (0)

We are kind of teaching AI by consulting AI... and many people are getting the same output, it's kind of. Even if it's a mistake or it's not a mistake, it's like you're reproducing the same storyline over and over again. Which is very dangerous and that's where my other point of view comes back in.

Transcript_FB1: 86 - 86 (0)

muss man natürlich immer mehr auch vertrauen, dass sie diese Sachen so produziert. Und ja, man muss ja den Kauf, den Controlleraufwand dann irgendwann zurückfahren können, und ich habe dieses Vertrauen noch nicht so ganz muss ich ehrlich sagen.

PM: OK.

FI2: Ich glaube, es braucht es diese menschliche Kontrolle unbedingt, um sicherzustellen, dass nicht etwas kommuniziert wird, dass am Schluss nicht Unternehmenswerten entspricht,

Transcript_FI2: 56 - 58 (0)

If you use Copilot, it depends on the prompt you use...you can use a prompt, shorten the text and he does it, but he does it in a manner which is not reliable. Maybe it might be good, and you can...

Transcript_FI1: 16 - 16 (0)

but also it's a challenge because the texts are very plain and always the same

Trancript_E2: 77 - 77 (0)

E1: I think one thing that we discuss a lot is, well the output and the information that you sometimes receive is faulty. I think that it's very important to not trust the information and the output unless you already have put the input in, if that makes sense. There's a lot

of mistakes that happen regarding facts and things like that, and I think that's the main part for us. To always fact-check.

Transcript_E1: 40 - 40 (0)

Second of all, is it useful for our use case? And how is the output? I think that's the most important ones.

Transcript_E1: 52 - 52 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Unreliability of outputs > Outputs' incompatibility with company's values

HR2: Well, the most important thing is really the thing about the job. Security the job transformation, yeah.

PM: OK.

HR2: And in second place, I would say transparency and trustworthiness.

PM: Transparency. What do you mean more specifically?

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to go out with them, also for the company and the brand of course-

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Transcript_FI2: 58 - 58 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Unreliability of outputs > Faulty outputs

HR2: And that's really something that is nice to see. But of course, it's a responsibility where you have to look into and that you don't replace, that you also don't lose your quality standards there.

Transcript_HR2: 50 - 50 (0)

But then you see some details that are completely wrong and then you need... then I tell "OK, maybe just make sure that here there is a mistake that this is not because this AI generation doesn't always, alright, hit all the spots.

Transcript_HR1: 54 - 54 (0)

it can be pretty much wrong.

Transcript_P2: 81 - 81 (0)

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Transcript_FI2: 56 - 56 (0)

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Transcript_FI1: 16 - 16 (0)

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Transcript_E1: 40 - 40 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Unreliability of outputs > Superficial and repetitive outputs

In German we call it "Geschwurbel". It's like a lot of hot air. Like, it sounds fantastic. But once you

read, it's not saying anything. So ChatGPT is really good at that.

Transcript_FB1: 64 - 64 (0)

Even if it's a mistake or it's not a mistake, it's like you're reproducing the same storyline over and over again. Which is very dangerous

Transcript_FB1: 86 - 86 (0)

but also it's a challenge because the texts are very plain and always the same

Trancript_E2: 77 - 77 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Biases

So, AI can always be biased, can always be always based on past learnings that can be wrong.

Transcript_HR1: 52 - 52 (0)

FB2: Because when you input something in AI, you have to be a

little bit careful of unconscious bias. And it's really easy to have these biases without knowing. So, for example, if you write in the prompts, "He has to have 10 years of experience and he has to have this and he has to have that", AI might assume that because you wrote "he" all the time... and you know, we write "he" just to write something. You could also write "she", doesn't matter as long as you're consistent. And then the machine might just say, "OK-

PM: Yes. Yes, yes, yes, yes.

FB2: If it's a woman, then out, because this person wants a male, obviously", even though you might not want that, you know

Transcript_FB2: 58 - 60 (0)

FB2: Of course. You know there are limitations. That's why we don't in today's world, we don't

use the N word for example, because it's just wrong to do it. But that system probably... I don't know, it probably would, because it doesn't... it's not told "Hey, you can't use these words". So, the thing is-

Transcript_FB2: 124 - 124 (0)

I mean, depending on the models, models have biases. Because they're trained with historic data, so if historic data, for example, has issues with discrimination

Transcript_FI1: 34 - 34 (0)

So, if you say for example "Give me a text for [meaning: *about*] a person that is absolutely intelligent". I

Transcript_FI1: 34 - 34 (0)

ChatGPT maybe responds based on outdated or biased data.

Transcript_E2: 115 - 115 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Biases
> Sexism

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FB2: If it's a woman, then out,

Transcript_FB2: 58 - 60 (0)

you say for example "Give me a text for [meaning: *about*] a person that is absolutely intelligent". It might be that there are only common examples of men

Transcript_FI1: 34 - 34 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Biases
> Discriminatory language

FB2: Of course. You know there are limitations. That's why we don't in today's world, we don't use the N word for example, because it it's just wrong to do it. But

that system probably... I don't know, it probably would, because it doesn't... it's not told "Hey, you can't use these words". So, the thing is-

Transcript_FB2: 124 - 124 (0)

has issues with discrimination

Transcript_F11: 34 - 34 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Lack of control

HR2: Mostly agree. Some people use it more randomly and I would say less carefully, but then they know that there will be a review process by me so.

Transcript_HR2: 74 - 74 (0)

HR1: - And I think this is dangerous. So sometimes it's also the quality that is not guaranteed. And I think it's super important that also if you use AI tools, you check the sources and you make sure that you own the message and you own the AI tool or not that the AI tool owns you because it's

dangerous because, yeah, you still should be in control -

Transcript_HR1: 32 - 32 (0)

ou know it's always difficult there is no real reason to say why it's not OK

Transcript_HR1: 54 - 54 (0)

it's just you cannot control it 100%. You will never be able to, but AI is such a fast thing and its tonnes of maybe internal data that land in those counts that you cannot control anymore.

Transcript_HR1: 62 - 62 (0)

P2: -Rights or wrongs. That is, yeah, it's a machine at the end, and the content comes from somewhere and it can be pretty much wrong.

Transcript_P2: 81 - 81 (0)

our processes. We have to be able to validate it. And I think that this is the same for AI. And of course this is difficult because by definition AI is not based on rules. So, an AI process is... I don't know, from from a theoretical point of view, how it would be possible to validate?

Transcript_P1: 64 - 64 (0)

FB2: I think it's cool. Yeah, I'm not. I'm not a big fan of that person. But so, I don't even... I've never even used it and then I won't. And one reason why I wouldn't use that for example, is because that has no restrictions.

PM: Yeah, me neither.

FB2: It will give you the answer, however racist, however morally and ethically wrong it will give you the answer, and you won't might

say, "Well, that's good for freedom of-

Transcript_FB2: 118 - 120 (0)

F12: Und deshalb müssen wir diese abgegrenzten Lösungen verwenden, und auch dort dürfen die sensiblen Sachen... die dürfen gar nicht hochgeladen werden. Es ist natürlich schwierig, das zu kontrollieren, vor allem, weil wir eine sehr dezentrale Organisation sind. Mit etwa 60 Standorten in der Schweiz.

Transcript_F12: 46 - 46 (0)

F12: Mhm. Ja, da müsste... das ist ein bisschen ein Blick in die Glaskugel, oder? Aber ich höre natürlich von gewissen Kollegen, dass die Prozesse schon viel, viel automatisierter sind.

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PM: Mhm.

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Transcript_FI2: 112 - 114 (0)

do not trust the source,

Trancript_E2: 75 - 75 (0)

So, one of the things is always "How? How well do we know at all?" I think that that's more on the

global perspective though, when they decide on what tools we're able to use specifically. But I do know they always check. What's happening with our data? What's happening with our inputs? I think that's a big, big part as well. And we're also not able to use all the information and all the tools. I think that's also very important. So, we have different classifications for different tools. So, I think when it comes to scenarios on what we want to work with and not want to work with it

Transcript_E1: 52 - 52 (0)

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is also something we have to watch. Yeah.

Transcript_E1: 72 - 72 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Lack of control > AI lacking necessary structural restrictions

it's just you cannot control it 100%. You will never be able to, but AI is such a fast thing and its tonnes of maybe internal data that land in those counts that you cannot control anymore.

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FB2: I think it's cool. Yeah, I'm not. I'm not a big fan of that person. But so, I don't even... I've never even used it and then I won't. And one reason why I wouldn't use that for example, is because that has no restrictions.

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say, "Well, that's good for freedom of-

Transcript_FB2: 118 - 120 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Lack of control > Difficulty in controlling AI use within team members

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Transcript_HR2: 74 - 74 (0)

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Transcript_FI2: 46 - 46 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Lack of control > Uncertainty regarding AI use

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Transcript_P1: 64 - 64 (0)

So, one of the things is always "How? How well do we know at all?"

Transcript_E1: 52 - 52 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Lack of control > Unknown source of information

And I think it's super important that also if you use AI tools, you check the sources

Transcript_HR1: 32 - 32 (0)

If you say, OK, these are the sources based on those, the machine can answer, then it's fine

Transcript_HR1: 52 - 52 (0)

P2: -Rights or wrongs. That is, yeah, it's a machine at the end, and the content comes from somewhere and it can be pretty much wrong.

Transcript_P2: 81 - 81 (0)

do not trust the source,

Trancript_E2: 75 - 75 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Lack of control > Difficulty in determining future challenges

Because the tools I mean this is yeah this is developing so fast.

Transcript_P2: 69 - 69 (0)

Ja, da müsste... das ist ein bisschen ein Blick in die Glaskugel, oder?

Transcript_FI2: 54 - 54 (0)

das komplette Potenzial dieser neuen Technologien noch gar nicht so ganz abschliessend abschätzbar ist.

PM: Mhm.

FI2: Ich denke, das ist ein ongoing process, und das wird uns noch die nächsten Jahre ganz sicher beschäftigen, und ich denke auch eine Lösung, die jetzt vielleicht für dieses Jahr gut ist, muss nächstes Jahr vielleicht schon wieder überdacht werden

Transcript_FI2: 112 - 114 (0)

E1: And also, about different companies, I think which is watching very carefully on what's happening in the market as well. I know, like recently with the development of DeepSeek and what that means. Then again for the political environment, I think that is also something we have to watch. Yeah.

Transcript_E1: 72 - 72 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Manipulation and disinformation

ou make sure that you own the message and you own the AI tool or not that the AI tool owns you

Transcript_HR1: 32 - 32 (0)

We have to be super safe that we don't promote any information, so, if we're allowed at all, without any or there is without-

Transcript_P1: 28 - 28 (0)

But if you're dealing with baby food, it's another thing you can't mess around you. You know, you can't have some of the-

PM: Yeah, yeah. There was no one, yes. Yes.

FB2: -Own products descriptions which I mean this is terrible, you know? So. So I assume that's where it would go

Transcript_FB2: 216 - 218 (0)

r think enough for themselves and relies only on the output of ChatGPT, which makes people very manipulative [*probably meaning "manipulated"*] to whoever runs the AI.

Transcript_FB1: 80 - 80 (0)

ChatGPT can pretend to be to have humanity and be social. But that's bullshit. It's just programmed to do it. It can switch in

another direction just as quickly, if you program it

Transcript_FB1: 140 - 140 (0)

FI2: Ja ein sehr hoher Wert ist natürlich, dass die Leute uns vertrauen, dass wir medizinische Informationen, die wir veröffentlichen, dass es sich hundertprozentig darauf verlassen können, dass diese auch wirklich stimmen, also Tipps zu Impfungen, zu Medikamenten und so weiter, dass diese wirklich genauso gut sind, wie wenn sie von einem Arzt kommen.

Transcript_FI2: 68 - 68 (0)

it's always a challenge to avoid misinformation, false information

Trancript_E2: 75 - 75 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Overreliance on AI tools

it's still super important that we don't let us drive by AI, but first

think ourselves detached from AI and make a concept and think of what, what makes sense

Transcript_HR1: 50 - 50 (0)

e should not rely on AI based content or information.

Transcript_P1: 46 - 46 (0)

we don't want to be depending on AI, and I think this is again a big challenge.

Transcript_P1: 56 - 56 (0)

FB2: If there's an overreliance on AI you could go into issues.

Transcript_FB2: 128 - 128 (0)

FB1: So, I had to go through this process of having to read and having to write. Yeah, I think young people don't go through

that process anymore because you have ChatGPT at hand. There are so many ways to take a shortcut, which I personally think for developing young minds... it's really bad because I think it's very important for a young mind to go through... I'm repeating myself... through the process of reading, thinking, processing, and writing. It's a whole... it's a whole process which is not existent if you start using AI.

Transcript_FB1: 76 - 76 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Legal compliance

P2: I don't know, I mean. I think it's yeah; it is highly regulated. So, you need to be aware of how you use it. But I think this is also in other sectors. So, I was working before in the energy sector, it was very similar.

Transcript_P2: 115 - 115 (0)

so have to compliant with a huge number of different jurisdictions, and this of course is a challenge for the whole communication

team, to generate content. So, we are rely...So, first we have to be, as a principle, very limited in our communication. So especially I think we have to distinguish between financial or nowadays non-financial disclosures we are obliged to do, and then of course next to this there's corporate communication in terms of PR and marketing and promotion. And as I said, as we are active in a highly regulated environment...so, it's the space of Medtech and healthcare, we have to rely very much on expertise on subject experts.

Transcript_P1: 26 - 26 (0)

exchange compliance

Transcript_P1: 58 - 58 (0)

FB2: What is it, compliance with laws? So of course, anything we do needs to be within the law.

You, you know you can't do anything which is outside the law

Transcript_FB2: 182 - 182 (0)

wir haben sehr strenge Auflagen seitens der regulierenden Behörde

Transcript_FI2: 42 - 42 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Environmental issues

e have to be aware of is.... as a very responsible company and value-based company, the footprint behind it, it is a super energy intensive business, at least the technology available today. Hopefully we still see improvement, but basically one data centre requires one nuclear power plant, which is tremendous.

Transcript_P1: 50 - 50 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Data security and cybersecurity

but I prove first that there's no confidential data in it. If there's something that's not supposed to

go online or we are working in a people's business. So, we always have to be very careful about the data of the people.

Transcript_HR2: 34 - 34 (0)

And where I am concerned is if we start to use this thing for internal data and you cannot control this.

Transcript_HR1: 62 - 62 (0)

his is also dangerous when we share data about our company that is confidentialia

Transcript_P2: 65 - 65 (0)

Also, to secure cybersecurity and data privacy and data protectio

Transcript_P1: 44 - 44 (0)

privacy, data privacy and so, if anything, if any, legal data breach

might be... can be very painful for us. And we are handling very private information. So, we are active in the in the Medtech industry, and Medtech today of course is connected. So, we are offering our devices are connected to cloud solutions, so.... and cybersecurity is key to us

Transcript_P1: 58 - 58 (0)

FB2: OK, so it's important to explain one thing with regards to the implementation of AI within [COMPANY'S NAME]. So we... like other companies as well, we have a lot of things which are confidential, which we don't want to share with a wider audience. I mean if you take the annual report, we could not have shared it yesterday, we couldn't share it. Today it's public and so we can share if we can put it on ChatGPT, whatever it may be because it's public knowledge but a lot of other things-

Transcript_FB2: 28 - 28 (0)

Because people could also go outside and share things which are not supposed to share, you know.

Transcript_FB2: 126 - 126 (0)

wir sehr hochsensible Gesundheitsdaten bei uns verarbeiten, auch die Kunden-Kommunikation enthält natürlich teilweise sehr sensible Informationen über die psychische oder physische Gesundheit dieser Kundinnen und Kunden.

PM: Ja.

F12: Und die dürfen natürlich keinesfalls irgendwie ins World Wide Web gelangen.

Transcript_F12: 42 - 44 (0)

his is mainly addressing things like data protection. It is things like what kind of information you can use. For example, we don't use any data of persons versus LLMs

Transcript_F11: 44 - 44 (0)

hey will use it more and more and then misuse the data protection. The topic like, yeah, "How we can avoid data getting stolen". That's a big point. I would say which, which is something they have to balance and to find a solution between

Trancript_E2: 107 - 107 (0)

What's happening with our data? What's happening with our inputs? I think that's a big, big part as well. And we're also not able to use all the information and all the

tools. I think that's also very important. So, we have different classifications for different tools. So, I think when it comes to scenarios on what we want to work with and not want to work with it? First, yeah, what's happening with our data.

Transcript_E1: 52 - 52 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Copyright issues and unclear content ownership

but we definitely see a challenge in transparency, transparency and responsibility?

Transcript_HR2: 48 - 48 (0)

So that's also something what I mean with transparency, if you if you say "We use AI tools to create content". Yes, you can say that, and you have to claim that on websites, right? You have to say "Hey, this is created by AI", but I think that's a bit of an easy way out.

Transcript_HR2: 68 - 68 (0)

The thing is, if I don't review it, I think I really need to be transparent and tell "OK this is the original text and this is the DeepL translation, or this is the DeepL or ChatGPT or Copilot short version".

Transcript_HR1: 36 - 36 (0)

P2: Yeah, I think of course in terms of intellectual property, so.

PM: Mm hmm.

P2: I think there are tools like Perplexity for example.

PM: Yeah.

P2: Where you always have to source. Also, Copilot is giving you the source, so I think it's extremely important that we are not stealing-

PM: Yes.

P2: -Content from...that is protected, for example, and reusing that and then taking this as yours.

Transcript_P2: 53 - 59 (0)

finally data, data ownership. You know data ownership.

Transcript_P1: 58 - 58 (0)

he text mostly, if you don't change a lot of things we expect you to put in a remark saying this has been created with the help of AI. This is this is mainly relevant in sense of using images

Transcript_F11: 40 - 40 (0)

and this maybe comes into like the ethical perspective of a lot because it is using pictures that are not our own.

Transcript_E1: 28 - 28 (0)

Copyright infringement, that type of thing is a huge problem and I think that's where ethical discussions have to go or already are happening

Transcript_E1: 34 - 34 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Perceived authenticity of AI generated content

What we really claim for is what we stand for, right? That we want to give people work and now we use AI to replace people's work so. That is, of course, something that is always in discussion and that we always look into, and we see... I have to say that we don't, we don't lose people, but we see how people can transform.

Transcript_HR2: 48 - 48 (0)

HR2: -Of course, we are trying to be a very human focused and that we, yeah, take our values very seriously. So, there are already the baseline is already in that direction. So, people have the same mindset. But of course, you still see mailings that are created

completely by AI and then it's going out and you say, "OK, yes, but maybe next time-

Transcript_HR2: 78 - 78 (0)

And in in communication, you know there will be also more and more tools to improve. Images. Videos. All this stuff and the question is "What is authenticity and what is not so?

Transcript_HR1: 52 - 52 (0)

So, the question is how much it needs to be perfect, how much does it need to be authentic

Transcript_HR1: 56 - 56 (0)

P2: No, it's mainly text, and we think it it's it also needs to be authentic. So, we want to show employees in our videos, and we also have our picture database for the corporate design and corporate identity. This is produced with

real human beings and real photographers.

Transcript_P2: 49 - 49 (0)

hingegen für längere Beiträge, Fachbeiträge, die Autorentexte sind und dann auch ins gedruckte Kundenmagazin kommen da besteht schon die Erwartung, dass man die auch wirklich noch selber schreibt.

Transcript_FI2: 84 - 84 (0)

Ja, so etwas, ich weiss gar nicht, wie ich das ausdrücken soll. Das ist so authentisch klingt so eine gewisse Handschrift hat, oder?

Transcript_FI2: 128 - 128 (0)

This is this is mainly relevant in sense of using images, I mean this is not in the field of communication primarily, but yeah if we

would use... but we don't... we for example clearly decided not to use AI generated pictures of humans because we we're a company saying we want to be close to the people.

Transcript_F11: 40 - 40 (0)

E2: If I see for example, I am thrilled, or we are thrilled to announce I know already that's AI.

Transcript_E2: 87 - 87 (0)

E1: -It didn't seem real, and I think right now you're still able to tell if an image is AI generated to a certain extent. I know there's like really good models that you wouldn't know, but yeah, it didn't land that well.

Transcript_E1: 68 - 68 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Lack of empathy or human touch

FB2: -Any normal person would say save the child, but the robot of course doesn't know that. And this is where you have a little bit of a, you know you need the human elements to come into it.

Transcript_FB2: 68 - 68 (0)

Ethical risks and issues > Job security

HR2: And yeah, that you really make sure that the job security is still given that you don't say, "Hey, we have ChatGPT now and we don't need you anymore."

Transcript_HR2: 52 - 52 (0)

FB2: You also have to be a little bit on the on the, on the careful side when it comes to jobs.

PM: Mm hmm.

FB2: So do you get a chatbot to replace the customer service reception? Because a chatbot will do an equally good job. And this is where you have to look at

things. I was in the UK a very long time ago. With this, I mean there was a colleague. I was sitting down saying someone was in the back. I could hear a colleague, and she was speaking to a customer.

PM: Mm hmm.

FB2: And this customer had a problem which wasn't directly related to the products, but she helped her anyway, and it was a bit more of a personal thing, which I was quite happily surprised about, because it was, it turned out... it was an old woman, and she couldn't do something.

PM: Yes.

FB2: -Which was only semi-related and of course a chatbot wouldn't do that. So, would you, you know?, be OK with job losses to replace them with chatbots, is that a good thing ethically, but also the term of the service that is provided? You've been

on... I'm sure because of probably what you're studying on these chatbots, sometimes you have to go through 1000 [*of chatbots, referring to customer service-related situations*] in some companies, a 1000 of really annoying-

Transcript_FB2: 76 - 82 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies

HR2: So, the process how we start... basically I mean... we always create a text depending maybe in German or sometimes in English. If we get something from the holding, we have it in English and then we translate it or we see what we need, what languages we need. But usually we need French, German, Italian and English. The other four languages, so I say, "hey ChatGPT", but I prove first that there's no confidential data in it. If there's something that's not supposed to go online or we are working in a people's business. So, we always have to be very careful about the data of the people. So we check if we can go out. And then I really implement into ChatGPT and say, "Hey, can you please translate it please?"

Be aware that there are special needs in the Swiss German language, and I'm also the French and Switzerland is different. Please take that into consideration." So always also a bit of training-

Transcript_HR2: 34 - 34 (0)

HR2: And then a native Italian speaker, native French speaker, a native English speaker, reads through the text, scans if it makes sense, if the sentences are right. Sometimes it uses some weird abbreviations and so on, or it translates things in our corporate language that are not supposed to be translated. They [*proofreaders*] know what they are, they are taught to check that and then they make their corrections and then I can use AI and human collaboration translation.

Transcript_HR2: 38 - 38 (0)

HR2: -Teaches them things in the best case and shows them that we have expertise that we can transform. And if I now give that

responsibility to AI and then go out with maybe information that is not on that level, and I am still claiming that the brand is known for something on a high level and people trust us. I think we have to keep that standard up and with AI of course you have to have guidelines and everything in place that this is still given. So that's also something what I mean with transparency, if you if you say "We use AI tools to create content". Yes, you can say that, and you have to claim that on websites, right? You have to say "Hey, this is created by AI", but I think that's a bit of an easy way out. So, for me it's also-

Transcript_HR2: 68 - 68 (0)

HR2: They can rely on that. That's perfectly fine. I'm fine with that rule. And in general, we do have guidelines in the company that are really going along with our values, with our company values and that is-

Transcript_HR2: 76 - 76 (0)

HR2: So, first of all, I mean when it came up, it came up really fast. So, we were kind of the first in marketing, the first group to test it really. And we also said, “Hey, yeah, we are really we are *[A BIG HR COMPANY - changed otherwise identifiable]* So it takes too long for us to wait for something to come from the holding. So, the holding, the main company also said in our... in every country they said “Hey, try it out yourself, you are responsible of what you’re doing. You know your market best and try it out. Be creative, use it. Be careful. And then be aware that there will be something coming.” So, we created guidelines, we got guidelines, general guidelines and then we specialized them on the Swiss market and looked at what would make sense for us. Mostly everything makes sense for us. That makes sense for global, but then we have some specific things, of course, and yeah. Details. It’s... but yeah, exactly. And then we offered also trainings from our IT department. We have trainings for people who are being on boarded that we included. “Hey, that’s how we use AI. That’s what our principles are. Please take into consideration that maybe in your former company that was not important or

something else was important. So, we make people aware. And yeah.

Transcript_HR2: 86 - 86 (0)

HR2: It says that's definitely in it and also what tools we are allowed to use. We are not allowed to use all the tools definitely. Yeah, and mainly since we are not that really strict and we give a frame where we don't give like really hard borders. So, we always apply to people's sense of responsibility. Everybody has a chance to really try and do it on their own best knowing and will. But we really make the people aware. "Hey, that's how we use it. That's how you're supposed to use it". But also feel free within those frames to try things out and yeah.

Transcript_HR2: 90 - 90 (0)

HR2: -I well, in communications, not me in that case, but the global communications department of course, has the finger on it and say, "Hey, OK, what how do we

react after what happened?" But IT is riding the worst-case scenario. Let's say that and we're coming up with the solutions communication wise because then communication steps in, right?

Transcript_HR2: 104 - 104 (0)

HR1: -And what I would like to introduce for comes is tool that, based on certain sources that I choose, gives me some answers for media, for example. Studies. Past answers. Official talk tracks. And based on that gives me some answers and I don't want, you know, uncontrolled searches. I really want to define based on what the machine gives me the answer and for example this is not possible or not yet possible with Copilot because you can't just have so much uploaded and then search through because it doesn't have a memory. So, you really need, in my opinion the AI to be more serious and better, and to be really that we are on top of the AI and not vice versa. It's really important to be able to adapt those to the needs and to choose the sources to make sure the result is really thorough.

Transcript_HR1: 34 - 34 (0)

HR1: Well, let's say for example, we have a speech for someone, and I formulated it, or somebody formulated it in a in a text, right? And then I'm saying "oh, wow. This is not really nice, not really practical for the speaker, so let's make bullets out of it." So, I put it into Copilot for example, and ask "hey, please rewrite this speech, but in bullet points." And then it's very fast. It's done and it would take me like half an hour or 15 minutes to do it myself and like that, it's done. Let's say I still need like these 10 minutes because I have to review it. The thing is, if I don't review it, I think I really need to be transparent and tell "OK this is the original text and this is the DeepL translation, or this is the DeepL or ChatGPT or Copilot short version". Like, I think it's important to say, "OK I can translate, I don't have time, but I can send you the AI generated version so please check it". Yeah.

Transcript_HR1: 36 - 36 (0)

HR1: Well. You know, and they at [COMPANY NAME], the ethical challenge is mainly in the HR recruitment field. It's not directly communications. It's really about if you have an AI that goes through applications, how much can be automated and how not. And I think they're the principle is the same as in communication is super important that that there is a human involved, and that human leads the tool. And you need really to have an ideal collaboration between tool and human to have a good outcome. So, AI can always be biased, can always is always based on past learnings that can be wrong. So, if you have an AI supporting you in the recruitment processes, it's important to own it. And in communication... well. Let's see. I think it's dangerous if you have like an AI tool getting independent that is not controlled anymore by humans. So, a chat bot or an AI answering machine. But you can always build it in a way that is fine, right? If you say, OK, these are the sources based on those, the machine can answer, then it's fine if you if you just insert a Q&A and it's based on that or some additional sources. Then it's fine, but as long as you own the content and know what it's based on it's

fine. And in in communication, you know there will be also more and more tools to improve. Images. Videos. All this stuff and the question is “What is authenticity and what is not so?” There are many photo shootings’ costs that you can save if you have just 1-2 pictures and the rest is like AI, generate the background. I think it's super important that then you name the source and tell “OK, this was based on a shooting and yeah, that's the background”. I think Mango [*clothing brand, not related to HR1's company*] generated some.

Transcript_HR1: 52 - 52 (0)

HR1: It's difficult, so in communication we had like AI workshop and the company that completely forbid to use AI in communication, for example in videos, because you can have tools that go over videos and cut out the ähms, oohs, or you know and it's quite cool. So, the question is how much it needs to be perfect, how much does it need to be authentic. And I think some authenticity-

Transcript_HR1: 56 - 56 (0)

HR1: Yes, yes. We just set up like AI responsible toolkits and ethics that we communicated and now every eemployee need to do an AI training, so it's mandatory, so it has just rolled out now. So, this training start now I have not done it myself yet so. It's starting now, but we have evaluated a toolkit and also some ethics, some standards. And now everybody needs to go through training, I think this is super important. It's about, yeah, using AI correctly in a work environment.

Transcript_HR1: 64 - 64 (0)

HR1: And that safe alternative will be to build per department, for example AI tools based on the use case and needs that the department has. So, in my opinion, AI should be much more about how AI in certain departments can be implemented, and we should, you know, focus on department for department and then start to work there. It's there is not one tool that fits all one. One fits all.

Transcript_HR1: 76 - 76 (0)

P2: The rule for sure is that in Viva Engage and so on, it's automatically written if you use the translation function so that people are aware, OK, this is a machine translation, another human translation. I think this is very important also for the quality standard we have.

Transcript_P2: 45 - 45 (0)

P2: And otherwise, all the content we produce, we share, is always checked by human beings. So, we use it as an efficient productivity enhancement. We are testing it, but we are not yet there so that we delegate things like... for example summaries or something like that. What you could also offer, obviously as we can see in the daily newspapers, they sometimes have these AI summaries. So, we are not doing that yet. So

does that help you a little bit, but we do not have big guidelines yet. I mean we have the data department but yeah, so this is a bit what we are building up now.

Transcript_P2: 47 - 47 (0)

P2: And I think of course also, yeah, if you if you use it in pictures and so on, so... are you are you flagging it, so saying, "OK, this is AI, fine". I think this is absolutely necessary that you do that. I mean there is also... I just read an article today in the "Persönlich" do you know that? Yeah. And there was about the Tagesanzeiger, how they do it now, they do this testing also with summaries. And there were two links to the guidelines, also that and I think this is very important. So, the most important guidelines are written there, and it will be the next task for sure, also for us to see if we comply to these guidelines or not,

or if we have to implement something further.

PM: Is it something like... the ideas that you've shared with me right now. So, it is idea of intellectual property and being careful with pictures and videos. Is it something that is shared among your department? Do you see people having maybe different concerns about the use of AI or would you say that you are on the same line, on the same page?

P2: I think this is something where we did awareness. We need to build up still. Of course, there are guidelines also for the usage of AI tools. So, we are not allowed to use ChatGPT and so on.

Transcript_P2: 61 - 63 (0)

P2: Well, this is a good question I cannot answer right now. But I mean, at least I trust there also

our IT department that tested that.
And when I choose the internal-

Transcript_P2: 73 - 73 (0)

P2: For cybersecurity, data security and so on. So also, we in our team, we have two ambassadors, and we do regular feedback and awareness. In the sense that we talk about the topics, "What can we do better? How do we use it?" So, I think that we are... we have a good way of dialogue in in the team.

Transcript_P2: 89 - 89 (0)

P1: With the with the highest priority to be compliant and to be compliant with any kind of regulation. So, we have the communication team which is generating content, then we have...to every content there is a subject matter experience, matter experts assigned, and he has to prove it.

And then it's even reviewed by the management and every task, most of these tasks, the most relevant tasks are even done in an audit trail or audit proven system. So, we manage this based on... on an SAP tool so that we can really show and prove... so we are compliant.

Transcript_P1: 36 - 36 (0)

P1: But we are now putting this on a solid foundation, and this is a task ongoing, this is a work stream. So, we will define, we will establish, and we will implement, and this is now, these days. I just got a notification that we will reach... and it will roll out rather soon in the next couple of days, a proper... let's say company-based, company-specific AI tool-

Transcript_P1: 42 - 42 (0)

P1: Is. We this is our daily business and we do this in every process and our processes. We have to be able to validate it. And I think that this is the same for AI. And of course this is difficult because by definition AI is not based on rules. So, an AI process is... I don't know, from from a theoretical point of view, how it would be possible to validate? But I would say, to take this on a corporate level is very important. Instead of every department or every person, every individual has AI, I don't know... a different way to deal with it and using apps on a personal smartphone instead of working, so working outside the system. I think this we should minimise... maybe we should block it, we should avoid it at all. And we should... we have to force the people to work within the system with tools that are at least maybe in in, in a sense, validated. That means we establish... we approve certain systems, and everybody has to use it. And then

of course, then we can add certain processes and documentation and handbooks. I think this is definitely the way we should go. I don't know by heart if this is already foreseen, but by the way, this is an excellent input, and I will pass it on.

Transcript_P1: 64 - 64 (0)

P1: And this was the reason why we decided to establish a work task force and to and to and to install certain corporate wide solutions. But maybe we are not. We are not a front runner. We are not the front runner, so these are recognised but we have to, we have everything we do must be risk based.

Transcript_P1: 72 - 72 (0)

FB2: -Contracts, recipes, whatever, whatever it may be, those are confidential, and we don't

want to share them. So, this is where you get a little bit of a dilemma whereby you want your people, you want your staff to use AI because it's a great tool, or great tools I should say. But you also are a little bit... you know, you need to be able to care for. So, we use Microsoft Copilot as our tool and when using it of course we keep it within our own Microsoft encrypted environment.

Transcript_FB2: 30 - 30 (0)

FB2: So, so that's our provider. Does that mean that people don't use external AI? But of course, they do. And we do have our list of do's and don'ts on what you should use, what you should and shouldn't share with them with the external world, and the thing is if you if you can't speak to your friend's neighbour about It, well don't then use it on that. Oh, I'm sorry on AI. Personally, I'm a little bit older so it takes me a little bit

more time maybe to pick up. I'm also extremely busy and this is why.

Transcript_FB2: 32 - 32 (0)

FB2: Yes, and that works for everything, and I can give you an actually good example which I spoke to my colleague about. This is something which most companies are using now. There's... it's in CVs, curriculum which come in... by the way, my function falls within the HR department, and that's why it's a bit related to me, so you have AI that checks the CVs, but you also need the human element.

Transcript_FB2: 56 - 56 (0)

FB2: I mean, yes. As a supervisor... so if it's something which could have a big impact, it will always be checked and generally

we check multiple times by different people because it's very, very easy to get something on. Of course, even for humans, which is why... if you, if you do a job like mine... I would write something and then I would leave it and then I'd go back to it and check it again.

Transcript_FB2: 112 - 112 (0)

FB2: I think it's cool. Yeah, I'm not. I'm not a big fan of that person. But so, I don't even... I've never even used it and then I won't. And one reason why I wouldn't use that for example, is because that has no restrictions.

PM: Yeah, me neither.

FB2: It will give you the answer, however racist, however morally and ethically wrong it will give you the answer, and you won't might say, "Well, that's good for freedom of-

Transcript_FB2: 118 - 120 (0)

FB2: So, one of the main... there's two pillars. One of them is personal productivity. So in other words, your job is made easier by AI, that's the task of AI. The other one would be it would be a more marketing thing and how can the tool help in in pack-design, for example, that that's quite specific. I'm sorry, that is quite specific and quite restricted, I would say, but for us, for here, the main strategy at the moment is personal productivity.

Transcript_FB2: 132 - 132 (0)

FB2: Absolutely, it's still at the beginning. So, for example, I have the webinar to tell "Listen", you know for a start, before that even where the things say, "Listen we know about AI, this is what you can and can't do". Then there's a

webinar saying, “OK, look, this is how it works”, and we will have more webinars as we as we go along again it's purely a matter of time. I'm using my notes and... fine enough... one of the one of the greatest things of AI for example is, and you'll probably do it after the meeting is...you can have a summary of what the meeting is all about. So, when you go and do your you when you do your writing.It's very simple. You have a nice, lovely summary. I didn't have that when I did my master's not very long ago actually, but just ten years ago. But it would have helped a lot to be able to actually press a button, which is what I did with the meeting I had. And I have a whole list of meeting roles-

Transcript_FB2: 138 - 138 (0)

FB2: We do. And the thing is, it's two things. So, I have already cre-

ated a lot of guidelines and policies. Man, we got a manuals, handbook. Same things.

PM: Yes.

FB2: Etcetera, etcetera. But this was this was before and now I need to read, not redo them. I need to update them, let's say.

PM: Yeah.

FB2: There's that one. And the second thing is position papers.

Transcript_FB2: 154 - 158 (0)

FB1: -If you work with short term, if you give him 100 pages and say analyze, then he will not do it well. But short things with a good prompt that that works. I... depending on what kind of social media, I also use it for social media. I have my written prompts. Don't tell our clients. Sometimes the output is really good. Sometimes not and I have to rewrite so yeah, I and you cannot try. You always need to con-

trol. It's like a small child. You always need to control because you never know.

Transcript_FB1: 60 - 60 (0)

FB1: -To invoke rules, our boss always says to use human sense. Common sense.

Transcript_FB1: 94 - 94 (0)

FB1: That's a good question which I haven't been confronted with because I would say that all the senior consultants...I'm like the only one mainly using AI, the others, not that digitalized. So, they do not rely that much. On AI. And the young ones too. But their texts never go out without us checking it. So, I would say that's automatically. We have control of what goes out.

Transcript_FB1: 108 - 108 (0)

Das nennt sich [COMPANY'S NAME] Translator, ist aber ei-

gentlich wie DeepL mit dem Unterschied, dass die Daten nicht ins World Wide Web rausgehen zu Trainingszwecken.

Transcript_FI2: 28 - 28 (0)

FI2: Ähm ja, wir veröffentlicht sehr viel Content zum Thema, eben wie Gesundheitstipps, medizinisches Wissen, und da haben wir ein klares, ein 4 Augen Prinzip, das mindestens 2 Menschen den Text noch durchgelesen und kontrolliert haben müssen, bevor er veröffentlicht wird.

Transcript_FI2: 50 - 50 (0)

FI2: Wir haben intern auch einen medizinischen Dienst mit Fachleuten, die diese Sachen gegenlesen und kontrollieren und

ja, diese Qualität, die dürfen wir einfach nicht verlieren.

Transcript_FI2: 70 - 70 (0)

Und im Moment dann auch noch ein bisschen mit den entsprechenden Leitlinien, wie man mit diesen Tools wie frei mal mit diesen umgehen soll.

PM: Ja. Genau das wäre auch meine nächste Frage gewesen, was denn ihre Strategien sozusagen, um diese Herausforderung zu vermeiden. Ich finde schon spannend, dass sie schon ihre eigenen Tools nutzen. Ich glaube, das vermeidet schon ein bisschen, das Risiko, aber sonst haben sie Leitlinien, haben sie gesagt, wir sehen Sie aus?

FI2: Ja.

PM: Welche Leitlinien haben Sie also? Was umfassen diese?

F12: Also bis jetzt gibt es nur Leitlinien bezüglich Datenschutze

Transcript_F12: 76 - 80 (0)

F12: Was jetzt für die Kommunikationsarbeit betrifft, sind wir noch daran, diese zu erstellen. Wir hatten da intern schon Workshops gemacht und eben da habe ich festgestellt, dass die Haltungen im Team auch ziemlich noch auseinander gehen.

Transcript_F12: 82 - 82 (0)

F12: Und ja, wir werden wir werden sicher differenzieren, je nach Art von Kommunikation, wie stark KI zum Einsatz kommen kann. Also ich habe vorhin schon angesprochen, beispielsweise zur Generierung von Kurztönen für Social Media ist sicher ein sehr effizientes Werkzeug und da haben wir.... das ist klar.... da

kann man es anwenden, hingegen für längere Beiträge, Fachbeiträge, die Autorentexte sind und dann auch ins gedruckte Kundenmagazin kommen da besteht schon die Erwartung, dass man die auch wirklich noch selber schreibt. Und KI dort vielleicht mehr als Inspiration nutzen? Für Formulierungsvorschläge, für Rechercheaufgaben, für Themen zu meinem Thema gesamtheitlich zu erfassen, ist man es... für diese Zwecke mehr einsetzt und weniger jetzt für die Schreibearbeit an sich.

Transcript_FI2: 84 - 84 (0)

FI2: Ich mach das nicht standardmässig, aber wenn ich einen Text redigiere, also redaktionell nochmal überarbeite und mir fällt auf, dass der der Stil wechselt-

PM: Aha.

FI2: -Von einem Abschnitt zum anderen dann lass ich das durch ein entsprechendes Kontrolltool laufen und meistens sieht man dann recht schnell.

PM: Ja. Haben sie auch interne Kontrolltools oder sind diese öffentliche Kontrolltools, dass Sie nutzen?

FI2: Das da können wir, da verwenden wir öffentliche, dafür haben wir keine eigenes, bis jetzt.

Transcript_FI2: 86 - 90 (0)

FI2: Ja eben auch, so smarte Leitlinien zu formulieren für die einzelnen Kommunikationsskanäle ist für uns sicher. Ist sicher sehr wichtig, und das ist eine Arbeit, die Moment an dran sind. Und dann geht es sicher darum, auch die Leute, die mit diesen Tools arbeiten, möglichst alle auf einen guten Wissensstand zu bringen eben gesagt, eben zum

Beispiel Weiterbildungen in Sachen wie «Wie prompte ich richtig», «Wie setze ich diese Ergebnisse richtig ein?», «Wie kann ich es auch einschätzen, was ist qualitativ gut, was ist weniger gut, wo kann ich das Maximum rausholen aus den Tools?», und «Wie nutze ich sie effizient?» Da braucht es sicher noch eine, da müssen wir noch ein 2 Stufen weiterkommen, das ist klar.

Transcript_FI2: 120 - 120 (0)

FI1: Well, I would say today it's on a daily base, but we need to differ on... on one hand we have a really open tool, like we currently have Copilot. This is some kind of ChatGPT adoption which is secure, which is currently based on GPT 4.0 model, and is provided by Microsoft with all this data protection possibilities, which enables us to use more than just public data. And I'd say I know of my

colleagues at the communication department, that they often use it as a hint giver or to start with something, or to challenge some texts. And so... therefore this approach... and we enable that also with an intense program at [*COMPANY'S NAME*] and, and I'd say, and I know from these colleagues, that they often use it.

Transcript_F11: 12 - 12 (0)

F11: We primarily for the flexible usage, we use Copilot. We know that some people use, on their private computers, they use other tools, but from the official side at our company it is Copilot, for the for the chat functionality versus an LLM feature. We certainly also have quite a journey behind us in identifying concrete use cases where you need a more strict implementation, and where you also use cloud resources. We currently work primarily with Azure,

and there we have an AI foundation developed which can be used to implement specific use cases. Or we work together with some partners that provide us with concrete implementations, for example, one use case in communication is to shorten a press text. Often you need to provide different newspapers with more shorter information than we edited, and therefore we have developed a hardened prompt setting, or agents, which really shorten the text but still keep the tone of voice of [COMPANY'S NAME] and the way we communicate the essential information we want to provide in this text and therefore we have developed like a more strict workflow in use cases like this.

Transcript_F11: 14 - 14 (0)

F11: -Controlling everything", I mean, we must be aware at [COMPANY'S NAME] and we use all these Gen AI tools, primarily

human based. This means it's always the human that controls and that deploys. So that is, we'd have no automated tasks in communication where we just for example say, "This is the text and send it directly to the newspaper". There are always men in the loop. A human, I mean, not just men.

Transcript_F11: 18 - 18 (0)

F11: Yeah, there is. There's quite some, I mean, what we did, we did make an intense business analysis where we collected all the use cases, primarily focusing on generative AI adoption. At our company currently this is a catalogue of around 450 use cases which we know of, and some of them are worth to be implemented in the way that we say "Well this needs to be implemented", the more reliable approach. But those are most are mostly not in the communications

environment because in communications, well, I'd say with copilot itself you have quite a good tool set to use. And sure, with this example of shortening text, this is a good sample which helps us to communicate. I mean, on the other hand we have we have like... but this is more on the pilot phase, things to edit or to-

Transcript_F11: 22 - 22 (0)

F11: We have several, yeah. And we might invite every, every department to share with us. I know they have some... I mean it always starts personal, then then you maybe share it in in your department... we're not aware of every prompt that is being shared, but what we just provide centrally is this library where we say "Well, share it with the whole company". I mean in our company... it is good to know we are cooperative banks, so this means we have

Transcript_F11: 30 - 30 (0)

F11: Well, interestingly, I mean...we're used to... as long as, as you understand what you do. We don't hear a big issue with these elements, to be honest, I'm sure we're aware of that. That's why we do a lot of literacy, so that people understand what they can expect. But as long as it's not automated, there is no issue. We still have enough people that control these, these texts, and honestly in in business related communication, the discrimination part, for example, well, it's not so huge if we communicate, for example, our numbers. I mean, these ethical questions we often hear about are really important if you maybe have some educational formats or whatever and that is often not the case in our in our situation.

Transcript_F11: 36 - 36 (0)

F11: There are issues but, but I think it's not ones that are more relevant because we are a financial institution and as I say it, it depends on the kind of text you do. I mean, what's the, what's the public and who is at adressant, and is there no biases in it, or...yeah, things like these questions need to be posed. I mean, there's just something, but it's just this is more... Well, it might be addressed in the ethical part. We say to our employees "If you don't redigate [meaning: *edit*] the text mostly, if you don't change a lot of things we expect you to put in a remark saying this has been created with the help of AI. This is this is mainly relevant in sense of using images, I mean this is not in the field of communication primarily, but yeah if we would use... but we don't... we for example clearly decided not to use AI generated pictures of humans because we we're a company saying we want to be close to the people. So, we

want to show real people but we for example use AI to generate ideas-

Transcript_F11: 40 - 40 (0)

F11: We do have for the usage of Copilot. I mean there, there we put on a small set of rules which we defined in a in a cross functional team. And this... is but his is mainly addressing things like data protection. It is things like what kind of information you can use. For example, we don't use any data of persons versus LLMs. We have some information that we say "Well, check on legitimacy and freeing text of discrimination. So, proof on that directly. Yeah, we have some kind of telling them when to mark, if it's Gen AI generated content. Yes. So, these are some rules we define and which we also train the people.

Transcript_F11: 44 - 44 (0)

F11: -Approve if it's free of discrimination. I'm in charge. Even though I use a tool, so therefore, as long as we don't use it automated it is the same mechanisms that that that we have today implemented. This is mainly-

PM: Yes.

F11: -Four eyes' principles, things like that, that that we say, "Well, we have some clearance policy", how we check texts that go public. But they're not done because of AI

Transcript_F11: 50 - 52 (0)

E2: I would say we always have to double check it, of course. So, in my case it's just the LinkedIn post, but I know that also it's used to create a draft for brochures, for example. But then we always make sure to double-check the content. Of course, we have a

procedure of how our content gets approved internally and also externally. So that's a very strong process.

PM: Yes. You always have someone which is also checking the outputs of ChatGPT?

E2: Yes. Not overall, but in our like normal process, the content creation is going through many hands, so this is the same. It does not depend on if it's created by or with the help of ChatGPT or if it's created just writing like this, yeah.

Transcript_E2: 69 - 71 (0)

E2: I think it's always a challenge to avoid misinformation, false information. To also, if we use ChatGPT or AI to really be aware that we...do not trust the source, so we have to double check and therefore, I think the use is still limited because you still have to

have some experts or professionals double checking the content and also fake news.

Transcript_E2: 75 - 75 (0)

2: I mean, we have a page on our Internet regarding opportunities and limitations of generative AI.

PM: Mm hmm. Is it something that you can describe? Yeah.

E2: I'm just throwing it down. I will definitely ask my boss if I can share the info.

PM: Yeah, I mean, I don't need to, I don't need to read it in detail, but I was more curious to know if it is something that helps you to sort of navigate the limitations.

E2: Yeah. Yeah. I mean, there are some kind of recommendations. For example, the first step, be aware of its limitations there.

Now they are talking more about ChatGPT.

Transcript_E2: 109 - 113 (0)

E2: If there is an issue, I would just report it to my boss and then it would go, but I have really no idea what an issue in this field and all the security data could be. That's not something we are dealing with. That's something in our IT department, yeah.

Transcript_E2: 151 - 151 (0)

E2: Trainings kind of and there the last one in our last trainings, they mentioned the deep fakes to pay attention. So, it's not completely related to communication, but also it touches base. So, there is some, some, yeah there is more information on a regular basis I would say about AI, yeah.

Transcript_E2: 155 - 155 (0)

E1: Yeah. Yeah, we don't at the moment, we have an internal policy that we don't, I think, and this maybe comes into like the ethical perspective of a lot because it is using pictures that are not our own. But we are working on a tool that will be doing it. So, we will be able to do image generation with [COMPANY'S NAME] internal pictures. So, it is in progress. We don't know when it's going to start, but we have seen some results, and it looks fantastic. So, if that's going to work soon, I'm very excited, yeah.

Transcript_E1: 28 - 28 (0)

E1: The process is that we do have a global generation AI team, so they are responsible for implementing new tools, staying in contact with the regions to figure out what we need and what our

needs are and when they implement a tool is basically available to everyone and we stay up to date and then we can it's up to us to use it or not use it. So, it's pretty simple.

Transcript_E1: 30 - 30 (0)

E1: We do have... well, this is up to every team, but we have the policy in our team that we look over it. We will never just use the copy that is generated. We will always like work through that and have our own opinion that still matters in that case, yeah.

Transcript_E1: 32 - 32 (0)

E1: So, we have biweekly Gen AI calls that are led by the global team, so everyone's able to join them, ask questions, get the newest updates on what's happening

at the moment within our company. So that's a helpful way and channel to figure things out. But yeah, I think that's mostly what's happening. And then every team kind of does their own thing. So, in our team we have updates as well that are led by the social media team.

Transcript_E1: 42 - 42 (0)

E1: So, one of the things is always "How? How well do we know at all?" I think that that's more on the global perspective though, when they decide on what tools we're able to use specifically. But I do know they always check. What's happening with our data? What's happening with our inputs? I think that's a big, big part as well. And we're also not able to use all the information and all the tools. I think that's also very important. So, we have different classifications for different tools. So, I think when it

comes to scenarios on what we want to work with and not want to work with it? First, yeah, what's happening with our data. Second of all, is it useful for our use case? And how is the output? I think that's the most important ones.

Transcript_E1: 52 - 52 (0)

E1: Absolutely. Yeah. So, we have a whole wiki online with different prompts and also different systems on how to work with.

Transcript_E1: 56 - 56 (0)

E1: The different models. Also, guidelines on again what data to enter. What type of persona the model would be in a sense, so it's very, very helpful.

Transcript_E1: 58 - 58 (0)

E1: I wouldn't know exactly how it is for other teams just because we're such a big company. I know that for our team, which is around 20 people in Switzerland, we have a global community which is thousands of people that do communications for [COMPANY'S NAME] and we have specific prompts that that's the only thing I know. And I know that the Generative AI team has a specific person that is responsible just for the communications departments.

Transcript_E1: 84 - 84 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Human in the loop

but I prove first that there's no confidential data in it.

Transcript_HR2: 34 - 34 (0)

d then a native Italian speaker, native French speaker, a native English speaker, reads through the text, scans if it makes sense, if the sentences are right. Sometimes it uses some weird abbreviations and so on, or it translates

things in our corporate language that are not supposed to be translated.

Transcript_HR2: 38 - 38 (0)

is super important that that there is a human involved, and that human leads the tool. And you need really to have an ideal collaboration between tool and human to have a good outcome

Transcript_HR1: 52 - 52 (0)

nd otherwise, all the content we produce, we share, is always checked by human beings.

Transcript_P2: 47 - 47 (0)

to every content there is a subject matter experience, matter experts assigned, and he has to prove it. And then it's even reviewed by the management and every task,

most of these tasks, the most relevant tasks are even done in an audit trail or audit proven system

Transcript_P1: 36 - 36 (0)

FB2: Yes, and that works for everything, and I can give you an actually good example which I spoke to my colleague about. This is something which most companies are using now. There's... it's in CVs, curriculum which come in... by the way, my function falls within the HR department, and that's why it's a bit related to me, so you have AI that checks the CVs, but you also need the human element.

Transcript_FB2: 56 - 56 (0)

FB2: I mean, yes. As a supervisor... so if it's something which could have a big impact, it will always be checked and generally

we check multiple times by different people because it's very, very easy to get something on. Of course, even for humans, which is why... if you, if you do a job like mine... I would write something and then I would leave it and then I'd go back to it and check it again.

Transcript_FB2: 112 - 112 (0)

You always need to control. It's like a small child. You always need to control because you never know.

Transcript_FB1: 60 - 60 (0)

But their texts never go out without us checking it. So, I would say that's automatically. We have control of what goes out.

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medizinisches Wissen, und da haben wir ein klares, ein 4 Augen Prinzip, das mindestens 2 Menschen den Text noch durchgelesen und kontrolliert haben müssen, bevor er veröffentlicht wird.

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F12: Wir haben intern auch einen medizinischen Dienst mit Fachleuten, die diese Sachen gegenlesen und kontrollieren und ja, diese Qualität, die dürfen wir einfach nicht verlieren.

Transcript_F12: 70 - 70 (0)

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no automated tasks in communication where we just for example say, "This is the text and send it directly to the newspaper". There are always men in the loop. A human, I mean, not just men.

Transcript_F11: 18 - 18 (0)

-Four eyes' principles

Transcript_F11: 52 - 52 (0)

Of course, we have a procedure of how our content gets approved internally and also externally. So that's a very strong process.

PM: Yes. You always have someone which is also checking the outputs of ChatGPT?

E2: Yes. Not overall, but in our like normal process, the content creation is going through many hands,

Transcript_E2: 69 - 71 (0)

so we have to double check and therefore, I think the use is still limited because you still have to have some experts or professionals double checking the content and also fake news.

Transcript_E2: 75 - 75 (0)

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Solutions and mitigation strategies > Human in the loop > Four eyes principle

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Solutions and mitigation strategies > Human in the loop > Experts review

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Transcript_E2: 75 - 75 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > AI control tools

FI2: -Von einem Abschnitt zum anderen dann lass ich das durch ein entsprechendes Kontrolltool laufen und meistens sieht man dann recht schnell.

Transcript_FI2: 88 - 88 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Limiting AI use

: It says that's definitely in it and also what tools we are allowed to use. We are not allowed to use all the tools definitely.

Transcript_HR2: 90 - 90 (0)

-And what I would like to introduce for comes is tool that, based on certain sources that I choose, gives me some answers for media, for example. Studies. Past answers. Official talk tracks. And based on that gives me some answers and I don't want, you know, uncontrolled searches. I really want to define based on what the machine gives me the answer and for example this is not possible or not yet possible with Copilot because you can't just have so much uploaded and then search through because it doesn't have a memory. So, you really need, in my opinion the AI to be more serious and better, and to be really that we are on top of the AI and not vice versa. It's really important to be able to adapt those to the needs and to choose the sources to make sure the result is really thorough.

Transcript_HR1: 34 - 34 (0)

HR1: It's difficult, so in communication we had like AI workshop and the company that completely forbid to use AI in communication, for example in videos, because you can have tools that go over

videos and cut out the ähms, ooohs, or you know and it's quite cool. So, the question is how much it needs to be perfect, how much does it need to be authentic. And I think some authenticity-

Transcript_HR1: 56 - 56 (0)

So, we are not allowed to use ChatGPT and so on.

Transcript_P2: 63 - 63 (0)

So, we will define, we will establish, and we will implement, and this is now, these days. I just got a notification that we will reach... and it will roll out rather soon in the next couple of days, a proper... let's say company-based, company-specific AI tool-

Transcript_P1: 42 - 42 (0)

Instead of every department or every person, every individual

has AI, I don't know... a different way to deal with it and using apps on a personal smartphone instead of working, so working outside the system. I think this we should minimise... maybe we should block it, we should avoid it at all. And we should... we have to force the people to work within the system with tools that are at least maybe in in, in a sense, validated. That means we establish... we approve certain systems, and everybody has to use it. And then of course, then we can add certain processes and documentation and handbooks. I think this is definitely the way we should go. I don't know by heart if this is already foreseen, but by the way, this is an excellent input, and I will pass it on.

Transcript_P1: 64 - 64 (0)

FB2: I think it's cool. Yeah, I'm not. I'm not a big fan of that person. But so, I don't even... I've

never even used it and then I won't. And one reason why I wouldn't use that for example, is because that has no restrictions.

Transcript_FB2: 118 - 118 (0)

Das nennt sich [*COMPANY'S NAME*] Translator, ist aber eigentlich wie DeepL mit dem Unterschied, dass die Daten nicht ins World Wide Web rausgehen zu Trainingszwecken.

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Transcript_F11: 40 - 40 (0)

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E1: So, one of the things is always “How? How well do we know at all?” I think that that's more on the global perspective though, when they decide on what tools we're able to use specifically. But I do know they always check. What's happening with our data? What's happening with our inputs? I think that's a big, big part as well. And we're also not able to use all the information and all the tools. I think that's also very important. So, we have different classifications for different tools. So, I think when it comes to scenarios on what we want to work with and not want to work with it? First, yeah, what's happening with our data. Second of all, is it useful for our use case? And how is the output? I think that's the most important ones.

Transcript_E1: 52 - 52 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Limiting AI use > Only using company approved tools

: It says that's definitely in it and also what tools we are allowed to use. We are not allowed to use all the tools definitely.

Transcript_HR2: 90 - 90 (0)

So, we are not allowed to use ChatGPT and so on.

Transcript_P2: 63 - 63 (0)

That means we establish... we approve certain systems, and everybody has to use it.

Transcript_P1: 64 - 64 (0)

FB2: I think it's cool. Yeah, I'm not. I'm not a big fan of that person. But so, I don't even... I've never even used it and then I won't. And one reason why I wouldn't use that for example, is because that has no restrictions.

Transcript_FB2: 118 - 118 (0)

when they decide on what tools we're able to use specifically.

Transcript_E1: 52 - 52 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Limiting AI use > Using company owned tools that operate on known internal sources

t I would like to introduce for comes is tool that, based on certain sources that I choose, gives me some answers for media, for example. Studies. Past answers. Official talk tracks. And based on that gives me some answers and I don't want, you know, uncontrolled searches. I really want to define based on what the machine gives me the answer

Transcript_HR1: 34 - 34 (0)

just got a notification that we will reach... and it will roll out rather soon in the next couple of days, a proper... let's say company-based, company-specific AI tool-

Transcript_P1: 42 - 42 (0)

when using it of course we keep it within our own Microsoft encrypted environment.

Transcript_FB2: 30 - 30 (0)

Das nennt sich [COMPANY'S NAME] Translator, ist aber eigentlich wie DeepL mit dem Unterschied, dass die Daten nicht ins World Wide Web rausgehen zu Trainingszwecken.

Transcript_FI2: 28 - 28 (0)

is provided by Microsoft with all this data protection possibilities, which enables us to use more than just public data

Transcript_FI1: 12 - 12 (0)

So, we will be able to do image generation with [COMPANY'S NAME] internal pictures

Transcript_E1: 28 - 28 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Limiting AI use > Banning AI video and/ or image generation

HR1: It's difficult, so in communication we had like AI workshop and the company that completely forbid to use AI in communication, for example in videos, because you can have tools that go over videos and cut out the ähms, oohs, or you know and it's quite cool. So, the question is how much it needs to be perfect, how much does it need to be authentic. And I think some authenticity-

Transcript_HR1: 56 - 56 (0)

This is this is mainly relevant in sense of using images, I mean this is not in the field of communication primarily, but yeah if we would use... but we don't... we for example clearly decided not to use AI generated pictures of humans because we we're a company saying we want to be close to the people

Transcript_F11: 40 - 40 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Limiting AI use > Banning AI completely

I think this we should minimise... maybe we should block it, we should avoid it at all.

Transcript_P1: 64 - 64 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Corporate-level solutions

HR2: So, first of all, I mean when it came up, it came up really fast. So, we were kind of the first in marketing, the first group to test it really. And we also said, "Hey, yeah, we are really we are *[A BIG HR COMPANY - changed otherwise identifiable]* So it takes too long for us to wait for something to come from the holding. So, the holding, the main company also said in our... in every country they said "Hey, try it out yourself, you are responsible of what you're doing. You know your market best and try it out. Be creative, use it. Be careful. And then be aware that there will be something coming." So, we created guidelines, we got guidelines, general guidelines and then we specialized them on the Swiss market and looked at what would make sense for us. Mostly everything makes sense for us. That makes sense for global, but then we have some specific things, of course, and

yeah. Details. It's... but yeah, exactly. And then we offered also trainings from our IT department. We have trainings for people who are being on boarded that we included. "Hey, that's how we use AI. That's what our principles are. Please take into consideration that maybe in your former company that was not important or something else was important. So, we make people aware. And yeah.

Transcript_HR2: 86 - 86 (0)

HR2: -I well, in communications, not me in that case, but the global communications department of course, has the finger on it and say, "Hey, OK, what how do we react after what happened?" But IT is riding the worst-case scenario. Let's say that and we're coming up with the solutions communication wise because then communication steps in, right?

Transcript_HR2: 104 - 104 (0)

now every eemployee need to do an AI training, so it's mandatory, so it has just rolled out now. So,

this training start now I have not done it myself yet so. It's starting now, but we have evaluated a toolkit and also some ethics, some standards. And now everybody needs to go through training, I think this is super important. It's about, yeah, using AI correctly in a work environment.

Transcript_HR1: 64 - 64 (0)

HR1: And that safe alternative will be to build per department, for example AI tools based on the use case and needs that the department has. So, in my opinion, AI should be much more about how AI in certain departments can be implemented, and we should, you know, focus on department for department and then start to work there. It's there is not one tool that fits all one. One fits all.

Transcript_HR1: 76 - 76 (0)

But I mean, at least I trust there also our IT department that tested that.

Transcript_P2: 73 - 73 (0)

e have two ambassadors, and we do regular feedback and awareness. In the sense that we talk about the topics, "What can we do better? How do we use it?" So, I think that we are... we have a good way of dialogue in in the team

Transcript_P2: 89 - 89 (0)

nd to install certain corporate wide solutions

Transcript_P1: 72 - 72 (0)

FB2: So, one of the main... there's two pillars. One of them is personal productivity. So in other words, your job is made easier by AI, that's the task of AI. The other one would be it would be a more marketing thing and how can the

tool help in in pack-design, for example, that that's quite specific. I'm sorry, that is quite specific and quite restricted, I would say, but for us, for here, the main strategy at the moment is personal productivity.

Transcript_FB2: 132 - 132 (0)

bsolutely, it's still at the beginning. So, for example, I have the webinar to tell "Listen", you know for a start, before that even where the things say, "Listen we know about AI, this is what you can and can't do". Then there's a webinar saying, "OK, look, this is how it works", and we will have more webinars as we as we go along again it's purely a matter of tim

Transcript_FB2: 138 - 138 (0)

FI2: Und deshalb müssen wir diese abgegrenzten Lösungen verwenden, und auch dort dürfen

die sensiblen Sachen... die dürfen gar nicht hochgeladen werden. Es ist natürlich schwierig, das zu kontrollieren, vor allem, weil wir eine sehr dezentrale Organisation sind. Mit etwa 60 Standorten in der Schweiz.

Transcript_FI2: 46 - 46 (0)

FI2: Was jetzt für die Kommunikationsarbeit betrifft, sind wir noch daran, diese zu erstellen. Wir hatten da intern schon Workshops gemacht und eben da habe ich festgestellt, dass die Haltungen im Team auch ziemlich noch auseinander gehen.

Transcript_FI2: 82 - 82 (0)

FI2: Ja eben auch, so smarte Leitlinien zu formulieren für die einzelnen Kommunikationskanäle ist für uns sicher. Ist sicher sehr wichtig, und das ist

eine Arbeit, die Moment an dran sind. Und dann geht es sicher darum, auch die Leute, die mit diesen Tools arbeiten, möglichst alle auf einen guten Wissensstand zu bringen eben gesagt, eben zum Beispiel Weiterbildungen in Sachen wie «Wie prompte ich richtig», «Wie setze ich diese Ergebnisse richtig ein?», «Wie kann ich es auch einschätzen, was ist qualitativ gut, was ist weniger gut, wo kann ich das Maximum rausholen aus den Tools?», und «Wie nutze ich sie effizient?» Da braucht es sicher noch eine, da müssen wir noch ein 2 Stufen weiterkommen, das ist klar.

Transcript_FI2: 120 - 120 (0)

we have developed like a more strict workflow in in use cases like this.

Transcript_FI1: 14 - 14 (0)

we did make an intense business analysis where we collected all the use cases, primarily focusing on generative AI adoption. At our company currently this is a catalogue of around 450 use cases which we know of, and some of them are worth to be implemented in the way that we say “Well this needs to be implemented”, the more reliable approach

Transcript_F11: 22 - 22 (0)

honest, I'm sure we're aware of that. That's why we do a lot of literacy, so that people understand what they can expect

Transcript_F11: 36 - 36 (0)

That's something in our IT department, yeah.

Transcript_E2: 151 - 151 (0)

E2: Trainings kind of and there the last one in our last trainings, they mentioned the deep fakes to pay attention. So, it's not completely related to communication, but also it touches base. So, there is some, some, yeah there is more information on a regular basis I would say about AI, yeah.

Transcript_E2: 155 - 155 (0)

E1: The process is that we do have a global generation AI team, so they are responsible for implementing new tools, staying in contact with the regions to figure out what we need and what our needs are and when they implement a tool is basically available to everyone and we stay up to date and then we can it's up to us to use it or not use it. So, it's pretty simple.

Transcript_E1: 30 - 30 (0)

we have biweekly Gen AI calls that are led by the global team, so everyone's able to join them, ask questions, get the newest updates on what's happening at the moment within our company. So that's a helpful way and channel to figure things out. But yeah, I think that's mostly what's happening. And then every team kind of does their own thing. So, in our team we have updates as well that are led by the social media team.

Transcript_E1: 42 - 42 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Corporate-level solutions > Strict AI workflows

FB2: So, one of the main... there's two pillars. One of them is personal productivity. So in other words, your job is made easier by AI, that's the task of AI. The other one would be it would be a more marketing thing and how can the

tool help in in pack-design, for example, that that's quite specific. I'm sorry, that is quite specific and quite restricted, I would say, but for us, for here, the main strategy at the moment is personal productivity.

Transcript_FB2: 132 - 132 (0)

F12: Und deshalb müssen wir diese abgegrenzten Lösungen verwenden, und auch dort dürfen die sensiblen Sachen... die dürfen gar nicht hochgeladen werden

Transcript_F12: 46 - 46 (0)

we have developed like a more strict workflow in in use cases like this.

Transcript_F11: 14 - 14 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Corporate-level solutions >

HR2: So, first of all, I mean when it came up, it came up really fast.

AI internal workshops and trainings

So, we were kind of the first in marketing, the first group to test it really. And we also said, "Hey, yeah, we are really we are *[A BIG HR COMPANY - changed otherwise identifiable]* So it takes too long for us to wait for something to come from the holding. So, the holding, the main company also said in our... in every country they said "Hey, try it out yourself, you are responsible of what you're doing. You know your market best and try it out. Be creative, use it. Be careful. And then be aware that there will be something coming." So, we created guidelines, we got guidelines, general guidelines and then we specialized them on the Swiss market and looked at what would make sense for us. Mostly everything makes sense for us. That makes sense for global, but then we have some specific things, of course, and yeah. Details. It's... but yeah, exactly. And then we offered also trainings from our IT department. We have trainings for people who are being on boarded that we included. "Hey, that's how we use AI. That's what our principles are. Please take into consideration that maybe in your former company that was not important or something else was important.

So, we make people aware. And yeah.

Transcript_HR2: 86 - 86 (0)

every eemployee need to do an AI training

Transcript_HR1: 64 - 64 (0)

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Transcript_FB2: 138 - 138 (0)

Wir hatten da intern schon Workshops gemacht

Transcript_F12: 82 - 82 (0)

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effizient?» Da braucht es sicher noch eine, da müssen wir noch ein 2 Stufen weiterkommen, das ist klar.

Transcript_FI2: 120 - 120 (0)

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Transcript_FI1: 36 - 36 (0)

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Trancript_E2: 155 - 155 (0)

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Transcript_E1: 42 - 42 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Corporate-level solutions > Involvement of AI or IT departments

HR2: -I well, in communications, not me in that case, but the global communications department of course, has the finger on it and say, "Hey, OK, what how do we react after what happened?" But IT is riding the worst-case scenario. Let's say that and we're coming up with the solutions communication wise because then communication steps in, right?

Transcript_HR2: 104 - 104 (0)

But I mean, at least I trust there also our IT department that tested that.

Transcript_P2: 73 - 73 (0)

That's something in our IT department, yeah.

Transcript_E2: 151 - 151 (0)

E1: The process is that we do have a global generation AI team, so they are responsible for implementing new tools, staying in contact with the regions to figure out what we need and what our needs are and when they implement a tool is basically available to everyone and we stay up to date and then we can it's up to us to use it or not use it. So, it's pretty simple.

Transcript_E1: 30 - 30 (0)

E1: I wouldn't know exactly how it is for other teams just because we're such a big company. I know that for our team, which is around 20 people in Switzerland, we have a global community which is thousands of people that do communications for [COMPANY'S NAME] and we have specific prompts that that's the only thing I

know. And I know that the Generative AI team has a specific person that is responsible just for the communications departments.

Transcript_E1: 84 - 84 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Corporate-level solutions > Department or company-based use cases

e should, you know, focus on department for department and then start to work there. It's there is not one tool that fits all one. One fits all.

Transcript_HR1: 76 - 76 (0)

Und ja, wir werden wir werden sicher differenzieren, je nach Art von Kommunikation, wie stark KI zum Einsatz kommen kann.

Transcript_FI2: 84 - 84 (0)

we did make an intense business analysis where we collected all the use cases, primarily focusing on generative AI adoption. At our

company currently this is a catalogue of around 450 use cases which we know of, and some of them are worth to be implemented in the way that we say “Well this needs to be implemented”, the more reliable approach

Transcript_F11: 22 - 22 (0)

we have a global community which is thousands of people that do communications for [COMPANY'S NAME] and we have specific prompts that that's the only thing I know.

Transcript_E1: 84 - 84 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Corporate-level solutions > Internal task forces

we decided to establish a work task force

Transcript_P1: 72 - 72 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Corporate-level solutions > Guidelines

HR2: They can rely on that. That's perfectly fine. I'm fine with that

rule. And in general, we do have guidelines in the company that are really going along with our values, with our company values and that is-

Transcript_HR2: 76 - 76 (0)

HR1: Yes, yes. We just set up like AI responsible toolkits and ethics that we communicated and now every eemployee need to do an AI training, so it's mandatory, so it has just rolled out now. So, this training start now I have not done it myself yet so. It's starting now, but we have evaluated a toolkit and also some ethics, some standards. And now everybody needs to go through training, I think this is super important. It's about, yeah, using AI correctly in a work environment.

Transcript_HR1: 64 - 64 (0)

there are guidelines also for the usage of AI tools

Transcript_P2: 63 - 63 (0)

And then of course, then we can add certain processes and documentation and handbooks

Transcript_P1: 64 - 64 (0)

nd we do have our list of do's and don'ts on what you should use, what you should and shouldn't share with them with the external world, and the thing is if you if you can't speak to your friend's neighbour about It, well don't then use it on that

Transcript_FB2: 32 - 32 (0)

FB2: We do. And the thing is, it's two things. So, I have already created a lot of guidelines and policies. Man, we got a manuals, handbook. Same things.

PM: Yes.

FB2: Etcetera, etcetera. But this was this was before and now I need to read, not redo them. I need to update them, let's say.

PM: Yeah.

FB2: There's that one. And the second thing is position papers.

Transcript_FB2: 154 - 158 (0)

Und im Moment dann auch noch ein bisschen mit den entsprechenden Leitlinien, wie man mit diesen Tools wie frei mal mit diesen umgehen soll.

PM: Ja. Genau das wäre auch meine nächste Frage gewesen, was denn ihre Strategien sozusagen, um diese Herausforderung zu vermeiden. Ich finde schon spannend, dass sie schon ihre eigenen Tools nutzen. Ich glaube, das vermeidet schon ein bisschen, das Risiko, aber sonst

haben sie Leitlinien, haben sie gesagt, wir sehen Sie aus?

F12: Ja.

PM: Welche Leitlinien haben Sie also? Was umfassen diese?

F12: Also bis jetzt gibt es nur Leitlinien bezüglich Datenschutze

Transcript_F12: 76 - 80 (0)

F11: We have several, yeah. And we might invite every, every department to share with us. I know they have some... I mean it always starts personal, then then you maybe share it in in your department... we're not aware of every prompt that is being shared, but what we just provide centrally is this library where we say "Well, share it with the whole company". I mean in our company... it is good to know we are cooperative banks, so this means we have

Transcript_F11: 30 - 30 (0)

F11: We do have for the usage of Copilot. I mean there, there we put on a small set of rules which we defined in a in a cross functional team. And this... is but his is mainly addressing things like data protection

Transcript_F11: 44 - 44 (0)

2: I mean, we have a page on our Internet regarding opportunities and limitations of generative AI.

PM: Mm hmm. Is it something that you can describe? Yeah.

E2: I'm just throwing it down. I will definitely ask my boss if I can share the info.

PM: Yeah, I mean, I don't need to, I don't need to read it in detail, but I was more curious to know if it is

something that helps you to sort of navigate the limitations.

E2: Yeah. Yeah. I mean, there are some kind of recommendations. For example, the first step, be aware of its limitations there. Now they are talking more about ChatGPT.

Transcript_E2: 109 - 113 (0)

E1: Absolutely. Yeah. So, we have a whole wiki online with different prompts and also different systems on how to work with.

Transcript_E1: 56 - 56 (0)

guidelines on again what data to enter.

Transcript_E1: 58 - 58 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Corporate-level solutions > Guidelines > Position papers

FB2: There's that one. And the second thing is position papers.

Transcript_FB2: 158 - 158 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Corporate-level solutions > Guidelines > Rules and recommendations

HR2: They can rely on that. That's perfectly fine. I'm fine with that rule. And in general, we do have guidelines in the company that are really going along with our values, with our company values and that is-

Transcript_HR2: 76 - 76 (0)

also for the usage of AI tools

Transcript_P2: 63 - 63 (0)

and we do have our list of do's and don'ts on what you should use, what you should and shouldn't share with them with the external world, and the thing is if you if you

can't speak to your friend's neighbour about it, well don't then use it on that

Transcript_FB2: 32 - 32 (0)

guidelines and policies.

Transcript_FB2: 154 - 154 (0)

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Datenschutzes

Transcript_FI2: 80 - 80 (0)

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Transcript_FI1: 44 - 44 (0)

here are some kind of recommendations

Transcript_E2: 113 - 113 (0)

E1: The different models. Also, guidelines on again what data to enter. What type of persona the model would be in a sense, so it's very, very helpful.

Transcript_E1: 58 - 58 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Corporate-level solutions > Guidelines > Handbooks and manuals

And then of course, then we can add certain processes and documentation and handbooks

Transcript_P1: 64 - 64 (0)

manuals, handbook

Transcript_FB2: 154 - 154 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Corporate-level solutions > Guidelines > Prompting lists

F11: We have several, yeah. And we might invite every, every department to share with us. I know they have some... I mean it always starts personal, then then you maybe share it in in your department... we're not aware of every prompt that is being shared, but what we just provide centrally is this library where we say "Well, share it with the whole company". I mean in our company... it is good to know we are cooperative banks, so this means we have

Transcript_F11: 30 - 30 (0)

So, we have a whole wiki online with different prompts and also different systems on how to work with.

Transcript_E1: 56 - 56 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Corporate-level solutions > Guidelines > AI toolkits

We just set up like AI responsible toolkits and ethics

Transcript_HR1: 64 - 64 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Common sense

FB1: -To invoke rules, our boss always says to use human sense. Common sense.

Transcript_FB1: 94 - 94 (0)

Solutions and mitigation strategies > Disclosure of AI implementation

So that's also something what I mean with transparency, if you if you say "We use AI tools to create content". Yes, you can say that, and you have to claim that on websites, right? You have to say "Hey, this is created by AI", but I think that's a bit of an easy way out.

Transcript_HR2: 68 - 68 (0)

I think I really need to be transparent and tell "OK this is the original text and this is the DeepL translation, or this is the DeepL or ChatGPT or Copilot short version"

Transcript_HR1: 36 - 36 (0)

I think it's super important that then you name the source and tell "OK, this was based on a shooting and yeah, that's the background".

Transcript_HR1: 52 - 52 (0)

t's automatically written if you use the translation function so that people are aware, OK, this is a machine translation, another human translation. I think this is very important also for the quality standard we have.

Transcript_P2: 45 - 45 (0)

you don't change a lot of things we expect you to put in a remark saying this has been created with the help of AI.

Transcript_FI1: 40 - 40 (0)

Evaluation of current strategies

HR2: Well, perfect would be proactive, but we are very aware

that's not always the case. And in the rush of the business, then you have to be of course reactive too. And we had those situations. We did of course have them already that there are processes in place when something happens, about what we can do. Of course more general, at communication level... Very often, it is not that hot for us, so we can quickly de-escalate since we have really low hierarchies here and be very free and open about the answers there, but yeah, we also have reactive.

Transcript_HR2: 92 - 92 (0)

HR2: I think there are some blind spots. I think with some things.

PM: Mm hmm.

HR2: You know, in my opinion, can be more strict and maybe you have to be more strict because we're really different levels of profiles and people working for us. I

mean, our core business is consulting and recruiting. That of course doesn't match what is going on in our head functions here, like finance, marketing administration-

PM: Yeah.

HR2: -What we have, and it would be great to have a clearer definition on what job you have, on how to use the tools, because I think. Maybe we could be more free to use them, but the guidelines are very to the core business, especially as to the core business which limits us in in cases where we could be more free.

Transcript_HR2: 96 - 100 (0)

HR1: Yes. Well, yes, it's prevention because you cannot hinder people in using it, so it's like I don't know, you can maybe try to make your children not watch TV, not watch a cell phone, whatever. But at a certain point they will learn, and they will do it yourself. Even you learn it early when you know

when they still are in initial stage and listen to you or the new to it. Too late, too late, and then it's... They might already have learned some patterns that are completely wrong or there might be some damage. So, it's better to prevent and to do something. To go into the right direction because you never, you can never stop the progress and this is progress.

Transcript_HR1: 66 - 66 (0)

HR1: I think it's fine. We are doing like we also found AI departments where we focus on this and really make sure that we drive it. In general, yes, I think we do the right thing. On the other hand, I must say, companies sometimes... you know, you like to see the nice AI story, but what we often forget is everything is based on data and everything that is in the company. And to introduce AI, you should have a database, a digital database that is solid that you have a single source of truth that you know where is what, and in a global company with so many different countries it's super important that you first get the basics before you introduce AI. So, I always think AI is like it makes

visible what you have on data, maybe sometimes forgotten. But it doesn't prevent you... you really need to control the base as well the database.

Transcript_HR1: 72 - 72 (0)

P2: Our approach... I guess it's both, you tried to avoid it and when it happens, I think this is with every damage you cause. You always try to avoid it, and you implement as I said with awareness campaigns and so on.

Transcript_P2: 107 - 107 (0)

P2: No, I think we have a good measure in place.

Transcript_P2: 111 - 111 (0)

P1: -Outside. We have to be very reflected for which and what purpose we are using it. Therefore, for the time being...I'm

quite happy about how we handle it and how we do it, because it is limited. We try to take benefit, but on the other hand we are not... we don't want to be depending on AI, and I think this is again a big challenge.

Transcript_P1: 56 - 56 (0)

P1: Yes, it's good. Given our industry, I would say this is very reasonable.

Transcript_P1: 68 - 68 (0)

FB2: Oh yeah, yeah. For AI specifically, we have a policy, and we have our do's and don'ts.

Transcript_FB2: 178 - 178 (0)

FB2: No, the general ones work, because you have things like... the dos is that...they're to legal

and ethical standards. Ensure data privacy and security report issues. Seek advice in case of doubt. They don't avoid sensitive data and open AI systems. Prevent unauthorized AI usage. Circumvent legal compliance or unreflected use. You know. So, I mean, I can't think of anything which would have you could use AI to write your [?], but that's a little bit obvious.

Transcript_FB2: 186 - 186 (0)

FB1: Yes. Yes.

Transcript_FB1: 120 - 120 (0)

FI2: Beim Datenschutz sicher eher präventiv, das müssen wir bei allem anderen eher reaktiv, weil wir schon die Haltung haben, die Leute sollen das ausprobieren, um überhaupt herauszufinden, was für Möglichkeiten, dass das bietet, wie sie

das integrieren können, ihre tägliche Arbeit, das ist auch gewünscht, so von unserem CEO, der selber sehr technikaffin ist, und deshalb ja lassen wir die Leute ausprobieren und dann, wenn wir sehen, «Hey, da tauchen Probleme auf»-.

Transcript_FI2: 98 - 98 (0)

FI2: Ähm, ganz ehrlich, wir sind da noch etwas in der Findungsphase. Ich denke, dieser Prozess ist noch länger nicht abgeschlossen, auch weil das das komplette Potenzial dieser neuen Technologien noch gar nicht so ganz abschliessend abschätzbar ist.

Transcript_FI2: 112 - 112 (0)

FI1: Because we say that the person publishes, the responsibility lies in human. So, nowadays, if I write the text... if I would work in

the communication department, I send it out and it is full of discrimination, then I am responsible. If I use Gen AI to generate something and I don't-

Transcript_FI1: 48 - 48 (0)

FI1: For the moment, I think it's enough. The question would be if you use agentic AI elements, I mean fully automated process is in our production case. So, meaning that we won't have enough resources to check the texts, but I absolutely say this is not the strategy we follow.

PM: Yes. Yes.

FI1: We still want to have people that that approve, and in communications I don't see that we have currently use cases that really are in need of full automation. Yeah.

Transcript_FI1: 56 - 58 (0)

E2: I think it's preventive, yeah.

Transcript_E2: 145 - 145 (0)

E2: For the moment, I'm happy. Yes. Maybe another topic would be the video creations. We have announced... ah, now that we are mentioning it. We have also on a regular basis some compliance-

Transcript_E2: 153 - 153 (0)

Absolutely. The first one, so preventative.

Transcript_E1: 46 - 46 (0)

E1: We had this conversation last week with one of the Gen AI teams and the two things we're missing is image generation and the other thing is presentations.

So, slides generation. So, anything visual, I think a lot of also iconography is a big part, so anything visual I think we're still lacking models that we can use, but they are aware of that and are working on that. So, let's hope.

Transcript_E1: 60 - 60 (0)

prompts are a lot of the time, very over engineered.

PM: Mm hmm. Yep.

E1: They're a bit complicated sometimes I just need quick info and I'm not going to use them. I actually don't think...I don't think I use them. That is great to say [*ironic*], "OK, I don't think I use them. I think I'll write my own"

Transcript_E1: 94 - 96 (0)

Evaluation of current strategies >
Satisfied

P2: No, I think we have a good measure in place.

Transcript_P2: 111 - 111 (0)

Therefore, for the time being...I'm quite happy about how we handle it and how we do it, because it is limited.

Transcript_P1: 56 - 56 (0)

FB2: No, the general ones work, because you have things like... the dos is that...they're to legal and ethical standards. Ensure data privacy and security report issues. Seek advice in case of doubt. They don't avoid sensitive data and open AI systems. Prevent unauthorized AI usage. Circumvent legal compliance or unreflected use. You know. So, I mean, I can't think of anything which would have you could use

AI to write your [?], but that's a little bit obvious.

Transcript_FB2: 186 - 186 (0)

FB1: Yes. Yes.

Transcript_FB1: 120 - 120 (0)

For the moment, I think it's enough. The question would be if you use agentic AI elements, I mean fully automated process is in our production case. So, meaning that we won't have enough resources to check the texts, but I absolutely say this is not the strategy we follow.

PM: Yes. Yes.

F11: We still want to have people that that approve, and in communications

Transcript_F11: 56 - 58 (0)

Evaluation of current strategies >
Partially satisfied

HR2: I think there are some blind spots. I think with some things.

PM: Mm hmm.

HR2: You know, in my opinion, can be more strict and maybe you have to be more strict because we're really different levels of profiles and people working for us. I mean, our core business is consulting and recruiting. That of course doesn't match what is going on in our head functions here, like finance, marketing administration-

PM: Yeah.

HR2: -What we have, and it would be great to have a clearer definition on what job you have, on how to use the tools, because I think. Maybe we could be more free to use them, but the guidelines are very to the core business, especially as to the core business

which limits us in in cases where we could be more free.

Transcript_HR2: 96 - 100 (0)

es, I think we do the right thing. On the other hand, I must say, companies sometimes... you know, you like to see the nice AI story, but what we often forget is everything is based on data and everything that is in the company. And to introduce AI, you should have a database, a digital database that is solid that you have a single source of truth that you know where is what, and in a global company with so many different countries it's super important that you first get the basics before you introduce AI.

Transcript_HR1: 72 - 72 (0)

FI2: Ähm, ganz ehrlich, wir sind da noch etwas in der Findungsphase. Ich denke, dieser Prozess ist noch länger nicht abgeschlossen, auch weil das das komplette Potenzial dieser neuen Technologien noch gar

nicht so ganz abschliessend abschätzbar ist.

Transcript_FL2: 112 - 112 (0)

For the moment, I'm happy. Yes. Maybe another topic would be the video creations

Trancript_E2: 153 - 153 (0)

E1: We had this conversation last week with one of the Gen AI teams and the two things we're missing is image generation and the other thing is presentations. So, slides generation. So, anything visual, I think a lot of also iconography is a big part, so anything visual I think we're still lacking models that we can use, but they are aware of that and are working on that. So, let's hope.

Transcript_E1: 60 - 60 (0)

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PM: Mm hmm. Yep.

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Transcript_E1: 94 - 96 (0)

Evaluation of current strategies >
Partially satisfied > Complicated or inefficient strategy

They're a bit complicated sometimes I just need quick info and I'm not going to use them. I actually don't think...I don't think I use them

Transcript_E1: 96 - 96 (0)

Evaluation of current strategies >
Partially satisfied > Further improvements needed

HR2: I think there are some blind spots. I think with some things.

PM: Mm hmm.

HR2: You know, in my opinion, can be more strict and maybe you have to be more strict because we're really different levels of profiles and people working for us. I mean, our core business is consulting and recruiting. That of course doesn't match what is going on in our head functions here, like finance, marketing administration-

PM: Yeah.

HR2: -What we have, and it would be great to have a clearer definition on what job you have, on how to use the tools, because I think. Maybe we could be more free to use them, but the guidelines are very to the core business, especially as to the core business which limits us in in cases where we could be more free.

Transcript_HR2: 96 - 100 (0)

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Transcript_HR1: 72 - 72 (0)

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Transcript_FI2: 112 - 112 (0)

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Trancript_E2: 153 - 153 (0)

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presentations. So, slides generation. So, anything visual, I think a lot of also iconography is a big part, so anything visual I think we're still lacking models that we can use, but they are aware of that and are working on that.

Transcript_E1: 60 - 60 (0)

Evaluation of current strategies >
Preventive approach

it's prevention because you cannot hinder people in using it,

Transcript_HR1: 66 - 66 (0)

P1: Yes, it's good. Given our industry, I would say this is very reasonable.

Transcript_P1: 68 - 68 (0)

FB2: Oh yeah, yeah. For AI specifically, we have a policy, and we have our do's and don'ts.

Transcript_FB2: 178 - 178 (0)

F1: Because we say that the person publishes, the responsibility lies in human. So, nowadays, if I write the text... if I would work in the communication department, I send it out and it is full of discrimination, then I am responsible. If I use Gen AI to generate something and I don't-

Transcript_F1: 48 - 48 (0)

E2: I think it's preventive, yeah.

Trancript_E2: 145 - 145 (0)

Absolutely. The first one, so preventative.

PM: OK.

E1: As I mentioned, we're very careful always trying to figure out every possible scenario first.

Transcript_E1: 46 - 48 (0)

Evaluation of current strategies >
Both preventive and reactive approach

ell, perfect would be proactive, but we are very aware that's not always the case. And in the rush of the business, then you have to be of course reactive too.

Transcript_HR2: 92 - 92 (0)

P2: Our approach... I guess it's both, you tried to avoid it and when it happens, I think this is with every damage you cause. You always try to avoid it, and you implement as I said with awareness campaigns and so on.

Transcript_P2: 107 - 107 (0)

eim Datenschutz sicher eher präventiv, das müssen wir bei allem anderen eher reaktiv,

Transcript_FI2: 98 - 98 (0)

Spontaneous reflections and opinions

HR2: An anecdote. Well, I have something funny. Well, actually... I don't know if you can use it for anything, but we really and that's the nice thing about the AI we have, we created a Christmas song. For our CEO with AI last year and it was so funny because it could really, I don't remember which tool we used for that. A colleague did it. She used it and she created it and she could really take the voices of some of our employees and make it sound like somebody is really singing it. And then they went through the whole company and went viral, basically. And it was a really fun story and people thought it was real. And there was also a part where we said, "OK, now it's becoming a bit scary. Now we have to really..." And now the ethical part comes in again. And we said, "OK, are we transparent now, are we telling people <Hey? It's not real is it's actually AI or don't we?>" And then we decided of

course to make it a fun joke. And at the Christmas party.

PM: OK, OK.

HR2: We sang at all and then we said “Hey, and if you listen closely, our voices are not that nice. So, you know, now we created an AI. AI makes everything more perfect. But if you want to have a real person in place, then maybe make it more personal. Then you can also listen to the real song now.” So, we made it a bit of a fun situation and also to make people aware.

Transcript_HR2: 110 - 112 (0)

o, but for me it's just the next step in digitalization we have like you know, machines. Calculators that are faster and faster and faster and faster, and now the next step is just that instead of numbers machines can also work with words and letters, so that's kind of the normal process. It's just we need to own it, and we need to put the formula in correctly and we

need to control it. I know I don't think that everybody is very conscious about it, but in communication, yes, I think we are.

Transcript_HR1: 58 - 58 (0)

HR1: Yes. Well, yes, it's prevention because you cannot hinder people in using it, so it's like I don't know, you can maybe try to make your children not watch TV, not watch a cell phone, whatever. But at a certain point they will learn, and they will do it yourself. Even you learn it early when you know when they still are in initial stage and listen to you or the new to it. Too late, too late, and then it's... They might already have learned some patterns that are completely wrong or there might be some damage. So, it's better to prevent and to do something. To go into the right direction because you never, you can never stop the progress and this is progress.

Transcript_HR1: 66 - 66 (0)

P2: And you cannot forbid to use every tool. Our approach is more

to offer as fast as possible a secure environment where people can use it without... yeah, without feeling always in danger. Can they use it or not? So, I think Copilot with Microsoft is a very good solution.

Transcript_P2: 71 - 71 (0)

P2: We still need to use our capabilities, the human factor is very important in checking the content, in requesting...Is it true? Is it not true? Because of course everyone that uses it finds out very quickly, OK, there is also a lot of-

Transcript_P2: 79 - 79 (0)

P2: Yeah, I think it's to learn from each other. People are also creative. Some people use it more for inspiration, others more for productivity. And there is day by

day, there is coming out something you can do with it, you can try it out and yeah we want to do the this this this right this part joyful for the people so that they inspire each other also in the usage.

Transcript_P2: 101 - 101 (0)

I think I think AI is here to stay

Transcript_P1: 54 - 54 (0)

P1: But on the other hand, I think we are aware about risks related to this topic. And so, we tried really to balance risk and benefit.

Transcript_P1: 78 - 78 (0)

FB2: -Contracts, recipes, whatever, whatever it may be, those are confidential, and we don't want to share them. So, this is

where you get a little bit of a dilemma whereby you want your people, you want your staff to use AI because it's a great tool, or great tools I should say. But you also are a little bit... you know, you need to be able to care for. So, we use Microsoft Copilot as our tool and when using it of course we keep it within our own Microsoft encrypted environment.

Transcript_FB2: 30 - 30 (0)

FB2: -Hard. So, is it possible? Absolutely it is, will it? Will it really happen? I am not quite sure if it will, because you still need to have that human touch to know what to do.

Transcript_FB2: 94 - 94 (0)

FB2: -You know, getting our people to learn how to use the AI tools properly and also... of course this

goes for myself too, when I'm prompting I'm not very politically correct, to be honest with you. Maybe because I'm a bit older and that's OK. But you know, in certain cases it's not OK. So, then you need to be careful. So, you need to educate people and yourself in using these tools properly and as they're meant to be used and it's good to you know, do a bit of a trial-and-error thing till you till you actually together but that is a concern. That is a quite a big concern. Because people could also go outside and share things which are not supposed to share, you know.

Transcript_FB2: 126 - 126 (0)

FB2: -What I'm trying to do with the team is to see where we have strengths and where we have weaknesses. So, if you're good in AI then you can help the rest. If I'm good at creating and cutting videos, then I'll do it for you. You

see that sort of thing. I haven't gotten there yet, but that's the.

Transcript_FB2: 190 - 190 (0)

FB2: I don't think we've had any AI related crises. The thing is, it only comes to me if it's, you know, goes beyond borders, and if the, for example, the name of the company, the reputation could be affected. So, so, I mean, I don't know if there were any on a country level.

Transcript_FB2: 200 - 200 (0)

FB1: Which is actually... I'm very happy about that. So, we are still needed. You still need us.

Transcript_FB1: 68 - 68 (0)

FB1: So, I had to go through this process of having to read and having to write. Yeah, I think young people don't go through

that process anymore because you have ChatGPT at hand. There are so many ways to take a shortcut, which I personally think for developing young minds... it's really bad because I think it's very important for a young mind to go through... I'm repeating myself... through the process of reading, thinking, processing, and writing. It's a whole... it's a whole process which is not existent if you start using AI.

Transcript_FB1: 76 - 76 (0)

FB1: I personally think that it's not a topic because we work with communication people as well. So, if we would say we will use it, they have to use it then suddenly companies may say, "Ah, we don't need as many people anymore."

PM: Yes.

FB1: So this is a conversation that just doesn't happen yet.

PM: So, it's not really...

FB1: We're... we as an agency are certainly not gonna start the conversation.

PM: Yes, OK. That's fair.

FB1: Ethical or not ethical? I mean, we need to work so...

Transcript_FB1: 126 - 132 (0)

FB1: Looking into the future and bringing it back to where I started. I start to wonder if ChatGPT or certain AI should have, like an age, like what? At what age? You should be able to start using it, and in universities and school. Because otherwise ..., as "man auf Deutsch sagen würde, schaffen wir uns selbst ab" but not in a good way, because ChatGPT can pretend to be to have humanity and be social. But that's bullshit. It's just programmed to do it. It can switch in another direction just as quickly, if you program it. So having to rely on AI without questioning it, without being critical about it ... I think that's a real big danger and I think many people don't know how to use it properly. Because it seems so easy.

Transcript_FB1: 140 - 140 (0)

FI2: Und die Schwierigkeit, die ich in Zukunft sehe, ist...die Kleine, die jetzige Generation von Leuten, die in der Unternehmenskommunikation arbeitet, die hat das alles noch selber gelernt, das zu formulieren, sich zu überlegen, jedes Wort auf die Goldwaage zu legen.

PM: Ja.

FI2: Und die kann einen von der KI verfassten Text auch entsprechend einordnen und bewerten.

PM: Ja.

FI2: Wenn man aber schon von Grunde auf damit gelernt hat, mit KI-Texte zu schreiben, oder verfassen zu lassen, ja... dann mache ich mich etwa Sorgen, ob man in Zukunft diese Fähigkeit, ob die irgendwann verloren geht, oder? Ob sie das auch wirklich

einschätzen und gewichten können.

Transcript_F12: 60 - 64 (0)

F12: Beim Datenschutz sicher eher präventiv, das müssen wir bei allem anderen eher reaktiv, weil wir schon die Haltung haben, die Leute sollen das ausprobieren, um überhaupt herauszufinden, was für Möglichkeiten, dass das bietet, wie sie das integrieren können, ihre tägliche Arbeit, das ist auch gewünscht, so von unserem CEO, der selber sehr technikaffin ist, und deshalb ja lassen wir die Leute ausprobieren und dann, wenn wir sehen, «Hey, da tauchen Probleme auf»-.

Transcript_F12: 98 - 98 (0)

F12: Na, ich denke, dass wir können das mit unserem 4 Augen

Prinzip können wir diesen Fall eigentlich ausschliessen.

Transcript_FI2: 108 - 108 (0)

F11: Well, interestingly, I mean...we're used to... as long as, as you understand what you do. We don't hear a big issue with these elements, to be honest, I'm sure we're aware of that. That's why we do a lot of literacy, so that people understand what they can expect. But as long as it's not automated, there is no issue. We still have enough people that control these, these texts, and honestly in in business related communication, the discrimination part, for example, well, it's not so huge if we communicate, for example, our numbers. I mean, these ethical questions we often hear about are really important if you maybe have some educational formats or whatever and that is often not the case in our in our situation.

Transcript_F11: 36 - 36 (0)

F11: It is no issue as long as we have people that are able to edit these texts.

Transcript_F11: 60 - 60 (0)

F11: This is probably a problem that might come up, say, but this is a challenge in education. We have...I mean, how do people learn to write discrimination free texts if they only generate stuff? But that is not a problem we have nowadays, that might be an issue if, for example, academic teaching isn't having the effect that people know what they would do, if they would do it themselves. You understand what I mean? And at the moment we have these people aboard and if we hire somebody, we want to see their personal competences. We don't say, "Well, the most important is

that you can prompt, you don't need to be able to really check the text quality". I mean that would be that. Yeah. I mean if we were a tech company, maybe we say "Well, we won't have enough people in our communications department" then this might be a question, but at the moment this is not something we follow strategically as long as we say it's the human in the loop approach

Transcript_F11: 62 - 62 (0)

E2: Yes, I think definitely it will be a threat, but we should see it as a chance.

Trancript_E2: 91 - 91 (0)

E2: To work smarter and to also, we will still need a workforce, I think so, but the profile or the job profile will change, and I think now the challenge for us is to first

understand what the new skills will be we need, what kind of job-

Transcript_E2: 93 - 93 (0)

E2: -Or background or jobs will still be needed. And then try to push ourselves to do the jump and yeah and learn the new skills or get prepared for the new the new world kind of. Because I think that's definitely a threat. And people who are just saying, "Yeah, I don't care. It's nothing. Nothing is going to change. I don't want to change." There will be a problem in some years I think so.

Transcript_E2: 95 - 95 (0)

E2: In the company I'm working for now, I would say people are completely open, so it's an industry where we are. So, we'll we are so... it's constantly evolving. So, I

would say most people have an open mindset regarding changes.

Transcript_E2: 97 - 97 (0)

E2: Yeah. Yeah. It's a good question. I would say they're more optimistic or I don't see that they're so scared or they see challenges. I think there may be more. It's difficult for me to answer. I can, yeah.

Transcript_E2: 103 - 103 (0)

E1: Not in our field just because we're very careful, I think as a company in general, we try to really figure out everything before we start with a new tool or a new-

Transcript_E1: 36 - 36 (0)

E1: Yeah, I think a mixture of both we had for Christmas globally,

they did the first AI visual campaign with the visual image generator.

PM: OK.

E1: Though it was all about factories and the [COMPANY'S NAME] buildings and Santa Claus, and how we're helping Santa Claus going digital. It was very fun to see what is possible with image generation, but then we also noticed how much work it will be used afterwards. I don't know. You know about fingers [*in AI's image generation*] that don't align and things like that. So, it was a lot of Photoshop after the actual image generation. So yeah, that was one example, but the output was great. It was very creative in a sense, but also it didn't land that well with our audience. I think it was very-

Transcript_E1: 64 - 66 (0)

E1: I think communications is very open to new tools in general, so we were very open.

Transcript_E1: 76 - 76 (0)

Spontaneous reflections and opinions > External perception of replaceability of communication professionals

FB1: I personally think that it's not a topic because we work with communication people as well. So, if we would say we will use it, they have to use it then suddenly companies may say, "Ah, we don't need as many people anymore."

PM: Yes.

FB1: So this is a conversation that just doesn't happen yet.

PM: So, it's not really...

FB1: We're... we as an agency are certainly not gonna start the conversation.

PM: Yes, OK. That's fair.

Transcript_FB1: 126 - 131 (0)

Spontaneous reflections and opinions > Peer learning and inspiration in AI usage

P2: Yeah, I think it's to learn from each other. People are also creative. Some people use it more for inspiration, others more for productivity. And there is day by day, there is coming out something you can do with it, you can try it out and yeah we want to do the this this this right this part joyful for the people so that they inspire each other also in the usage.

Transcript_P2: 101 - 101 (0)

FB2: -What I'm trying to do with the team is to see where we have strengths and where we have weaknesses. So, if you're good in AI then you can help the rest. If I'm good at creating and cutting videos, then I'll do it for you. You see that sort of thing. I haven't gotten there yet, but that's the.

Transcript_FB2: 190 - 190 (0)

Spontaneous reflections and opinions > AI is a dilemma: Great tools with many risks

So, this is where you get a little bit of a dilemma whereby you want your people, you want your staff to use AI because it's a great tool, or great tools I should say. But you also are a little bit... you know, you need to be able to care for

Transcript_FB2: 30 - 30 (0)

E2: Yes, I think definitely it will be a threat, but we should see it as a chance.

Trascript_E2: 91 - 91 (0)

Spontaneous reflections and opinions > Need for AI education

So, you need to educate people and yourself in using these tools properly and as they're meant to be used and it's good to you know, do a bit of a trial-and-error thing till you till you actually together

Transcript_FB2: 126 - 126 (0)

start to wonder if ChatGPT or certain AI should have, like an age, like what? At what age? You should be able to start using it, and in universities and school. Because otherwise ..., as "man auf Deutsch sagen würde, schaffen wir uns selbst ab" but not in a good way, because ChatGPT can pretend to be to have humanity and be social. But that's bullshit. It's just programmed to do it.

Transcript_FB1: 140 - 140 (0)

FI2: Beim Datenschutz sicher eher präventiv, das müssen wir bei allem anderen eher reaktiv, weil wir schon die Haltung haben, die Leute sollen das ausprobieren, um überhaupt herauszufinden, was für Möglichkeiten, dass das bietet, wie sie das integrieren können, ihre tägliche Arbeit, das ist auch gewünscht, so von unserem CEO, der selber sehr technikaffin ist, und deshalb ja lassen wir die Leute ausprobieren und

dann, wenn wir sehen, «Hey, da tauchen Probleme auf»-.

Transcript_FI2: 98 - 98 (0)

this is a challenge in education

Transcript_FI1: 62 - 62 (0)

E2: -Or background or jobs will still be needed. And then try to push ourselves to do the jump and yeah and learn the new skills or get prepared for the new the new world kind of. Because I think that's definitely a threat. And people who are just saying, "Yeah, I don't care. It's nothing. Nothing is going to change. I don't want to change." There will be a problem in some years I think so.

Trancript_E2: 95 - 95 (0)

Spontaneous reflections and opinions > Inevitability of AI use

but for me it's just the next step in digitalization we have like you know, machines. Calculators that

are faster and faster and faster and faster, and now the next step is just that instead of numbers machines can also work with words and letters, so that's kind of the normal process.

Transcript_HR1: 58 - 58 (0)

you cannot hinder people in using it, so it's like I don't know, you can maybe try to make your children not watch TV, not watch a cell phone, whatever. But at a certain point they will learn, and they will do it yourself.

Transcript_HR1: 66 - 66 (0)

and you cannot forbid to use every tool

Transcript_P2: 71 - 71 (0)

I think I think AI is here to stay

Transcript_P1: 54 - 54 (0)

Spontaneous reflections and opinions > Communication sector's awareness of AI risks

I know I don't think that everybody is very conscious about it, but in communication, yes, I think we are.

Transcript_HR1: 58 - 58 (0)

I think we are aware about risks related to this topic. And so, we tried really to balance risk and benefit.

Transcript_P1: 78 - 78 (0)

FI2: Na, ich denke, dass wir können das mit unserem 4 Augen Prinzip können wir diesen Fall eigentlich ausschliessen.

Transcript_FI2: 108 - 108 (0)

We don't hear a big issue with these elements, to be honest, I'm sure we're aware of that

Transcript_FI1: 36 - 36 (0)

Spontaneous reflections and opinions > Risk for overreliance in younger generations

had to go through this process of having to read and having to write. Yeah, I think young people don't go through that process anymore because you have ChatGPT at hand

Transcript_FB1: 76 - 76 (0)

F12: Und die Schwierigkeit, die ich in Zukunft sehe, ist...die Kleine, die jetzige Generation von Leuten, die in der Unternehmenskommunikation arbeitet, die hat das alles noch selber gelernt, das zu formulieren, sich zu überlegen, jedes Wort auf die Goldwaage zu legen.

PM: Ja.

F12: Und die kann einen von der KI verfassten Text auch entsprechend einordnen und bewerten.

PM: Ja.

F12: Wenn man aber schon von Grunde auf damit gelernt hat, mit

KI-Texte zu schreiben, oder verfassen zu lassen, ja... dann mache ich mich etwa Sorgen, ob man in Zukunft diese Fähigkeit, ob die irgendwann verloren geht, oder? Ob sie das auch wirklich einschätzen und gewichten können

Transcript_FI2: 60 - 64 (0)

ut that is not a problem we have nowadays, that might be an issue if, for example, academic teaching isn't having the effect that people know what they would do, if they would do it themselves

Transcript_FI1: 62 - 62 (0)

Spontaneous reflections and opinions > Need for communication professionals

We still need to use our capabilities, the human factor is very important in checking the content, in requesting

Transcript_P2: 79 - 79 (0)

So, is it possible? Absolutely it is, will it? Will it really happen? I am not quite sure if it will, because you still need to have that human touch to know what to do.

Transcript_FB2: 94 - 94 (0)

FB1: Which is actually... I'm very happy about that. So, we are still needed. You still need us.

Transcript_FB1: 68 - 68 (0)

E2: To work smarter and to also, we will still need a workforce, I think so, but the profile or the job profile will change, and I think now the challenge for us is to first understand what the new skills will be we need, what kind of job-

Trancript_E2: 93 - 93 (0)

Spontaneous reflections and opinions > Reduction of ethical risks thanks to human involvement

F1: It is no issue as long as we have people that are able to edit these texts.

Transcript_F1: 60 - 60 (0)

Spontaneous reflections and opinions > Low likelihood of AI - related ethical crisis

FB2: I don't think we've had any AI related crises. The thing is, it only comes to me if it's, you know, goes beyond borders, and if the, for example, the name of the company, the reputation could be affected. So, so, I mean, I don't know if there were any on a country level.

Transcript_FB2: 200 - 200 (0)

E2: Yeah. Yeah. It's a good question. I would say they're more optimistic or I don't see that they're so scared or they see challenges. I think there may be more. It's difficult for me to answer. I can, yeah.

Transcript_E2: 103 - 103 (0)

E1: Not in our field just because we're very careful, I think as a company in general, we try to really figure out everything before we start with a new tool or a new-

Transcript_E1: 36 - 36 (0)

Spontaneous reflections and opinions > AI friendliness in communication sector

E2: In the company I'm working for now, I would say people are completely open, so it's an industry where we are. So, we're we are so... it's constantly evolving. So, I would say most people have an open mindset regarding changes.

Transcript_E2: 97 - 97 (0)

E1: I think communications is very open to new tools in general, so we were very open.

Transcript_E1: 76 - 76 (0)

Spontaneous reflections and opinions > Failed internal AI use cases

E1: Though it was all about factories and the [COMPANY'S NAME] buildings and Santa Claus, and how we're helping Santa Claus going digital. It was very fun to see what is possible with image generation, but then we also noticed how much work it will be used afterwards. I don't know. You know about fingers [*in AI's image generation*] that don't align and things like that. So, it was a lot of Photoshop after the actual image generation. So yeah, that was one example, but the output was great. It was very creative in a sense, but also it didn't land that well with our audience. I think it was very-

Transcript_E1: 66 - 66 (0)

Spontaneous reflections and opinions > Successful internal AI use cases

HR2: An anecdote. Well, I have something funny. Well, actually... I don't know if you can use it for anything, but we really and that's the nice thing about the AI we have, we created a Christmas

song. For our CEO with AI last year and it was so funny because it could really, I don't remember which tool we used for that. A colleague did it. She used it and she created it and she could really take the voices of some of our employees and make it sound like somebody is really singing it. And then they went through the whole company and went viral, basically. And it was a really fun story and people thought it was real. And there was also a part where we said, "OK, now it's becoming a bit scary. Now we have to really..." And now the ethical part comes in again. And we said, "OK, are we transparent now, are we telling people <Hey? It's not real is it's actually AI or don't we?>" And then we decided of course to make it a fun joke. And at the Christmas party.

PM: OK, OK.

HR2: We sang at all and then we said "Hey, and if you listen closely, our voices are not that

nice. So, you know, now we created an AI. AI makes everything more perfect. But if you want to have a real person in place, then maybe make it more personal. Then you can also listen to the real song now." So, we made it a bit of a fun situation and also to make people aware.

Transcript_HR2: 110 - 112 (0)

